

ФЕДЕРАЛЬНАЯ СИСТЕМА
ОСОБО ОХРАНЯЕМЫХ
ПРИРОДНЫХ ТЕРРИТОРИЙ

МИНПРИРОДЫ
РОССИИ

ЗАПОВЕДНАЯ
МОРДОВИЯ

ISSN 2500-008X

Nature Conservation Research

ЗАПОВЕДНАЯ НАУКА

4/2023

Main Editorial Office

Editor-in-Chief: Dr. Sc. Alexander B. Ruchin (Russia)
Associate Editor: PhD Oleg G. Grishutkin (Russia)
Associate Editor: Sergey S. Ogurtsov (Russia)
English Language Editor: PhD Jacob Koopman (Poland)
Managing Editor: PhD Anatoliy A. Khapugin (Russia)

Handling Editors

Prof. Dr. hab. Oleg Aleksandrowicz (Poland)	PhD Nataliya A. Milchakova (Russia)
Dr. Sc. Alexander A. Ananin (Russia)	Ph. Dr. Dale G. Miquelle (USA)
Prof. Amaël Borzée (China)	Dr. Sc. Sergey V. Naidenko (Russia)
Mag. Dr. Roland K. Eberwein (Austria)	PhD Michela Pacifici (Italy)
PhD Leonid V. Egorov (Russia)	PhD Maria Silvia Pinna (Italy)
Ph. Dr. Zigmantas Gudžinskas (Lithuania)	PhD Sergey K. Ryndevich (Belarus)
Corresponding Member RAS Ernest V. Ivanter (Russia)	Dr. Marko S. Sabovljević (Serbia)
Dr. Sc. Mikhail V. Kalyakin (Russia)	PhD Boris I. Sheftel (Russia)
Dr. Sc. Lyudmila G. Korneva (Russia)	PhD Dmitry A. Shitikov (Russia)
Dr. Sc. Juri P. Kurhinen (Russia, Finland)	Dr. Sc. Tatyana B. Silaeva (Russia)
Dr. Sc. Georgiy A. Lada (Russia)	Dr. Sc. Alexander N. Tashev (Bulgaria)
Dr. William B. Leacock (USA)	Dr. Sc. Boris S. Tuniyev (Russia)
Dr. Aniruddha Majumder (India)	Dr. Robert P. Wagensommer (Italy)
PhD Peter Manko (Slovakia)	Dr. Sc. Igor A. Zhigarev (Russia)
Dr. Emanuel H. Martin (Tanzania)	Dr. Sc. Alexander S. Zamotajlov (Russia)
Dr. Sc. Yuri A. Mazei (Russia)	

Редакционная коллегия

Главный редактор: д.б.н. Александр Борисович Ручин (Россия)
Заместитель главного редактора: к.г.н. Олег Геннадьевич Гришуткин (Россия)
Заместитель главного редактора: Сергей Сергеевич Огурцов (Россия)
Редактор английского языка: PhD Jacob Koopman (Poland)
Исполнительный редактор: к.б.н. Анатолий Александрович Хапугин (Россия)

Редакционный совет

Prof. Dr hab. Oleg Aleksandrowicz (Poland)	Dr. Aniruddha Majumder (India)
д.б.н. Александр Афанасьевич Ананин (Россия)	PhD Peter Manko (Slovakia)
Prof. Amaël Borzée (China)	Dr. Emanuel H. Martin (Tanzania)
Dr. Robert P. Wagensommer (Italy)	к.б.н. Наталья Афанасьевна Мильчакова (Россия)
Ph. Dr. Zigmantas Gudžinskas (Lithuania)	Ph. Dr. Dale G. Miquelle (USA)
к.б.н. Леонид Валентинович Егоров (Россия)	д.б.н. Сергей Валерьевич Найдено (Россия)
Mag. Dr. Roland K. Eberwein (Austria)	PhD Michela Pacifici (Italy)
д.б.н. Игорь Александрович Жигарев (Россия)	PhD Maria Silvia Pinna (Italy)
д.б.н. Александр Сергеевич Замотайлов (Россия)	к.б.н. Сергей Константинович Рындевич (Республика Беларусь)
Член-корреспондент РАН Эрнест Викторович Ивантер (Россия)	Dr. Marko S. Sabovljević (Serbia)
д.б.н. Михаил Владимирович Калякин (Россия)	д.б.н. Татьяна Борисовна Силаева (Россия)
д.б.н. Людмила Генриховна Корнева (Россия)	Dr. Sc. Alexander N. Tashev (Bulgaria)
д.б.н. Юрий Павлович Курхinen (Россия, Финляндия)	д.б.н. Борис Сакоевич Туниев (Россия)
д.б.н. Георгий Аркадьевич Лада (Россия)	к.б.н. Борис Ильич Шефтель (Россия)
Dr. William B. Leacock (USA)	к.б.н. Дмитрий Александрович Шитиков (Россия)
д.б.н. Юрий Александрович Мазей (Россия)	

RESEARCH ARTICLES

ОРИГИНАЛЬНЫЕ СТАТЬИ

GENETIC STRUCTURE OF *SOLIDAGO* × *NIEDEREDERI* (ASTERACEAE) POPULATION IN THE «ALEKSIN BOR» NATURAL MONUMENT (EUROPEAN RUSSIA)

Sergey N. Lysenkov¹

¹Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

e-mail: s_lysenkov@mail.ru

²Main Botanical Garden of RAS, Russia

e-mail: mawa.galkina@gmail.com

Received: 01.06.2023. Revised: 27.07.2023. Accepted: 12.08.2023.

Solidago × *niederederi* (Asteraceae) is a natural hybrid of the native *S. virgaurea* and the alien invasive *S. canadensis*, originated in Europe. Its naturalisation potential is still questionable. One of the largest (more than 20 ramet clusters, treated as individuals) known population of this nothospecies, is located in the «Aleksin Bor» Natural Monument (Aleksin town, Tula Region, Russia) in the floodplain of the River Oka. We studied its genetic structure with the help of chloroplast and nuclear markers. Analysis of sequence of nuclear ribosomal internal transcribed spacer ITS 1–2 showed that all individuals with intermediate morphology are actually hybrids. Data on the intergenic chloroplast non-coding spacer rpl32–trnL showed that *S. canadensis* is the maternal species in 60% of the studied individuals. It was shown that even closely located individuals were not clones; therefore, they were results of sexual, rather than vegetative reproduction. Analysis of ISSR markers showed that the studied individuals of *S.* × *niederederi* in this population are not only F₁ hybrids, but also their descendants (F₂ hybrids and/or backcrosses, mostly with *S. canadensis*). We conclude that *S.* × *niederederi* has successfully been naturalised in the studied community and, possibly, is outcompeting its native parental species, *S. virgaurea*, through introgression.

Key words: alien species, biological invasions, hybridisation, nothospecies, ISSR, ITS 1–2, rpl32–trnL

Introduction

Solidago × *niederederi* Khek (Asteraceae) is a European hybrid of the native *S. virgaurea* L. and the alien invasive *S. canadensis* L. of North American origin. Morphological traits of this hybrid are intermediate, which makes it easy to distinguish it in nature from both parental species in most cases (Nilsson, 1976; Gudžinskas & Žalneravičius, 2016; Vinogradova & Galkina, 2020). Despite the fact that this taxon was described as early as the beginning of the XX century (Khek, 1905), and the oldest finding, apparently, dates back to 1899 (Skokanová et al., 2020a), its findings in Europe became relatively frequent only at late XX – early XXI centuries (Skokanová et al., 2020b). Its hybrid nature has been confirmed genetically in 2016, with a hybridisation process occurring in both directions (Pliszko & Zalewska-Gałosz, 2016). Now, the questions of the naturalisation degree of *S.* × *niederederi*, its invasion potential, and its potential threat to native *S. virgaurea* remain unresolved (Skokanová et al., 2020b; Vinogradova & Galkina, 2020; Skokanová et al., 2022).

In most cases, the findings of *S.* × *niederederi* are single individuals (Skokanová et al., 2020b). It suggests that they appeared as a result of new hybridisation acts, rather than the reproduction of already existed individuals of this hybrid. This is consistent with the available data on the reduced pollen viability (Migdalek et al., 2014), and the absence of long rhizomes, which facilitate vegetative propagation of this nothospecies (Pliszko & Kostrakiewicz-Gierałt, 2019). At the same time, data on seed germination are contradictory; existing estimates of germinated seeds percent range from extremely low (Vinogradova & Galkina, 2020) to high values (Pliszko & Kostrakiewicz-Gierałt, 2017). These results allow suggesting that in most cases *S.* × *niederederi* individuals appear as *de novo* inter-species hybrids rather than as a result of self-reproduction of the hybrid species. It should be noted that this does not affect its status as a nothospecies in accordance with Article H3.1 of the International Code of Nomenclature for Algae, Fungi and Plants (Turland et al., 2018).

In this regard, each more or less large population is of particular interest for clarifying the

problem of reproduction mechanisms and possible expansion of *S. × niedereideri*. Its population has been discovered in 2020 in the floodplain of the River Oka in the «Aleksin Bor» Natural Monument (northwest of the Tula Region, European Russia) (Lysenkov & Galkina, 2022). It looks like a promising object for studying this issue. The initial analysis of the two discovered individuals had already shown that this population emerged as a result of at least two hybridisation acts (Lysenkov & Galkina, 2022). Later, more than 20 individuals with intermediate morphology were found in the study area, which makes this population of *S. × niedereideri* one of the most numerous within the known distribution area (Skokanová et al., 2020b).

This study was aimed to identify the naturalisation strategy of *S. × niedereideri* in this population. Specifically, we aimed: 1) to confirm the species affiliation of *Solidago* with intermediate morphology using methods of molecular genetics; 2) to determine the maternal and paternal species for the discovered hybrids; 3) to reveal the propagation mechanism of *S. × niedereideri* in this population.

Material and Methods

The studied *S. × niedereideri* population is located on a *Solidago*-forb meadow with high abundance of *S. canadensis* in a floodplain on the right bank of the River Oka in the «Aleksin Bor» Natural Monument (Aleksin, Tula Region, Russia; 54.53° N, 37.06° E). At the studied site, the climate is humid continental with a mean temperature of +18.6°C in July, and -6.5°C in January; the mean annual temperature is +6.0°C, and the annual precipitation is 614 mm according to data for 2012–2022 from the weather station, located 2.8 km south-east from the study site (https://rp5.ru/Архив_погоды_в_Алексине). The soil is slightly acidic loam. In the study area, the first finding of three ramet clusters of *S. × niedereideri* was made in 2020 during the study of insect visitation. One of them has also been found in 2019, though it was not studied properly. In August 2021, the meadow was specially surveyed to discover *Solidago* specimens, which are phenotypically intermediate between *S. virgaurea* and *S. canadensis*. We treated them based on the inflorescence structure: the branches of the inflorescence are long and diverge at an acute angle; the size of the capitula is larger than in *S. canadensis* and smaller than in *S. virgaurea*.

All detected specimens with intermediate morphology (n = 21) were photographed and mapped using a Garmin GPS navigator with an accuracy of 3 m. For each individual, the number of generative ramets has been counted. One leaf was sampled from each individual for genetic analysis of nuclear and chloroplast markers. Some specimens were collected into herbaria (one ramet per collected individual). For genetic analysis, leaves have been sampled from *S. canadensis* (n = 15) and *S. virgaurea* (n = 8), located closely (at a distance of less than 0.5 m) to the hybrids. In August 2022, this meadow was thoroughly surveyed again. We searched with GPS for individuals found in 2021 as well as individuals that had not been seen before.

For molecular genetic analysis, DNA was extracted from the collected leaves using the Extran kit (Synthol, Russia). Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) was carried out in a T-100 amplifier (Biorad, USA). For the nuclear ribosomal internal transcribed spacer (ITS 1–2), primers nnc18s10 (AGGAGAAGTCGTAACAA), forward, and c26A (GTTTCTTTTCCTCCGCT), reverse (Wen & Zimmer, 1996) were used at an annealing temperature of 58°C. For the chloroplast highly variable intergenic non-coding spacer rpl32–trnL, primers rpl32 F (forward) and trnL UAG (reverse) were used at an annealing temperature of 57°C. Purification of the PCR product for sequencing was carried out with a mixture of ammonium acetate and ethanol (when preparing 96% ethanol for 50 ml of such a mixture, 1.5 ml of 5 M ammonium acetate, 4.7 ml of water and 43.8 ml of 96% ethanol are taken). DNA was sequenced with an automatic sequencer ABI 3500xl (Applied Biosystems) of the company Synthol (Russia). The obtained nucleotide sequences were processed with BioEdit v. 7.0.5.3 (Hall, 1999). The obtained data were deposited in the GenBank database (NCBI, 2022) (Table 1).

Four ISSR primers were also used, namely UBC841 [(GA8)YG], M2 [(AC)8(C/T)G], M7 [(AC)8(C/T)G], M11 [(CACACA)2 (A/G)]. Pre-denaturation took place for 3 min at 94°C. Elongation lasted 30 s at 94°C, then 30 s at 37°C with M11, at 45°C with UBC 841, at 50°C with M2, and at 55°C with primer M7. Then elongation took place for 1 min at 72°C. The described process was repeated 35 times, and each subsequent time the elongation lasted 2 s longer at 72°C. The final stage was elongated for 3 min at 72°C.

The amplification products have been separated by electrophoresis in 1.7% agarose gel with the addition of ethidium bromide in $0.5 \times$ TBE buffer for 1 h. Then the DNA fragments have been photographed in ultraviolet light in GelDoc-It Imaging System (LCD/LM-26E, USA) (Fig. S1). To determine their lengths, a 100bp + molecular weight marker was used. Images with DNA fragments have been analysed using CrossChecker software (Buntjer, 2000), with compilation of binary matrices of the presence/absence of frag-

ments of the same length. The obtained data are presented in the form of a matrix of binary features, in which the presence or absence of a certain fragment has been coded as 1 or 0, respectively. The resulting matrix has been analysed, with the non-metric multidimensional scaling method using the Jaccard distance in PAST v. 4.06 (Hammer et al., 2001). The hybridity of the studied specimens has been analysed, based on the results of ISSR analysis with NewHybrids software (Anderson & Thompson, 2002).

Table 1. *Solidago* spp. specimens used for molecular genetic analysis

Species	Specimen code	Barcode	Specimen ID in GenBank	
			ITS 1–2	rpl32–trnL
<i>Solidago juncea</i> Aiton (outgroup)	Sj	MHA0095780	MT584230	MT587694
<i>Solidago canadensis</i> L.	ScTu	MW 1066856	MZ224518	MZ230669
	Sc2	MHA0454305	ON637729	ON677260
	Sc3	–	ON637730	ON677261
	Sc5	MHA0454303	ON637731	ON677262
	Sc6	MHA0454302	ON637732	ON677263
	Sc8	–	ON637733	ON677264
	Sc9	–	ON637734	ON677265
	Sc12	–	–	ON677266
	Sc13	–	ON637735	ON677267
	Sc14	MHA0454308	ON637736	ON677268
	Sc15	–	ON637737	ON677269
	Sc16	–	ON637738	ON677270
	Sc17	MHA0454304	ON637739	ON677271
	Sc20	MHA0454306	ON637740	ON677272
Sc21	MHA0454307	ON637741	ON677273	
<i>Solidago × niedereideri</i> Khek	Sn1Tu	MW 1066857	MZ224519	MZ230670
	Sn2Tu	MW 1066858	MZ224520	MZ230671
	Sn2	MHA0454295	ON637742	ON677274
	Sn3	–	–	ON677275
	Sn5	MHA0454291	ON637743	ON677276
	Sn6	MHA0454290	–	ON677277
	Sn7	MHA0454299	ON637744	ON677278
	Sn8	MHA0454297	–	ON677279
	Sn9	–	ON637745	ON677280
	Sn10	–	ON637746	ON677281
	Sn11	–	–	ON677282
	Sn12	–	–	ON677283
	Sn13a	–	–	ON677284
	Sn13b	–	–	ON677285
	Sn14	MHA0454294	ON637747	ON677286
	Sn15	–	ON637748	ON677287
	Sn16	–	ON637749	ON677288
	Sn17	MHA0454292	ON637750	ON677289
	Sn19	MHA0454296	ON637751	ON677290
	Sn21	–	ON637752	ON677291
	<i>Solidago virgaurea</i> L.	Sv1Tu	MW 1066859	MZ224521
Sv2Tu		MW 1066859	MZ224522	MZ230672
Sv1		–	ON637753	ON677292
Sv2		MHA0454273	ON637754	ON677293
Sv3		–	ON637755	ON677294
Sv4		–	–	ON677295
Sv5		–	ON637756	ON677296
Sv6		MHA0454274	ON637757	ON677297
Sv16	–	ON637758	ON677298	

To investigate the propagation mechanism of *S. × niedereideri*, we used ITS 1–2 and ISSR data to distinguish between vegetative propagation (in this case, some of closely located individuals would be genetically identical) and sexual reproduction. In the latter case, we can distinguish between two hypotheses: i) all individuals are a result of *de novo* hybridisation events, i.e. F₁ hybrids (in this case, *S. × niedereideri* specimens would be intermediate in nuclear markers, with no overlap between parental species); ii) some individuals are resulted from sexual reproduction of existing hybrid individuals, i.e. F₂ hybrids and/or backcrosses (in this case, some *S. × niedereideri* specimens would be closer to one of parental species).

Results

In 2021, 21 clusters of ramets with morphology intermediate between *S. canadensis* and *S. virgaurea* have been found. The number of ramets per cluster varied from 1 to 24, with a mean value of 8.8 ± 6.7 (standard deviation); median and quar-

tiles are 7 (4–13). Henceforth we treated these ramet clusters as separate individuals.

Individuals with intermediate morphology were located either far from other *Solidago* individuals (by several metres) or close to *S. canadensis* clusters (at a distance of less than 1 m). Only in one case, both *S. virgaurea* and *S. canadensis* were located at close proximity.

Analysis of ITS 1–2 showed that all *S. virgaurea* individuals belong to the same group, while all *S. canadensis* individuals belong to the other group (Fig. 1). Individuals of *S. × niedereideri*, with heterozygosity at many (but not all) sites, segregating between parental species (e.g. see Fig. S2), are divided into two groups. One group is close to *S. virgaurea*; the second one is sister to the clade containing *S. canadensis*. At the same time, most of the hybrid individuals are close to *S. canadensis*. It is interesting that the individual with intermediate morphology, which is closest to *S. canadensis* according to ITS 1–2, has chloroplast DNA of *S. virgaurea* haplotype. This excludes its identification as *S. canadensis*.

Fig. 1. Phylogenetic tree of *Solidago* specimens from «Aleksin Bor» Natural Monument (Tula Region, European Russia) based on comparison of sequences of nuclear ribosomal internal transcribed spacers ITS 1–2, constructed with Neighbour Joining algorithm. Numbers at nodes are bootstrap values (%). Indices denote specimens’ codes (see Table 1).

Analysis of the chloroplast marker *rpl32-trL* showed that 12 (60%, 95% confidence interval 36–81%) plants had *S. canadensis* as a mother plant. Individuals with intermediate morphology with different chloroplast DNA origin did not differ in the number of ramets (median; min – max): 4; 2.5–13.5 for *S. virgaurea* vs. 7; 4.5–13.0 for *S. canadensis* ($p = 0.52$, according to the Mann-Whitney test). Five individuals with chloroplast DNA of *S. virgaurea* were situated near the dense groups of *S. canadensis*.

The distance between *S. × niedereideri* individuals in the population was (mean \pm SD) 5.3 ± 3.7 m with min–max at 0.5–161.5 m. In this case, three groups of closely located individuals (separated by less than 1 m from each other) can be distinguished (3, 4, and 5 individuals in each group). In none of these groups, the plants were genetically identical, according to the ISSR analysis. Moreover, in some cases, closely located individuals turned out to be genetically distant from each other.

Ordination of the ISSR analysis results (Fig. 2) showed that all studied individuals of the parental species (except for one *S. virgaurea* specimen) fall into clearly defined clusters, while *S. × niedereideri* specimens overlap with both of them, tending to be close to *S. canadensis*. The lack of allele segregating between parental species did not allow performing adequate hybrid analysis using NewHybrids software.

Discussion

All the studied specimens with intermediate morphology can indeed be attributed to the nothospecies *S. × niedereideri*, based on their position on the ITS 1–2 tree (Fig. 1). These data, together with ordination of ISSR data (Fig. 2), suggest that many specimens with intermediate morphology are not F_1 hybrids, but are backcrosses predominantly with *S. canadensis* or F_2 hybrids, all of which should be assigned to nothospecies *S. × niedereideri* according to the botanical nomenclature (Article 4.1; Turland et al., 2018). Altogether, these results suggest introgression in this three-species system. Possibly, individual Sv5, phenotypically identifiable as *S. virgaurea*, distinct from other conspecifics according to ISSR (Fig. 2), but not according to ITS (Fig. 1), also has an admixture of genes from *S. canadensis* due to the introgression. So, here we have a «hybrid swarm», previously not reported for these three species. In contrast to our results, analysis of the relative DNA content, carried out in mixed populations in Eastern Europe, showed that all studied *S. × niedereideri* individuals are likely F_1 hybrids, and only some individuals

phenotypically identifiable as *S. canadensis* could be backcrosses, but the authors themselves pointed to the weak validity of this conclusion (Skokanová et al., 2022). In addition, this situation differs from that, for example, with hybrids of *Arctium* spp. (Asteraceae), where all nothospecies individuals turned out to be F_1 hybrids, which, apparently, do not reproduce sexually (see Fig. 2 in the present paper, and Fig. 2 in Replinger et al., 2007).

The plastid markers showed that initial hybridisation events leading to the studied population of *S. × niedereideri* took place in both directions. The bidirectional hybridisation between *S. canadensis* and *S. virgaurea* was stated in the first research, confirmed the hybrid nature of *S. × niedereideri* (Pliszko & Zalewska-Gałosz, 2016), as in the first description of the studied population (Lysenkov & Galkina, 2022). Descendants of hybridisation events of both directions are in nearly equal proportions (though small sample size brought about low power). Hence, we did not see any evidence that one of the directions is more probable, or it leads to fitter individuals.

In the studied population, *S. × niedereideri* tends to grow closer to *S. canadensis* rather than to *S. virgaurea*. In the original description of the hybrid Khek (1905) pointed out that it grows «next to *S. canadensis* and not far from *S. virga aurea*». Since five individuals with chloroplast DNA of *S. virgaurea* were located near *S. canadensis*, their emergence cannot be explained by the seed abscission resulted from pollination of *S. canadensis*, which is unsurprising, given that *Solidago* fruits are wind-dispersing. However, in the studied plant community, the abundance of *S. virgaurea* is rather low. Therefore, its preferential proximity to *S. canadensis* can be just consequences of its higher abundance rather than any special affinity.

Fig. 2. Non-metric multidimensional scaling of studied *Solidago* spp. individuals based on ISSR results with Jaccard distances. Designations: green dots – *Solidago virgaurea*, purple dots – *S. canadensis*, orange dots – *S. × niedereideri*. Indices denote specimens' codes (see Table 1).

Even closely located ramet clusters are genetically different. Hence, we can reject the clonal propagation. This is consistent with the results of a study conducted in Poland, where no long rhizomes were found in *S. × niedereideri* (Pliszko & Kostrakiewicz-Gierałt, 2019). It was also hypothesised that *S. × niedereideri* can reproduce vegetatively through physical separation of ramets from a single clone due to *Sus scrofa* Linnaeus, 1758 rooting or plowing (Pliszko & Kostrakiewicz-Gierałt, 2019), but none of these possible processes took place in the studied meadow. So, the high amount of *S. × niedereideri* is explained by sexual reproduction.

Thus, the studied *S. × niedereideri* individuals can apparently be called a population that at least partially self-reproduces. Besides genetic data, this conclusion is supported by the fact that *S. × niedereideri* specimens are distributed in a small part of the field within the *S. canadensis* population, rather than evenly over the entire meadow. The age of this population is unknown, but it longs at least four year (2019–2022). Therefore, the conservative assessment of its invasion status according to Pyšek et al. (2004) is «casual alien plant». But we believe, that this population is naturalising now, since new individuals establish through sexual reproduction. However, *S. × niedereideri* does not seem to be invasive here, since we do not have evidence of offspring at considerable distances.

In the meadow, the soil texture and pH is within the range of those reported for *S. × niedereideri*, which is not surprising, given this range is rather wide, from sand to loam and from strongly acidic to slightly alkaline, respectively (Pliszko et al., 2023). In the study area, climatic conditions are also suitable for *S. × niedereideri*. So, the average annual temperature is 25°C, which is higher than 18°C, and the temperature of the coldest month is lower than 0°C (Jaźwa et al., 2018).

The parental *Solidago* species are obligate outcrossers (Werner et al., 1980; Kudo, 2022). Hence, self-pollination is also unlikely in *S. × niedereideri*. However, the hybrid is actively visited by anthophilous insects, common with parental species. For instance, Syrphidae and *Bombus* species can be the most important agents of the pollen transfer among all three species in the studied population (Lysenkov & Galkina, 2021).

Some *S. × niedereideri* individuals identified in 2021 were not found in August 2022; the only individual, known since 2019 (Lysenkov & Galkina, 2022), almost did not form shoots. At the same

time, in August 2022, ten previously undetected individuals, morphologically confidently identified as *S. × niedereideri* were found. It can evidence for a high turnover in this population, with some individuals dying (or at least not flowering, since we did not search for vegetative shoots), and some new ones appearing every year.

During 2019–2022, one of the parental species, *S. virgaurea*, practically disappeared in the studied meadow. Unfortunately, we did not measure accurately the percent cover of the vegetation. But, in 2019–2022, we observed insect visitations to all flowering plants in this plant community (Lysenkov, 2022). Therefore, we can try to use the number of insects visited this species as a rough estimate. In 2019, *S. virgaurea* accounted for 15% of all registered insect visits to flowers in the studied plant community, whereas in 2020 and 2021 for less than 5%. In 2022, only sparse *S. virgaurea* individuals remained in the meadow, which possibly reduces the opportunities for *de novo* formation of *S. × niedereideri* in new hybridisation events. There are known cases when an invasive species or its hybrid with a native species displaced the latter (e.g. Abbott et al., 2003; Bleeker et al., 2007; Zalapa et al., 2009). Due to the rarity of the hybrid, this threat from *S. × niedereideri* to the *S. virgaurea* in European Russia still seems to be insignificant (Vinogradova & Galkina, 2020), whereas in more Western European countries, where *S. × niedereideri* disperses more actively, this threat is considered significant (Skokanová et al., 2022). Almost full disappearance of *S. virgaurea* in this plant community, coupled with an increasing population size of *S. × niedereideri* and a high introgression rate, can be just a spurious correlation. So, special studies of causes are needed, but we suppose that these observations form evidence, though weak, in favour of a higher threat to native parental species from the hybrid.

Conclusions

New individuals of *S. × niedereideri* in the studied population are formed not only as a result of new hybridisation events between parental species but are also a result of sexual reproduction of already existing individuals, including through backcrossing with parental species. The resulting introgression apparently may lead to the displacement of the native species by the hybrid. Thus, *S. × niedereideri* behaves like a stabilised hybrid, treated as a species.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful to two anonymous reviewers, whose comments helped us to highly improve the manuscript. This study was conducted as a part of the State Assignment to the Lomonosov Moscow State University, project AAAA-A16-116021660031-5 «Analysis of Regularities in Micro- and Macroevolutions». The study has been performed within the framework of the State Task for the Main Botanical Garden of RAS (№122042500074-5) and the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation (grant №075-15-2021-678 for the Centre for Collective Use «Herbarium of the Main Botanical Garden of RAS»).

Supporting Information

The information on genetic analysis results (Electronic Supplement. Examples of genetic analysis results of the studied specimens of *Solidago* spp.) may be found in the [Supporting Information](#).

References

- Abbott R.J., James J.K., Milne R.I., Giles A.C.M. 2003. Plant introductions, hybridization and gene flow. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 358(1434): 1123–1132. DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2003.1289
- Anderson E.C., Thompson E.A. 2002. A model-based method for identifying species hybrids using multilocus genetic data. *Genetics* 160(3): 1217–1229. DOI: 10.1093/genetics/160.3.1217
- Bleeker W., Schmitz U., Ristow M. 2007. Interspecific hybridisation between alien and native plant species in Germany and its consequences for native biodiversity. *Biological Conservation* 137(2): 248–253. DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2007.02.004
- Buntjer J.B. 2000. Cross Checker: computer assisted scoring of genetic AFLP data. In: *Plant, Animal Genome 8th Conference*. S. Diego. P. 9–12.
- Gudžinskas Z., Žalneravičius E. 2016. *Solidago* × *snarskii* nothosp. nov. (Asteraceae) from Lithuania and its position in the infrageneric classification of the genus. *Phytotaxa* 253(2): 147–155. DOI: 10.11646/phytotaxa.253.2.4
- Hall T.A. 1999. BioEdit: A User-Friendly Biological Sequence Alignment Editor and Analysis Program for Windows 95/98/NT. *Nucleic Acids Symposium Series* 41: 95–98.
- Hammer Ø., Harper D.A.T., Ryan P.D. 2001. PAST: Paleontological Statistics Software Package for Education and Data Analysis. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 4(1): 9.
- Jaźwa M., Jędrzejczak E., Klichowska E., Pliszko A. 2018. Predicting the potential distribution area of *Solidago* × *niederederi* (Asteraceae). *Turkish Journal of Botany* 42(1): 51–56. DOI: 10.3906/bot-1703-17
- Khek E. 1905. Floristisches aus Ober-Oesterreich. *Allgemeine botanische Zeitschrift für Systematik, Floristik, Pflanzengeographie* 11(2): 21–23.
- Kudo G. 2022. Outcrossing syndrome in alpine plants: implications for flowering phenology and pollination success. *Ecological Research* 37(3): 288–300. DOI: 10.1111/1440-1703.12314
- Lysenkov S.N. 2022. Effect of *Solidago canadensis* invasion on the structure of interactions of native entomophilous plants and anthophilous insects. In: *Modern Problems of Biological Evolution*. Moscow: State Darwin Museum. P. 124–125. [In Russian]
- Lysenkov S.N., Galkina M.A. 2022. First Finding of *Solidago* × *niederederi* Khek. (Asteraceae) in Tula Region (European Part of Russia). *Russian Journal of Biological Invasions* 13(1): 81–86. DOI: 10.1134/S2075111722010106
- Lysenkov S.N., Galkina M.A. 2021. First found of *Solidago* × *niederederi* (Asteraceae) in Tula Oblast: What can Aleksin population of this species tell about its distribution and ecology?. In: *Study and conservation of biodiversity of Tula Region and other regions of Russia*. Tula: Tula State University. P. 89–95. [In Russian]
- Migdalek G., Kolczyk J., Pliszko A., Kościńska-Pajak M., Słomka A. 2014. Reduced pollen viability and achene development in *Solidago* × *niederederi* Khek from Poland. *Acta Societatis Botanicorum Poloniae* 83(3): 251–255. DOI: 10.5586/asbp.2014.025
- NCBI. 2022. Nucleotide database. Available from www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide
- Nilsson A. 1976. Spontana gullris hybrid (*Solidago canadensis* × *virgaurea*) i Sverige och Danmark. *Svensk Botanisk Tidskrift* 70: 7–16.
- Pliszko A., Kostrakiewicz-Gierałt K. 2017. Resolving the naturalization strategy of *Solidago* × *niederederi* (Asteraceae) by the production of sexual ramets and seedlings. *Plant Ecology* 218(11–12): 1243–1253. DOI: 10.1007/s11258-017-0762-6
- Pliszko A., Kostrakiewicz-Gierałt K. 2019. The importance of sexual, asexual and mixed ramet clusters in production of descendant ramets in populations of *Solidago* × *niederederi* (Asteraceae). *Biologia* 74(8): 953–960. DOI: 10.2478/s11756-019-00233-y
- Pliszko A., Kostrakiewicz-Gierałt K., Makuch-Pietras I. 2023. The effect of site conditions and type of ramet clusters on sexual and asexual ramets of *Solidago* × *niederederi* (Asteraceae). *NeoBiota* 85: 125–143. DOI: 10.3897/neobiota.85.98796
- Pliszko A., Zalewska-Gałosz J. 2016. Molecular evidence for hybridization between invasive *Solidago canadensis* and native *S. virgaurea*. *Biological Invasions* 18(11): 3103–3108. DOI: 10.1007/s10530-016-1213-3
- Pyšek P., Richardson D.M., Rejmánek M., Webster G.L., Williamson M., Kirschner J. 2004. Alien plants in checklists and floras: towards better communication

- between taxonomists and ecologists. *Taxon* 53(1): 131–143. DOI: 10.2307/4135498
- Repplinger M., Johannesen J., Seitz A., Comes H.P. 2007. Morphological and molecular evidence for hybridization and introgression in Central European *Arctium* (Asteraceae). *Plant Systematics and Evolution* 268(1–4): 75–95. DOI: 10.1007/s00606-007-0547-9
- Skokanová K., Mered'a P., Šingliarová B., Španiel S. 2020a. Lectotype of *Solidago ×niederederi* (Asteraceae) selected from a recently rediscovered original material. *Phytotaxa* 438(1): 62–64. DOI: 10.11646/phytotaxa.438.1.8
- Skokanová K., Šingliarová B., Španiel S., Hodálová I., Mered'a P. 2020b. Tracking the expanding distribution of *Solidago ×niederederi* (Asteraceae) in Europe and first records from three countries within the Carpathian region. *BioInvasions Records* 9(4): 670–684. DOI: 10.3391/bir.2020.9.4.02
- Skokanová K., Šingliarová B., Španiel S., Mered'a P., Mártonfióvá L., Zozomová-Lihová J. 2022. Relative DNA content differences reliably identify *Solidago ×niederederi*, a hybrid between native and invasive alien species. *Preslia* 94: 183–213. DOI: 10.23855/preslia.2022.183
- Turland N.J., Wiersma J.H., Barrie F.R., Greuter W., Hawksworth D.L., Herendeen P.S., Knapp S., Kusber W.-H., Li D.-Z., Marhold K., May T.W., McNeill J., Monro A.M., Prado J., Price M.J., Smith G.F. (Eds.). 2018. International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (Shenzhen Code) adopted by the Nineteenth International Botanical Congress Shenzhen, China, July 2017. In: *Regnum Vegetabile*. Vol. 159. Glashütten: Koeltz Botanical Books. 254 p. DOI: 10.12705/Code.2018
- Vinogradova Y.K., Galkina M.A. 2020. Hybridization as a factor of invasive activity of alien goldenrod species (*Solidago*). *Biology Bulletin Reviews* 10(1): 57–70. DOI: 10.1134/S2079086420010090
- Werner P.A., Bradbury I.K., Gross R.S. 1980. The Biology of Canadian Weeds. 45. *Solidago canadensis* L. *Canadian Journal of Plant Science* 60(4): 1393–1409. DOI: 10.4141/cjps80-194
- Wen J., Zimmer E.A. 1996. Phylogeny and biogeography of *Panax* L. (the ginseng genus, Araliaceae): inferences from ITS sequences of nuclear ribosomal DNA. *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 6(2): 167–177. DOI: 10.1006/mpev.1996.0069
- Zalapa J.E., Brunet J., Guries R.P. 2009. Patterns of hybridization and introgression between invasive *Ulmus pumila* (Ulmaceae) and native *U. rubra*. *American Journal of Botany* 96(6): 1116–1128. DOI: 10.3732/ajb.0800334

ГЕНЕТИЧЕСКАЯ СТРУКТУРА ПОПУЛЯЦИИ *SOLIDAGO × NIEDEREDERI* (ASTERACEAE) В ПАМЯТНИКЕ ПРИРОДЫ «АЛЕКСИН БОР» (ЕВРОПЕЙСКАЯ РОССИЯ)

С. Н. Лысенков¹

¹Московский государственный университет имени М.В. Ломоносова, Россия
e-mail: s_lysenkov@mail.ru

²Главный Ботанический сад имени Н.В. Цицина РАН, Россия
e-mail: mawa.galkina@gmail.com

Solidago ×niederederi – возникший в Европе гибрид между аборигенным *S. virgaurea* и инвазионным *S. canadensis*. Его способность к натурализации остается дискуссионной. Одна из самых больших известных популяций этого нотовида (более 20 кластеров рамет, рассматриваемых как особи) расположена в памятнике природы «Алексин Бор» (г. Алексин, Тульская область, Россия) в пойме р. Оки. Генетическая структура этой популяции была изучена с помощью хлоропластных и ядерных маркеров. Анализ последовательности ядерного рибосомального внутреннего транскрибируемого спейсера ITS 1–2 показал, что все особи с промежуточной морфологией действительно являются гибридами. Данные по межгенному хлоропластному некодирующему спейсеру rpl32–trnL показали, что *S. canadensis* является материнским видом для 60% изученных особей. Показано, что даже близко расположенные особи не являются клонами, т.е. они возникли в результате полового, а не вегетативного размножения. Анализ маркеров ISSR показал, что изученные особи *S. ×niederederi* в этой популяции – это не только гибриды F₁, но и их потомки (гибриды F₂ и/или бэккроссы, преимущественно с *S. canadensis*). Мы пришли к выводу, что *S. ×niederederi* успешно натурализуется в изучаемом сообществе и, возможно, вытесняется его аборигенный родительский вид *S. virgaurea* за счет интрогрессии.

Ключевые слова: ISSR, ITS 1–2, rpl32–trnL, биологические инвазии, гибридизация, нотовид, чужеродный вид

AVIFAUNA DIVERSITY ASSESSMENT IN THE COMMUNAL NATURAL PROTECTED AREA EL GAVILÁN, CENTRAL COAST OF OAXACA, MEXICO

Jesús García-Grajales*

Universidad del Mar, Mexico
*e-mail: archosaurio@yahoo.com.mx

Received: 01.06.2023. Revised: 27.07.2023. Accepted: 12.08.2023.

Tropical dry forest (TDF) is an ecosystem with a pronounced seasonality and high animal diversity. It is threatened by a wide variety of anthropogenic activities such as human population growth, deforestation rate, tourism development, forest fires, overhunting, and wildlife trade. One of the strategies for this biodiversity conservation is the creation of Communal Natural Protected Areas (CNPA), which are poorly explored. The aim of this study was to supply an assessment of the avian diversity in the CNPA El Gavilán on the Central Coast of Oaxaca (Mexico) during two seasons (dry and rainy). Sampling has been carried out at two localities (named as Centre and Mountain) between November 2018 and September 2019, using a point count method. At each locality, we sampled one transect varying in length, but with five-point counts separated by a minimum of 200 m. We made monthly two visits per transect. Birds were counted from a fixed raising position within a circle of 50-m radius for a specific period (10 min.) at every point. In total, 85 species were recorded, which belong to 65 genera, 24 families, and 13 orders. The most representative order was Passeriformes with 53 species. Most species (83) were considered very rare, and two species (*Aratinga canicularis* and *Calocitta formosa*) were rare. Regarding the avian diversity, ⁰D, the Centre locality had 74 species (19 exclusive species), while the Mountain locality had 65 species (11 exclusive species). The dry season had a higher diversity ($H' = 3.44$) than the rainy season ($H' = 3.41$), but there were no significant differences (Hutcheson $t = 0.365$, d.f. = 1, $p > 0.05$). Eighty-two percent (70 species) were considered residents, 15.3% (13 species) were winter migrants, 1.2% (one species) were summer migrants, and 1.2% (one species) were transient. Of the total registered taxa, 50 species were principally insectivorous, 14 species were grain-frugivorous, eight species were omnivorous, six species were carnivorous, and six species were nectarivorous. The avifauna of CNPA El Gavilán shows that a marked effect does not exist in the species composition between seasons. Due to the species richness recorded and estimated there, the study area should be considered in conservation policies, particularly because this territory is under intense pressure due to changes in land use.

Key words: abundance, insectivorous, migrant, resident, richness, transects, transient, trophic guild

Introduction

In Mexico, tropical dry forest (TDF) is an ecosystem with a pronounced seasonality and high animal diversity (Dirzo & Ceballos, 2010; Meave et al., 2012). However, this ecosystem is threatened by a wide variety of anthropogenic activities (Trejo, 2010), like growth of the human population, deforestation rate, tourism development, wildfires, overhunting, and wildlife trade (Olson & Dinerstein, 2002). Particularly, TDF occupies 16% of the territory of Oaxaca state and exists as two forest types, namely deciduous tropical forests and semi-deciduous tropical forests (Torres-Colín, 2004; Trejo, 2010). In this ecosystem, the animal diversity is high. Particularly in the Planicie Costera del Pacífico (central coast) and Sierra Sur, the overall species richness is the highest in the Oaxaca state (González-Pérez et al., 2004).

Besides the Protected Areas as the main strategy to preserve biodiversity (Monterrubio-Solís, 2019), another effective area-based conservation

measure for the protection of TDF is the creation of Communal Natural Protected Areas (CNPAs) (Peña-Azcona et al., 2022). In Oaxaca state, CNPAs operate as a mechanism for the conservation of biodiversity and local natural resources through the participation of local human communities (Rodríguez-Luna et al., 2011). One of them is the CNPA El Gavilán, which was certified in 2011 and located in the transition zone between Planicie Costera del Pacífico and Sierra Sur of Oaxaca state.

Among the vertebrate species affected by the loss of TDF and by the seasonal fluctuations in this ecosystem, birds represent one of the most important biological groups because they are involved in many ecological processes (Gonzalez-Christen, 2010). The structure of ecological communities varies with respect to the season and temporal changes (Modena et al., 2013; Falcão et al., 2014). Therefore, there is a growing concern to protect the biodiversity of this ecosystem (Dirzo & Ceballos, 2010). In addition, the avifauna monitor-

ing in TDF provides valuable information on the ecological health and status of these ecosystems. Taking it into account, the avifauna of TDF acts as an indicator of ecosystem quality because birds are very sensitive to deforestation and land-use change (Rurangwa et al., 2021).

In Mexico, the avifauna is characterised by a high species diversity, with 1123 bird taxa recorded (Navarro-Sigüenza et al., 2014). So, avian studies have benefited from extensive data already accumulated over decades (Peterson et al., 1998), and these generate more detailed analyses (Peterson et al., 1993, 1998).

In the Oaxaca state, although avifauna studies have increased in recent years (Vázquez et al., 2009; Bojorges-Baños, 2011a,b; Santos-Benítez et al., 2013; Lavariega et al., 2016; Ruiz Bruce Taylor et al., 2017; Ruiz et al., 2019; Lavariega et al., 2020), there are still poorly explored regions. For example, the transition zone between Planicie Costera del Pacífico and Sierra Sur of Oaxaca has not been studied thoroughly, while the Pacific coast of Oaxaca has a higher number of studies (Vázquez et al., 2009; Bojorges-Baños, 2011a,b; Santos-Benítez et al., 2013; Lavariega et al., 2016, 2020; Ruiz Bruce Taylor et al., 2017; Ruiz et al., 2019). Moreover, the knowledge of how the structure of ecological communities varies with respect to season and temporal changes remains poorly documented in the previously described transition zone (Cecon et al., 2006). The TDF is among the ecosystems most affected by deforestation and other human activities (Dirzo et al., 2011). It is important to understand the richness and seasonal variation in the assemblages of birds to guide successful conservation efforts.

Most avian inventories have been carried out on the central and southwestern coast of Oaxaca state, while no assessment of the avian diversity is available in CNPA El Gavilán. Moreover, in recent years, this area is under pressure due to various anthropogenic activities, such as high deforestation, overhunting, and human population growth around this site. Therefore, this study was aimed to supply an assessment of avifauna diversity between two seasons and two localities with different vegetation conditions in CNPA El Gavilán. Thus, we expect that this work will serve as a point of reference for later studies on the conservation, ecology, and distribution of birds, and contribute to better planning strategies for the conservation of bird species in

the transition area between the Planicie Costera del Pacífico and Sierra Sur of Oaxaca state.

Material and Methods

Study area

The fieldwork has been conducted in the CNPA El Gavilán (Fig. 1), located in the municipality of Santa María Tonameca on the central coast of Oaxaca state, Mexico. This site is situated in the transition zone between the coastal plain and the Sierra Madre del Sur physiographic province. The study area is located at an altitudinal gradient of 250–1100 m a.s.l., with pronounced slopes that make it difficult to transit vertically.

The climate is warm and sub-humid, with an annual mean temperature of 26.8°C. The annual mean precipitation is 2245 mm (García, 1973), with a long period of drought from November to May, and a short period of rains (Trejo, 2010). Some dominant tree species in this region are *Ceiba aesculifolia* subsp. *parvifolia* (Rose) P.E.Gibbs & Semir, *Lysiloma divaricatum* (Jacq.) J.F.Macbr., and *Plumeria rubra* L. (Torres-Colín, 2004). In forests formed by these trees, the main plants are shrubs, vines, and cacti (Trejo, 1998). Among them, the predominant species are *Vachellia campeachiana* (Mill.) Seigler & Ebinger, *V. farnesiana* (L.) Wight & Arn., *V. cornigera* (L.) Seigler & Ebinger, *Guaiacum coulteri* A.Gray, and *Opuntia decumbens* Salm-Dyck (Salas-Morales et al., 2003).

Fig. 1. The location of Communal Natural Protected Area El Gavilán in Santa María Tonameca municipality, Oaxaca state, Mexico.

We divided the CNPA El Gavilán into two localities (Centre and Mountain) according to their ecological and topographic characteristics and principal vegetation types. In the Centre locality, TDF dominate, while the Mountain locality is a transition zone from the TDF to the pine-oak (*Pinus* sp., *Oak* sp.) forest. Another reason for this division was due to logistical facilities and access to the study sites.

Data collection in the field

Sampling has been carried out between November 2018 and September 2019, during the dry season (November – May) and the rainy season (June – September). It was aimed to document the avian diversity using a point count distance sampling method (Reynolds et al., 1980). At each locality, one transect varying in length was set ranging from 250 m a.s.l. to 1000 m a.s.l., covering various altitudes and, overall, involving the dominant vegetation. Each transect was composed of five-point counts separated by a minimum altitude at 200 m a.s.l. Each monthly visit had duration of four days, i.e. two days per each locality. During each visit to a locality, two rounds of surveys have been conducted in the morning (06:00–11:00 h) and the afternoon (16:00–19:00 h) (Lloyd & Marsden, 2008), that covers the bird activity schedules (Navarro-Sigüenza et al., 2014); but it was only during hours of suitable weather (i.e. in the absence of rain or strong wind). During the rounds and at each point count, birds have been counted from a fixed raising position within a circle of 50-m radius for a specific period (10 m). Bird species were mainly recorded visually using Nikon (10 × 50 mm) binoculars, but also by songs, whenever possible photographs were taken with a Canon camera and lens 70–300 mm. The same procedures were realised in both seasons.

Alternately, in both seasons, five mist nets (12 × 6 m length) were put in each established transect, along pathways, edges, vegetation fragments, and near streams. The nets were open under the same scheme of schedules and the time as in the case of transects described above. They were checked every 30 min. to ensure that the birds remained alive and in good condition. The use of both methods (point counts and mist nets) in combination was expected to increase the number of bird species recorded (Zakaria & Rajpar, 2010). But the species registered by the mist net technique were excluded from the rela-

tive abundance analysis because this method is not suitable to assess relative abundance (Hutto et al., 1986). No specimens were collected after being identified and photographed. All specimens were released in the same area where they were caught.

Identification of birds was done by using field guides (Howell & Webb, 1995; Van Perlo, 2006; Bojorges-Baños, 2012). Taxonomic nomenclature and resident status were based on Chesser et al. (2022).

Data analysis

To estimate the total species richness, species accumulation curves were plotted to assess the completeness of the species inventory for each locality, using nonparametric estimators Chao 2 and Bootstrap, which are based on presence estimates (Hortal et al., 2006; Colwell, 2009). So, both estimators have been shown to be reliable for relatively small sampling units (i.e. circular plots, mist nets; Hortal et al., 2006). In addition, the combination of sampling methods increases the likelihood of detecting species, allowing for a higher number of species to be recorded. Regarding this, Bojorges-Baños & López-Mata (2006) demonstrated the importance of performing this type of combined samplings to achieve better results.

The species richness was estimated for each locality. In addition, the species richness was compared by calculating the effective numbers of species per season based on the sample coverage (Jost, 2006), which is the probability that the next recorded organism will be of the same species as the previously recorded one. The species richness is the number of species present in an area (Dettmers et al., 1999).

Alpha diversity was obtained in terms of equivalent numbers (Chao et al., 2010) from diversity orders, considering the ⁰D order diversity (species richness) and ¹D order diversity (common species) (Jost & González-Oreja, 2012) for each locality and season. In addition, to know the significant differences between locality and season diversity, the Shannon-Wiener index (*H'*) was obtained as a baseline to examine differences in bird diversity between seasons, and between localities and seasons using the t-test modified by Hutcheson (1970). Analyses were performed using PAST ver. 4.08 (Hammer et al., 2001).

The relative abundance (n/N) of bird species per locality, where n is the total number of birds of a particular species and N is the total number of birds of

all species, was obtained considering the percentage frequency of records, according to Resendiz-Cruz et al. (2017) categories, namely very abundant (90–100%), abundant (65–89%), common (31–64%), rare (10–30%), and very rare (1–9%).

Bird species were assigned to six trophic guilds (insectivore, frugivore, nectarivore, granivore, omnivore, and ground-feeding) based on primary diet items (Allen & Hoekstra, 1990; Arizmendi et al., 1990). In addition, seasonality was determined according to Arizmendi & Espinosa de los Monteros (1996), and Navarro-Sigüenza et al. (2014) criteria, and assigned as: 1) permanent resident (R), 2) winter migrant (Wm), 3) summer migrant (Sm), and 4) transient (T). In terms of endemism, birds have been classified to endemic species (species with a geographical distribution limited to one country), quasi-endemic (species with geographic distribution extends outside Mexico), and semi-endemic (species endemic to the country for a time of the year) (González-García & Gómez de Silva, 2003). We assigned conservation risk categories for each species based on Mexican Official Norm (NOM-059-SEMARNAT-2010; DOF, 2010) and the Global IUCN Red List (IUCN, 2019).

Results

In total, we recorded 85 species from 65 genera, 24 families, and 13 orders. Passeriformes had the highest species (53; 62%), followed by Apodiformes (7%) and Columbiformes (7%). Tyrannidae (12 species) and Cardinalidae (nine species) have the highest number of taxa. The genera *Vireo* and *Icterus* were the richest by species (Appendix).

Species accumulation curves according to Chao 2 and Bootstrap predicted an asymptote in 97 species and 95 species, respectively. In this research survey, this means that 87.62% and 89.47% of the estimated total richness were recorded (Fig. 2).

In the study area, most of the species (83) were considered very rare and two species (*Eupsittula canicularis* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Calocitta formosa* (Swainson, 1827)) were rare. Regarding the avian diversity, ⁰D, the Centre locality had 74 species (19 exclusive species), while the Mountain locality had 65 species (11 exclusive species). For avian diversity index, ¹D, the Centre locality showed 3.66 effective species, and the Mountain locality demonstrated 3.02 effective species. There was no significant difference in

species richness between localities ($X^2 = 0.578$, d.f. = 1, $p = 0.092$). According to the avian diversity found between seasons in the CNPA El Gavilán, the dry season had a little more diversity ($H' = 3.44$) than the rainy season ($H' = 3.41$), but there were no significant differences between them (Hutcheson $t = 0.365$, d.f. = 1, $p = 0.086$; Fig. 3). Regarding the diversity between localities (Fig. 4), the Centre locality had a higher diversity in the dry season than the rainy season (dry: $H' = 3.51$; rainy: $H' = 2.77$), and the Mountain had a higher diversity ($H' = 3.05$) in the dry season than in the rainy season ($H' = 2.77$).

According to the seasonality, 82.4% birds (70 species) are considered residents, 15.3% (13 species) are winter migrants, one species (1.2%) is a summer migrant, and one species (1.2%) is transient. Among the localities, the Centre locality had seven species, and one winter migrant species more than the Mountain locality.

Fig. 2. Species-accumulation curve for avian species in the Communal Natural Protected Area El Gavilán, Oaxaca state, Mexico.

Fig. 3. Avian diversity between seasons (dry and rainy) in the Communal Natural Protected Area El Gavilán, Oaxaca state, Mexico.

Fig. 4. Avian diversity between localities (A – Centre, B – Mountain) and seasons in the Communal Natural Protected Area El Gavilán, Oaxaca state, Mexico.

In the CNPA El Gavilán, nine species (10.58 %) are in some conservation category in the Official Mexican law. One species (*Amaurospiza concolor* Cabanis, 1861) is categorised as «Endangered», another species (*Glaucidium palmarum* Nelson, 1901) is categorised as «Threatened». Seven species (*Aulacorhynchus prasinus* (Gould, 1833), *Campephilus guatemalensis* (Hartlaub, 1844), *Aratinga canicularis* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Heliomaster longirostris* (Audebert & Vieillot, 1801), *Passerina ciris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Trogon collaris* Vieillot, 1817) are classified as «Special Protection». The Global IUCN Red List (IUCN, 2019) includes only one species (*Passerina ciris* (Linnaeus, 1758)), classified as Near Threatened. Ten species (*Saucerottia beryllina* (Deppe, 1830), *A. rutila* (Delattre, 1843), *Archilocus colubris* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Cynanthus latirostris* Swainson, 1827, *Heliomaster longirostris* (Audebert & Vieillot, 1801), *Phaetornis mexicanus* Hartert, 1897, *Falco rufigularis* Daudin, 1800, *F. sparverius* Linnaeus, 1758, *Aratinga canicularis*, *Glaucidium palmarum*) are included in Appendix II of CITES.

Only nine species (10.71%; *Glaucidium palmarum*, *Melanerpes chrysogenys* (Vigors, 1839), *Granatellus venustus* Bonaparte, 1850, *Ortalis poliocephala* (Wagler, 1830), *Phaetornis mexicanus*, *Pheugopedius felix* (P.L.Sclater, 1860), *Trogon citreolus* Gould, 1835, *Turdus rufopalliatus* Lafresnaye, 1840, *Vireo hypochryseus* P.L.Sclater, 1863) were recorded as endemic to Mexico, four species (4.71%, *Cynanthus latirostris*, *Dryocopus lineatus* (Linnaeus, 1766), *Empidonax difficilis* S.F.Baird, 1858, *E. occidentalis* Nelson, 1897) are semi-endemic, and two spe-

cies (2.35%, *Cacicus melanicterus* (Bonaparte, 1825), *Momotus mexicanus* Swainson, 1827) are quasi-endemic (Appendix).

Finally, the avian community of the CNPA El Gavilán was grouped into various guilds. Of them, 50 species are insectivorous principally, 14 species are grain-frugivorous, eight species are omnivorous, six species are carnivorous, and six species are nectarivorous. Regarding the abundance of these guilds between sites, carnivore birds showed no significant differences ($X^2 = 0.088$, d.f. = 1, $p = 0.065$), like nectarivorous birds ($X^2 = 0.315$, d.f. = 1, $p = 0.062$), omnivorous birds ($X^2 = 0.528$, d.f. = 1, $p = 0.071$), grain-frugivorous birds ($X^2 = 0.140$, d.f. = 1, $p = 0.068$), and insectivorous birds ($X^2 = 0.140$, d.f. = 1, $p = 0.072$).

Discussion

Mexico has a remarkable richness and diversity of species of many biological groups (Jiménez-Sierra et al., 2014). Recently, the avifauna of several regions in Oaxaca state has been studied to better understand the number of birds that each one contains (Bojorges-Baños, 2011a,b; Santos-Benítez et al., 2013; Lavariega et al., 2016), including the coast of Oaxaca state, but with a tendency to bird community associated with wetlands (Bojorges-Baños, 2011a,b; Ruiz Bruce Taylor et al., 2017). Therefore, little information exists for the Sierra Sur and Planicie Costera sub-provinces in Oaxaca state. For those reasons, this study supplies valuable information about the bird diversity in the transition zone between the Planicie Costera del Pacífico sub-province and Sierra Madre del Sur province, highlighting the

importance of the micro-basin about the regional avifauna richness.

The avifauna of the CNPA El Gavilán represents 7.6% of the 1123 species recorded in Mexico (Navarro-Sigüenza et al., 2014; Berlanga et al., 2015), 11.3% of 754 species recorded in Oaxaca state (Berlanga et al., 2008), and 24.3% of 350 species estimated for the coast of Oaxaca state (Bojorges-Baños, 2011a). Although, the species richness in Mexico may vary from latitudinal, altitudinal, and even vegetation situations as a product of the topographic and physiographic complexity of its landscapes (Wilson et al., 2013). This has been used as an indicator of biodiversity in mainland environments (Hortal et al., 2009) and for understanding the comparisons among communities (Gotelli & Chao, 2013). The high species richness obtained here can be explained by the presence of a high percentage of resident species. The physiognomy of vegetation could have influenced this presence with intrinsic factors such as food and plant composition (Hutto, 1985; Hewson et al., 2011).

According to Chao 2 and Bootstrap estimators, the species accumulation curve reached more than 85% of the intended species, providing that the inventory is reasonably complete. Although specific criteria have not been established to determine whether an inventory is complete or not, most occasions often establish arbitrary limits such as the fact that over 80% of the estimate of richness species is an acceptable value (Jiménez-Valverde & Hortal, 2003). One of the reasons is probably the sampling type (combination of methods) that was recommended for more records (Bojorges-Baños & López-Mata, 2006).

Avian feeding guilds are important for understanding the complexity of ecosystem structure and for supplying updated information on each type of habitat in the ecosystem (Azman et al., 2011). In TDF of southwestern Mexico, insectivorous birds were more abundant in the dry season (Almazán-Núñez et al., 2018) in response to the change in arthropod abundance (Tovar-Sánchez et al., 2004; Vega-Rivera et al., 2010) in the two seasons of a year. In consequence, many birds are more generalists in their diet (Almazán-Núñez et al., 2018). The insectivorous guild was the principal group recorded in the CNPA El Gavilán followed by the grain-frugivorous guild.

In the CNPA El Gavilán, the species composition is characterised by a considerable number of species with little abundance. However,

this is consistent with the general pattern of avifaunal communities, where rare or uncommon species exist, and few species are abundant (Rurangwa et al., 2021). Probably, these species may be responding to the habitat structure and not to climatic conditions. Then, they occupy more than one type of habitats during the year (Goetz et al., 2014).

Although TDF exhibits a marked seasonality that produces physiological stress in the organisms, which inhabit it (Ceccon et al., 2006), the structure of ecological communities varies with respect to the season and temporal changes in the availability of resources (Modena et al., 2013; Falcão et al., 2014). But the CNPA El Gavilán does not show a marked variation in its plant phenology between seasons. Therefore, there is no variation in the composition of bird species. A possible explanation is related to the high number of resident species found during both seasons, probably due to bird species adapted to the few phenological variants of the habitat (Peters et al., 2010; Morales-Betancourt et al., 2012; Mulwa et al., 2012; Almazán-Núñez et al., 2015). This pattern of ecological community structure has already been demonstrated in other regions of southwestern Mexico with similar vegetation conditions (Almazán-Núñez et al., 2018). Inside the CNPA El Gavilán, there are critical components that supply ideal ecological conditions for food processes, refuge, thermoregulation, resources that provide energy, and the permanence of vegetation, as well as water bodies.

Nine out of the 85 species found in this study are endemic to Mexico. All of them are listed under the species at risk of extinction category by the Mexican Ministry of Environment (DOF, 2010). This proportion of endemic, semi-endemic, and quasi-endemic birds is like the one observed in Oaxaca state (10.19% according to Navarro-Sigüenza et al., 2014), and it reflects the pattern occurring in Mexico, with a higher number of endemic species in mountain ecosystems (Navarro-Sigüenza et al., 2014). This underscores the need to secure the protection of these and other sites along the Central Pacific Coast of the Oaxaca state. Nonetheless, due to the species richness recorded and estimated here, this area should receive more attention from government authorities, particularly because this region is under intense pressure due to changes in land use around it (Salas-Morales & Casariego-Madorell, 2010). The promotion of more voluntary areas

for conservation as local initiatives under the program of Áreas Certificadas para la Conservación de Oaxaca state would probably slow down the threats of deforestation of the TDF on the coast of Oaxaca state (Ortega et al., 2010; Salas-Morales & Casariego-Madorell, 2010). Therefore, this program could benefit the survival of species, mainly those that are endemic to Mexico or nationally threatened.

Conclusions

The avifauna of the CNPA El Gavilán shows that a marked effect does not exist in the species composition between seasons. The most representative order was Passeriformes.

The insectivorous guild was the principal group recorded, followed by the grain-frugivorous guild. Due to the species richness found and estimated here, the study area should be considered in conservation policies, particularly because this region is under intense pressure due to changes in the land use.

Acknowledgements

We thank Grupo Comunitario El Gavilán for the help in the fieldwork. We also thank Carlos Alberto Luis Curiel, Jorge Arturo Rama Aguilar, Sarahí Mendoza León, and Gary Abner García (all – Puerto Escondido, Oaxaca, Mexico) for their support and participation in fieldwork for this research. We specially acknowledge to the editor and reviewers of the Nature Conservation Research for the valuable contributions to the text. This study was conducted under agree between Grupo Comunitario El Gavilán and Promoción del Desarrollo (Department of Universidad del Mar, Mexico). We thank Allison Tai Rosewicz (Universidad del Mar, Mexico) for the help with the language review. The first author thanks the Sistema Nacional de Investigadores (SNI) for its recognition and support.

References

- Allen T.F.H., Hoekstra T.W. 1990. The confusion between scale-defined levels and conventional levels of organization in ecology. *Journal of Vegetation Science* 1(1): 5–12. DOI: 10.2307/3236048
- Almazán-Núñez R.C., Arizmendi M.C., Eguiarte L.E., Corcuera P. 2015. Distribution of the community of frugivorous birds along a successional gradient in a tropical dry forest in south-western Mexico. *Journal of Tropical Ecology* 31(1): 57–68. DOI: 10.1017/S0266467414000601
- Almazán-Núñez R.C., Álvarez-Álvarez E.A., Pineda-López R., Corcuera P. 2018. Seasonal variation in bird assemblage composition in a dry forest of southwestern Mexico. *Ornitología Neotropical* 29: 215–224. DOI: 10.58843/ornneo.v29i1.297
- Arizmendi M.C., Berlanga H., Márquez-Valdemar L., Navarizo-Ornelas M.L., Ornelas J.F. 1990. *Avifauna de la región de Chamela, Jalisco*. México: Universidad Autónoma de México. 62 p.
- Arizmendi M.C., Espinosa de los Monteros A. 1996. Avifauna de los bosques de cactáceas columnares del Valle de Tahuacán, Puebla. *Acta Zoológica Mexicana* 67: 25–46. DOI: 10.21829/azm.1996.67671755
- Azman N.M., Latip N.S., Sah S.A., Akil M.A., Shafie N.J., Khairuddin N.L. 2011. Avian diversity and feeding guilds in a secondary forest, an Oil Palm plantation and a paddy field in riparian areas of the Kerian River Basin, Perak, Malaysia. *Tropical Life Sciences Research* 22(2): 45–64.
- Berlanga H., Rodríguez-Contreras V., Olivera de Ita A., Escobar M., Rodríguez L., Vieyra J., Vargas V. (Eds.). 2008. *Red de conocimientos sobre las aves de México*. México: CONABIO. 56 p.
- Berlanga H., Gómez de Silva H., Vargas-Canales M., Rodríguez-Contreras V., Sánchez-González L.A., Ortega-Álvarez R., Calderón-Parra R. 2015. *Aves de México: Lista actualizada de especies y nombres comunes*. México: CONABIO. 36 p.
- Bojorges-Baños J.C. 2011a. Registros adicionales de algunas especies de aves en la cuenca baja del Río Verde, Oaxaca, México. *Huitzil* 12(2): 39–42.
- Bojorges-Baños J.C. 2011b. Riqueza de especies de aves de la microcuenca del Río Cacaluta, Oaxaca, México. *Universidad y Ciencia* 27(1): 87–95.
- Bojorges-Baños J.C. 2012. *Aves del jardín botánico de Puerto Escondido*. Mexico: Universidad del Mar. 105 p.
- Bojorges-Baños J.C., López-Mata L. 2006. Asociación de la riqueza y diversidad de especies de aves y estructura de la vegetación en una selva mediana subperennifolia en el centro de Veracruz, México. *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad* 77(2): 235–249.
- Ceccon E., Huante P., Rincón E. 2006. Abiotic factors influencing tropical dry forests regeneration. *Brazilian Archives of Biology and Technology* 49(2): 305–312. DOI: 10.1590/S1516-89132006000300016
- Chao A., Chiu C.H., Jost L. 2010. Phylogenetic diversity measures based on hill numbers. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 365(1558): 3599–3609. DOI: 10.1098/rstb.2010.0272
- Chesser R.T., Billerman S.M., Burns K.J., Cicero C., Dunn J.L., Hernández-Baños B.E., Jiménez R.A., Kratter A.W., Mason N.A., Rasmussen P.C., Remsen J.V., Stotz D.F., Winker K. 2022. *Check-list of North American Birds (online)*. American Ornithological Society. Available from <https://checklist.americanornithology.org/taxa/>
- Colwell R.K. 2009. *EstimateS: Statistical estimation of species richness and shared species from samples. Version 8.2*. Available from <http://purl.oclc.org/estimates>

- Dettmers R., Buehler D.A., Bartlett J.G., Klaus N.A. 1999. Influence of point count length and repeated visits on habitat model performance. *Journal of Wildlife Management* 63(3): 815–823. DOI: 10.2307/3802794
- Dirzo R., Ceballos G. 2010. Las selvas secas de México: un reservorio de biodiversidad y laboratorio viviente. In: G. Ceballos, L. Martínez, A. García, E. Espinoza, J. Bezaury, R. Dirzo (Eds.): *Diversidad, amenazas y áreas prioritarias para la conservación de las selvas secas del Pacífico de México*. México: CONABIO. P. 13–17.
- Dirzo R., Young H.S., Mooney H.A., Ceballos G. (Eds.). 2011. *Seasonally dry tropical forests: ecology and conservation*. USA, Washington: Island Press. 394 p. DOI: 10.5822/978-1-61091-021-7
- DOF. 2010. *Norma Oficial Mexicana NOM-059-SEMARNAT.2010, Protección ambiental – Especies nativas de México de flora y fauna silvestres, categorías de riesgo y especificaciones para su inclusión, exclusión o cambios*. México: Órgano del Gobierno Constitucional de los Estados. Available from <https://www.dof.gob.mx/normasOficiales/4254/semarnat/semarnat.htm>
- Falcão L.A.D., do Espírito-Santo M.M., Leite L.O., Garro R.N.S.L., Avila-Cabadilla L.D., Stoner K.E. 2014. Spatiotemporal variation in phyllostomid bat assemblages over a successional gradient in a tropical dry forest in southeastern Brazil. *Journal of Tropical Ecology* 30(2): 123–132. DOI: 10.1017/S0266467413000862
- García E. 1973. *Los climas de México*. México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. 235 p.
- Goetz S.J., Sun M., Zolkos S., Hansen A., Dubayah R. 2014. The relative importance of climate and vegetation properties on patterns of North American breeding bird species. *Environmental Research Letters* 9(3): 034013. DOI: 10.1088/1748-9326/9/3/034013
- Gonzalez-Christen A. 2010. *Los mamíferos de Veracruz: Distribución, endemismo y estado de conservación*. México: Secretaría de Educación, Universidad Veracruzana y Consejo Veracruzano de Investigación Científica y Desarrollo Tecnológico. 187 p.
- González-García F., Gómez de Silva H. 2003. Especies endémicas: riqueza, patrones de distribución y retos para su conservación. In: H. Gómez de Silva, A. Olivera de Ita (Eds.): *Conservación de aves en México*. México: National Fish and Wildlife Foundation/ Comisión Nacional para el Conocimiento y Uso de la Biodiversidad. P. 151–194.
- González-Pérez G., Briones-Salas M.A., Alfaro A.M. 2004. Integración del conocimiento faunístico del Oaxaca. In: A.J. García-Mendoza, M.J. Ordoñez, M.A. Briones-Salas (Eds.): *Biodiversidad de Oaxaca*. México: Instituto de Biología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Fondo Oaxaqueño para la Conservación de la Naturaleza, World Wildlife Fund. P. 449–466.
- Gotelli N.J., Chao A. 2013. Measuring and estimating species richness, species diversity, and biotic similarity from sampling data. In: S.A. Lavin (Ed.): *Encyclopedia of biodiversity*. USA: Waltham Academic Press. P. 195–211.
- Hammer Ø., Harper D.A.T., Ryan P.D. 2001. PAST: Paleontological statistics software package for education and data analysis. *Palaentologia Electronica* 4(1): 1–9.
- Hewson C.M., Austin G.E., Gough S.J., Fuller R.J. 2011. Species-specific responses of woodland birds to stand-level habitat characteristics: the dual importance of forest structure and floristics. *Forest Ecology and Management* 261(7): 1224–1240. DOI: 10.1016/j.foreco.2011.01.001
- Hortal J., Borges P.A.V., Gaspar C. 2006. Evaluating the performance of species richness estimators: sensitivity to sample grain size. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 75(1): 274–287. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2656.2006.01048.x
- Hortal J., Triantis K.A., Meiri S., Thébault E., Sfenthourakis S. 2009. Island species richness increases with habitat diversity. *American Naturalist* 174(6): 205–217. DOI: 10.1086/645085
- Howell S.N.G., Webb S. 1995. *A guide to the birds of Mexico and Northern Central America*. USA: Oxford University Press. 1010 p.
- Hutcheson K. 1970. A test for comparing diversities based on the Shannon formula. *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 29(1): 151–154. DOI: 10.1016/0022-5193(70)90124-4
- Hutto R.L. 1985. Habitat selection by nonbreeding, migratory land birds. In: L.C. Cody (Ed.): *Habitat Selection in Birds*. New York: Academic Press. P. 455–476.
- Hutto R.L., Pletschet S.M., Hendricks P. 1986. A Fixed-radius Point Count Method for Nonbreeding and Breeding Season Use. *Auk* 103(3): 593–602. DOI: 10.1093/auk/103.3.593
- IUCN. 2019. *IUCN Red List of threatened species. Version 2019.2*. Available from <https://www.iucnredlist.org>
- Jiménez-Valverde A., Hortal J. 2003. Las curvas de acumulación de especies y la necesidad de evaluar la calidad de los inventarios biológicos. *Revista Ibérica de Aracnología* 8: 151–161.
- Jiménez-Sierra C.L., Sosa-Ramírez J., Cortés-Calva P., Solís-Cámara A.B., Íñiguez-Dávalos L.I., Ortega-Rubio A. 2014. México país megadiverso y la relevancia de las áreas naturales protegidas. *Investigación y Ciencia* 22(60): 16–22.
- Jost J.L. 2006. Entropy and diversity. *Oikos* 113(2): 363–375. DOI: 10.1111/j.2006.0030-1299.14714.x
- Jost J.L., González-Oreja J.A. 2012. Midiendo la diversidad biológica: más allá del índice de Shannon. *Acta Zoológica Liloana* 56 (1–2): 3–14.
- Lavariega M.C., Martín-Regalado C.N., Gómez-Ugalde R.M., Aragón J. 2016. Avifauna de la Sierra de Cuatro Venados, Oaxaca, México. *Huitzil* 17(2): 198–214.
- Lavariega M.C., Briones-Salas M., Monroy-Gamboa A.G., Herrera-Arenas O., Rubio-Espinoza M. 2020. Riqueza y conservación de las aves del suroeste de Oaxaca. *Huitzil* 21(2): e-591. DOI: 10.28947/htmo.2020.21.2.470

- Lloyd H., Marsden S.J. 2008. Bird community variation across *Polylepis* woodland fragments and matrix habitats: implications for biodiversity conservation within a high Andean landscape. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 17(11): 2645–2660. DOI: 10.1007/s10531-008-9343-2
- Meave J.A., Romero-Romero M.A., Salas-Morales S.H., Pérez-García E.A., Gallardo-Cruz J.A. 2012. Diversidad, amenazas y oportunidades para la conservación del bosque tropical caducifolio en el estado de Oaxaca, México. *Ecosistemas* 21(1–2): 85–100.
- Modena E.S., Souza A.L.T., Rodrigues M. 2013. Trophic structure and composition of an understory bird community in a succession gradient of Brazilian Atlantic forest. *Ornithologia* 6: 78–88.
- Monterrubio-Solis C. 2019. Formalización de Áreas Destinadas Voluntariamente a la Conservación en territorios comunitarios e indígenas, avances y reverses. *EntreDiversidades* 6(1): 79–110. DOI: 10.31644/ED.12.2019.a03
- Morales-Betancourt J., Castaño-Villa G., Fountúrbel F. 2012. Resource abundance and frugivory in two manakin species (Aves: Pipridae) inhabiting a reforested area in Colombia. *Journal of Tropical Ecology* 28(5): 511–514. DOI: 10.1017/S0266467412000442
- Mulwa R.K., Böhning-Gaese K., Schleuning M. 2012. High bird species diversity in structurally heterogeneous farmland in Western Kenya. *Biotropica* 44(6): 801–809. DOI: 10.1111/j.1744-7429.2012.00877.x
- Navarro-Sigüenza A.G., Rebón-Gallardo M.F., Gordillo-Martínez A., Peterson A.T., Berlanga-García H., Sánchez-González L.A. 2014. Biodiversidad de aves en México. *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad* 85: 476–495. DOI: 10.7550/rmb.41882
- Olson D.M., Dinerstein E. 2002. The global 200: priority ecoregions for global conservation. *Annals of the Missouri Botanical Garden* 89(2): 199–224. DOI: 10.2307/3298564
- Ortega D., Sánchez G., Solano C., Huerta M.A., Meza V., Galindo-Leal C. 2010. *Áreas de conservación certificadas en el estado de Oaxaca*. México: World Wildlife Fund, Comisión Nacional de Áreas Naturales Protegidas, Secretaría de Medio Ambiente y Recursos Naturales. 608 p.
- Peters V.E., Mordecai C.R., Carroll C.R., Cooper R.J., Greenberg R. 2010. Bird community response to fruit energy. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 79(4): 824–835. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2656.2010.01699.x
- Peterson A.T., Flores-Villela O.A., Leon-Paniagua L.S., Llorente-Bousquets J.E., Luis-Martínez M.A., Navarro-Sigüenza A.G., Torres-Chavez M.G., Vargas-Fernandez I. 1993. Conservation Priorities in Mexico: Moving up in the World. *Biodiversity Letters* 1(2): 33–38. DOI: 10.2307/2999648
- Peterson A.T., Navarro-Sigüenza A.G., Benítez-Díaz H. 1998. The need for continued scientific collecting; a geographic analysis of Mexican bird specimens. *Ibis* 140(2): 288–294. DOI: 10.1111/j.1474-919X.1998.tb04391.x
- Peña-Azcona I., Ortega-Argueta A., García-Barrios R., Elizondo C. 2022. Áreas de conservación voluntaria en México: alcances y desafíos. *Revista de Ciencias Ambientales* 56(2): 122–147. DOI: 10.15359/rca.56/2.7
- Resendiz-Cruz I., Perez-Montes L.E., Navarro-Sigüenza A.G. 2017. La comunidad de aves del sureste del valle del Mezquital, México: Estructura y composición. *Huitzil* 18(1): 157–175.
- Reynolds R.T., Scott J.M., Nussbaum R.A. 1980. A Variable Circular-Plot Method for Estimating Bird Numbers. *Condor* 82(3): 309–313. DOI: 10.2307/1367399
- Rodríguez-Luna E., Gómez-Pompa A., López-Acosta J.C., Velázquez-Rosas N., Aguilar-Domínguez Y., Vázquez-Torres M. 2011. *Atlas de los espacios naturales protegidos de Veracruz*. Xalapa, Veracruz: Gobierno del Estado de Veracruz, Centro de Investigaciones Tropicales. 350 p.
- Ruiz Bruce Taylor M.D.M., Rangel-Salazar J.L., Enríquez P.L., León-Cortés J.L., García-Estrada C. 2017. Variation in hierarchical guild structure between two bird assemblages of a wetland in the Mexican Pacific. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 65(4): 1540–1553. DOI: 10.15517/rbt.v65i4.26266
- Ruiz Bruce M.D.M., León-Cortés J.L., Enríquez P.L., García-Estrada C., Rangel-Salazar J.L. 2019. Habitat-use patterns among migrant and resident landbirds of contrasting dietary habits in a Southern Mexican Wetland. *Ardeola* 66(2): 291–310. DOI: 10.13157/arla.66.2.2019.ra3
- Rurangwa M.L., Aguirre-Gutiérrez J., Matthews T.J., Niyigaba P., Wayman J.P., Tobias J.A., Whittaker R.J. 2021. Effects of land-use change on avian taxonomic, functional and phylogenetic diversity in a tropical montane rainforest. *Diversity and Distributions* 27(9): 1732–1746. DOI: 10.1111/ddi.13364
- Salas-Morales S.H., Saynes-Vásquez A., Schibli L. 2003. Flora de la costa de Oaxaca, México: Lista florística de la región de Zimatán. *Boletín de la Sociedad Botánica de México* 72: 21–58. DOI: 10.17129/botsci.1669
- Salas-Morales S.H., Casariego-Madorell M.A. 2010. Zimatán, Oaxaca. In: G. Ceballos, L. Martínez, A. García, E. Espinoza, J. Bezaury, R. Dirzo (Eds.): *Diversidad, amenazas y áreas prioritarias para la conservación de las selvas secas del Pacífico de México*. México: CONABIO – Fondo De Cultura Económica. P. 527–531.
- Santos-Benítez A.R., Hernández-Ramírez A.L., Lavariega M.C., Gómez-Ugalde R.M. 2013. Diversidad de aves en cultivos de Santa María Yahuiche, Sierra Madre de Oaxaca, México. *Revista Mexicana de Ciencias Agrícolas* 6: 1241–1250.
- Torres-Colín I. 2004. Tipo de vegetación. In: A.J. García-Mendoza, M.J. Ordoñez, M.A. Briones-Salas (Eds.): *Biodiversidad de Oaxaca, México*. México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México, Fondo Oax-

aqueño para la Conservación de la Naturaleza, World Wildlife Fund. P. 105–117

Tovar-Sánchez E., Cano-Santana Z., Oyama K. 2004. Canopy arthropod communities on Mexican oaks at sites with different disturbance regimes. *Biological Conservation* 115(1): 79–87. DOI: 10.1016/S0006-3207(03)00096-X

Trejo I. 1998. *Distribución y diversidad de selvas bajas de México: relación con clima y suelo*. PhD Thesis. México: Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México. 210 p.

Trejo I. 2010. Las selvas secas del Pacífico Mexicano. In: G. Ceballos, L. Martínez, A. García, E. Espinoza, J. Bezaury, R. Dirzo (Eds.): *Diversidad, amenazas y áreas prioritarias para la conservación de las selvas secas del Pacífico de México*. México: Comisión Nacional para el Conocimiento y Uso de la Biodiversidad, Fondo De Cultura Económica. P. 41–51.

Van Perlo B. 2006. *Birds of Mexico and Central America*. New Jersey, USA: Princeton University Press. 336 p.

Vázquez L., Vázquez-Reyes J.A., Arizmendi M.C. 2009. Registro del gavilán pescador (*Pandion haliaetus*) en el valle de Tehuacán-Cuicatlán, norte de Oaxaca. *Huitzil* 10(1): 24–26.

Vega-Rivera J.H., Arizmendi M.C., Morales P.L. 2010. Aves. In: G. Ceballos, A. García, E. Espinoza, C.J. Bezaury, R. Dirzo (Eds.): *Diversidad, amenazas y áreas prioritarias para la conservación de las selvas secas del Pacífico de México*. México: CONABIO-Fondo de Cultura. P. 145–164.

Wilson L.D., Mata-Silva V., Johnson J.D. 2013. A conservation reassessment of the reptiles of Mexico based on the EVS measure. *Amphibian and Reptile Conservation* 7(1): 1–47.

Zakaria M., Rajpar M.N. 2010. Bird species composition and feeding guilds based on point count and mist netting methods at the Paya Indah Wetland Reserve, Peninsular Malaysia. *Tropical Life Science Research* 21(2): 7–26.

Appendix. Bird species recorded in the Communal Natural Protected Area El Gavilán, state Oaxaca, Mexico in 2018–2019.

Order	Family	Species	n	RA	Sst	NOM-059	IUCN	End	CITES
Galliformes	Cracidae	<i>Ortalis poliocephala</i>	55	vr	R		LC	En	
Accipitriformes	Cathartidae	<i>Cathartes aura</i>	2	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Coragyps atratus</i>	22	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Accipitridae	<i>Buteogallus anthracinus</i>	2	vr	R	UP	LC	ne	
		<i>Buteo plagiatus</i>	8	vr	R		LC	ne	
Columbiformes	Columbidae	<i>Patagioenas flavirostris</i>	11	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Columbina inca</i>	1	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Columbina passerina</i>	15	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Columbina talpacoti</i>	5	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Leptotila verreauxi</i>	7	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Zenaida asiatica</i>	24	vr	R		LC	ne	
Cuculiformes	Cuculidae	<i>Crotophaga sulcirostris</i>	37	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Morococcyx erythropygus</i>	3	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Piaya cayana</i>	30	vr	R		LC	ne	
Strigiformes	Strigidae	<i>Glaucidium palmarum</i>	2	vr	R	Th	LC	En	II
Caprimulgiformes	Caprimulgidae	<i>Nyctidromus albicollis</i>	30	vr	R		LC	ne	
Apodiformes	Trochilidae	<i>Phaethornis mexicanus</i>	7	vr	R		LC	En	II
		<i>Cynanthus latirostris</i>	10	vr	R		LC	Se	II
		<i>Amazilia rutila</i>	90	vr	R		LC	ne	II
		<i>Saucerottia beryllina</i>	2	vr	R		LC	ne	II
		<i>Heliomaster longirostris</i>	3	vr	R	UP	LC	ne	II
		<i>Archilochus colubris</i>	7	vr	Wm		LC	ne	II
Trogoniformes	Trogonidae	<i>Trogon citreolus</i>	36	vr	R		LC	En	
		<i>Trogon collaris</i>	1	vr	R	UP	LC	ne	
Coraciiformes	Momotidae	<i>Momotus mexicanus</i>	30	vr	R		LC	Qe	
Piciformes	Ramphastidae	<i>Aulacorhynchus prasinus</i>	53	vr	R	UP	LC	ne	
	Picidae	<i>Melanerpes chrysogenys</i>	18	vr	R		LC	En	
		<i>Dryocopus lineatus</i>	1	vr	R		LC	Se	
		<i>Campephilus guatemalensis</i>	6	vr	R	UP	LC	ne	
Falconiformes	Falconidae	<i>Falco sparverius</i>	1	vr	R		LC	ne	II
		<i>Falco rufigularis</i>	4	vr	R		LC	ne	II

Psittaciformes	Psittacidae	<i>Aratinga canicularis</i>	170	r	R	UP	LC	ne	II
Passeriformes	Furnariidae	<i>Xiphorhynchus flavigaster</i>	31	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Tyrannidae	<i>Empidonax minimus</i>	1	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Empidonax difficilis</i>	1	vr	Wm		LC	Se	
		<i>Empidonax occidentalis</i>	10	vr	R		LC	Se	
		<i>Myiozetetes similis</i>	2	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Pitangus sulphuratus</i>	9	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Myiodynastes luteiventris</i>	8	vr	Sm		LC	ne	
		<i>Megarynchus pitangua</i>	5	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Tyrannus melancholicus</i>	6	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Myiarchus cinerascens</i>	5	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Myiarchus nuttingi</i>	39	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Myiarchus tyrannulus</i>	12	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Attila spadiceus</i>	2	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Tityridae	<i>Tityra semifasciata</i>	19	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Pachyramphus aglaie</i>	3	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Vireonidae	<i>Vireo solitarius</i>	1	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Vireo huttoni</i>	3	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Vireo hypochryseus</i>	47	vr	R		LC	En	
		<i>Vireo gilvus</i>	9	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Vireo olivaceus</i>	6	vr	T		LC	ne	
	Corvidae	<i>Calocitta formosa</i>	241	r	R		LC	ne	
	Hirundinidae	<i>Stelgidopteryx serripennis</i>	9	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Troglodytidae	<i>Campylorhynchus rufinucha</i>	83	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Thryophilus pleurostictus</i>	6	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Pheugopedius felix</i>	3	vr	R		LC	En	
	Poliophtilidae	<i>Poliophtila caerulea</i>	14	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Poliophtila albiloris</i>	9	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Turdidae	<i>Catharus ustulatus</i>	11	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Turdus rufopalliatu</i>	3	vr	R		LC	En	
	Fringilidae	<i>Euphonia affinis</i>	4	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Icteriidae	<i>Icteria virens</i>	2	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Icteridae	<i>Cacicus melanicterus</i>	43	vr	R		LC	Qe	
		<i>Icterus graduacauda</i>	7	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Icterus gularis</i>	32	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Icterus pustulatus</i>	1	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Icterus spurius</i>	5	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Parulidae	<i>Mniotilta varia</i>	2	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Oreothlypis ruficapilla</i>	5	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Setophaga ruticilla</i>	4	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Setophaga pitiayumi</i>	1	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Setophaga petechia</i>	16	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Basileuterus lachrymosus</i>	4	vr	R		LC	ne	
	Cardinalidae	<i>Piranga rubra</i>	1	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Piranga ludoviciana</i>	4	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Habia rubica</i>	42	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Granatellus venustus</i>	1	vr	R		LC	En	
		<i>Cardinalis cardinalis</i>	1	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Amaurospiza concolor</i>	3	vr	R	D	LC	ne	
		<i>Cyanocompsa parellina</i>	2	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Passerina cyanea</i>	1	vr	Wm		LC	ne	
		<i>Passerina ciris</i>	1	vr	Wm	UP	NT	ne	
	Thraupidae	<i>Saltator atriceps</i>	7	vr	R		LC	ne	
		<i>Volatinia jacarina</i>	6	vr	R		LC	ne	

Note: n (number of individuals registered), RA (Relative Abundance, va – very abundant, a – abundant, c – common, r – rare, vr – very rare), Sst (Seasonality, R – resident, Wm – Winter migrant, Sm – Summer migrant, T – transient), NOM-059 (NOM-059-SEMARNAT-2010, UP – Under protection, Th – Threatened, D – Danger of extinction), IUCN (LC – Least Concern, NT – Near Threatened), End (Endemism, En – Endemic, Se – Semi-endemic, Qe – Quasi-endemic, ne – Non endemic), CITES (II – Appendix II).

ОЦЕНКА РАЗНООБРАЗИЯ ОРНИТОФАУНЫ НА ОБЩЕСТВЕННОЙ ОСОБО ОХРАНЯЕМОЙ ПРИРОДНОЙ ТЕРРИТОРИИ ЭЛЬ ГАВИЛАН, ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЕ ПОБЕРЕЖЬЕ ШТАТА ОАХАКА, МЕКСИКА

Х. Гарсиа-Грахалес*^{ID}, К. Д. Хуарес-Сантьяго, А. Буэнростро-Сильва^{ID}

Университет дель Мар, Мексика
*e-mail: archosaurio@yahoo.com.mx

Тропический сухой лес – экосистема с ярко выраженной сезонностью и высоким разнообразием животных. В качестве угроз для нее выступает широкий спектр антропогенной деятельности, такой как рост населения, темпы обезлесения, развитие туризма, лесные пожары, чрезмерная охота и торговля дикими животными. Одной из стратегий сохранения этого биоразнообразия является создание малоизученных общественных особо охраняемых природных территорий (ОООПТ). Цель данного исследования состояла в том, чтобы дать оценку разнообразия фауны птиц в ОООПТ Эль Гавилан на центральном побережье штата Оахака (Мексика) в течение двух сезонов (засухи и дождей). Сбор данных проводился в двух локациях (условно названных Центр и Гора) с ноября 2018 г. по сентябрь 2019 г. методом точечного подсчета. В каждой локации было заложено по одной трансекте разной длины, но с пятиточечными учетами, разделенными минимум 200 м. Каждая трансекта ежемесячно посещалась дважды. Учет птиц производился с фиксированного места на подъеме в пределах окружности радиусом 50 м в течение определенного времени (10 мин.) в каждом пункте. Всего было зарегистрировано 85 видов, относящихся к 65 родам, 24 семействам и 13 отрядам. Отряд Passeriformes был наиболее богатым с 53 видами. Большинство таксонов (83) были оценены как очень редкие, а два вида (*Aratinga canicularis* и *Calocitta formosa*) как редкие. Относительно видового разнообразия, ⁰D, в локации Центр было отмечено 74 вида (в том числе 19 эксклюзивных, отмеченных только там, видов), а в локации Гора – 65 видов (в том числе 11 эксклюзивных видов). Сезон засухи отличался более высоким разнообразием ($H' = 3.44$), чем сезон дождей ($H' = 3.41$), хотя достоверных различий не было (Hutcheson $t = 0.365$, d.f. = 1, $p > 0.05$). К неперелетным видам было отнесено 70 видов (82.0%), 13 видов (15.3%) являются зимними перелетными, один вид (1.2%) – летним перелетным и один вид (1.2%) – пролетным. Из общего числа зарегистрированных таксонов 50 видов были преимущественно насекомоядными, 14 видов – зерноядными, восемь – всеядными, шесть – плотоядными и шесть – нектароядными. Изучение орнитофауны ОООПТ Эль Гавилан показало, что заметных различий в видовом составе между сезонами не наблюдается. Поскольку видовое богатство было зарегистрировано и оценено на данной территории, эту информацию следует учитывать в природоохранной политике, особенно потому, что эта территория находится под сильным давлением из-за изменений в землепользовании.

Ключевые слова: видовое богатство, насекомоядный вид, неперелетный вид, обилие, перелетный вид, пролетный вид, трансекты, трофическая группа

GENERAL PATTERNS OF MACROZOOBENTHOS DISTRIBUTION IN TWO RIVERS BASINS OF THE KHABAROVSKY KRAI (FAR EAST OF RUSSIA)

Lada V. Vorobjeva^{1,*}

¹All-Russian Research Institute of Fishery and Oceanography, Russia

*e-mail: vorobjeva.lada@yandex.ru

²A.N. Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution of the RAS, Russia

Received: 02.06.2023. Revised: 28.07.2023. Accepted: 17.08.2023.

This article analyses the distribution patterns of macrozoobenthos in watercourses of the basins of the River Bajal and River Anyuy (Khabarovsk Krai, Russia) on the territories of the Bajal Sanctuary and Anyuy National Park. The distance-based linear models (DistLM) method was used to estimate the proportion of distribution of macroinvertebrates explained by the factors considered in the study (river basin, current velocity, substrate, channel width, temperature, pH). All of these factors contributed significantly, together explaining about one-third of the variability of macroinvertebrate distribution. The main explanatory factors were river basin and substrate (9.3% and 10.5%, respectively), as well as the current velocity (5.7%). Based on the cluster analysis, eight statistically significant groups of samples on the basis of similarity of taxonomic composition were identified. A set of indicator taxa was determined for each group and their indicator values were found. Using the Kruskal-Wallis analysis, the environmental factors significantly differing between the obtained groups and subgroups were singled out. There are well-defined patterns in the confinement of taxonomic complexes to certain habitats. Local environmental factors are the strong filter influencing the formation of taxonomic communities. The factor of belonging to the river basin also plays a significant role in the formation of invertebrate communities, which should be considered in the planning of monitoring studies on a large spatial scale. However, the distinguished groups and subgroups are characterised by a low level of internal similarity. Only about a quarter of the total species number belongs to indicator taxa, and samples do not form discrete clusters with obvious hiatus on the ordination diagram. The longitudinal distribution of macroinvertebrates for each river can be characterised as a punctuated gradient.

Key words: community, environmental factor, freshwater macroinvertebrates, Russian Far East, watercourse

Introduction

Understanding the patterns of the community formation and their interaction with the environment is necessary for successful planning of environmental monitoring and conservation activities. Ecosystems of Protected Areas are not or slightly disturbed by anthropogenic activity, so they can play the role of reference sites for assessing the degree of disturbance during monitoring studies. One of the key questions of community ecology is whether communities exist as discrete units or form an entire continuum. The first scenario assumes that species groups respond to changes in environmental factors in a similar way, forming closely related groups. In the second case, the species response is individual. A more detailed discussion of the problem is given by Ipatov & Kirikova (1997). The history of this concern goes back about a hundred years (Clements, 1916; Gleason, 1926), but the problem remains controversial (e.g. Heino et al., 2003; Heino, 2005; Merovich & Petty, 2010; Tolonen et al., 2016).

The paramount importance of local environmental factors in the formation of freshwater macroinvertebrate communities is often highlighted

in the literature (Pardo & Armitage, 1997; Beisel et al., 1998; Doisy & Rabeni, 2001; Johnson et al., 2004; Costa & Melo, 2008; Korte, 2010; Kubosova et al., 2010; Silva et al., 2014). Environmental factors are a system of filters that allow only those taxa of the regional fauna that have suitable biological and morphological features to colonise a habitat. Factors influencing the community formation in rivers represent a hierarchical system, in which macroscale factors affect conditions at lower hierarchical levels. Altogether, four main levels of the factor scale are distinguished, namely watershed basin, watercourse, watercourse section, and habitat (Poff, 1997; Dallas, 2007a; Heino et al., 2012; Grönroos et al., 2013).

The effects of environmental factors acting at various spatial scales, as well as the interactions between local communities, are the subject of the metacommunity concept (Leibold et al., 2004). A metacommunity is defined as a set of local communities in different areas, united by certain patterns of distribution of species composition. On a large spatial scale, differences in the taxonomic composition of communities can be explained by the limited

dispersal abilities of organisms. On the contrary, on a small scale, differences between the fauna of various habitats can be smoothed out by the movement effect of organisms, that is, the fauna from neighbouring habitats can partially mix and merge (the phenomenon of «mass effect»).

In studies of river ecosystems, an important spatial unit is the watershed. Within a basin, the influence of barriers to the dispersal of organisms is thought to be minimised, since dispersal within one is more likely than between different basins. Thus, the structure of communities within a watershed is mainly determined by abiotic environmental factors, which increases its predictability (Heino & Mykrä, 2008; Heino et al., 2017). The effect of such filters is the largest at the mesoscale (metres and tens of metres), where the structure of communities is not affected by either the «mass effect» smoothing the differences, or the limited dispersal abilities of species (Heino et al., 2017; Chertoprud, 2021). Habitat studies at the mesoscale allow a comprehensive analysis of the river ecosystem (Brunke et al., 2001). A clear classification of habitats is important for the research design, which makes the selection of sampling sites not random (Kubosova et al., 2010).

Four groups of aquatic organisms have been identified, which differ in the correlation between their spatial distribution and the heterogeneity of environmental conditions, namely weak passive dispersers with aquatic adult specimens (Oligochaeta, Hirudinea, Gastropoda, Bivalvia, Aranea, Crustacea), weak aerial dispersers with flying adults (Ceratopogonidae, Chironomidae), intermediate aerial dispersers with flying adults (Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera, Megaloptera, Trichoptera, Diptera: Tipuloidea, Tabanidae, Empididae), and strong aerial dispersers with flying adults (Odonata, Heteroptera: Corixidae, Coleoptera: Dytiscidae). Environmental factors to the greatest extent determine the distribution pattern of strong aerial dispersers (up to 80% of variations), while dispersal barriers explain a small proportion of variability (5% of variations). For weak passive dispersers with aquatic adults, only 50% of variation was explained by environmental factors. Mixed influence of environmental factors and dispersal barriers were responsible for 30% and 10%, respectively (Heino, 2013a). Therefore, actively dispersing organisms that are able to select the most suitable conditions are usually confined to specific habitats, while passive dispersers are more likely to demonstrate a random distribution (Grönroos et al., 2013; Heino, 2013b).

This research presents an original approach to the analysis of distributional patterns of organ-

isms based on the example of macrozoobenthos of two Far Eastern rivers (Khabarovsk Krai, Russia). The first task was to assess the contribution of environmental factors to the overall variability in the distribution of organisms. The second task was to check whether it is possible to identify statistically significant classes of communities in the absence of an a priori hypothesis of their existence. Environmental factors determining the habitat type were the main focus of the research. Finally, in the case of reliable identification of community types, the third task was to identify indicator taxa and typical life forms for each of them.

Material and Methods

Study Area

The research has been carried out during the field work in the study area of two rivers located in the Far East, namely the River Anyuy and the River Bajal (Fig. 1). The River Anyuy flows through the territory of the Anyuy National Park (Nanaysky district of the Khabarovsk Krai). The study area was located in the taiga zone, on the western slopes of the Sikhote-Alin mountain range, at an altitude of 50–250 m a.s.l. The River Bajal flows through the territory of the Bajal Sanctuary (Solnechny district of the Khabarovsk Krai). It is the right tributary of the River Amgun in its lower reaches. Both rivers belong to the Amur River Basin.

Fig. 1. Map of the Khabarovsk Krai (A) with positions of basins of River Anyuy (1) and River Bajal (2) (black squares). B – middle course of River Bajal (B). C – sampling process on intense flow (C). Authors of the photos: B – I.N. Nikonova, C – E.S. Chertoprud.

Sampling Methods

Samples were collected in August 2016 (River Anyuy) and August 2018 (River Bajal) (Fig. 1). Sampling stations covered both the main rivers of the basins and the mouth zones of some of their tributaries. At each station, the following factors were considered: altitude, sediment type, channel width, depth, water temperature, mineralisation (PPM), acidity (pH), and current velocity. At each station, environmental variables such as water temperature (°C), pH, and total mineralisation (PPM) were measured with a portable multiparameter water quality device YIERYI 5 in 1 (Italy). The current velocity was measured manually using a floating object with standard mass and measuring the distance travelled by it per unit of time. The area of a sample was approximately 1500 cm². At each sampling station, three samples were collected and then combined into one complex sample.

While taking quantitative samples, stones of an average size of 15–20 cm were lifted from the bottom, while a hydrobiological net was placed under the rock to avoid the loss of organisms. Samples from pebbles (average size: 3–6 cm) and loose soils (plant detritus and silty sand) were taken with a hydrobiological scraper. All organisms were selected from the substrate with tweezers and preserved in 90% ethanol. A total of 31 quantitative samples were taken in the Bajal River basin, and 80 quantitative samples were taken in the Anyuy River basin.

Most organisms have been identified up to the species level. However, in some cases, larval stages could only be identified up to the genus or family level. We used mainly the following taxonomic literature: Tsalolikhin (1997, 2000, 2001, 2004), Lelley (2006), Teslenko & Zhiltsova (2009). Insect life forms were determined according to Merritt et al. (2019), molluscs and oligochaetes were characterised according to Chertoprud (2021) and our own expert assessment, amphipod *Gammarus koreanus* according to Astakhov & Skriptsova (2020).

Statistical Analysis

To identify the groups of samples based on the similarity of taxonomic composition, a hierarchical cluster analysis has been carried out using the group-average link. The similarity profile analysis (SIMPROF) procedure was used to assess the statistical significance of the selected groups. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (nMDS) was used to visualise the location of samples based on taxonomic similarity. The table with data on the relative abundance of taxa in the samples was used for the analysis. The data were square-root transformed.

The sample similarity matrix was calculated based on the Bray-Curtis similarity index. All the methods described by Clarke et al. (2014).

To identify the environmental factors that contributed most to explain the sample distribution, the distance-based linear models (DistLM) method was used, together with the selection of step-wise factors and the AICc criterion (Anderson et al., 2008). Additionally, a non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was performed to determine the environmental factors that differed significantly for the selected groups of samples (Glantz, 2012). The canonical analysis of principal co-ordinates (CAP) was used to cross-validate the groups obtained in the cluster analysis. In the process of cross-validation, a random sample was selected and the ability of the model to correctly classify it according to a priori division into groups was checked. Thus, the higher percentage of the correct classification corresponded to the more reliable identification of groups.

For each group of samples obtained in the course of the cluster analysis, indicator taxa were identified by calculating the IndVal index (Legendre & Legendre, 2012). The index combined the assessment of taxon specificity for the analysed group (the frequency of occurrence of the taxon outside the given group) and fidelity (the frequency of occurrence of the taxon in samples within the group). The IndVal value could range from 1 to 100. The maximum indicator value of a taxon was observed, when it was found in all samples of the group. All statistical analyses were performed using PRIMER v7 (PRIMER-e, Quest Research Limited, New Zealand) and PAST 4.06b software (Hammer et al., 2001).

Results

Taxonomical composition of macrozoobenthos

In the Bajal River basin and the Anyuy River basin, 216 invertebrate taxa were found and identified to species, groups of species or genus levels. Oligochaetes (families Tubificidae and Enchytraeidae), bivalves (family Euglesidae) and dipterans (family Psychodidae and, in certain cases, Limoniidae) have been identified to the family level, while black flies (subfamily Simuliinae) to the subfamily level. Amphibiotic insects were the predominant group among macroinvertebrates in the surveyed watercourses of the Khabarovsk Krai. They accounted for more than 90% (201 taxa) of the species richness among the observed hydrobionts. A total of 89 taxa, including 86 insects, have been found in the Bajal River basin. The Anyuy River basin can boast a diversity of 184 taxa including 171 insects.

Factors regulating the spatial distribution of organisms

The following factors were considered in the DistLM analysis: river basin, substrate, temperature (°C), channel width (m), depth (m) and water flow velocity (m/s) at the sampling site, pH, mineralisation (PPM). The contribution of only six factors to the variability in macroinvertebrate distribution was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) (Table 1). The total proportion of explained variance was about 32%, with the following key factors explaining the largest proportion of variability: substrate (about 10.5%), river basin (about 9%), and water flow velocity (5.7%). Thus, about one-third of the variability in the distribution of aquatic organisms is associated with the environmental factors included in the analysis. The remaining unexplained

variability appears to be due both to factors not included in the analysis and to stochastic processes in the aquatic ecosystem.

Classification of community types

The cluster analysis identified five statistically significant groups of samples (indicated by the black branches, three of which (№1, №2, and №3 in Fig. 2) were, in turn, divided into two subgroups each. Five samples with rare variants of the macrozoobenthos composition, which have not been included in any of the clusters, were combined into a separate group №6. Thus, eight statistically significant relatively independent clusters were identified with an internal similarity level from 37% (№2B) to 4% (№4) (Fig. 2). Group №6 was not included in the subsequent analysis, not being statistically significant.

Table 1. Significant factors ($p < 0.001$) determined variability in the spatial distribution of macroinvertebrates (results of Sequential test of DistLM using AICc criterion, selection procedure of predictor variables: step-wise, with comparison to full model, selection procedure: all specified)

Factor	*Prop.	**Cumul.
River basin	0.09314	0.09314
Water flow velocity (m/s)	0.05711	0.15026
Substrate	0.10489	0.25515
Channel width (m)	0.02952	0.28466
Temperature (°C)	0.01957	0.30423
pH	0.01532	0.31955
R ² for best model (selection procedure: step-wise)		0.31955
AICc for best model (selection procedure: step-wise)		978.87
R ² for full model (selection procedure: all specified)		0.33183
AICc for full model: (selection procedure: all specified)		981.77

Note: *Prop. – contribution to the explained variability; **Cumul. – cumulative explained distribution.

Fig. 2. Dendrogram for hierarchical clustering (group-average link method, Bray-Curtis similarity index) of macrozoobenthos taxonomical structure from samples of various water courses of the Bajal River basin and Anyuy River basin. Main sample groups are marked. Red points – groups with internal similarity level of about 10% and less; blue points – subgroups with internal similarity level $> 11\%$; red dashed branches – groups with no evidence from SIMPROF for the significant clustering structure; black branches – statistically significant groups according to SIMPROF.

A CAP cross-validation procedure has been performed for each level of clustering. In all selected groups (except group №6), 80–100% of samples were classified correctly (Table 2). For the first level of clustering, the first squared canonical correlation is 0.93857, p -value < 0.001. For the second level of clustering, the first squared canonical correlation is 0.9335, p -value < 0.001.

The nMDS plot (Fig. 3) illustrates the interposition of sample groups according to the results of the second level of clustering. Highly similar samples are located closer to each other and form dense point clouds. The identified community types are relatively clear-cut and specific in species structure. However, it is noticeable that the groups of samples belonging to different communities are not discrete. Different point clouds merged smoothly into each other, and there are no clear gaps (hiatuses) between them.

The influence of the river basin factor on the distribution of macrozoobenthos is shown separately (Fig. 4). Samples from the Bajal River basin and Anyuy River basin form two almost non-overlapping groups of points (except one point from Anyuy River basin), highlighting the faunal specificity of these two areas. The absence of a hiatus between the point clouds indicates the gradual nature of the faunal change.

Table 2. Results of CAP cross-validation procedure for samples classification identified on the basis of hierarchical clustering analysis

First level of clustering		
Groups or subgroups	Number of samples	Correct cross-validation (%)
1	22	90.91
2	43	100.00
3	36	91.67
4	6	80.00
5	9	88.89
6	5	40.00
Second level of clustering		
1A	16	93.75
1B	6	100.00
2A	24	100.00
2B	19	100.00
3A	26	88.46
3B	10	100.00
4	6	80.00
5	9	88.89
6	5	40.00

Fig. 3. nMDS ordination of the samples from water courses of the Khabarovsk Krai (Russian Far East), based on Bray-Curtis similarity index and factored with division of the second level of cluster analysis.

Fig. 4. nMDS ordination of the samples located in watercourses of Khabarovsk Krai (Russian Far East), based on Bray-Curtis similarity index and factored with the rivers basin.

Definition of key environmental factors and indicator taxa for different community types

The Kruskal-Wallis test was performed to assess whether there were significant differences in environmental factors between the selected groups of samples corresponding to the community types. The results of the Kruskal-Wallis test for the second level of clustering are shown in Table 3, and the selected indicator taxa are presented in Table 4. A total of 147 reliable indicator taxa with an indicator value of > 20 (IndVal > 20) were identified for the distinguished communities.

It is shown that the distribution of macroinvertebrates is not random. Selected samples are divided into groups (communities) based on the species (taxonomic) structure. The Kruskal-Wallis test showed that the abiotic factors are significantly different between the distinguished community types. For each type, a set of significant indicator taxa was identified indicating the presence of specific species complexes associated with specific habitats.

Table 3. Values of environmental factors that determine differences between samples patterns on the second level of clustering (Kruskal-Wallis test)

Factor		Groups and subgroups								
		1A	1B	2A	2B	3A	3B	4	5	6
Temperature (°C)	Median	12.00	11.00	13.00	12.00	12.50	14.00	21.00	13.00	16.00
	H	35.43								
	Chi-squared	34.66								
	p-value	< 0.001								
Channel width (m)	Median	9.00	5.00	10.00	10.00	2.50	50.00	20.00	7.00	10.00
	H	45.65								
	Chi-squared	45.02								
	p-value	< 0.001								
Depth (m)	Median	0.15	0.45	0.55	0.40	0.30	2.00	1.00	0.50	0.50
	H	44.81								
	Chi-squared	44.06								
	p-value	< 0.001								
Current velocity (m/s)	Median	0.12	0.02	0.35	0.60	0.20	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.30
	H	59.31								
	Chi-squared	57.94								
	p-value	< 0.001								
pH	Median	7.90	7.90	8.20	8.00	8.00	7.95	8.40	8.10	8.30
	H	18.14								
	Chi-squared	17.61								
	p-value	≈ 0.020								
Mineralisation (PPM)	Median	20.00	20.00	19.50	16.00	16.00	19.00	26.00	18.00	21.00
	H	16.45								
	Chi-squared	16.19								
	p-value	≈ 0.036								
River basin	Bajal	16	6	3	9	0	0	0	0	1
	Anyuy	0	0	21	10	26	10	5	9	4
Substrate	Stones	14	0	18	16	6	1	1	1	0
	Pebbles	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Snags	0	0	5	1	8	1	1	1	0
	Detritus	0	1	1	1	9	7	2	1	2
	Macrophytes	0	0	0	1	2	1	0	0	1
	Sand	0	5	0	0	0	0	0	1	2
	Silt	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	5	0

Discussion

The macroinvertebrate fauna of the freshwaters of the Russian Far East has been relatively well studied (Haritonov & Malikova, 1998; Markarchenko et al., 2005; Tiunova, 2007, 2009; Markarchenko et al., 2008; Tiunova & Korotenko, 2008; Yavorskaya, 2008; Teslenko, 2009, 2014; Tiunova & Gorovaya, 2011; Zasyrkina, 2011, 2018; Teslenko et al., 2014; Potikha, 2015; Orel, 2016; Potikha & Vshivkova, 2016). A number of published data are devoted to the functional and spatial structure of macrozoobenthos communities, in particular, to the trophic structure (Kocharina & Khamenkova, 2003; Tiunova, 2006; Labay, 2007), their distribution in the watercourse of the rivers (Potikha, 2011; Labay et al., 2019), including confinement to microhabitats (Tiunova, 2008) and peculiarities of benthos composition in watercourses of various types and assessment of their water quality (Yavorskaya, 2015, 2016, 2021). One of the most recent attempts to classify macrozoobenthos communities in the Khabarovsk Krai is presented in Chertoprud et al. (2020). According to this classification, communities are identified on

the basis of dominance structure and a priori limited to previously distinguished habitats.

For the macrozoobenthos of the studied areas, the environmental factors considered in the analysis explained about 30% of the variability in distribution. The main regulating factors were river basin and substrate type (about 10% of the explained distribution per factor), and flow velocity (about 5.7%). The low proportion of explained variability of the macroinvertebrate distribution is a typical phenomenon for river ecosystems, at least within a single basin (Sandin, 2003; Heino & Mykra, 2008; Kubosova et al., 2010; Heino et al., 2012, 2014; Silva et al., 2014). The composition of macroinvertebrate species complexes in rivers is hardly predictable due to frequent flood events leading to the habitat destruction and, as a consequence, their secondary colonisation by organisms. Another factor that determines the low predictability of the composition of river communities is the high number of rare species. The higher percentage of rare species in the river fauna correspond to the lower percentage of explained variability in the distribution of organisms (Heino & Mykra, 2008).

Table 4. Macrozoobenthos indicator taxa of samples patterns on the second level of clustering, identified on the basis of the IndVal index (values > 20)

Groups and subgroups	Taxon	IndVal	p-value	Character of movement	Functional feeding group
1A	<i>Ameletus cedrensis</i> Potikha, 1985	66.12	< 0.0001	Swimmers; clingers	Scrapers; collectors-gatherers (detritus. diatoms)
	<i>Suwallia</i> sp. Ricker, 1943	62.15	< 0.0001	Clingers	Predators (engulfers)
	<i>Mesocapnia</i> sp. Rauser, 1968	49.02	< 0.0001	Clingers	Shredders-detritivores
	<i>Rhitrogena putoranica</i> (Kluge, 1980)	38.86	< 0.0001	Clingers	Scrapers; facultative collectors-gatherers
	<i>Brachypsyche</i> sp. Schmid, 1952	37.91	< 0.0001	Climbers; sprawlers; clingers	Shredders-detritivores
	<i>Pictetiella asiatica</i> Zwick & Levanidova, 1971	36.54	< 0.0001	Clingers	Predators (engulfers)
	<i>Drunella triacantha</i> Tshernova, 1949	34.54	< 0.0001	Clingers; sprawlers	Scrapers; facultative predators; facultative collectors-gatherers
	<i>Ephemerella dentata</i> Bajkova, 1967	30.81	< 0.0001	Swimmers; clingers at rest	Collectors-gatherers; scrapers
	<i>Rhithrogena hirasana</i> Imanishi, 1935	24.41	< 0.0001	Clingers	Scrapers; facultative collectors-gatherers
	<i>Ephemerella aurivillii</i> Bengtsson, 1908	24.37	0.0004	Swimmers; clingers at rest	Collectors-gatherers; scrapers
1B	<i>Tipula salisetorum</i> Siebke, 1870	79.84	< 0.0001	Burrowers in plant detritus	Obligate shredders-detritivores
	<i>Micropsectra</i> sp. Kieffer, 1908	68.50	< 0.0001	Sprawlers	Collectors-gatherers
	<i>Siphonurus immanis</i> Kluge, 1985	56.87	< 0.0001	Swimmers; climbers at rest	Collectors-gatherers
	<i>Oreodytes</i> sp. (larvae) Seidlitz, 1887	33.33	0.0031	Swimmers; climbers at rest	Predators (piercers)
	<i>Chaetocladius</i> sp. Kieffer, 1911	33.33	0.0023	Sprawlers	Collectors-gatherers
	<i>Lumbriculus variegatus</i> (Muller, 1774)	33.33	0.0025	Burrowers	Collectors-gatherers
	<i>Arctopelopia griseipennis</i> (Wulp, 1858)	28.47	0.0033	Sprawlers	Predators (engulfers)
	<i>Polypedilum</i> gr. <i>nubeculosum</i>	25.06	0.0026	Burrowers	Collectors-gatherers. predators (engulfers)
	<i>Heterotrissocladus</i> gr. <i>marcidus</i>	20.44	0.0114	Sprawlers; borrowers	Collectors-gatherers scrapers
2A	<i>Epeorus</i> gr. <i>pellucidus</i>	49.72	< 0.0001	Clingers	Scrapers; facultative collectors-gatherers
	<i>Glossosoma</i> sp. Curtis, 1834	29.17	< 0.0001	Clingers (turtle shell case)	Obligate scrapers
	<i>Pagastia orientalis</i> Chernovskij, 1949	26.16	< 0.0001	Sprawlers	Collectors-gatherers; scrapers
	<i>Optioservus kubotai</i> Nomura, 1958	24.91	0.0002	Clingers	Scrapers (larvae); collectors-gatherers (adults)
	<i>Drunella lepnavae</i> Tshernova, 1949	23.47	< 0.0001	Clingers; sprawlers	Scrapers; facultative predators; facultative collectors-gatherers
	<i>Neophylax ussuriensis</i> Martynov, 1914	23.04	< 0.0001	Clingers	Obligate scrapers
	<i>Brachycentrus americanus</i> (Banks, 1899)	21.34	0.0003	Clingers	Shredders-herbivores
	<i>Atherix ibis</i> (Fabricius, 1798)	20.37	< 0.0001	Sprawlers-burrowers	Predators (piercers)
	<i>Ephemerella kozhovi</i> Bajkova, 1967	20.06	0.0003	Swimmers; clingers at rest	Collectors-gatherers; scrapers
2B	Simuliinae spp.	73.30	< 0.0001	Clingers	Filter feeders; collectors
	<i>Epeorus maculatus</i> Tshernova, 1949	56.37	< 0.0001	Clingers	Scrapers
	<i>Orthocladus</i> sp. van der Wulp, 1874	25.58	< 0.0001	Sprawlers; burrowers	Collectors-gatherers
3A	<i>Gammarus koreanus</i> Fabricius, 1775	52.85	< 0.0001	Sprawlers	Shredders-detritivores, predators
3B	<i>Baetis</i> gr. <i>vernus</i>	78.56	< 0.0001	Swimmers; clingers / climbers at rest	Collectors-gatherers; facultative scrapers
	<i>Baetis fuscatu</i> s Linnaeus, 1761	40.44	< 0.0001	Swimmers; clingers / climbers at rest	Collectors-gatherers; facultative scrapers
	<i>Ephemerella zapekinae</i> Bajkova, 1967	39.36	< 0.0001	Swimmers; clingers at rest	Collectors-gatherers; scrapers
	<i>Diura</i> sp. Billberg, 1820	37.62	< 0.0001	Clingers	Predators (engulfers)
4	<i>Juga nodosa</i> (Westerlund, 1897)	75.42	< 0.0001	Sparwlers	Collectors-gatherers
	<i>Ecdyonurus abracadabrus</i> Kluge, 1983	40.00	0.0017	Clingers	Scrapers; facultative collectors-gatherers
	<i>Labiobaetis atrebatinus</i> (Eaton, 1870)	4000	0.0019	Swimmers; clingers / climbers at rest	Collectors-gatherers; facultative scrapers
	<i>Drunella cryptomeria</i> (Imanishi, 1937)	34.90	0.0005	Clingers; sprawlers	Scrapers; facultative predators; facultative collectors-gatherers
	<i>Microtendipes</i> gr. <i>pedellus</i>	34.42	0.0023	Clingers (net spinners)	Filter feeders; collectors; gatherers
	<i>Baetis ussuricus</i> Kluge, 1983	29.56	0.0024	Swimmers; clingers / climbers at rest	Collectors-gatherers; facultative scrapers
	<i>Rheopelopia ornata</i> (Meigen, 1838)	25.38	0.0087	Sprawlers	Predators (engulfers and piercers)
	<i>Radix</i> sp. Montfort, 1810	23.72	0.0080	Sparwlers	Collectors-gatherers
5	Tubificidae spp.	45.52	< 0.0001	Burrowers	Collectors-gatherers
	Euglesidae spp.	37.57	< 0.0001	Burrowers	Filter feeders
	<i>Paratendipes albimanus</i> (Meigen, 1919)	33.33	0.0005	Burrowers (tube builders)	Collectors-gatherers
	<i>Chrysops</i> sp. Meigen, 1803	22.22	0.0056	Sprawlers-burrowers	Predators (piercers)
	<i>Anabolia servata</i> (McLachlan, 1880)	20.70	0.0043	Climbers-sprawlers	Shredders-detritivores; facultative collectors-gatherers

The strong majority of hydrobionts encountered in the research are amphibiotic insects with a flying imago capable to the active dispersion. A considerable influence of abiotic environmental factors on spatial distribution is typical for these organisms. Indeed, groups of samples corresponding to individual habitat types were identified (Fig. 3). However, these groups are not clearly separated from each other, smoothly passing from one to another, and some even overlap to a considerable extent. The substrate type was the main abiotic factor explaining most of the variability in the distribution of organisms. The key role of sediment type for macrozoobenthos has been noted previously (Pardo & Armitage, 1997; Dallas, 2007b; Chertoprud, 2021). The river flow velocity was the second important abiotic factor. It has been shown that the composition of hydrobionts differs significantly between habitats with fast and slow flow and habitats with no flow (Rabeni et al., 2002). Macroinvertebrates reach the highest species richness in fast flowing habitats (Rabeni et al., 2002), which is consistent with the data from the present research. The optimal current velocity for benthic fauna is 0.11–0.50 m/s (Korte, 2010). Under such conditions, the most diverse species complexes are formed, with functional feeding groups represented by scrapers, gatherers, shredders and predators. In this research, samples from subgroup №2A of the habitat with a median flow velocity of 0.35 m/s showed the highest taxonomic richness.

Clustering of the samples revealed five statistically significant groups differing in composition and quantitative characteristics of the macrozoobenthos. Three of these groups were not homogeneous within themselves, and each of them was therefore divided into two subgroups. Thus, the eight main blocks of samples obtained in this way correspond to individual community types. Brief descriptions of habitats, faunistic characteristics in the context of the literature data and the relevance of the identified communities with the previously proposed classifications are presented below.

Group №1 is entirely within the Bajal River basin. These samples are collected from the coldest and the shallowest areas with a slow current velocity on stony and silty substrates. At the second clustering level, this group is divided into subgroup №1A and subgroup №1B.

Samples from subgroup №1A are collected in a habitat characterised by a lower median

depth and higher water flow velocity than in subgroup №1B. The substrate types are represented by stones (including small pebbles) and snags. The described habitat is presented on hard substrates in the shore shallow zone of rivers and streams from the Bajal River basin. The species richness subgroup №1A is 61 taxa. According to its description, subgroup №1A corresponds to the habitat «shore areas of accumulated gravel» with a predominance of Ephemeroptera larvae from genus *Ameletus* Eaton, 1865 (Takemon, 1997), and is also comparable to the habitat «shore area of stream and drain» (Tiunova, 2008). An important role of *Ameletus* mayflies on shore gravels has also been reported for rivers on Sakhalin Island (Labay, 2007). In this community, functional feeding groups are represented by scrapers, collectors-gatherers, and to a lesser extent shredders-detritivores and predators. In terms of the movement type, the majority of species are clingers, which is indicative of the predominance of stony substrates.

In subgroup №1B, the median flow velocity and water temperature are the lowest of all the habitats covered in this study. Samples from subgroup №1B included mainly sandy substrate and plant detritus and placed on soft substrates in streams of the Bajal River basin. The species richness is 39 taxa. This habitat corresponds to the «stream side with groundwater inflow» according to Tiunova (2008), with species of the family Tipulidae as the predominant group of hydrobionts. The main indicator taxon of subgroup №1B, *Tipula salisetorum* Siebke, 1870, is a typical cold-water species (Chebanova, 2008). The functional feeding groups are dominated by collector-gatherers, as well as shredders-detritivores and predators, while in terms of the movement type the groups are represented by burrowers, sprawlers and swimmers. Such a composition is typical for soft sediments.

Group №2, marked with the highest flow velocity among all the groups, includes samples from both Anyuy River basin and Bajal River basin. This entire group of samples corresponds to the zone of «accumulated stones in a riffle of high flow», i.e. stony substrates on riffles with fast flow, where the community included species of the genus *Epeorus* Eaton, 1881 and the subfamily Diamesinae (Takemon, 1997). In the studied streams of the Khabarovsk Krai, this group was divided into two subgroups with different flow velocities.

In samples of subgroup №2A, the substrates were represented by stones and snags. The species richness is 108 taxa. The habitat is mainly represented in the watercourses of the Anyuy River basin, with only three samples from the Bajal River basin. This habitat with slightly slower waterflow (compared to subgroup №2B) corresponded to the Chertoprud et al. (2020) classification, i.e. stony substrates at medium to fast flow (0.4–0.7 m/s), with dominance of *Epeorus* gr. *pellucidus*. In terms of functional feeding group composition, this community is close to subgroup №1A, where scrapers and collector-gatherers prevail, while some predators and shredders-detritivores are also presented. Clingers dominate in terms of movement type, but there are also sprawlers (Diptera larvae), which live on the surface of rocks and in the cavities between them.

The median and average flow velocity of the samples in subgroup №2B is the highest among all the groups of the second clustering level (subgroup №2A is the second in terms of flow velocity). This subgroup includes samples from both river basins. The species richness is 88 taxa. This community corresponds to chimaroritral (Chertoprud et al., 2020) and includes habitat of «stone patch on an intense stream roll» (Tiunova, 2008). These are stony areas with an intense flow (0.7–1.0 m/s), with a high abundance of Simuliidae larvae. The community may also include *Epeorus* (*Iron*) *maculatus* Tshernova, 1949 (Tiunova, 2008). Functional feeding groups are represented by sedentary filter feeders (family Simuliidae), which is typical for rivers and streams with fast currents, as well as scrapers and collectors-gatherers. Groups of movement type include sprawlers living in the fouling film on stones (*Orthocladius* sp.) and clingers.

Group №3 includes samples with an average value of temperature, depth, and velocity flow. It entirely refers to the Anyuy River basin. Among all the groups, it has the highest proportion of plant detritus and snags in substrates, and stones, macrophytes and silt are found less.

Subgroup №3A is characterised by the smallest median channel width among all second-level cluster groups. Samples from subgroup №3A were mainly collected on plant detritus, snags and stones. The species richness is 82 taxa. Subgroup №3A corresponds to the gammarocrenal community, the main type of crenal communities of the Khabarovsk Krai with a dramatic dominance of *Gammarus* sp. Fabricius, 1775 (Cher-

toprud et al., 2020). *Gammarus koreanus* Ueno, 1940, which belongs to the shredders-detritivores and facultative predators in terms of functional feeding groups and sprawlers in terms of the movement types, is the only important indicator species in this community.

Subgroup №3B has the highest median and average stream channel width and depth. Substrates were represented mostly by plant detritus. The species richness is 44 taxa. In terms of characteristics, this community is close to phytoritral and eurypal (Chertoprud et al., 2020); it is located on the shore edge in the lower reaches of the River Anyuy. Functional feeding groups include predators and collectors-gatherers. The movement types are represented by swimmers and clingers, which also corresponds to the phytal and ripal habitat structure, according to Chertoprud et al. (2020).

Group №4 refers entirely to the Anyuy River basin. It is a small group of samples characterised by a wide and deep channel, the highest median water temperature, mineralisation and pH values among all the groups. Substrates are represented by stones, snags, plant detritus and silt. The species richness is 42 taxa. This community with relatively warm and slowly flowing waters corresponds to the malacoripal (Chertoprud et al., 2020) with a dominance of Gastropoda species. The habitats were mainly found in the River Alima, a tributary of the River Anyuy. Functional feeding groups mainly include scrapers and collectors-gatherers, with presence of some predators. In terms of movement types organisms are represented by clingers, swimmers and sprawlers. The diversity of indicator taxa and their life forms reflects the variability of substrates.

Group №5 is also related to the Anyuy River basin, mainly to small streams. Samples from this group are characterised by a low median and average flow velocity and the highest proportion of silty substrates among all the groups. The species richness is 56 taxa. This community combines the features of eupelal, epipelal, and crenopelal according to Chertoprud et al. (2020). Functional feeding groups are represented by filter feeders, collectors-gatherers, shredders-detritivores and predators. Groups of movement types are mostly sprawlers and burrowers, which is typical for silty substrates.

In the macrozoobenthos distribution, a considerable part of the variability is also explained by the river basin factor. Within a river basin, bar-

riers to the macroinvertebrate dispersal are weak. Therefore, local abiotic factors, such as substrate and flow velocity, have a predominant influence on community structure (Heino & Mykra, 2008). The high significance of the river basin factor for the macrozoobenthos of the Far Eastern rivers can be explained both by the unaccounted differences in the environment conditions of basins and by their geographical distance from each other. It is shown that the influence of the river basin increases as distance between the compared geographical areas expands (Heino et al., 2014, 2017).

The river continuum concept (RCC) (Vannote et al., 1980) suggests that the physical factors, such as width, depth, flow velocity, flow volume, and temperature in a river system represent a continuous gradient changing in a regular manner from the headwater to the river mouth. The longitudinal gradient of the community composition is observed in accordance with the environmental changes. Headwater streams are often shadowed by riparian vegetation, which reduces the autotrophic production. Coarse particulate organic matter of allochthonous origin is a predominant food source and the proportion of shredders and collectors is high in the benthic communities. With increasing of stream size, the importance of allochthonous organic matter reduces, like the shading of the channel. It leads to an increase in primary production including algae attached to hard surfaces and proportion of scrapers feeding on said algae is maximised in midsized rivers. As one moves towards the river mouth, the role of autotrophic organic matter decreases, fine particulate organic matter predominates as a food resource, and collectors become the dominant functional feeding group in invertebrate communities.

In the surveyed streams, elements of the river continuum are observed. The indicator taxa for the subgroup №3B with the highest median depth and channel width, corresponding to the sections of the lower reaches of the River Anyuy and some of its tributaries are represented by a high proportion of collectors. It conforms to the description of benthic communities in large rivers in RCC. Samples of subgroup №3A, taken mainly from small tributaries of the River Anyuy with their indicator taxon *Gammarus koreanus* being predominantly shredder, correspond to headwater streams in RCC. Among the indicator taxa in group №2 (midsized rivers), scrapers are widely represented, which also conforms to

RCC. However, in case of the continual longitudinal changes, the similarity of communities at adjacent stations would be higher than in general for the entire river or for the river network. In the surveyed streams, it should be noted that spatially close samples are not always more similar taxonomically than spatially distant ones. For example, many neighbouring samples, collected in the Bajal River channel, are included in different subgroups (№1A and №2A). Subgroup №2B, characterised by the highest internal similarity, includes samples from both river basins. Other groups also include samples from different streams. It is usual for rivers, when the composition of hydrobionts differs less in similar habitats of neighbouring rivers, than in different habitats within the same watercourse (Doisy & Rabeni, 2001; Dallas, 2007b; Costa & Melo, 2008).

Townsend (1989) noted that the river continuum concept is not universally applicable worldwide. Townsend (1989) proposed the concept of patch dynamics, based on the notion of the mosaic nature of the river bottom and the importance of disturbances in the formation of communities. Disturbance refers to any event that results in the removal of organisms from habitats and opens up the possibility for subsequent colonisation, such as flood. The constant process of drifting and colonisation of substrates is called «continuous redistribution of benthos». In the process of recolonisation, the key role is played by patches of the channel, in which organisms can survive during a high disturbance, i.e. refugia (e.g. near the banks and in backwaters in general). The location of refugia patches is random, and in general stochastic processes play a large role in the formation of communities in streams and rivers. Bogatov (1995) proposed a concept combining RCC and patch dynamics. It is noted that, although refugia in the riverbed are located randomly, their number and diversity naturally increase from the headwater to the ritral. At the same time, the diversity of organisms increases, too. Probably, the high biodiversity in ritral, noted in RCC, is explained by the high number of refugia. Indeed, in the surveyed watercourses, the largest number of taxa was noted in the subgroup of samples belonging to the ritral (№2A). It is noted that the continuum is usually quickly restored after disturbances due to organisms recolonising habitats from refugia.

Perry & Schaeffer (1987) indicated the existence of a longitudinal gradient in the compo-

sition of communities in rivers, but this gradient is not continuous. It is interrupted by abrupt changes. These changes can be triggered by tributaries, geological discontinuities, or land use factors. Such communities can differ sharply in composition from neighbouring ones. Thus, the distribution of the benthos is characterised as a punctuated gradient. According to the riverine ecosystem synthesis (RES) (Thorp et al., 2006), the distribution of species from the headwater to the mouth reflects the functional process zones (FPZ) to a higher extent than the spatial position along the longitudinal dimension of the rather network. FPZ refers to large hydrogeomorphic patches formed by catchment geomorphology and flow characteristics. Both short-term and long-term variability and predictability of environmental conditions differ among types of hydrogeomorphic patches both within and among rivers. The formation of communities is predominantly influenced by stochastic processes associated with hydraulics (flow velocity, turbulence, and substrate mobility), droughts and floods.

In the explored streams, 50 taxa have been identified as relatively strong significant indicators ($\text{IndVal} > 20$) for the respective communities. This is only a quarter of the totally identified taxonomical richness. Within the selected sample groups, the similarity level is relatively low (from about 4% to about 37%). The high variability of structure is typical for river benthic communities (Merovich & Petty, 2010). The continual distribution has been observed for macroinvertebrate communities in many river systems (Rabeni et al., 2002; Heino et al., 2003, 2014; Tolonen et al., 2016), even in the case of discrete changes in environment conditions (Merovich & Petty, 2010).

Thus, this study revealed the existence of relatively distinct species complexes of hydrobionts corresponding to habitats differing in substrate type and flow velocity. However, the low proportion of indicator taxa for these habitats indicates a mixture of species composition from neighbouring habitats. Organisms respond individually to changes in environmental conditions, resulting in a continuous distribution of macrozoobenthos (Merovich & Petty, 2010). Environmental factors serve as an important ecological filter that allows only species with certain adaptations to exist in habitats (Poff, 1997). In macroscale studies covering several large river systems, a significant proportion of community variability is explained by the river basin factor (Heino et al., 2017).

It should be noted that some elements of the river continuum, in terms of Vannote et al. (1980) concept, exist in surveyed streams. At the same time, abrupt changes between neighbouring communities can be observed as well as a relatively high degree of taxonomical similarity between reaches with similar environmental conditions from different streams. The distribution of macroinvertebrates thereby can be characterised as a punctuated gradient described by Perry & Schaeffer (1987). In spite of patchiness of the river bottom and a high significance of stochastic factors in the formation of stream communities, there is a well-defined pattern in distribution of macroinvertebrates.

Conclusions

Studies carried out in the pristine environment, undisturbed or minimally disturbed by anthropogenic activity, such as the natural reserves, are essential for understanding the natural patterns of ecosystem functioning. This understanding is necessary for a correct assessment of the ecosystem condition during monitoring studies by comparison with reference conditions. Analysis of the distribution of macroinvertebrate communities of two Far Eastern rivers basins on the territories of the Bajal Sanctuary and Anyuy National Park shows that the distribution of organisms does not correspond completely to either continuity or discreteness. Well-defined statistically significant groups of samples based on taxonomical similarity have been discovered as well as environmental factors corresponding to these groups. A complex of indicator taxa has been also determined for each group. Local abiotic factors such as substrate type and water flow velocity strongly influence the formation of species complexes. In addition, the factor of the river basin itself played an important role, as supported by the differences between samples from the Anyuy and the Bajal river basins. However, the obtained groups are characterised by a high internal variability and do not form discrete clusters with obvious hiatus on the ordination diagram. Longitudinal patterns of distributions partly conform to the river continuum concept; however, abrupt changes of taxonomical composition between the neighbouring samples can be noticed. Thus, the longitudinal distribution of macroinvertebrates for each river can be characterised as a punctuated gradient. When planning monitoring studies of aquatic ecosystems based on macrozooben-

thos, the variability of hydrobionts communities at different scales must be taken into account.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the staff of the Joint Directorate of State Natural Reserves and National Parks of Khabarovsk Territory (Russia) for their assistance in organising expeditionary studies. We are grateful to Mikhail V. Chertoprud (Associate Professor of Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia) and Dmitry M. Palatov (Senior Researcher of the A.N. Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution of the RAS, Russia) for taxonomical identification of the macroinvertebrates from the Anyuy River basin; Irina N. Nikonova (Senior Specialist of the All-Russian Federal Research Institute of Fisheries and Oceanography, Russia) for the photographs; Nikolay A. Aseyev (Researcher of Institute of Higher Nervous Activity and Neurophysiology of RAS, Russia); and Anna M. Evseyeva (Moscow, Russia), Irina N. Nikonova, Ivan S. Reshetov (Tambov, Russia), Matvey V. Roshin (Researcher of Institute of Higher Nervous Activity and Neurophysiology of RAS, Russia) for support within sampling in the Anyuy River basin and Bajal River basin.

Supporting Information

The primary data on the zoobenthos samples and environmental factors (Electronic Supplement. Data on the abundance of zoobenthos organisms in samples and the values of environmental factors) may be found in the [Supporting Information](#).

References

- Anderson M.J., Gorley R.N., Clarke K.R. 2008. *PERMANOVA+ for PRIMER: Guide to Software and Statistical Methods*. Plymouth: PRIMER-E. 214 p.
- Astakhov M.V., Skriptsova A.V. 2020. Potential of utilization of allochthonous invertebrates by *Gammarus koreanus* Uéno (Amphipoda). *Transactions of Papanin Institute for Biology of Inland Waters RAS* 92(25): 28–38. DOI: 10.47021/0320-3557-2021-28-40 [In Russian]
- Beisel J.N., Usseglio-Polatera P., Thomas S., Moreteau J.C. 1998. Stream community structure in relation to spatial variation: the influence of mesohabitat characteristics. *Hydrobiologia* 389(1–3): 73–88. DOI: 10.1023/A:1003519429979
- Brunke M., Hoffmann A., Puscha M. 2001. Use of Mesohabitat-Specific Relationships Between Flow Velocity And River Discharge to Assess Invertebrate Minimum Flow Requirements. *Regulated Rivers: Research and Management* 17(6): 667–676. DOI: 10.1002/rrr.626
- Bogatov V.V. 1995. Combined conception of functioning river ecosystems. *Bulletin of the Far Eastern Branch, Russian Academy of Sciences* 3: 51–61. [In Russian]
- Chebanova V.V. 2008. *Benthos of salmon rivers in Kamchatka*. Moscow: VNIRO. 172 p. [In Russian]
- Chertoprud M.V. 2021. Main Classes of Rheophilic Macroinvertebrates Communities and Their Regional Variability in Eurasia. *Inland Water Biology* 14(5): 555–572. DOI: 10.1134/S2079086411030017
- Chertoprud M.V., Chertoprud E.S., Vorob'eva L.V., Palatov D.M., Tsyganov A.N., Reshetov I.S., Kovacheva N.P. 2020. Macrozoobenthic Communities of the Piedmont and Lowland Watercourses of the Lower Amur Region. *Inland Water Biology* 13(1): 51–61. DOI: 10.1134/S1995082920010046
- Clarke K.R., Gorley R.N., Somerfield P.J., Warwick R.M. 2014. *Change in Marine Communities: An Approach to Statistical Analysis and Interpretation, 3rd ed.* Plymouth: PRIMER-E. 262 p.
- Clements F.E. 1916. *Plant Succession. An Analysis of the Development of Vegetation*. Washington: Carnegie Institution. 512 p.
- Costa S.S., Melo A.S. 2008. Beta diversity in stream macroinvertebrate assemblages: among-site and among-microhabitat components. *Hydrobiologia* 598(1): 131–138. DOI: 10.1007/s10750-007-9145-7
- Dallas H.F. 2007a. The effect of biotope-specific sampling for aquatic macroinvertebrates on reference site classification and the identification of environmental predictors in Mpumalanga, South Africa. *African Journal of Aquatic Science* 32(2): 165–173. DOI: 10.2989/AJAS.2007.32.2.8.205
- Dallas H.F. 2007b. The influence of biotope availability on macroinvertebrate assemblages in South African rivers: implications for aquatic bioassessment. *Freshwater Biology* 52(2): 370–380. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2427.2006.01684.x
- Doisy K.E., Rabeni C.F. 2001. Flow conditions, benthic food resources, and invertebrate community composition in a low-gradient stream in Missouri. *Journal of the North American Benthological Society* 20(1): 17–32. DOI: 10.2307/1468185
- Glantz S.A. 2012. *Primer of Biostatistics, 7th ed.* McGraw-Hill. 312 p.
- Gleason H.A. 1926. The individualistic concept of the plant association. *Bulletin of the Torrey Botanical Club* 53(1): 7–26. DOI: 10.2307/2479933
- Grönroos M., Heino J., Siqueira T., Landeiro V.L., Kotanen J., Bini L.M. 2013. Metacommunity structuring in stream networks: roles of dispersal mode, distance type, and regional environmental context. *Ecology and Evolution* 3(13): 4473–4487. DOI: 10.1002/ece3.834
- Hammer Ø., Harper D.A.T., Ryan P.D. 2001. PAST: Paleontological Statistics Software Package for Education and Data Analysis. *Palaeontologia Electronica* 4(1): 1–9.
- Haritonov A.Yu., Malikova E.I. 1998. Odonata of the Russian Far East: a summary. *Odonatologica* 27(3): 375–381.
- Heino J. 2005. Metacommunity patterns of highly diverse stream midges: gradients, checkerboards, and nestedness, or is there only randomness?. *Ecological Entomology* 30(5): 590–599. DOI: 10.1111/j.0307-6946.2005.00728.x

- Heino J. 2013a. Does dispersal ability affect the relative importance of environmental control and spatial structuring of littoral macroinvertebrate communities?. *Oecologia* 171(4): 971–980. DOI: 10.1007/s00442-012-2451-4
- Heino J. 2013b. Environmental heterogeneity, dispersal mode, and co-occurrence in stream macroinvertebrates. *Ecology and Evolution* 3(2): 344–355. DOI: 10.1002/ece3.470
- Heino J., Grönroos M., Soininen J., Virtanen R., Muotka T. 2012. Context dependency and metacommunity structuring in boreal headwater streams. *Oikos* 121(4): 537–544. DOI: 10.1111/j.1600-0706.2011.19715.x
- Heino J., Ilmonen J., Paasivirta L. 2014. Continuous variation of macroinvertebrate communities along environmental gradients in northern streams. *Boreal Environment Research* 19(1): 21–38.
- Heino J., Muotka T., Mykrä H., Paavola R., Hämäläinen H., Koskenniemi E. 2003. Defining macroinvertebrate assemblage types of headwater streams: implications for bioassessment and conservation. *Ecological Applications* 13(3): 842–852. DOI: 10.1890/1051-0761(2003)013[0842:DM ATOH]2.0.CO;2
- Heino J., Mykrä H. 2008. Control of stream insect assemblages: roles of spatial configuration and local environmental factors. *Ecological Entomology* 33(5): 614–622. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2311.2008.01012.x
- Heino J., Soininen J., Alahuhta J., Lappalainen J., Virtanen R. 2017. Metacommunity ecology meets biogeography: effects of geographical region, spatial dynamics and environmental filtering on community structure in aquatic organisms. *Oecologia* 183(1): 121–137. DOI: 10.1007/s00442-016-3750-y
- Ipatov V.S., Kirikova L.A. 1997. *Phytocenology*. Saint Petersburg: Saint Petersburg State University. 316 p. [In Russian]
- Johnson R.K., Goedkoop W., Sandin L. 2004. Spatial scale and ecological relationships between the macroinvertebrate communities of stony habitats of streams and lakes. *Freshwater Biology* 49(9): 1179–1194. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2427.2004.01262.x
- Kocharina S.L., Khamenkova E.V. 2003. Structure of the bottom invertebrate communities in the some streams of the Tauj River basin (the Magadan Region). In: *Vladimir Ya. Levaniidov's Biennial Memorial Meetings*. Vol. 2. P. 96–106. [In Russian]
- Korte T. 2010. Current and substrate preferences of benthic invertebrates in the rivers of the Hindu Kush-Himalayan region as indicators of hydromorphological degradation. *Hydrobiologia* 651(1): 77–91. DOI: 10.1007/s10750-010-0291-y
- Kubosova K., Brabec K., Jarkovsky J., Syrovatka V. 2010. Selection of indicative taxa for river habitats: a case study on benthic macroinvertebrates using indicator species analysis and the random forest methods. *Hydrobiologia* 651(1): 101–114. DOI: 10.1007/s10750-010-0280-1
- Labay V.S. 2007. Distribution of benthos in the lower ritrale of the River Poronai under the influence of some abiotic environmental factors. *Proceedings of the Sakhalin branch of VNIRO* 9: 184–206. [In Russian]
- Labay V.S., Novoselova A.I., Berezova O.N., Sharlay O.B., Shpilko T.S., Nikitin V.D., Prokhorov A.P. 2019. Macrobenthos of the crenal and rithral zones of a typical «salmon» river in northeastern Sakhalin Island (on example of the Dagi River). *Izvestiya TINRO* 196(1): 138–154. DOI: 10.26428/1606-9919-2019-196-138-154 [In Russian]
- Legendre P., Legendre L. 2012. *Numerical ecology*. 3rd ed. Amsterdam: Elsevier B.V. 990 p.
- Leibold M.A., Holyoak M., Mouquet N., Amarasekare P., Chase J.M., Hoopes M.F., Holt R.D., Shurin J.B., Law R., Tilman D., Loreau M., Gonzalez A. 2004. The metacommunity concept: a framework for multi-scale community ecology. *Ecology Letters* 7(7): 601–613. DOI: 10.1111/j.1461-0248.2004.00608.x
- Leley A.S. (Ed). 2006. *Key to the insects of Russian Far East. Vol. 6. Part 4: Diptera and Siphonaptera*. Vladivostok: Dalnauka. 936 p. [In Russian]
- Makarchenko E.A., Makarchenko M.A., Zorina O.V., Sergeeva I.V. 2005. Preliminary data on fauna and taxonomy of chironomids (Diptera, Chironomidae) of the Russian Far East. In: *Vladimir Ya. Levaniidov's Biennial Memorial Meetings*. Vol. 3. P. 394–420. [In Russian]
- Makarchenko E.A., Makarchenko M.A., Zorina O.V., Yavorskaya N.M. 2008. Preliminary data on chironomid fauna (Diptera, Chironomidae) of the Amur river basin. In: *Freshwater ecosystems of the Amur River basin*. Vladivostok: Institute of Biology and Soil Sciences, FEB RAS. P. 189–208. [In Russian]
- Merovich G.T., Petty J.T. 2010. Continuous response of benthic macroinvertebrate assemblages to a discrete disturbance gradient: consequences for diagnosing stressors. *Journal of the North American Benthological Society* 29(4): 1241–1257. DOI: 10.1899/09-164.1
- Merritt R.W., Cummins K.W., Berg M.B. (Eds.). 2019. *An introduction to the aquatic insects of North America*. Dubuque: Kendall Hunt. 1481 p.
- Orel O.V. 2016. Fauna of non-biting midges of subfamily Chironominae (Diptera, Chironomidae) of the Russian Far East. In: *Freshwater Life*. Vol. 2. Vladivostok: Dalnauka. P. 185–196. [In Russian]
- Pardo I., Armitage P.D. 1997. Species assemblages as descriptors of mesohabitats. *Hydrobiologia* 344(1–3): 111–128. DOI: 10.1023/A:1002958412237
- Perry J.A., Schaeffer D.J. 1987. The longitudinal distribution of riverine benthos: A river dis-continuum?. *Hydrobiologia* 148(3): 257–268. DOI: 10.1007/BF00017528
- Poff N.L. 1997. Landscape filters and species traits: towards mechanistic understanding and prediction in stream ecology. *Journal of the North American Benthological Society* 16(2): 391–409. DOI: 10.2307/1468026
- Potikha E., Vshivkova T. 2016. The caddisfly faunas (Insecta, Trichoptera) of Protected Natural Areas in

- southern Far East Russia. *Zoosymposia* 10: 357–383. DOI: 10.11646/zoosymposia.10.1.33
- Potikha E.V. 2011. Dynamic of benthos biomass and density in small rivers in the Central Sikhote-Alin. In: *Vladimir Ya. Levanidov's Biennial Memorial Meetings*. Vol. 5. P. 425–446. [In Russian]
- Potikha E.V. 2015. A Taxonomic List of the Mayflies, Stoneflies and Caddisflies (Insecta: Ephemeroptera, Plecoptera and Trichoptera) of the Sikhote-Alin Biosphere Reserve. *Achievements in the Life Sciences* 9(1): 22–31. DOI: 10.1016/j.als.2015.05.004
- Rabeni C.F., Doisy K.E., Galat D.L. 2002. Testing the biological basis of a stream habitat classification using benthic invertebrates. *Ecological Applications* 12(3): 782–796. DOI: 10.1890/1051-0761(2002)012[0782:TTBBOA]2.0.CO;2
- Sandin L. 2003. Benthic macroinvertebrates in Swedish streams: community structure, taxon richness, and environmental relations. *Ecography* 26(3): 269–282. DOI: 10.1034/j.1600-0587.2003.03380.x
- Silva D.R.O., Ligeiro R., Hughes R.M., Callisto M. 2014. Visually determined stream mesohabitats influence benthic macroinvertebrate assessments in headwater streams. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment* 186(9): 5479–5488. DOI: 10.1007/s10661-014-3797-3
- Takemon Y. 1997. Management of biodiversity in aquatic ecosystems: dynamic aspects of habitat complexity in stream ecosystems. In: T. Abe, S.A. Levin, M. Higgashi (Eds.): *Biodiversity: an ecological perspective*. New York: Springer-Verlag. P. 259–275.
- Teslenko V.A. 2009. Stoneflies (Plecoptera) of the Russian Far East: diversity and zoogeography. *Aquatic Insects* 31(1): 693–706. DOI: 10.1080/01650420902812230
- Teslenko V.A. 2014. New records of stoneflies (Plecoptera) for the Bureya and Zeya rivers basins. In: *Vladimir Ya. Levanidov's Biennial Memorial Meetings*. Vol. 6. P. 654–659. [In Russian]
- Teslenko V.A., Matafonov P.V., Matafonov D.V. 2014. To the stonefly fauna (Insecta, Plecoptera) of Upper Amur River basin (Transbaikalia). In: *Vladimir Ya. Levanidov's Biennial Memorial Meetings*. Vol. 6. P. 660–669. [In Russian]
- Teslenko V.A., Zhiltzova L.A. 2009. *Key to the stoneflies (Insecta, Plecoptera) of Russia and adjacent countries. Imagines and nymphs*. Vladivostok: Dalnauka. 382 p. [In Russian]
- Thorp J.H., Thoms M.C., Delong M.D. 2006. The riverine ecosystem synthesis: biocomplexity in river networks across space and time. *River Research and Applications* 22(2): 123–147. DOI: 10.1002/rra.901
- Tiunova T.M. 2006. Trophic Structure of Invertebrate Communities in Ecosystems of Salmon Rivers in the Southern Far East. *Russian Journal of Ecology* 37(6): 419–425. DOI: 10.1134/S1067413606060099
- Tiunova T.M. 2007. Current knowledge of the mayfly fauna (Ephemeroptera) in the Far East of Russia and adjacent territories. *Euroasian Entomological Journal* 6(2): 181–194. [In Russian]
- Tiunova T.M. 2008. Composition and the structure of zoobenthos communities of microbiotopes in the metarhithral of small foothill river the temperate-cold-water type. In: *Vladimir Ya. Levanidov's Biennial Memorial Meetings*. Vol. 4. P. 31–45. [In Russian]
- Tiunova T.M. 2009. Biodiversity and distribution of mayflies (Ephemeroptera) in the Russian Far East. *Aquatic Insects* 31(1): 671–691. DOI: 10.1080/01650420902800581
- Tiunova T.M., Gorovaya E.A. 2011. Mayfly fauna (Insecta, Ephemeroptera) of the Low Amur and its left bank tributaries. In: *Vladimir Ya. Levanidov's Biennial Memorial Meetings*. Vol. 5. P. 522–539. [In Russian]
- Tiunova T.M., Korotenko G.A. 2008. Mayflies (Insecta: Ephemeroptera) of northern Sikhote-Alin (the ecology-faunistic review and value in feeding of fishes. *Izvestiya TINRO* 154: 165–188. [In Russian]
- Tolonen K.E., Leinonen K., Marttila H., Erkinaro J., Heino J. 2016. Environmental predictability of taxonomic and functional community composition in high-latitude streams. *Freshwater Biology* 62(1): 1–16. DOI: 10.1111/fwb.12832
- Townsend C.R. 1989. The patch dynamics concept of stream community ecology. *Journal of the North American Benthological Society* 8(1): 36–50. DOI: 10.2307/1467400
- Tsalolikhin S.J. (Ed.). 1997. *Key to freshwater invertebrates of Russia and adjacent lands*. Vol. 3: Arachnids. Lower insects. St. Petersburg: Zoological Institute RAS. 439 p. [In Russian]
- Tsalolikhin S.J. (Ed.). 2000. *Key to freshwater invertebrates of Russia and adjacent lands*. Vol. 4: Dipteran insects. St. Petersburg: Nauka. 998 p. [In Russian]
- Tsalolikhin S.J. (Ed.). 2001. *Key to freshwater invertebrates of Russia and adjacent lands*. Vol. 5: Higher insects. St. Petersburg: Nauka. 825 p. [In Russian]
- Tsalolikhin S.J. (Ed.). 2004. *Key to freshwater invertebrates of Russia and adjacent lands*. Vol. 6: Molluscs. Polychaetes. Nemerteans. St. Petersburg: Nauka. 528 p. [In Russian]
- Yavorskaya N.M. 2008. Chironomid larvae (Diptera, Chironomidae) from several rivers of the Amur basin and rivers of the Tatar Strait continental coast. *Izvestiya TINRO* 152: 201–214. [In Russian]
- Vannote R.L., Minshall G.W., Cummins K.W., Sedell J.R., Cushing C.E. 1980. The River Continuum Concept. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 37(1): 131–137. DOI: 10.1139/f80-01.
- Yavorskaya N.M. 2015. Community structure of benthic invertebrates of the Levaya River (Amur River basin) (Khabarovsk territory). *Amurian Zoological Journal* 7(1): 14–19. [In Russian]
- Yavorskaya N.M. 2016. Structure of zoobenthos in the left-bank tributaries of the Lower Amur (Khabarovsk Territory). *Regional Problems* 19(4): 40–45. [In Russian]

- Yavorskaya N.M. 2021. Zoobenthos of salmon rivers in the Anyuysky National Park (Khabarovsky Region, Russia). *Amurian Zoological Journal* 13(2): 183–201. DOI: 10.33910/2686-9519-2021-13-2-183-201 [In Russian]
- Zasypkina I.A. 2011. Caddisflies (Insecta, Trichoptera) in the north of the Far East of Russia. In: *Vladimir Ya. Levanidov's Biennial Memorial Meetings*. Vol. 5. P. 187–198. [In Russian]
- Zasypkina I.A. 2018. An annotated check-list of Stoneflies (Insecta, Plecoptera) of the family Capniidae from the northern part of the Russian Far East. *Euroasian Entomological Journal* 17(2): 92–99. DOI: 10.15298/euroasentj.17.2.03 [In Russian]

ОБЩИЕ ЗАКОНОМЕРНОСТИ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ МАКРОЗООБЕНТОСА В БАССЕЙНАХ ДВУХ РЕК ХАБАРОВСКОГО КРАЯ (ДАЛЬНИЙ ВОСТОК РОССИИ)

Л. В. Воробьева^{1,*}

¹Всероссийский научно-исследовательский институт рыбного хозяйства и океанографии, Россия

*e-mail: vorobjeva.lada@yandex.ru

²Институт проблем экологии и эволюции имени А.Н. Северцова РАН, Россия

В данной работе проанализированы закономерности распределения макрозообентоса водотоков в бассейнах рек Баджал и Анюй (Хабаровский край, Россия) на территориях Баджальского заказника и Анюйского национального парка. С помощью процедуры DistLM (distance-based linear models) проведена оценка доли распределения макробеспозвоночных, объясненной учтенными в работе факторами (бассейн, скорость течения, субстрат, ширина русла, температура, pH). Все эти факторы вносили достоверный вклад, суммарно объясняя около трети распределения макробеспозвоночных. Основными объясняющими факторами были водосборный бассейн и субстрат (9.3% и 10.5% соответственно), а также скорость течения (5.7%). На основании кластерного анализа выделены восемь достоверных групп проб по признаку сходства таксономического состава. Выявлены четкие закономерности приуроченности таксономических комплексов к определенным биотопам. Локальные экологические факторы являются сильным фильтром, влияющим на формирование таксономических сообществ. Значимую роль в формировании сообществ играет и фактор принадлежности к бассейну реки, что следует учитывать при планировании мониторинговых исследований крупного пространственного масштаба. Однако выделенные группы и подгруппы характеризуются низким уровнем внутреннего сходства; около четверти общего числа видов относятся к таксонам-индикаторам, пробы не образуют дискретных кластеров на диаграмме ординации. Продольное распределение макробеспозвоночных для каждой реки можно охарактеризовать как прерывистый или «пунктирный» градиент.

Ключевые слова: водоток, Дальний Восток России, пресноводные макробеспозвоночные, сообщество, фактор среды

THE BIVALVES (MOLLUSCA) FROM PRIORITY MARINE REGIONS IN THE CENTRE-SOUTH OF THE MEXICAN TRANSITIONAL PACIFIC, ASSOCIATED WITH THE ROCKY INTERTIDAL ZONE

Victor I. López-Rojas¹ ,
Jesús G. Padilla-Serrato^{1,2}

¹Universidad Autónoma de Guerrero, Mexico

*e-mail: rfloresgarza@yahoo.com

²Programa de Investigadoras e Investigadores por México-CONAHCYT, Mexico

Received: 21.06.2023. Revised: 27.09.2023. Accepted: 01.10.2023.

In Mexico, due to its high biological diversity, use of its resources, and a lack of knowledge about its biodiversity, Priority Marine Regions have been designated. The classification of these regions has served as an instrument for the large-scale conservation because the species composition is relatively homogeneous in these regions. This study reports some ecological attributes of bivalves from the Priority Marine Regions located in the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion. Three samplings have been carried out in 2016–2018 in the rocky intertidal zone. In each sample per site, an area of 10 m² was covered, and the sampling unit was 1 m². A total of 4119 specimens were recorded, by identifying 53 species (35 genera, 18 families, and two specimens identified to genus). The richness of the species expected was calculated using non-parametric estimators, by showing acceptable completeness of the inventory. The highest species richness and diversity were recorded in the Copala-Punta Maldonado region (33 species), whereas the highest abundance and density were found in the Colola-Maruata region (30.9 individuals/m²). The best-represented species in abundance and distribution were *Chama coralloides*, *Brachidontes adamsianus*, *Isognomon janus*, and *Choromytilus palliopunctatus*. By considering their life form and degree of occurrence, studied bivalves attached to a hard substrate (epifaunal species) and restricted to habitats with particular characteristics (occasional species) were the most commonly found. The information provided here is directed to eight Marine Regions designated as a priority for conservation in Mexico, which is important for planning, decision-making, and formulating initiatives aimed at helping to co-ordinate management practice through outreach efforts to the conservation and sustainable use of bivalves as marine resources.

Key words: biodiversity, Bivalvia, conservation, ecological attributes, Mexican Pacific, molluscs

Introduction

Of the molluscs, marine bivalves are the group with the most information available (Ríos-Jara, 2015; Vahidi et al., 2021; Albert et al., 2022). Species of this group are important due to their ecological relevance as indicators of environmental deterioration and bioaccumulation of pollutants. In addition, they are fished and cultivated for human consumption and have ornamental, artisanal, and industrial use (Baqueiro-Cárdenas et al., 2007; Barrientos-Luján et al., 2022).

In Mexico, the information on bivalves deals with ecological issues where species inventory is also known. These studies have been carried out in the northern Pacific and Gulf of California (e.g. Hendrickx et al., 2007; Zamorano & Hendrickx, 2011; Esqueda-González et al., 2014, 2022; Pérez-Estrada et al., 2023), and other ones in the central Pacific. On the coasts of the states of Jalisco, Colima, and Michoacán, the studies of Holguín-Quiñones & González-Pedraza (1994), Landa-Jaime

& Arciniega-Flores (1998), Villarroel et al. (2000), Ríos-Jara et al. (2020), have been reported.

In the South Pacific, the studies of Holguín-Quiñones & González-Pedraza (1989), Zamorano et al. (2008), Flores-Garza et al. (2011, 2014), and López-Rojas et al. (2017) presented species lists. Overall, Castillo-Rodríguez (2014) reported 2576 species for the Mexican Pacific, 66.45% gastropods and 26% bivalves, while Barrientos-Luján et al. (2022) reported 265 species for the coasts of Oaxaca, Guerrero, and Michoacán.

Furthermore, considering their high diversity, bivalves have been used to understand the origin and dynamics of the latitudinal diversity gradient in the oceans (Roy et al., 2000; Krug et al., 2007). However, they have also been used to demonstrate that large-scale diversity patterns are set by the spatial and temporal dynamics of changes in origin, extinction, and geographic range (Jablonski et al., 2017; Chattopadhyay et al., 2021).

Marine ecoregions are areas where species composition is relatively homogeneous, which may be determined by the predominance of a small number of ecosystems or a distinct set of oceanographic or topographic features (Spalding et al., 2007). Likewise, ecoregions support global and regional conservation planning efforts. These designations are a logical framework for large-scale conservation strategies (Abell et al., 2008).

In the Mexican Pacific, five marine ecoregions were described, for which the priority need for a strategic plan for long-term biodiversity conservation is recognised. One of them is the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion. It presents a great variety of coastal ecosystems with a high diversity of fish, crustacean and mollusc species (Wilkinson et al., 2009). In the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion, there are some Priority Marine Regions, which have served as a logical framework for large-scale conservation as they are intended to ensure biological connectivity and protection of ecosystem integrity in areas, where the species composition is relatively homogeneous (Arriaga-Cabrera et al., 2009).

Interaction processes, spatial and temporal dynamics, species inventories, and community sizes are fundamental for an integral knowledge of marine biodiversity as well as for proposing conservation strategies and adequate management of

natural resources (Carrascal & Palomino, 2006; Ríos-Jara et al., 2020). Research tasks were to present the species richness, abundance and density, life forms, hierarchical location, diversity, and similarity of bivalve communities, which inhabit the rocky intertidal of the Priority Marine Regions of the central-southern zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion. This information will allow the development of better strategies for conserving and preserving marine resources.

Material and Methods

Study area

The study has been carried out in eight Priority Marine Regions located in the south-central zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion, which covers the coast of the states of Oaxaca, Guerrero, and Michoacán (Fig. 1). The selection of the sampling sites was made considering the spatial heterogeneity as well as the accessibility to the sites. Each site was georeferenced and classified according to its exposure to waves, type, and substrate stability, using the criteria of Flores-Garza et al. (2012). Finally, the rock type was determined according to the descriptions found in the geological charts of the Instituto Nacional de Estadística, Geográfica e Informática (INEGI, 2021), and by our own field observations (Table 1).

Table 1. Geographical location of the Priority Marine Regions, state, polygon, geographical extension and the sampling sites with their most relevant habitat characteristics

Priority Marine Regions	State	Polygon		Geographical extension (km ²)	Sampling sites	Habitat characteristics (Stability and type of substrate; type of rock; wave exposure)
		Latitude (N)	Longitude (W)			
36. Huatulco	Oaxaca	15.90° to 15.70°	96.18° to 95.75°	166	San Agustín	Middle stability with rock masses, large boulders, and coral fragments; acid intrusive igneous rock type; middle wave exposure
35. Puerto Ángel-Mazunte	Oaxaca	15.73° to 15.64°	96.30° to 96.35°	73	Puerto Ángel	Middle stability with rock masses, large boulders, and some rolled boulders; gneiss type metamorphic rock type; middle wave exposure
34. Chacahua-Escobilla	Oaxaca	16.04° to 15.79°	97.79° to 97.03°	615	Roca Blanca	High stability with rock masses; acid intrusive igneous rock type; high wave exposure
33. Copala-Punta Maldonado	Guerrero	16.54° to 15.60°	99.41° to 98.20°	6 352	Punta Maldonado	Middle stability with large boulders and rolled boulders; acid intrusive sedimentary sandstone rock type; middle wave exposure
32. Coyuca-Tres Palos	Guerrero	16.59° to 17.47°	99.42° to 100.55°	829	Acapulco	Low stability with Rolled boulders and gravel; acid intrusive igneous and artificial substrate rock type; middle wave exposure
31. Piedra Tlacoyunque	Guerrero	17.63° to 17.23°	101.72° to 101.03°	1 230	Ojo de Agua	Low stability with large boulders and rolled boulders; basic intrusive igneous rock type; middle wave exposure
30. Mexiquillo-Delta del Balsas	Michoacán	18.04° to 16.84°	102.81° to 101.94°	8 641	Caleta de Campos	Middle stability with rock masses, large boulders, and some rolled boulders; intermediate extrusive igneous (volcanic) rock type; middle wave exposure
29. Colola-Maruata	Michoacán	18.31° to 18.18°	103.42° to 103.2	112	Colola	High stability with rock masses; acid intrusive igneous rock type; high wave exposure

Fig. 1. Geographical location of the Priority Marine Regions (PMR) and sampling sites (numbers) in the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion. Designations of Priority Marine Regions: PMR36 – Huatulco, PMR35 – Puerto Ángel-Mazunte, PMR34 – Chacahua-Escobilla, PMR33 – Copala-Punta Maldonado, PMR32 – Coyuca-Tres Palos, PMR31 – Piedra Tlacoyunque, PMR30 – Mexiquillo-Delta del Balsas, PMR29 – Colola-Maruata. Sampling sites: 1 – San Agustín, 2 – Puerto Ángel, 3 – Roca Blanca, 4 – Punta Maldonado, 5 – Acapulco, 6 – Ojo de Agua, 7 – Caleta de Campos, 8 – Colola.

San Agustín (15.68° N, 96.23° W) was the sampling site in the Priority Marine Region Huatulco. It is considered a priority site for the conservation of corals (López-Pérez & López-García, 2008). It is located within the extensions of the Huatulco National Park (CONANP, 2023), also designated as a RAMSAR-1321 site (RAMSAR, 2023) and Huatulco Biosphere Reserve, Mexico (UNESCO, 2023). In the Priority Marine Region Puerto Ángel-Mazunte, Puerto Ángel (15.65° N, 96.48° W) was the sampling site considered a priority site for the coral conservation (López-Pérez & López-García, 2008). Roca Blanca (15.93° N, 97.35° W) was the sampling site in the Chacahua-Escobilla Priority Marine Region. It is located within the geographic extensions of the Lagunas de Chacahua National Park (CONANP, 2023), also designated as a RAMSAR-1819 site (RAMSAR, 2023).

In the Priority Marine Region Copala-Punta Maldonado, Punta Maldonado was the sampling site, considered a priority site for the conservation of Mexico’s coastal and oceanic environments (CONABIO, 2023). Acapulco (16.83° N, 99.9° W) was the sampled site in the Priority Ma-

rine Region Coyuca-Tres Palos and Ojo de Agua (17.30° N, 101.05° W) in the Priority Marine Region Piedra Tlacoyunque. Ojo de Agua belongs to the Petacalco-Piedra Tlacoyunque beaches and is considered a priority site for the conservation of the coastal and oceanic environments of Mexico (CONABIO, 2023).

Caleta de Campos (18.06° N, 102.75° W) was the sampling site in the Priority Marine Region Mexiquillo-Delta del Balsas, located between the Mexiquillo-Caleta de Campos beaches. It is considered a priority site for the conservation of coastal environments and oceanic of Mexico (CONABIO, 2023). Finally, Colola (18.28° N, 103.4° W) was the Priority Marine Region Colola-Maruata sampling site. Colola is an important nesting beach site for three sea turtles. It was designated a protected natural area (CONANP, 2023) and site RAMSAR-1788 (RAMSAR, 2023).

Collection of samples

Three field trips were conducted: the first in November 2016, the second in March 2017, and the third in February 2018. The systematic sampling has been carried out in the rocky intertidal

zone during low tide hours, covering an area of 10 m² parallel to the coast; the sampling unit was 1 m². All individuals within the sampling unit (1 m²) were collected. An exhaustive search for bivalves was carried out in soft sediments, among algae, under rocks, inside crevices and porous rocks, in coral remains, and inside other organisms. After the first 1 m² collection was completed, the frame that delimited the sampling unit was moved perpendicular to the coastline and placed again on the rocks. The distance between the sampling units was 2 m². This procedure was repeated until ten sampling units were completed. The collected specimens were preserved in 96% alcohol, then identified and quantified.

Laboratory work

Species identification was carried out using the references in Coan & Valentich-Scott (2012). The update of the nomenclature was consulted in the database of the MolluscaBase website (MolluscaBase, 2023). The species have been classified into functional groups according to their life forms and were catalogued with the criteria of Esqueda-González et al. (2014), namely endolithic bivalves (found inhabiting stones or other hard substrates), epifaunal bivalves (found attached to a hard substrate), and semi-infaunal bivalves (found partially buried in the sediment but protruding above the sediment).

Data analysis

Species richness (S) was measured based on the number of bivalve species found in the samples, and expected richness was calculated through sample-based rarefactions using the non-parametric estimators Chao1, Chao2, Jackknife1, Jackknife2, and bootstrap (Moreno, 2001). Observed and expected species accumulation curves were constructed with 10 000 randomisations without replacement based on the number of samples taken during the entire study, using the software PRIMER 6 (Clarke & Gorley, 2006).

The structure of the bivalve community was analysed by ecoregion (central-south zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion) and sites (Priority Marine Regions). Abundance (N) was estimated by the number of individuals found for each species. Singleton species were those represented by one individual, and doubletons were those represented by two individuals (Magurran, 2005). Density (De) was calculated as the mean of the number of individuals divided by the to-

tal sample units. The percentage of species was evaluated according to their life forms at each sampled site.

The Olmstead-Tukey correlation method determined the degree of occurrence of the species (hierarchical location) within the community (Sokal & Rohlf, 1969). This method is based on the calculation of two estimators, the relative abundance and the frequency of occurrence (average in percentage of the number of samples, in which all species are present) of the species. The dominant species (D) were those, which relative abundance and frequency of occurrence values exceeded the arithmetic mean of both estimates. The constant species (C) were those, which abundance value did not exceed the average value of the total abundance but exceeded the average estimate for the frequency of occurrence. The species' numerous little frequent (NLF) were those, which abundance value was higher than the estimated average value for abundance, and the value of frequency of occurrence did not exceed the estimated average value for this variable. Finally, the occasional species (O) were those, which abundance value and frequency of appearance did not exceed the estimated arithmetic mean for the frequency of appearance and abundance (Flores-Garza et al., 2012; Galeana-Rebolledo et al., 2012).

Diversity was generally measured for the south-central zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion and each of the Priority Marine Regions. The Shannon-Wiener index (H') with base 2 logarithm was applied, and equity was evaluated using Pielou's evenness or equity index (J'). Similarity analysis of bivalve communities was carried out with non-parametric multivariate techniques using PRIMER 6 (Clarke & Warwick, 1999). Similarity matrices were constructed using the Bray-Curtis index after transformation of the data by Log(x + 1) of the species abundance to homogenise the order of magnitude between values. The SIMPROF test was used as a criterion to identify statistically different groupings in the dendrogram (Clarke et al., 2008). Subsequently, the SIMPER test was performed to characterise the composition of each group to identify the species with the highest contribution to the formation of each biological association (Clarke & Gorley, 2006).

Results

A total of 4119 bivalve specimens were analysed for the south-central zone of the Mexican

Transitional Pacific ecoregion, distributed in 18 families, 33 genera, 53 species, and two specimens that were only identified to genus (Electronic Supplement). The species richness calculated, using non-parametric estimators, had a minimum of 63 species and a maximum of 77 species. These values had a representation of 72% and 87%, respectively, and the species accumulation curves showed an asymptotic trend (Fig. 2). The Copala-Punta Maldonado region had the highest richness with 33 species, followed by the Piedra de Tlacoynque region with 26 species, both located areas in the state of Guerrero. The lowest richness, with 13 species, was found in the Colola-Maruaata region in Michoacán (Electronic Supplement).

It was estimated that 13 species exceeded 1% of the relative abundance and together contributed 91.11% of the total abundance found. The species with the highest abundance were *Chama coralloides* (Olsson, 1971), *Brachidontes adamsianus* (Dunker, 1857), *Choromytilus palliopunctatus* (Carpenter, 1857), *Isognomon janus* (Carpenter, 1857), and *Leiosolenus aristatus* (Dillwyn, 1817). In ten species, including the two specimens identified to genus, a minimum abundance (singletons) was found. In four species, the presence of two individuals (doubletons) in the totality of samples was determined. The estimated density of bivalves for the south-central of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion was 17.2 individuals/m². The Colola-Maruaata region recorded the highest density with 30.9 individuals/m², followed by the Copala-Punta Maldonado region with 26.1 individuals/m². Finally, the Mexiquillo-Delta del Balsas region recorded the lowest density with 9.4 individuals/m² (Table 2).

Fig. 2. Observed bivalve species richness (S_{obs}) and expected species richness (rarefaction curves of Chao1, Chao2, Jackknife1, Jackknife2, and Bootstap) from the south-central zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion.

Regarding bivalve life forms, 18 species were endolithic. Of them, *Acar gradata* (Broderip & Sowerby, 1829), *A. pusilla* (Sowerby I, 1833), *A. rostrata* (Berry 1954), and *Isognomon janus*, which are normally reported as epifaunal, were found as endolithic in the Copala-Punta Maldonado, and Huatulco regions. In the Punta Maldonado-Copala region, the sampling site is composed of sedimentary sandstone-type rocks, while in the Huatulco region, these species were found in coral remains. Twenty-nine species of epifaunal bivalves and 12 semi-infaunal species were recorded (Electronic Supplement). The highest richness of epifaunal species was found in the Coyuca-Tres Palos region. The highest richness of endolithic species was recorded in the Copala-Punta Maldonado region, and the highest richness of semi-infaunal species was observed in the Piedra de Tlacoynque region (Table 2).

Table 2. Ecological attributes of bivalves from the Priority Marine Regions and the centre-south zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion

Priority Marine Regions	S	N	De	H'	J'	Life forms (%)			Degree of occurrence (%)			
						En	Ep	Se	D	C	NLF	O
36. Huatulco	19	457	15.23	2.73	0.64	31.58	57.95	10.57	68.53	10.49	10.49	10.49
35. Puerto Ángel-Mazunte	18	561	18.72	2.56	0.61	5.56	77.74	16.67	83.32	5.58	0.00	11.13
34. Chacahua-Escobilla	13	400	13.33	2.36	0.62	7.69	92.8	0.00	85.71	7.10	7.10	0.00
33. Copala-Punta Maldonado	33	783	26.14	3.75	0.74	51.52	39.34	9.16	45.45	6.06	9.09	39.40
32. Coyuca-Tres Palos	25	370	12.33	2.94	0.63	4.00	16.00	80.00	68.00	0.00	0.00	32.00
31. Piedra Tlacoynque	26	339	11.32	3.14	0.67	3.86	69.00	26.95	61.54	7.69	3.85	26.90
30. Mexiquillo-Delta del Balsas	16	282	9.43	2.71	0.68	6.25	87.50	6.25	81.25	6.25	0.00	12.50
29. Colola-Maruaata	13	927	30.91	2.06	0.56	7.70	84.60	7.70	100.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion	55	4119	17.22	3.63	0.64	25.00	53.60	21.41	35.71	5.35	8.92	50.00

Note: S – species richness, N – abundance, De – density, H' – diversity, J' – equity, E – epifaunal, En – endolithic, S – semi-infaunal, D – dominant, C – constant, NLF – numerous little frequent, O – occasional.

It was estimated that, in the south-central zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion, occasional species obtained the highest percentage (50%), followed by dominant (35.71%), NLF (8.92%), and constant species (5.35%) (Table 2). The Colola-Maruata and Chacahua-Escobilla regions registered the highest (100.00%, and 85.71%, respectively) percentage of dominant species. Species classified as constant and NLF were most present in the Huatulco region, with 10.50%. The highest percentage of occasional species was found in the Copala-Punta Maldonado and Coyuca-Tres Palos regions, with 39.4% and 32.0%, respectively (Table 2).

The values of the diversity and equity indices, estimated for the bivalves in the central-southern zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion, were $H' = 3.63$ bits/individual and $J' = 0.64$. In the Copala-Punta Maldonado region, the highest value of diversity and equity indices ($H' = 3.75$ bits/individual, and $J' = 0.74$) was registered, followed by the Piedra de Tlacoyunque region ($H' = 3.14$ bits/individual, and $J' = 0.67$). The lowest values of the diversity and equity index were recorded in the Colola-Maruata region ($H' = 2.05$ bits/individual, and $J' = 0.55$) (Table 2).

The SIMPROF analysis identified bivalve communities in two statistically distinct groupings. Group B was made up only of the community of the Copala-Punta Maldonado region (Fig. 3). Group A was made up of the rest of the communities; within this group the species *Chama coraloides*, *C. echinata* (Broderip, 1835), *Isognomon janus*, *Plicatula penicillata* (Carpenter, 1857), *Brachidontes adamsianus*, *Plicatulostrea anomioides* (Keen, 1958), *Acar gradata*, *Lamarcka mutabilis* (Sowerby I, 1833), *Saccostrea palmula* (Carpenter, 1857), *Choromytilus palliopunctatus*, *Limaria pacifica* (de' Orbigny, 1846), and *Striostrea prismatica* (Gray, 1824), classified as dominants, contributed 92.9%.

Fig. 3. Grouping dendrogramme, based on the Bray Curtis index, for the Priority Marine Regions in the central-south zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion.

In group A, the communities from the Colola-Maruata and Chacahua-Escobilla regions presented the highest percentage of similarity. Both sites showed affinity in the physical characteristics of the habitat, such as an increased exposure to waves and intrusive igneous rock massif substrates, which provide high stability. Among the ecological aspects of these sites, the following stand out: similarity in the values of species richness and diversity index (the lowest estimated in the analysed sites), clear dominance of epifaunal species, the highest number of species ranked as dominants, and the absence of occasional species (Table 2).

Subsequently, the bivalve communities of the Mexiquillo-Delta del Balsas and Puerto Angel-Mazunte regions had 70% similarity (Fig. 3). These sites are similar in terms of wave exposure (middle), substrate heterogeneity (middle), and rocky substrate that can be found as massifs, slabs, and some boulders, which provide mean stability. In the ecological characteristics of both communities, low species richness and diversity index (not as low as in the previously described sites) were registered. On both sites, epifaunal species had a clear dominance, with a high number of semi-infaunal species. In the hierarchy of species, the dominant ones are in the majority, but occasional species are also present (Table 2).

In the Piedra de Tlacoyunque and Coyuca-Tres Palos regions, the communities showed a 63.40% similarity (Fig. 3). In both sites, similarities were observed in the physical characteristics of the habitat, such as mean exposure to waves, high heterogeneity of the substrate, and the type of rocky substrate between slabs, some boulders, and gravel. In the ecological characteristics, the two communities presented high species richness and diversity values, an increased number of semi-infaunal and endolithic species, and a higher percentage of occasional species than on the sites with 70% similarity (Table 2).

Discussion

The number of bivalve species found in this study represents 8% of the total species reported by Castillo-Rodríguez (2014) for the Mexican Pacific, as well as 15% of the 265 species reported by Barrientos-Luján et al. (2022) in the Mexican Tropical Pacific. In this study, fewer bivalve species are reported compared to those published in the states of Jalisco, Colima, and Michoacán (Holguín-Quiñones & González-Pedraza, 1994;

Ríos-Jara et al., 2008). The difference in the species number represented from those published in Jalisco, Colima and Michoacán is attributed to the extension of the study areas that leads to the spatial variability of the different habitats, since it has been reported in studies conducted vertically to the coast, that the distribution of bivalves is wide, and the turnover of species is remarkable (Esqueda-González et al., 2018). However, our species list is similar to that published in the states of Guerrero and Oaxaca by Holguín-Quiñones & González-Pedraza (1989), Flores-Garza et al. (2014), and Flores-Rodríguez et al. (2014).

Non-parametric estimators of species richness have been used in several studies. The importance of considering them to obtain more complete inventories and their quality has been pointed out (Bouchet et al., 2002). It has also been observed that their bias and precision vary depending on the taxon examined. However, they are still a good indicator to evaluate the sampling effort and completeness of the inventory (Escalante, 2003; López-Gómez & Williams-Linera, 2006; González-Oreja et al., 2010; Bautista-Hernández et al., 2013). In this study, we used five non-parametric estimators to evaluate the inventory and the sampling effort, and according to the results, 70% of the estimated species for the community were exceeded.

The highest number of species was recorded in the Copala-Punta Maldonado and Piedra de Tlalcoyunque regions, both located in the state of Guerrero, which present medium wave stability with substrate variability (slabs and boulders), and medium to low stability. These characteristics of the area are conducive to the high bivalve species diversity (Galeana-Rebolledo et al., 2012; Flores-Garza et al., 2014; López-Rojas et al., 2017, 2020). The singleton and doubleton species had a percentage of 28% of the total species recorded for the south-central region of the Mexican Transitional Pacific. This percentage is high considering that many bivalve species tend to live in agglomerated form forming dense assemblages or populations, which are often referred to as beds or, in more extreme cases, reefs (Dame & Kenneth, 2011).

The species *Chama coralloides*, *Brachidontes adamsianus*, *Isognomon janus*, *Choromytilus palliopunctatus*, and *Leiosolenus aristatus* were dominant according to the degree of occurrence, as well as the most abundant and best distributed in the rocky intertidal of the south-central re-

gion of the Mexican Transitional Pacific. Other studies have already reported this behaviour carried out in the ecoregion (Villarroel et al., 2000; Flores-Garza et al., 2014; Flores-Rodríguez et al., 2014) and can be attributed to the fact that species of the families Chamidae and Mytilidae, in addition to being eurytopic, retain abilities to withstand extreme physical factors (i.e. temperature, salinity, desiccation, and oxygen tension), allowing them to exploit hard substrates and dominate rocky habitats (Suchanek, 1986; Dame, 1996; Cardoso et al., 2016). Even species of Isognomonidae are numerous and common bivalves, found in intertidal communities worldwide (Morton & Morton, 1983).

The bivalve community, reported here, was represented mostly by epifaunal species, followed by endolithic and, to a lesser extent, semi-epifaunal species in accordance with Esqueda-González et al. (2014) in the report of the three categories in Mazatlán Bay. The highest percentage of endolithic species was recorded in the Copala-Punta Maldonado region. López-Rojas et al. (2023) mentioned that the substrate type in Punta Maldonado is conducive to the optimal development of these species. Concerning hierarchical location, the highest percentage of bivalve species was restricted to habitats with particular characteristics (occasional species). The most abundant and widely distributed species (dominant species) also represented a high percentage, and well-distributed species with low abundance (numerous infrequent species), and abundant species with low distribution (constant species), represented a lower percentage.

Due to low local abundance and restricted distribution, 27 bivalve species were considered occasional or rare. In Acapulco, Galeana-Rebolledo et al. (2012) reported a high number of rare species, including *Septifer zeteki* (Hertlein & Strong, 1946), *Barbatia lurida* (Sowerby, 1833) and *Pododesmus foliatus* (Broderip, 1834), which are also reported in our study. With this comparison, we cannot confirm that there is a loss of rare species in the area. However, we consider that the behaviour of species with restricted distribution is related to the characteristics of the habitat, since in marine ecosystems, the increase in rare species is associated with the heterogeneity of the substrate (Ellingsen et al., 2007). It has also been mentioned that many area-specific species may be rare (Thrush et al., 2006). In this study, the highest number of rare species were

endolithic, specific to habitats, where the species can drill through rocks.

The diversity of bivalves from the rocky intertidal zone of the south-central region of the Mexican Transitional Pacific is high. Previous study conducted at sites in this ecoregion agrees with data reported in our research regarding the high diversity (Zamorano et al., 2008; Flores-Garza et al., 2014; Flores-Rodríguez et al., 2014). The diversity values correspond to what is expected in this ecoregion, since it is located in tropical zone, where the waters are influenced by the California and Humboldt currents, which favour the increase of diversity indices due to the convergence of oceanic currents or upwelling systems (Cruz-Motta et al., 2020). In addition, we can assume that habitat heterogeneity in the sampled sites contributed to the high diversity since bivalves are distinguished by their dominance of rocky intertidal zones, characterised by vertical gradients of dominant factors such as exposure to air, light, temperature, and wave action (Dame, 1996).

In the rocky intertidal habitats, it is expected that the similarity between bivalve communities may be influenced by the physical characteristics of the habitat, such as wave exposure, stability, and substrate type, since the interaction between them may infer their existence (Dame, 1996). It has even been reported that wave exposure can determine the distribution of bivalves inhabiting the intertidal zone (Esqueda-González et al., 2022). In this study, it was observed that the percentage of similarity decreased as the wave intensity decreased and the heterogeneity of the substrate type increased. Thus, the communities with the highest similarity percentage were those found in sites exposed to waves. In contrast, the communities with the lowest percentage were found in sites with high substrate heterogeneity.

The bivalve community of the Copala-Punta Maldonado region was statistically different from the others. We attribute this difference to the high number of endolithic species and the type of rock at the sampling site. This has already been reported in other bivalve studies, that the type of rock (sedimentary sandstone type) generates a habitat conducive to the development of endolithic bivalves (Owada, 2006).

Our results provide evidence that the increase in diversity is related to the complexity of the substrate and the variety of microhabitats, in which the availability of habitats with appropri-

ate conditions for bivalves increases. This observation agrees with Cruz-Motta et al. (2020), who reported that small-scale, site-specific ecological processes on rocky shores determine locally the diversity of rocky shore assemblages. Some other reports also state that the high species richness is related to the coastal geomorphology and heterogeneity of the sites sampled (Flores-Garza et al., 2011; Ríos-Jara et al., 2020).

Conservation planners are currently seeking effective strategies to protect species, dynamic ecosystem hotspots, and loss of diversity at the gene, species, and ecosystem scales (Harvey et al., 2021). These conservation strategies should consider community-level assessments, including species richness, habitat specificity, reproductive strategy, and endemism (Ríos-Jara et al., 2020). This study directly addresses the provision of information for ecosystem management and protection, as it is expected that marine communities with higher species richness may have greater resilience to the environmental stress (Selig et al., 2014).

In addition, this study was carried out on rocky intertidal coasts, for which it is known that, due to their ecological characteristics and accessibility, conjoint studies of these as a whole are appropriate to understand the changes caused by anthropogenic impacts and the effects of climate change (Cruz-Motta et al., 2010). The information provided here is important for future research planning, management decisions, and initiatives intended to help co-ordinating management practices through outreach efforts for the conservation and sustainable use of marine resources.

Conclusions

The richness of species and diversity of bivalves, reported by this study for the central-southern region of the Mexican Transitional Pacific, corresponds to data expected in a tropical zone. Furthermore, compared to the total number of species reported in the Mexican Pacific, it is high, considering that only specimens associated with the rocky intertidal zone of the Priority Marine Regions of Oaxaca, Guerrero, and Michoacán were included. Finally, the species richness estimators used to assess the inventory quality indicated that the sampling effort were appropriate to achieve a sufficient list of species.

The species *Chama coralloides*, *Brachidontes adamsianus*, *Isognomon janus*, *Choromytilus palliopunctatus*, and *Leiosolenus aristatus*, due

to their dominance and distribution, are considered representative bivalve species associated with the rocky intertidal zone, of the priority marine regions, from the central-southern region in the Mexican Transitional Pacific.

The most diverse priority marine regions were those with high substrate heterogeneity and mean wave intensity. Epifaunal bivalves were the most frequently found in the rocky intertidal zone, and the best represented according to their hierarchical location were the occasional and dominant bivalves. The bivalve communities with the highest similarity percentage were found in habitats with little substrate heterogeneity and high waves. The species, mostly contributed to the differences between the bivalve communities, were those which way of life was classified as endolithic.

This research reports on the bivalve community associated with the rocky intertidal zone in eight Priority Marine Regions for conserving biodiversity in Mexico. This information on species richness, diversity, and habitat specificity is important for planning further research, management decision-making, and insights helping to co-ordinate conservation practices and sustainable resource use.

Acknowledgements

The main author thanks CONAHCYT for the support of scholarships to carry out postgraduate studies and Padilla-Serrato thanks the «Investigadoras e Investigadores por México-CONAHCYT» programme.

Supporting Information

The data on the species list of bivalves and their characteristics (Electronic Supplement. Family/species, abundance, life forms, and frequency of the occurrence of bivalves (Mollusca) from the central-south zone of the Mexican Transitional Pacific ecoregion and Priority Marine Regions) may be found in the [Supporting Information](#).

References

Abell R., Thieme M.L., Revenga C., Bryer M., Kottelat M., Bogutskaya N., Coad B., Mandrak N., Balderas S.C., Bussing W., Stiassny M.L.J., Skelton P., Allen G.R., Unmack P., Naseka A., Ng R., Sindorf N., Robertson J., Armijo E., Higgins J.V., Heibel T.J., Wikramanayake E., Olson D., López H.L., Reis R.E., Lundberg J.G., Sabaj Pérez M.H., Petry P. 2008. Freshwater ecoregions of the world: a new map of biogeographic units for freshwater biodiversity conservation. *BioScience* 58(5): 403–414. DOI: 10.1641/B580507

Albert D.D.A., Bujeng V., Chia S. 2022. Identification of Mollusc Remains (Bivalve and Gastropod) from Archaeological Sites in Semporna, Sabah. *Tropical Life Sciences Research* 33(2): 197–237. DOI: 10.21315/tlsr2022.33.2.10

Arriaga-Cabrera L., Aguilar V., Espinoza J.M., Galindo C., Herrmann H., Santana E., Rosenzweig L. 2009. Regiones prioritarias y planeación para la conservación de la biodiversidad. *Capital Natural de México* 2: 433–457.

Baqueiro-Cárdenas E., Borabe L., Goldaracena-Islas C.G., Rodríguez-Navarro J. 2007. Los moluscos y la contaminación. Una revisión. *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad* 78: 1S–7S. DOI: 10.22201/ib.20078706e.2007.002.293

Barrientos-Luján N.A., Ríos-Jara E., Esqueda-González M.C. 2022. Moluscos (Mollusca). In: J.R. Bastida-Zavala, M.S. García-Madrigal (Eds.): *Invertebrados marinos y costeros del Pacífico sur de México*. Puerto Ángel: Universidad del Mar. P. 129–190.

Bautista-Hernández C.E., Monks S., Pulido-Flores G. 2013. Los parásitos y el estudio de su biodiversidad: un enfoque sobre los estimadores de la riqueza de especies. In: *Estudios científicos en el estado de Hidalgo y zonas aledañas*. Vol. 2. P. 13–17.

Bouchet P., Lozouet P., Maestrati P., Heros V. 2002. Assessing the magnitude of species richness in tropical marine environments: exceptionally high numbers of molluscs at a New Caledonia site. *Biological Journal of the Linnean Society* 75(4): 421–436. DOI: 10.1046/j.1095-8312.2002.00052.x

Cardoso F., Paredes C., Mogollón V., Palacios E. 2016. La familia Chamidae (Bivalvia: Venerida) en Perú, con la adición de cinco nuevos registros. *Revista Peruana de Biología* 23(1): 13–26. DOI: 10.15381/rpb.v23i1.11829

Carrascal L.M., Palomino D. 2006. Rareza, estatus de conservación y sus determinantes ecológicos. Revisión de su aplicación a escala regional. *Graellsia* 62: 523–538. DOI: 10.3989/graellsia.2006.v62.iExtra.131

Castillo-Rodríguez Z.G. 2014. Biodiversidad de moluscos marinos en México. *Revista Mexicana de Biodiversidad* 85: 419–430. DOI: 10.7550/rmb.33003

Chattopadhyay D., Sarkar D., Bhattacharjee M. 2021. The Distribution Pattern of Marine Bivalve Death Assemblage From the Western Margin of Bay of Bengal and Its Oceanographic Determinants. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8: 675344. DOI: 10.3389/fmars.2021.675344

Clarke K.R., Gorley R.N. 2006. *PRIMER v6: User Manual/Tutorial*. Plymouth: PRIMER-E. 192 p.

Clarke K.R., Warwick R.M. 1999. The taxonomic distinctness measure of biodiversity: weighting of step lengths between hierarchical level. *Marine Ecology Progress Series* 184: 21–29. DOI: 10.3354/meps184021

Clarke K.R., Somerfield P.J., Gorley R.N. 2008. Testing of null hypotheses in exploratory community analyses: similarity profiles and biota-environment linkage. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 366(1–2): 56–69. DOI: 10.1016/j.jembe.2008.07.009

- Coan E.V., Valentich-Scott P. 2012. *Bivalve seashells of tropical west America. Marine Bivalve mollusks from Baja California to Peru*. Santa Bárbara, California: Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History Monographs. 258 p.
- CONABIO. 2023. *Sitios Prioritarios para la Conservación de los Ambientes Costeros y Oceánicos de México*. Comisión Nacional para el Conocimiento y Uso de la Biodiversidad. Available from <https://bioteca.biodiversidad.gob.mx/janium-bin/sumario.pl?Id=20230802133559>
- CONANP. 2023. *Comisión Nacional de Áreas Naturales Protegidas, México*. Available from https://simec.conanp.gob.mx/consulta_fichas.php
- Cruz-Motta J.J., Miloslavich P., Palomo G., Iken K., Konar B., Pohle G., Trott T., Benedetti-Cecchi L., Herrera C., Hernández A., Sardi A., Bueno A., Castillo J., Klein E., Guerra-Castro E., Gobin J., Gómez D.I., Riosmena-Rodríguez R., Mead A., Bigatti G., Knowlton A., Shirayama Y. 2010. Patterns of spatial variation of assemblages associated with intertidal rocky shores: a global perspective. *PLoS ONE* 5(12): e14354. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0014354
- Cruz-Motta J.J., Miloslavich P., Guerra-Castro E., Hernández-Agreda A., Herrera C., Barros F., Navarrete S.A., Sepúlveda R.D., Glasby T.M., Bigatti G., Cardenas-Calle M., Carneiro P.B.M., Carranza A., Flores A.A.V., Gil-Kodaka P., Gobin J., Gutiérrez J.L., Klein E., Krull M., Lazarus J.F., Londoño-Cruz E., Lotufo T., Macaya E.C., Mora C., Mora E., Palomo G., Parraqué M., Pellizzari F., Retamales R., Rocha R.M., Romero L. 2020. Latitudinal patterns of species diversity on South American rocky shores: local processes lead to contrasting trends in regional and local species diversity. *Journal of Biogeography* 47(9): 1966–1979. DOI: 10.1111/jbi.13869
- Dame R.F. 1996. *Ecology of Marine Bivalves: An Ecosystem Approach*. Boca Raton: CRC Press. 272 p.
- Dame R.F., Kenneth M.J. 2011. *Ecology of marine bivalves: an ecosystem approach*. Taylor & Francis. 284 p.
- Ellingsen K.E., Hewitt J.E., Thrush S.F. 2007. Rare species, habitat diversity and functional redundancy in marine benthos. *Journal of Sea Research* 58(4): 291–301. DOI: 10.1016/j.seares.2007.10.001
- Escalante E.T. 2003. ¿Cuántas especies hay? Los estimadores no paramétricos de Chao. *Elementos* 52: 53–56.
- Esqueda-González M.C., Ríos-Jara E., Galván-Villa C., Rodríguez-Zaragoza F. 2014. Species composition, richness, and distribution of marine bivalve molluscs in Bahía de Mazatlán, México. *ZooKeys* 399: 43–69. DOI: 10.3897/zookeys.399.6256
- Esqueda-González M.C., Ríos-Jara E., Galván-Villa C.M., Rodríguez-Zaragoza F.A. 2018. Spatial analysis of bivalve mollusks diversity in Mazatlan Bay, Mexico. *Marine Biodiversity* 48(6): 1943–1959. DOI: 10.1007/s12526-017-0703-6
- Esqueda-González M.C., Ríos-Jara E., Galván-Villa C.M., Rodríguez-Zaragoza F.A. 2022. Structure of the bivalve (Mollusca) assemblage of Mazatlan bay, Mexico, and its relationship to environmental variables. *Community Ecology* 23(3): 349–364. DOI: 10.1007/s42974-022-00112-8
- Flores-Garza R., Torreblanca-Ramírez C., Flores-Rodríguez P., García-Ibáñez S., Galeana-Rebolledo L., Valdés-González A., Rojas-Herrera A.A. 2011. Mollusc community from a rocky intertidal zone in Acapulco, México. *Biodiversity* 12(3): 144–153. DOI: 10.1080/14888386.2011.625520
- Flores-Garza R., Galeana-Rebolledo L., García-Ibáñez S., Torreblanca-Ramírez C. 2012. Polyplacophora species richness, composition and distribution of its community associated with the intertidal rocky substrate in the marine priority region No. 32 in Guerrero, Mexico. *Open Journal of Ecology* 2(4): 192–201. DOI: 10.4236/oje.2012.24023
- Flores-Garza R., López-Rojas V., Flores-Rodríguez P., Torreblanca-Ramírez C. 2014. Diversity, Distribution and Composition of the Bivalvia Class on the Rocky Intertidal Zone of Marine Priority Region 32, Mexico. *Open Journal of Ecology* 4(15): 961–973. DOI: 10.4236/oje.2014.415080
- Flores-Rodríguez P., Flores-Garza R., García-Ibáñez S., Torreblanca-Ramírez C., Galeana-Rebolledo L., Santiago-Cortés E. 2014. Mollusks of the Rocky Intertidal Zone at Three Sites in Oaxaca, Mexico. *Open Journal of Ecology* 4(4): 326–337. DOI: 10.4236/ojms.2014.44029
- Galeana-Rebolledo L., Flores-Garza R., Torreblanca-Ramírez C., García-Ibáñez S., Flores-Rodríguez P., López-Rojas V.I. 2012. Biocenosis de Bivalvia y Polyplacophora del intermareal rocoso en playa Tlacopanocha, Acapulco, Guerrero, México. *Latin American Journal of Aquatic Research* 40(4): 943–954. DOI: 10.3856/vol40-issue4-fulltext-11
- González-Oreja J.A., de la Fuente-Díaz-Ordaz A.A., Hernández-Santín L., Buzo-Franco D., Bonache-Regidor C. 2010. Evaluación de estimadores no paramétricos de la riqueza de especies. Un ejemplo con aves en áreas verdes de la ciudad de Puebla, México. *Animal Biodiversity and Conservation* 33(1): 31–45. DOI: 10.32800/abc.2010.33.0031
- Harvey M.S., Ralph G.M., Polidoro B.A., Maxwell S.M., Carpenter K.E. 2021. Identifying key biodiversity areas as marine conservation priorities in the greater Caribbean. *Biodiversity and Conservation* 30(13): 4039–4059. DOI: 10.1007/s10531-021-02291-8
- Hendrickx M.E., Brusca R.C., Cordero M., Ramírez G.R. 2007. Marine and brackish-water molluscan biodiversity in the Gulf of California, Mexico. *Scientia Marina* 71(4): 637–647. DOI: 10.3989/scimar.2007.71n4637
- Holguín-Quiñones O.E., González-Pedraza A.C. 1989. *Moluscos de la franja costera del Estado de Oaxaca*,

- México. México: Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Dirección de Bibliotecas y Publicaciones. 221 p.
- Holguín-Quiñones O.E., González-Pedraza A.C. 1994. *Moluscos de la franja costera de Michoacán, Colima y Jalisco, México*. México: Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Dirección de Bibliotecas y Publicaciones. 133 p.
- INEGI. 2021. *Instituto Nacional de Geografía, Estadística e Informática*. Available from <https://www.inegi.org.mx/app/mapas/>
- Jablonski D., Huang S., Roy K., Valentine J.W. 2017. Shaping the latitudinal diversity gradient: new perspectives from a synthesis of paleobiology and biogeography. *American Naturalist* 189(1): 1–12. DOI: 10.1086/689739
- Krug A.Z., Jablonski D., Valentine J.W. 2007. Contrarian clade confirms the ubiquity of spatial origination patterns in the production of latitudinal diversity gradients. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 104(46): 18129–18134. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.0709202104
- Landa-Jaime V., Arciniega-Flores J. 1998. Macromoluscos bentónicos de fondos blandos de la plataforma continental de Jalisco y Colima, México. *Ciencias Marinas* 24(2): 155–167.
- López-Gómez A.M., Williams-Linera G. 2006. Evaluación de métodos no-paramétricos para la estimación de riqueza de especies de plantas leñosas en cafetales. *Boletín de la Sociedad Botánica de México* 78: 7–15. DOI: 10.17129/botsoci.1717
- López-Pérez R.A., López-García A. 2008. Identificación de sitios prioritarios para la conservación de corales formadores de arrecife en el estado de Oaxaca, México. *Hidrobiológica* 18(3): 239–250.
- López-Rojas V.I., Flores-Garza R., Flores-Rodríguez P., Torreblanca-Ramírez C., García-Ibáñez S. 2017. La clase Bivalvia en sitios rocosos de las Regiones Marinas Prioritarias en Guerrero, México: riqueza de especies, abundancia y distribución. *Hidrobiológica* 27(1): 69–86. DOI: 10.24275/uam/izt/dcbshidro/2017v27n1/Flores
- López-Rojas V.I., Flores-Garza R., García-Ibáñez S., Ruiz-Campos G., Flores-Rodríguez P., Violante-González J., Torreblanca-Ramírez C. 2020. New records of bivalves in the Mexican Pacific Transitional Zone. *Biodiversity* 21(3): 150–164. DOI: 10.1080/14888386.2020.1847192
- López-Rojas V.I., Flores-Garza R., Ruiz-Campos G., Torreblanca-Ramírez C., García-Ibáñez S., Flores-Rodríguez P., Violante-González J. 2023. Bivalvos endolíticos de Punta Maldonado, Guerrero, México (Océano Pacífico Oriental). *Caldasia* 45(1): 83–97. DOI: 10.15446/caldasia.v45n1.95071
- Magurran A.E. 2005. Species abundance distributions: pattern or process?. *Functional Ecology* 19(1): 177–181.
- MolluscaBase. 2023. *Molluscabase*. Available from <https://www.molluscabase.org/>
- Moreno C.E. 2001. *Métodos para medir la biodiversidad*. Vol. 1. España: M&T-Manuales y Tesis SEA. 83 p.
- Morton B., Morton J. 1983. *The sea shore ecology of Hong Kong*. Vol. 1. Hong Kong. University Press. 366 p.
- Owada M. 2006. Functional morphology and phylogeny of the rock-boring bivalves *Leiosolenus* and *Lithophaga* (Bivalvia: Mytilidae): a third functional clade. *Marine Biology* 150(5): 853–860. DOI: 10.1007/s00227-006-0409-y
- Pérez-Estrada C.J., Rodríguez-Estrella R., Brun-Murillo F.G., Gurgo-Salice P., Valles-Jiménez R., Morales-Bojórquez E., Medina-López, M.A. 2023. Diversity and seasonal variation of the molluscan community associated with the seagrass *Halodule wrightii* in a marine protected area in the southern Gulf of California. *Aquatic Ecology* 57(2): 299–319. DOI: 10.1007/s10452-023-10011-3
- RAMSAR. 2023. *Servicio de Información sobre Sitios Ramsar*. Available from <https://rsis.ramsar.org/>
- Ríos-Jara E. 2015. Diversidad de moluscos marinos en el Pacífico mexicano. *Biodiversitas* 118: 12–16.
- Ríos-Jara E., López-Uriarte E., Galván-Villa C.M. 2008. Bivalve molluscs from the continental shelf of Jalisco and Colima, Mexican Central Pacific. *American Malacological Bulletin* 26(1/2): 119–131. DOI: 10.4003/006.026.0212
- Ríos-Jara E., Galván-Villa C.M., Esqueda-González M.C., Ayón-Parente M., Zaragoza F.A.R., Bastida-Izaguirre D., Reyes-Gómez A. 2020. Species richness and biogeographical affinities of the marine molluscs from Bahía de Chamela, Mexico. *Biodiversity Data Journal* 8: e59191. DOI: 10.3897/BDJ.8.e59191
- Roy K., Jablonski D., Valentine J.W. 2000. Dissecting latitudinal diversity gradients: functional groups and clades of marine bivalves. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 267(1440): 293–299. DOI: 10.1098/rspb.2000.0999
- Selig E.R., Turner W.R., Troëng S., Wallace B.P., Halpern B.S., Kaschner K., Lascelles B.G., Carpenter K.E., Mittermeier R.A. 2014. Global priorities for marine biodiversity conservation. *PloS ONE* 9(1): e82898. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0082898
- Sokal R.R., Rohlf F.J. 1969. *Biometry. The principles and practices of statistics in biological research*. San Francisco: W.H. Freeman. 776 p.
- Spalding M.D., Fox H.E., Allen G.R., Davidson N., Ferdaña Z.A., Finlayson M., Halpern B.S., Jorge M.A., Lombana A., Lourie S.A., Martin K.D., McManus E., Molnar J., Recchia C.A., Robertson J. 2007. Marine ecoregions of the world: a bioregionalization of coastal and shelf areas. *BioScience* 57(7): 573–583. DOI: 10.1641/B570707
- Suchanek T.H. 1986. Mussels and their role in structuring rocky shore communities. In: G. Moore, R. Seed (Eds.): *The Ecology of Rocky Coasts*. Sevenoaks (UK): Hodder and Stoughton. P. 70–96.
- Thrush S.F., Gray J.S., Hewitt J.E., Ugland K.I. 2006. Predicting the effects of habitat homogenization on marine biodiversity. *Ecological Applications* 16(5): 1636–1642. DOI: 10.1890/1051-0761(2006)016[1636:pteohh]2.0.co;2

- UNESCO. 2023. *The United Nations Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization*. Available from <https://en.unesco.org/biosphere/lac/huatulco>
- Vahidi F., Fatemi S.M.R., Danehkar A., Mashinchian Moradi A., Musavi Nadushan R. 2021. Patterns of mollusks (Bivalvia and Gastropoda) distribution in three different zones of Harra Biosphere Reserve, the Persian Gulf, Iran. *Iranian Journal of Fisheries Sciences* 20(5): 1336–1353.
- Villarroel M.M., Magaña M.A., Gómez C.B., Del Río Z.O., Lucio P.J., Sánchez S.J. 2000. Diversidad de moluscos en el litoral rocoso de Michoacán, México. *Mexicoa* 2(1): 54–63.
- Wilkinson T., Wiken E., Bezaury-Creel J., Hourigan T., Agardy T., Herrmann H., Janishevski L., Madden C., Morgan L., Padilla M. 2009. *Ecorregiones marinas de América del Norte*. Montreal. Montreal, Canadá: Comisión para la Cooperación Ambiental. 200 p.
- Zamorano P., Hendrickx M.E. 2011. State of knowledge about the community of mollusks on both sides of the Baja California peninsula, Mexico: A comparative analysis. *Cahiers de Biologie Marine* 52: 13–22.
- Zamorano P., Barrientos-Luján N.A., Ramírez-Luna S. 2008. Malacofauna del infralitoral rocoso de Agua Blanca, Santa Elena Cozacoatlán, Oaxaca. *Ciencia y Mar* 12(36): 19–33.

ДВУСТВОРЧАТЫЕ МОЛЛЮСКИ (MOLLUSCA) КАМЕНИСТОЙ ПРИЛИВНОЙ ЗОНЫ В ПРИОРИТЕТНЫХ МОРСКИХ РЕГИОНАХ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ ЧАСТИ ЮГА МЕКСИКАНСКОГО ПЕРЕХОДНОГО ТИХООКЕАНСКОГО РЕГИОНА

В. И. Лопес-Роха¹ ,
П. Флорес-Родригес¹

¹Автономный Университет Герреро, Мексика

*e-mail: rfloresgarza@yahoo.com

²Программа для исследователей Мексики-НСГНТ, Мексика

В Мексике из-за ее высокого биоразнообразия, использования ее ресурсов и отсутствия знаний о биоразнообразии были определены приоритетные морские регионы. Классификация этих регионов послужила инструментом крупномасштабной охраны, поскольку видовой состав в этих регионах относительно однороден. В этом исследовании сообщается о некоторых экологических характеристиках двустворчатых моллюсков из приоритетных морских регионов, расположенных в мексиканском переходном тихоокеанском экорегионе. В 2016–2018 гг. на каменистой литорали было проведено три отбора проб. В каждой пробе с участка была охвачена площадь 10 м², а единица выборки составляла 1 м². Всего было зарегистрировано 4119 экземпляров, выявлено 53 вида (35 родов, 18 семейств и 2 экземпляра, идентифицированных до рода). Ожидаемое видовое богатство было рассчитано с использованием непараметрических оценок, демонстрирующих приемлемую полноту инвентаризации. Наибольшее видовое богатство и разнообразие отмечены в регионе Копала-Пунта Мальдонадо (33 вида), тогда как наибольшая численность и плотность отмечены в регионе Колола-Маруата (30.9 особей/м²). Наибольшие показатели численности и распространения характеризовались *Chama coralloides*, *Brachidontes adamsianus*, *Isognomon janus* и *Choromytilus palliopunctatus*. Относительно жизненной формы и степени распространенности наиболее представленными двустворчатыми моллюсками были группы видов, прикрепленных к твердому субстрату (эпифаунальные виды) и приуроченных к местообитаниям с определенными характеристиками (случайные виды). Представленная здесь информация представляет данные для восьми морских регионов, признанных приоритетными для охраны природы в Мексике. Это важно для планирования, принятия решений и формулирования инициатив, направленных на помощь в координации методов управления посредством информационно-просветительской деятельности по сохранению и устойчивому использованию двустворчатых моллюсков как морских ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: *Bivalvia*, биоразнообразие, Мексиканский Тихоокеанский регион, моллюски, охрана, экологические характеристики

LONG-TERM VARIATIONS IN NUTRITIONAL CONDITION OF *PANULIRUS ARGUS* (DECAPODA: PALINURIDAE) IN CUBA: ANALYTICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL APPROACHES

Alexander Lopeztegui-Castillo

Centro de Investigaciones Biológicas del Noroeste, Mexico
e-mail: alopeztegui@yahoo.com

2

Received: 04.06.2023. Revised: 28.09.2023. Accepted: 02.10.2023.

Nutritional condition indices have been frequently used as morphophysiological indicators to study variations on lobster's physiology and energy reserves. This study was aimed to determine long-term spatio-temporal variations in nutritional conditions of *Panulirus argus* (hereinafter – lobster), considering two indices, namely the analytic Blood Refractive Index (BRI) and the morphometric Kcl (total weight / carapace length relationship). Information from eleven sites in the Caibarién region, sampled in 2010–2015, and twelve sites in the Batabanó region, sampled in 2011–2017, were named as the Current Period. Morphometric data for Kcl estimation, including 1987–1988 in the Caibarién region, and 1981–1993 in the Batabanó region, were grouped as the Past Period. Temporary variations were determined comparing Past and Current periods at each region. Spatial variations were determined by comparing the data between the two regions. For analysed lobsters in the Current period, we determined BRI = 14.3, Kcl = 7.0 in the Caibarién region, and BRI = 15.2, Kcl = 7.0 in the Batabanó region. For the Past period, the Kcl value was 5.8 and 6.3 in the Caibarién and Batabanó region, respectively. Both Kcl and BRI indices were higher for male individuals. This could be associated with the reproductive process, and intrinsic morphometric differences between sexes could influence though. Morphometric parameters were higher for the Current Period. Spatial variations of morphometric parameters were significantly different for the Past Period, which were attributed to different environmental conditions in each region. The BRI index was higher in the Batabanó region, which was possibly associated with the better status of the benthic communities and the better water quality. Present results contribute to understanding lobster's nutritional condition in natural habitats, mainly in the Caibarién region, where few studies have been carried out to date.

Key words: crustaceans' energy reserves, decapods, ecophysiology, morphophysiological indices, spiny lobster

Introduction

The use of morphophysiological indices to quantify lobsters' metabolism variations has been a developed topic since the middle of the XX century. Recently, it has been resumed, within the framework of ecophysiology, for the study of several crustaceans like crabs, shrimps, and spiny lobsters, with highly commercial interest (Rainbow, 1997; Perera et al., 2007; Fitzgibbon et al., 2017a,b; Goncalves et al., 2021). Nutritional condition indices can be listed among the most used morphophysiological indicators for studying lobsters' physiology and the impact of environmental variations on metabolism and energy reserves of these crustaceans (Simon et al., 2015, 2016; Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021; Wang F., 2021; Wang S. et al., 2021). Nutritional condition in marine crustaceans has been defined as the magnitude, to which organisms have accumulated energy reserves substances that allow normal physiological function and growth (Moore et al., 2000). In addition, it has been interpreted as the consequence of the interactive biotic and abiotic factors, which determine the habitat quality (Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2012b).

The Sabana-Camaguey archipelago (SCA) is in the central-eastern region of the northern coast of Cuba. Due to the tourism development, a lot of hotels and hydrotechnical structures have been built to support touristic activities, which includes snorkeling and Self Contained Underwater Breathing Apparatus diving, hiking, sport fishing, and surfing. Consequently, people influx and anthropogenic impacts gradually increased (Alcolado et al., 1999, 2007; Betanzos-Vega et al., 2013; Martínez-Daranas et al., 2021). Additionally, geographic location of coasts, keys, and coral reef barriers in the SCA cause a naturally limited circulation of inner waters. Also, rivers damming, causeways construction and the natural narrowness of this shelf, contribute limiting waters circulation and increasing the environmental stress (Montalvo-Estévez et al., 2008, 2010; Puga et al., 2013; Cobas et al., 2015; Martínez-Daranas et al., 2021).

Due to its natural, archaeological, and scientific values, the SCA was appointed by the Ministry of Science, Technology and Environment of Cuba, as a high priority area for biodiversity con-

servation. Because of their valuable resources of biodiversity and its vulnerability to pollution from shipping activities, the SCA was declared by the International Maritime Organization as a Sensitive Marine Protected Area being the second approved region after the Great Australian Barrier Reef. The SCA is currently proposed as a Special Region of Sustainable Development, also including some defined areas, like Buena Vista Bay, designated as a Biosphere Reserve by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. Recently (2002), four RAMSAR sites (Buena Vista Biosphere Reserve, North Wetland of Ciego de Ávila, North Wetland of Camagüey, and Rio Maximo Wildlife Refuge) were designated within the SCA area (Alcolado et al., 2007).

Panulirus argus (Latreille, 1804) (hereinafter –lobster) supports commercial fisheries from Rio de Janeiro (Brazil) to North Carolina (USA). This species is the most valuable fishery resource of Cuba (Alzugaray et al., 2018; Baisre, 2018), where the Gulf of Batabanó is the most important fishery area (Cruz et al., 1990; Puga et al., 2005, 2013). Most of the studies describing nutritional condition of lobster from the Gulf of Batabanó have included the relationship between the total weight and the total length of the lobster (Ktl), as a nutritional condition indicator (Buesa, 1965; Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2012a,b; Lopeztegui-Castillo & Capetillo-Piñar, 2021). Nevertheless, several studies around the world have used the relation between total weight and carapace length (Kcl) to estimate lobster's nutritional condition (Lozano-Álvarez et al., 2017; Martínez-Calderón et al., 2018).

More than twenty nutritional condition indicators have been described for crustaceans (Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021). However, some analytical methods, like hemolymph refractive indices, and some morphometrics, like body weight/body length relationships, have been recommended to carry out field studies, basically because they are inexpensive, non-destructive, and relatively simple, fast, and feasible (Oliver & MacDiarmid, 2001; Briones-Fourzán et al., 2009; Gutzler & Butler, 2017). Nevertheless, these indices could differently reflect nutritional condition changes, based on the involved methodology and the temporary scale of the factors causing such changes (Robertson et al., 2000; Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021).

Lobster's catches in the Caibarién region, at the central sector of the SCA, constitute 85% of

the total lobster catches in this shelf. But it has decreased to 66% in respect to the highest production period (1984–1989), when an average of 1656 ton were annually captured (Morales & Puga, 2008; Morales et al., 2013). The Caibarién fishing region has been exposed to several natural and anthropogenic stressors which have significantly disturbed benthic communities, including seagrasses, lobsters, and their food items (Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2021b; Martínez-Daranas et al., 2021). This study was aimed to determine the long-term spatio-temporal variation in nutritional conditions of commercial individuals of the lobster from the Caibarién and Batabanó fishing region. To determine differences between sexes, two nutritional condition indices are considered, one analytic and one morphometric.

Material and Methods

Study area description and location of the sampling sites

In the Caibarién region, eleven sampling sites were located both near to the shelf edge and in inner waters, based on the areas previously studied (Alcolado et al., 1998, 1999, 2007) and considering the main lobster's fishing zones (Fig. 1). Considering similar criterion, twelve sampling sites were situated in the Gulf of Batabanó (Fig. 2), where previous studies reported useful baseline information (Alcolado, 1990; Capetillo-Piñar et al., 2015). Based on the information provided by the National Center for Protected Areas of Cuba, all sampled sites in the Caibarién region, and 42% of sampled sites in the Batabanó region belong to areas which have been categorised as National Parks, Ecological Reserves, Wildlife Sanctuaries, or Protected Areas with Managed Resources (Ruiz-Plasencia et al., 2019). That means that 70% of the sampled sites were located within, or extremely near to Protected Areas.

Sampling has been carried out in 2010, 2011, 2013 and 2015 in the Caibarién region, and in 2011, 2014, 2015, 2016 and 2017 in the Batabanó region. Sites 1, 3, 9 and 10 (inner sites in Caibarién region) were sampled in 2010–2015. The other sites in this region were sampled only in 2015. All information registered in the XXI century (2010–2015 in the Caibarién region and 2011–2017 in the Batabanó region) was named as the Current Period.

Nutritional condition indices

Total body weight (TW) / carapace length (CL) relationship was calculated (Kcl, $g \times mm^{-1}$)

and used as a morphometric indicator of lobster’s nutritional condition (Robertson et al., 2000; Lozano-Álvarez et al., 2017). Higher values of Kcl mean that lobsters are gaining weight faster than size, which is nutritionally desirable. Based on the proportionally direct relationship between hemolymph (blood) refractive index and hemolymph total protein concentration (Wang & McGaw, 2014), the blood refractive index (BRI, $g \times dl^{-1}$) was determined and used as an analytic indicator of lobster’s nutritional condition (Moore et al., 2000). Using sterile 3-cc syringes (one per lobster), the hemolymph was extracted from the pericardial sinus, which has a mid-dorsal position in the lobster’s cephalothorax. Immediately after extraction, the hemolymph was placed on a hand-held Fisher Brix (0–50%) refractometer.

Lobsters were sampled immediately after their capture on commercial ships. We analysed only lobsters without external signs of moulting, reproduction, or diseases, and with having all their corresponding body parts (appendices). Lobsters were sexed, measured, and weighed according to Cruz (2002). A Vernier caliper (± 0.1 mm) was used to measure the carapace length,

and the total body wet weight was determined by a technical scale (± 0.1 g).

Origin and processing data

BRI was determined only for the Current Period in both regions (Caibarién and Batabanó). Nevertheless, for the Batabanó region, several morphometric data have been recorded, which were used comparatively. For 1981, 1983, 1988 and 1993 in the Batabanó region, and for 1987 and 1988 in the Caibarién region, the total body weight and carapace length data were collected from fisheries records archived in the Fisheries Research Center. These years were named as Past Period.

The applied Shapiro-Wilks test failed exploring for data normality. Then, non-parametric tests were selected for processing data. Paired comparisons between sexes (male vs. female) and regions (Batabanó region vs. Caibarién region) were carried out by Mann-Whitney U-test. Long-term variations were two scales determined, one comparing the Past and the Current periods (temporary scale), and one comparing between periods regions (spatial scale). The data were analysed using STATISTICA 10 (StatSoft, Inc., 2011).

Fig. 1. Study area and location of the eleven sampled sites in the Caibarién fishing region, central sector of Sabana-Camaguey archipelago, Cuba. Coloured sites are located within Protected Areas.

Results

Lobster’s nutritional condition indices in the Caibarién and Batabanó regions

A total number of 10 551 individuals of the lobster were measured. That makes it possible to

certainly estimate the morphometric nutritional condition index (Kcl) in the Caibarién and Batabanó fishing regions. Based on the hemolymph, extracted from 4980 lobsters, the BRI index was consistently determined (Table 1).

Fig. 2. Study area and location of the twelve sampled sites in the Batabanó fishing region, southwestern shelf of Cuba. Coloured sites are located within or extremely near to Protected Areas.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics of variables analysed for the Current and Past periods in the Caibarién and Batabanó fishing regions

Indicators	N	Mean	Median	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Deviation
(Caibarién region, Current Period)						
CL (mm)	1380	92.8	93.2	69.0	128.5	13.4
TW (g)	1380	658.4	651.8	191.2	1041.0	187.9
BRI	1380	14.3	14.3	4.6	28.8	4.3
Kcl	1380	7.0	7.1	2.6	10.1	1.4
(Batabanó region, Current Period)						
CL (mm)	3600	92.9	93.1	69.0	130.0	12.0
TW (g)	3600	656.6	652.0	190.1	1058.0	187.2
BRI	3600	15.2	15.2	4.7	29.9	4.3
Kcl	3600	7.0	7.1	2.2	10.4	1.3
(Caibarién region, Past Period)						
CL (mm)	2448	80.4	80.0	69.0	120.0	8.7
TW (g)	2448	471.5	450.0	225.0	1260.0	145.6
Kcl	2448	5.8	5.6	3.5	10.6	1.1
(Batabanó region, Past Period)						
CL (mm)	3123	86.1	83.0	69.0	154.0	18.2
TW (g)	3123	561.8	500.0	183.3	1575.0	278.4
Kcl	3123	6.3	6.0	2.0	16.6	1.9

Note: N – total number of sampled lobsters, CL – carapace length, TW – total body weight, Kcl – morphometric nutritional condition index, BRI – blood refractive index.

Differences between regions, or periods, were numerically unremarkable. Nevertheless, statistical analysis detected significant ($p < 0.05$) cases. Long term temporary variations (between Past and Current periods) showed significant differences for all morphometric parameters measured in the Caibarién and Batabanó fishing regions. It was higher in the Current Period (Table 2).

By grouping the sites sampled inside each region, it was found that the long-term spatial variations (comparison between the Caibarién and Batabanó fishing regions) showed significant differences for all morphometric parameters measured in the Past Period. For the Current Period, non-significant differences were found (Fig. 3).

Table 2. Mann-Whitney U-test ($p < 0.05$) comparing lobster’s (*Panulirus argus*) morphometric indicators between the Past and Current periods in the Caibarién and Batabanó regions, Cuba

Indicators	Caibarién region (N = 3828)			Batabanó region (N = 6723)		
	Z	U	p	Z	U	p
TW (g)	-29.01	702 009	0.001 >	-23.69	3 741 063	0.001 >
CL (mm)	-30.07	736 805	0.001 >	-23.81	3 732 020	0.001 >
Kcl	-26.59	816 283	0.001 >	-23.57	3 750 825	0.001 >

Note: N – total number of sampled lobsters, CL – carapace length, TW – total body weight, Kcl – morphometric nutritional condition index.

Fig. 3. Morphometric indicators estimated for *Panulirus argus*, and compared between the Caibarién and Batabanó fishing regions (Cuba), in the Past (A) and Current (C) periods. Designations: CL – carapace length, TW – total body weight, Kcl – morphometric nutritional condition index.

Despite these morphometric similarities between lobsters from each region in the Current Period, the analytic BRI index showed significant differences, demonstrating a higher average value in the Batabanó region. Nevertheless, temporal inferences respecting the Past Period could not be made, since the BRI index was assessed only for the Current Period (Fig. 4).

Males and females of lobsters showed different nutritional condition in both regions. Both (Kcl

and BRI) nutritional condition indices detected significant differences between sexes. For male lobsters, higher values were found in both the Caibarién and Batabanó fishing regions (Fig. 5).

Discussion

In the Past Period, lobster’s nutritional condition, analysed by Kcl, was higher in the Batabanó region than in the Caibarién region. In the Current Period, only BRI detected nutritional conditions to be higher in the Batabanó region, suggesting that each region has had a different environmental impact through time. Additionally, this could be partially due to methodological differences between the applied methods. Kcl and BRI indices could be differently affected by environmental factors. Kcl variation requires time for the occurrence of processes affecting lobsters’ weight and size. Conversely, BRI detects rapid changes in the concentration of circulating proteins, which could be caused by the impact of factors varying in a short-term temporal scale. Consequently, both indices differently expose lobster’s nutritional condition, which results from the interaction of factors determining habitat quality (Oliver & MacDiarmid, 2001; Lopeztegui-Castillo & Capetillo-Piñar, 2021).

Fig. 4. Blood refractive index (BRI) for *Panulirus argus*, compared between the Caibarién and Batabanó fishing regions (Cuba) in the Current Period.

Fig. 5. Nutritional condition indices for males and females of *Panulirus argus* during the Current Period, in the Caibarién and Batabanó regions, Cuba. Designations: Kcl – morphometric nutritional condition index, BRI – blood refractive index.

Variations in lobster's nutritional condition have been reported as a seasonal process depending on lobster's reproduction and moult cycles (Perera et al., 2007; Rodríguez-García et al., 2015; Simon et al., 2015). In addition, food availability, diseases, and lobster's abundance could make vary lobster's energy reserves and the nutritional stage (Lozano-Alvarez & Aramoni-Serrano, 1996; Briones-Fourzán et al., 2009; Rotllant et al., 2014; Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2021a). Among other environmental factors affecting the organism's nutritional condition, the salinity, dissolved oxygen, temperature, noise, and ocean acidification processes have been studied intently (Fitzgibbon et al., 2017a,b; Harrington & Hamlin, 2019; Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021). However, any factors determining lobster's habitat quality can potentially affect the nutritional condition, if it varies in the necessary magnitude or if its influence remains for the required time. Turbidity variations, which quasi-permanent focuses at both sides of the causeways and with higher values in Buena Vista Bay (Betanzos-Vega et al., 2013), could also affect lobster's feeding and energy substances reserved. Variation in each factor will affect the nutritional condition in a typical way, which will be detected, depending on the sensitivity and characteristics of the indicators and used methods (Robertson et al., 2000; George, 2001; Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021).

Methodological differences between BRI and Kcl have been well analysed and interpreted based on the study scale (field or laboratory), temporary scale (long or short term), and other biological parameters like morphometric differences between sexes (Wang & McGaw, 2014; Gutzler & Butler, 2017; Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021). The morphometric Kcl index depends on the magnitude, in which lobster's weight and length vary. Such variation could take some days (for an individual level) or some months (for a numerous lobster group). Conversely, lobster's blood protein concentration could change in a few minutes, which could be almost immediately detected by the analytic BRI index. Changes in blood protein concentration may instantly reflect environmental conditions. That is why this methodology can be unreliable when only a few animals (< 30) are used (Oliver & MacDiarmid, 2001; Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2012b). However, when BRI average value results from measuring several lobsters, it reflects the real and generalised habitat quality (Moore et al., 2000; George, 2001; Oliver & MacDiarmid, 2001; Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2012a,b; Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021).

Lobster's abundance and distribution have been used as an efficient bioindicators of habitat conditions and can massively contribute to the ecosystem-based management approach (Valavi et al., 2009; Briones-Fourzán et al., 2019; Ghafari & Fitrianti, 2021). Based on the present results, using the lobsters' nutritional condition as an additional habitat quality indicator, could be acceptable and recommended only when analytical indices are used, like BRI, varying in a short-term scale depending on contemporary habitat resources. The lobster's metabolism and nutritional condition could be affected by the food availability (quantitative and qualitative), the presence of contaminants, like microplastic or heavy metals, stress induced by salinisation or turbidity, and many others environmental factors that determine habitat quality (Chou et al., 2003; Cau et al., 2023; Kampouris et al., 2023).

The lobster's nutritional condition was higher in males than in females. It was found in both regions and for both indices detected. These differences have been reported by almost all previous studies on lobster populations in Cuba (Buesa, 1965; Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2012a,b; Lopeztegui-Castillo & Capetillo-Piñar, 2021). Consequently, it can be assumed as a natural common phenomenon at least on the Cuban lobster population. Environmental changes should have been sufficiently remarked to affect the nutritional condition of male and female lobsters. Consequently, both nutritional condition indices changed despite distinct sensibility and methodological differences between them. No significant differences between diets of both sexes have been reported for this species in Cuba (Herrera et al., 1991; Martínez-Coello et al., 2015). Hence, nutritional condition differences must be attributed to each sex physiology and behaviour. The nutritional condition of juveniles of the lobster in a Mexican reef lagoon did not show differences between sexes (Briones-Fourzán et al., 2009). In fact, juveniles of both sexes use to co-exist in the same habitat. Nevertheless, adult lobsters could acquire habits with different seasonal variation for each sex (Cruz et al., 1990). Food availability, predator abundance, seagrass density, physical structure of the sea bottom and shelter availability could determine movements and behavioural differences between adult males and females (González-Sansón et al., 1991; Lozano-Alvarez et al., 2017; Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021). Consequently, lobster's growth, weight gains and the accumulation of the energetic reserves could be different between sexes.

The nutritional condition Kcl index was higher in the Current Period. This contradicts the deterioration observed in benthic communities and seagrasses, which constitute food for lobsters, which have significantly decreased in the Batabanó region (Arias-Schreiber et al., 2008; Cerdeira-Estrada et al., 2008; Lopeztegui-Castillo & Capetillo-Piñar, 2008; Hidalgo-Rodríguez & Areces-Mallea, 2009; Lopeztegui-Castillo & Martínez-Coello, 2020; Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2021a) and in the Caibarién region (Hidalgo et al., 2015; Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2021b; Martínez-Daranas et al., 2021). The morphometric nature of Kcl could contribute explaining this apparent contradiction, it can vary mostly resulting from changes in lobster's population parameters like weight and length. Increment of mean size and size at first maturity on the Cuban lobster population have been reported as a consequence of fishing pressures (de León, 2005). Similar results have been reported for *Panulirus cygnus* RW George, 1962 populations, which density has been decreased, because of intensive fishing pressure (Chittleborough, 1979). Also, it was similarly reported for the *Jasus lalandii* (H. Milne Edwards, 1837) population and for other *Jasus* species (Beyers & Goosen, 1987). Basically, larger lobsters could produce and release a higher number of eggs (Pollock, 1991, 1993, 1995). Since variations of food availability in the natural habitat do not have a direct and immediate impact on the Kcl index, which could be impacted by many others morphometric parameters, this index should be prudently used as nutritional condition indicator.

However, other authors have attributed to an increased mean size and size at first maturity, to recruitment fails (Baisre, 2000a,b). In the Cuban lobster population, recruitment fails have been documented from 1990, resulting essentially from natural meteorological events like intensive hurricane, and a decreased nutrient concentration at the coastal zone (Baisre, 2000a,b, 2006). Additionally, the Cuban coastal zone has been impacted by other tropical processes like sewage water input, bottom trawling, and mangrove cutting (Baisre & Arbolea, 2006; Vales-García & Aguilar-González, 2021). Even caffeine has been recently reported as an important contaminant in the coastal zone (Vieira et al., 2022). It is a reason why it should be included in further studies considering that most of the Cuban people are used to drinking a lot of coffee. These factors impacting lobster's population parameters have intensified from 1990 (Alzugaray et al., 2018; Puga et al., 2013), decreasing

in carrying capacity of marine ecosystems, particularly in nursery areas. The *Puerulus* settlement has been consequently affected, reinforcing bottleneck processes, and causing changes in lobster's population dynamics (Puga et al., 1991; Parrish & Polovina, 1994; Baisre, 2000a,b).

Large lobsters could come from deeper areas where food availability is not a limiting resource. In those cases, the increment of the mean lobster size implies a lobster mean weight increment. Therefore, this could cause an increased Kcl. The probability of finding large lobsters coming from deeper water is higher on shelf edge sites (González-Sansón et al., 1991). Such sites are numerous in the Caibarién region because of the narrowness and the strategy location of the fishing areas. Accordingly, a different magnitude of Kcl variation was found between periods, detecting significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the Past period, and only slightly differences ($p > 0.05$) in the Current period. This means that Kcl variation is higher in the Caibarién region (1.5 units) than in the Batabanó region (1.1 units), possibly caused by a different environmental impact in the regions. The number, diversity, and magnitude of environmental factors, impacting coastal marine ecosystems, were higher in the Caibarién region (García-García et al., 2008; Montalvo-Estévez et al., 2008, 2010, 2013, 2014). The unfavourable environmental conditions in the Caibarién region could have caused moving fishing areas to the shelf edges, increasing the probability of finding larger lobsters. Also, the incipient improvement of habitat conditions on some sites of the Caibarién region contributes to a less affected lobster's nutritional condition. Such incipient improvement has been potentially attributed to the effectiveness of multiple management measures, like increasing Protected Areas (Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2021b).

By providing information about lobster's nutritional condition in natural habitats of the Caibarién fishing region, our results constitute a usefulness baseline. Due to no standardisation among the numerous methods determining nutritional condition in crustaceans, it would be needed and recommended to analyse variations more than pointed values in each study (Gutzler & Butler, 2017; Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021). Nevertheless, the environmental deterioration in the Caibarién region confers both variations and point value importance, as references of lobster's nutritional condition in polluted and anthropised coastal zone sites (Alcolado & Espinosa, 1996; Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2021b; Martínez-Daranas et al., 2021). In addition to the information,

gradually provided by previous studies developed in Cuba (Lopeztegui-Castillo et al., 2012a,b, 2023; Lopeztegui-Castillo, 2021; Lopeztegui-Castillo & Capetillo-Piñar, 2021), Kcl index was locally estimated, by improving the comparison of results. Based on this, it is suggested that the Kcl index is not an efficient indicator of truly lobsters' nutritional condition.

Conclusions

Lobster's nutritional condition has been typically higher in the Batabanó region than in the Caibarién region. Nevertheless, only BRI currently detected significant differences, suggesting that both regions have had a different environmental impact through time. Methodological differences between indices could partially influence though. Long-term temporary variations showed an increased Kcl index in both fishing regions. The morphometric nature of the Kcl index could contribute to explaining this increment, by resulting from changes in lobster's population parameter, such as weight and length, which could change because of intensive fishing pressure.

The lobster's nutritional condition, which could be used as an additional habitat quality indicator based on the BRI results, was higher in males than in females. In fact, this can be assumed as a natural common phenomenon at least in the Cuban lobster population, possibly resulting from reproductive processes and local feeding regime. Being remained through the time, differences between sexes suggest that regional environmental changes should have been remarked enough to affect the nutritional condition of male and female lobsters. Consequently, both nutritional condition indices changed despite distinct sensibility and methodological differences between them.

Acknowledgements

The author appreciated the collaboration of Diomara, Mercedes, Yamilé, Franklyn, Oneisy, Evelyn and Samuel (Cuban fisheries biologists), the ancient and the current Lambada boat's crew, and other people from Batabanó and Caibarién Fishery Industries (Cuba). The Fisheries Research Centre of Cuba should be thanked for supporting sample cruises and providing data. The author thanks CONACYT for a doctoral fellowship.

References

- Alcolado P.M. 1990. *El Bentos de la Macrolaguna del Golfo de Batabanó*. La Habana: Editorial Academia. 161 p.
- Alcolado P.M., Espinosa J. 1996. Empleo de las comunidades de moluscos marinos de fondos blandos como bioindicadores de la diversidad del megazoobentos y de la calidad ambiental. *Iberus* 14(2): 79–84. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4642526
- Alcolado P.M., Espinosa J., Martínez-Estalella N., Ibarzábal D., del Valle R., Martínez-Iglesias J.C., Abreu M., Hernandez-Zanuy A. 1998. Prospección del megazoobentos de los fondos blandos del Archipiélago Sabana-Camagüey, Cuba. *Avicennia* 8/9: 87–104.
- Alcolado P.M., García E.E., Espinosa N. (Eds.). 1999. *Protección de la biodiversidad y desarrollo sostenible en el ecosistema Sabana-Camagüey*. Madrid: CESYTA S.L. 143 p.
- Alcolado P.M., García E.E., Arellano-Acosta M. (Eds.). 2007. *Ecosistema Sabana-Camagüey. Estado actual, avances y desafíos en la protección y uso sostenible de la biodiversidad*. La Habana: Editorial Academia. 183 p.
- Alzugaray R., Puga R., Piñero R., Estela de León M., Cobas L.S., Morales O. 2018. The Caribbean spiny lobster (*Panulirus argus*) fishery in Cuba: current status, illegal fishing, and environmental variability. *Bulletin of Marine Science* 94(2): 393–408. DOI: 10.5343/bms.2016.1126
- Arias-Schreiber M., Wolf M., Cano M., Martínez-Daranas B., Marcos Z., Hidalgo G., Castellanos S., del Valle R., Abreu M., Martínez J.C., Díaz J., Areces A. 2008. Changes in benthic assemblages of the Gulf of Batabanó (Cuba) – results from cruises undertaken during 1981–85 and 2003–04. *Pan-American Journal of Aquatic Science* 3(1): 49–60.
- Baisre J.A. 2000a. The Cuban Spiny Lobster Fishery. In: B.F. Phillips, J. Kittaka (Eds.): *Spiny Lobsters: Fisheries and Culture*. Oxford: Blackwell Science, John Wiley & Sons. P. 135–152. DOI: 10.1002/9780470698808.ch7
- Baisre J.A. 2000b. Chronicle of Cuban marine fisheries (1935–1995). Trend analysis and fisheries potential. In: *FAO Fisheries Technical Paper*. №394. Rome: FAO. 26 p.
- Baisre J.A. 2006. Assessment of nitrogen flows into the Cuban landscape. *Biogeochemistry* 79(1/2): 91–108. DOI: 10.1007/s10533-006-9004-z
- Baisre J.A. 2018. Overview of Cuban commercial marine fisheries: The last 80 years. *Bulletin of Marine Science* 94(2): 359–375. DOI: 10.5343/bms.2017.1015
- Baisre J.A., Arboleya Z. 2006. Going against the flow: Effects of river damming in Cuban fisheries. *Fisheries Research* 81(2–3): 283–292. DOI: 10.1016/j.fishres.2006.04.019
- Betanzos-Vega A., Capetillo-Piñar N., Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Martínez-Daranas B. 2013. Variación espacio-temporal de la turbidez y calidad en cuerpos de agua marina de uso pesquero, región norcentral de Cuba, 2008–2010. *Serie Oceanológica* 12: 24–35.
- Briones-Fourzán P., Baeza-Martínez K., Lozano-Álvarez E. 2009. Nutritional indices of juvenile Caribbean spiny lobsters in a Mexican reef lagoon: Are changes over a 10-year span related to the emergence of *Panulirus argus*. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 370(1–2): 82–88. DOI: 10.1016/j.jembe.2008.12.004

- Briones-Fourzán P., Álvarez-Filip L., Barradas-Ortiz C., Morillo-Velarde P.S., Negrete-Soto F., Segura-García I., Sánchez-González A., Lozano-Álvarez E. 2019. Coral reef degradation differentially alters feeding ecology of co-occurring congeneric spiny lobsters. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 5: 516. DOI: 10.3389/fmars.2018.00516
- Buesa R.J. 1965. *Biología de la langosta Panulirus argus, Latreille, 1804 (Crustacea, Decapoda, Reptantia) en Cuba*. La Habana: Instituto Nacional de la Pesca, Mimeogr. 228 p.
- Beyers C.J., Goosen P.C. 1987. Variations in fecundity and size at sexual maturity of female rock lobster *Jasus lalandii* in the Benguela ecosystem. *South African Journal of Marine Science* 5(1): 513–521. DOI: 10.2989/025776187784522216
- Capetillo-Piñar N., Villalejo-Fuerte M.T., Tripp-Quezada A. 2015. Distinción taxonómica de los moluscos de fondos blandos del Golfo de Batabanó, Cuba. *Latin American Journal of Aquatic Research* 43(5): 856–872. DOI: 10.3856/vol43-issue5-fulltext-6
- Cau A., Gorule P.A., Bellodi A., Carreras-Colom E., Moccia D., Pittura L., Regoli F., Follesa M.C. 2023. Comparative microplastic load in two decapod crustaceans *Palinurus elephas* (Fabricius, 1787) and *Nephrops norvegicus* (Linnaeus, 1758). *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 191: 114912. DOI: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2023.114912
- Cerdeira-Estrada S., Lorenzo-Sánchez S., Areces-Mallea A., Martínez-Bayón C. 2008. Mapping of the spatial distribution of benthic habitats in the Gulf of Batabanó using Landsat-7 images. *Ciencias Marinas* 34(2): 213–222. DOI: 10.7773/cm.v34i2.1293
- Chittleborough R.G. 1979. Natural regulation of the population of *Panulirus longipes cygnus* George and responses to fishing pressure. *Rapports et Proces-Verbaux des Reunions Conseil International pour l'Exploration de la Mer* 175: 24–32.
- Chou C.L., Paon L.A., Moffatt J.D., King T. 2003. Selection of bioindicators for monitoring marine environmental quality in the Bay of Fundy, Atlantic Canada. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 46(6): 756–762. DOI:10.1016/S0025-326X(03)00045-6
- Cobas G.S., Morales O., Puga R., Piñeiro R., de León M.E. 2015. Factores estresantes al hábitat de la langosta espinosa en la zona norcentral de Cuba. *Revista Cubana de Investigaciones Pesqueras* 32(1): 48–54.
- Cruz R., Baisre J.A., Díaz E., Brito R., García C., Carrodegas C. 1990. *Atlas biológico-pesquero de la langosta en el archipiélago cubano*. La Habana: Ministerio de la Industria Pesquera. 125 p.
- Cruz R. 2002. *Manual de métodos de muestreo para la evaluación de las poblaciones de langosta espinosa*. Roma: FAO Documento Técnico de Pesca №399. 43 p.
- De León M.E., López-Martínez J., Lluch-Cota D., Hernández-Vázquez S., Puga R. 2005. Decadal variability in growth of the Caribbean spiny lobster *Panulirus argus* (Decapoda: Paniluridae) in Cuban waters. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 53(3–4): 475–486. DOI: 10.15517/rbt.v53i3-4.14616
- Fitzgibbon Q.P., Simon C.J., Smith G.G., Carter C.G., Battaglione S.C. 2017a. The impact of seismic air gun exposure on the haemolymph physiology and nutritional condition of spiny lobster, *Jasus edwardsii*. *Marine Pollution Bulletin* 125(1–2): 146–156. DOI: 10.1016/j.marpolbul.2017.08.004
- Fitzgibbon Q.P., Simon C.J., Smith G.G., Carter C.G., Battaglione S.C. 2017b. Temperature dependent growth, feeding, nutritional condition and aerobic metabolism of juvenile spiny lobster, *Sagmariasus verreauxi*. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part A* 207: 13–20. DOI: 10.1016/j.cbpa.2017.02.003
- García-García N., Puentes O., Montalvo-Estévez J.F. 2008. Contaminación orgánica en el sector de la bahía de Buenavista cercano a la desembocadura del río Guaní, Villa Clara, Cuba. *Revista Cubana de Química* 20(3): 39–45.
- George J. 2001. The usefulness and limitations of handheld refractometers in veterinary laboratory medicine: an historical and technical review. *Veterinary Clinical Pathology* 30(4): 201–210. DOI: 10.1111/j.1939-165X.2001.tb00432.x
- Ghafari M.I.A., Fitrianti V. 2021. Pioneer assessment on megabenthic community suggest the recent ecological condition of coral reef in Senggigi Beach, Western Lombok Island, Indonesia. *Indo Pacific Journal of Ocean Life* 5(1): 14–21. DOI: 10.13057/oceanlife/o050103
- Goncalves R., Lund I., Gesto M. 2021. Interactions of temperature and dietary composition on juvenile European lobster (*Homarus gammarus*, L.) energy metabolism and performance. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part A: Molecular & Integrative Physiology* 260: 111019. DOI: 10.1016/j.cbpa.2021.111019
- González-Sansón G., Herrera A., Díaz E., Brito R., Gotera G., Arrinda C., Ibarzábal D. 1991. Bioecología y conducta de la langosta (*Panulirus argus*, Latr.) en las zonas profundas del borde de la plataforma en la región suroccidental de Cuba. *Revista de Investigaciones Marinas* 12(1–3): 140–153.
- Gutzler B.C., Butler M.J. 2017. Comparison of methods for determining nutritional condition in spiny lobsters. *Journal of Shellfish Research* 36(1): 175–179. DOI: 10.2983/035.036.0118
- Harrington A.M., Hamlin H.J. 2019. Ocean acidification alters thermal cardiac performance, hemocyte abundance, and hemolymph chemistry in subadult American lobsters *Homarus americanus* H. Milne Edwards, 1837 (Decapoda: Malacostraca: Nephropidae). *Journal of Crustacean Biology* 39(4): 468–476. DOI: 10.1093/jcobiol/ruz015
- Herrera A., Díaz E., Brito R., González G., Gotera G., Espinosa J., Ibarzábal D. 1991. Alimentación natural de la langosta *Panulirus argus* en la región de Los Indios (Plataforma SW de Cuba) y su relación con el bentos. *Revista de Investigaciones Marinas* 12(1–2): 172–182.

- Hidalgo-Rodríguez G., Areces-Mallea A. 2009. Estimación cualitativa y cuantitativa del macrozoobentos en la macrolaguna del Golfo de Batabanó, Cuba. *Revista Cubana de Investigaciones Pesqueras* 26(1): 73–79.
- Hidalgo G., Toledo W., Granados-Barba A. 2015. Diversidad y distinción taxonómica de la macrofauna en fondos blandos de la plataforma norte y suroccidental cubana. *Latin American Journal of Aquatic Research* 43(5): 845–855. DOI: 10.3856/vol43-issue5-fulltext-5
- Kampouris T.E., Syranidou E., Seridou P., Gagoulis K., Batjakas I.E., Kalogerakis N. 2023. MPs and NPs intake and heavy metals accumulation in tissues of *Palinurus elephas* (J.C. Fabricius, 1787), from NW Aegean Sea, Greece. *Environmental Pollution* 316(1): 120725. DOI: 10.1016/j.envpol.2022.120725
- Lopeztegui-Castillo A. 2021. Assessment of nutritional condition in crustaceans: a review of methodologies and guidelines for applying inexpensive and wide-ranging indices to the spiny lobster *Panulirus argus* (Latreille, 1804) (Decapoda: Achelata: Palinuridae). *Journal of Crustacean Biology* 41(4): ruab067. DOI: 10.1093/jcbiol/ruab067
- Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Capetillo-Piñar N. 2008. Macrozoobentos como estimador del potencial alimentario para la langosta espinosa (*Panulirus argus*) en tres zonas al Sur de Pinar del Río, Cuba. *Boletín del Centro de Investigaciones Biológicas* 42(2): 187–203.
- Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Capetillo-Piñar N. 2021. Condición nutricional de la langosta, *Panulirus argus* (Decapoda: Palinuridae): 60 años de índices extensivos y variación espacio-temporal en Cuba. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 69(2): 534–544. DOI: 10.15517/rbt.v69i2.43548
- Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Capetillo-Piñar N., Betanzos-Vega A. 2012a. Variaciones en la condición nutricional de langostas *Panulirus argus* (Decapoda: Palinuridae) en la región este del Golfo de Batabanó, Cuba. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 60(1): 263–271.
- Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Martínez-Coello D. 2020. 35 años de cambio en densidad y biomasa del megazoobentos del golfo de Batabanó, Cuba, e implicaciones para la langosta, *Panulirus argus* (Decapoda: Palinuridae). *Revista de Biología Tropical* 68(4): 1346–1356. DOI: 10.15517/RBT.V68I4.41209
- Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Suárez G., Capetillo-Piñar N., Alzugaray R. 2012b. Índice de refracción de la hemolinfa vs tasa peso total/largo total en la estimación de la condición nutricional de langostas *Panulirus argus*. *Boletín del Centro de Investigaciones Biológicas* 46(4): 369–384.
- Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Martínez-Coello D., Abitia-Cárdenas L.A. 2021a. Benthic index for estimating food availability in two soft bottoms fishing areas. *Thalassas* 37(2): 487–495. DOI: 10.1007/s41208-021-00341-0
- Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Capetillo-Piñar N., Betanzos-Vega A., Martínez-Daranas B., Martínez-Coello D., Abitia-Cárdenas L.A. 2021b. Space-time variations of megazoobenthos subject to natural and anthropogenic impacts in two Cuban bays: evidence of recovery?. *Latin American Journal of Aquatic Research* 49(1): 97–109. DOI: 10.3856/vol49-issue1-fulltext-2542
- Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Olivera-Espinosa Y., Abitia-Cárdenas L.A. 2023. Influence of environmental factors on nutritional condition of spiny lobster *Panulirus argus* (Decapoda: Palinuridae). *Thalassas* DOI: 10.1007/s41208-023-00546-5
- Lozano-Alvarez E., Aramoni-Serrano G. 1996. Alimentación y estado nutricional de las langostas *Panulirus inflatus* y *Panulirus gracilis* (Decapoda: Palinuridae) en Guerrero, México. *Revista de Biología Tropical* 44(3B): 453–461.
- Lozano-Álvarez E., Luviano-Aparicio N., Negrete-Soto F., Barradas-Ortiz C., Aguiñiga-García S., Morillo-Velarde P.S., Álvarez-Filip L., Briones-Fourzán P. 2017. Does reef architectural complexity influence resource availability for a large reef-dwelling invertebrate?. *Journal of Sea Research* 128: 84–91. DOI: 10.1016/j.seares.2017.08.010
- Martínez-Calderón R., Lozano-Álvarez E., Briones-Fourzán P. 2018. Morphometric relationships and seasonal variation in size, weight, and a condition index of post-settlement stages of the Caribbean spiny lobster. *PeerJ* 6: e5297. DOI: 10.7717/peerj.5297
- Martínez-Coello D., Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Amador-Marro U. 2015. Diferencias entre sexos en la composición de la dieta natural de la langosta *Panulirus argus* (Decapoda: Palinuridae) al este del golfo de Batabanó, Cuba. *Cuadernos de Investigación UNED* 7(2): 269–277. DOI: 10.22458/urj.v7i2.1153
- Martínez-Daranas B., Betanzos-Vega A., Lopeztegui-Castillo A., Capetillo-Piñar N., Castellanos-Iglesias S. 2021. Influence of several stressful factors on the condition of seagrasses at Sabana-Camagüey Archipelago, Cuba. *Regional Studies in Marine Science* 47: 101939. DOI: 10.1016/j.rsma.2021.101939
- Montalvo-Estévez J.F., García I., Loza S., Esponda S.C., César M.E., González de Zaya R., Hernández L. 2008. Oxígeno disuelto y materia orgánica en cuerpos de aguas interiores del Archipiélago Sabana-Camagüey, Cuba. *Serie Oceanológica* 4: 71–84.
- Montalvo-Estévez J.F., Perigó E., Martínez M., García I., Esponda S.C., Cesar M.E., García R., López D., García N., Blanco M. 2010. Compuestos de nitrógeno y fósforo en las aguas superficiales de tres zonas de la plataforma marina cubana. *Serie Oceanológica* 7: 27–36.
- Montalvo-Estévez J.F., García-Ramil I.A., Perigó-Arnaud E., Albuquerque-Brook O.C., García-García N. 2013. Calidad química del agua y sedimento en las bahías del archipiélago Sabana-Camagüey. *Revista Cubana de Química* 25(2): 123–133.
- Montalvo-Estévez J.F., García-Ramil I.A., Almeida-Rodríguez M., Betanzos-Vega A., García-García N. 2014. Modelación de la eutroficación e índice de calidad del

- agua en algunas bahías del archipiélago Sabana Camagüey. *Tecnología Química* 34(3): 184–196.
- Moore L.E., Smith D.M., Loneragan N.R. 2000. Blood refractive index and whole-body lipid content as indicators of nutritional condition for penaeid prawns (Decapoda: Penaeidae). *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 244(1): 131–143. DOI: 10.1016/S0022-0981(99)00127-6
- Morales O., Puga R. 2008. Evaluación del stock de langosta (*Panulirus argus*) en la zona nororiental de Cuba. *Revista Cubana de Investigaciones Pesqueras* 25(1): 13–19.
- Morales O., Puga R., de León M.E., Alzugaray R. 2013. Evaluación del esfuerzo de pesca sobre la población de langosta (*Panulirus argus*) en la región norcentral de Cuba. *Revista Cubana de Investigaciones Pesqueras* 30(1): 1–4.
- Oliver M.D., MacDiarmid A.B. 2001. Blood refractive index and ratio of weight to carapace length as indices of nutritional condition in juvenile rock lobsters (*Jasus edwardsii*). *Marine and Freshwater Research* 52(8): 1395–1400. DOI: 10.1071/MF01030
- Parrish F.A., Polovina J.J. 1994. Habitat thresholds and bottlenecks in production of the spiny lobster (*Panulirus marginatus*) in the northwestern Hawaiian Islands. *Bulletin of Marine Science* 54(1): 151–163.
- Perera E., Díaz-Iglesias E., Fraga I., Carrillo O., Galich G.S. 2007. Effect of body weight, temperature and feeding on the metabolic rate in the spiny lobster *Panulirus argus* (Latreille, 1804). *Aquaculture* 265(1–4): 261–270. DOI: 10.1016/j.aquaculture.2006.11.012
- Pollock D.E. 1991. Spiny lobsters at Tristan da Cunha, South Atlantic: inter-island variations in growth and population structure. *South African Journal of Marine Science* 10(1): 1–12. DOI: 10.2989/02577619109504614
- Pollock D.E. 1993. Recruitment overfishing and resilience in spiny lobster populations. *ICES Journal of Marine Science* 50(1): 9–14. DOI: 10.1006/JMSC.1993.1002
- Pollock D.E. 1995. Changes in maturation ages and sizes in crustacean and fish populations. *South African Journal of Marine Science* 15(1): 99–103. DOI: 10.2989/02577619509504836
- Puga R., de León M.E., Cruz R. 1991. Evaluación de la Pesquería de langosta espinosa *Panulirus argus* en Cuba. *Revista de Investigaciones Marinas* 12(1-3): 286–292.
- Puga R., Hernández-Vázquez S., López-Martínez J., de León M.E. 2005. Bioeconomic modelling and risk assessment of the Cuban fishery for spiny lobster *Panulirus argus*. *Fisheries Research* 75(1–3): 149–163. DOI: 10.1016/j.fishres.2005.03.014
- Puga R., Piñeiro R., Alzugaray R., Cobas L.S., de León M.E., Morales O. 2013. Integrating anthropogenic and climatic factors in the assessment of the Caribbean spiny lobster (*Panulirus argus*) in Cuba: Implications for fishery management. *International Journal of Marine Science* 3(6): 36–45.
- Rainbow P.S. 1997. Ecophysiology of trace metal uptake in crustaceans. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 44(2): 169–176. DOI: 10.1006/ECSS.1996.0208
- Robertson D.N., Butler M.J., Dobbs F.C. 2000. An evaluation of lipid- and morphometric-based indices of nutritional condition for early benthic stage spiny lobsters, *Panulirus argus*. *Marine and Freshwater Behaviour and Physiology* 33(3): 161–171. DOI: 10.1080/10236240009387088
- Rodríguez-García O.U., Castañeda-Fernández de Lara V., Rodríguez-Jaramillo C., Serviere-Zaragoza E. 2015. Nutritional condition and gonad development of juvenile and subadult California spiny lobster *Panulirus interruptus* in two habitats. *Revista de Biología Marina y Oceanografía* 50(2): 261–270. DOI: 10.4067/S0718-19572015000300005
- Rotllant G., Company J.B., Álvarez-Fernández I., García J.A., Aguzzi J., Durfort M. 2014. The effects of seasonal variation on the nutritional condition of *Nephrops norvegicus* (Astacidea: Nephropidae) from wild populations in the western Mediterranean. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 94(4): 763–773. DOI: 10.1017/S0025315414000022
- Ruiz-Plasencia I., Hernández-Albernas J., Ruiz-Rojas E. 2019. Catálogo de las áreas protegidas de Cuba. In: I. Ruiz (Ed.): *Las áreas protegidas de Cuba*. La Habana, Centro Nacional de Áreas Protegidas. P. 115–371.
- Simon C.J., Fitzgibbon Q.P., Battison A., Carter C.G., Battaglione S.C. 2015. Bioenergetics of nutrient reserves and metabolism in spiny lobster juveniles *Sagmariasus verreauxi*: predicting nutritional condition from hemolymph biochemistry. *Physiological and Biochemical Zoology* 88(3): 266–283. DOI: 10.1086/681000
- Simon C.J., Rodemann T., Carter C.G. 2016. Near-infrared spectroscopy as a novel non-invasive tool to assess spiny lobster nutritional condition. *PLoS ONE* 11(7): e0159671. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0159671
- StatSoft, Inc. 2011. *STATISTICA (data analysis software system), version 10*. Available from www.statsoft.com
- Valavi H., Savari A., Yavari V., Kochanian P., Safahieh A., Sedighi-Savadkuhi O. 2009. Coral reef anthropogenic impact bio-indicators in the Northern part of the Persian Gulf. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research* 7(3): 215–227.
- Vales-García M.A., Aguilar-González B. 2021. Manglar vivo en Cuba: costos y beneficios de las acciones basadas en ecosistemas. Análisis económico-ecológico en las provincias Sur Artemisa y Mayabeque. *Revista Ibero-Americana de Economía Ecológica* 34(1): 86–110.
- Vieira L.R., Soares A.M.V.M., Freitas R. 2022. Caffeine as a contaminant of concern: A review on concentrations and impacts in marine coastal systems. *Chemosphere* 286(P2): 131675. DOI: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.131675
- Wang F., Zhu Y., Jiang S., Lin L., Lu J. 2021. Nutritional qualities and sensory characteristics in the hepatopancreas and muscle of female mud crab (*Scylla paramamosain*) in three growth forms: A comparative study. *LWT* 146(22): 111477. DOI: 10.1016/j.lwt.2021.111477

- Wang G., McGaw I.J. 2014. Use of serum protein concentration as an indicator of quality and physiological condition in the lobster *Homarus americanus* (Milne-Edwards, 1837). *Journal of Shellfish Research* 33(3): 805–813. DOI: 10.2983/035.033.0315
- Wang S., Carter C.G., Fitzgibbon Q.P., Codabaccus B.M., Smith G.G. 2021. Effect of dietary protein on energy metabolism including protein synthesis in the spiny lobster *Sagmariasus verreauxi*. *Scientific Reports* 11(1): 11814. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-021-91304-1

ДОЛГОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЙ ПИТАНИЯ *PANULIRUS ARGUS* (DECAPODA: PALINURIDAE) НА КУБЕ: АНАЛИТИЧЕСКИЕ И МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ

А. Лопестегьи-Кастильо

Северо-Западный центр биологических исследований, Мексика
e-mail: alopeztegui@yahoo.com

Индексы условий питания часто использовались в качестве морфофизиологических индикаторов для изучения изменений в физиологии и энергетических запасов лобстеров. Целью данного исследования было определение долговременных пространственно-временных изменений условий питания *Panulirus argus* (далее – лобстер) с учетом двух индексов, включая аналитический показатель преломления крови (BRI) и морфометрический Kcl (отношение общего веса к длине панциря). Информация с одиннадцати участков в регионе Кайбарьен, отобранных в 2010–2015 гг., и двенадцати участков в регионе Батабано, отобранных в 2011–2017 гг., была обозначена как современный период. Морфометрические данные для оценки индекса Kcl, включающие 1987–1988 гг. в регионе Кайбарьен и 1981–1993 гг. в регионе Батабано, были сгруппированы как прошлый период. Временные изменения были определены путем сравнения современного и прошлого периодов в каждом регионе. Пространственные изменения определялись путем сравнения данных между регионами. Для проанализированных особей лобстера в текущий период были определены значения индексов BRI = 14.3, Kcl = 7.0 в регионе Кайбарьен и BRI = 15.2, Kcl = 7.0 в регионе Батабано. За прошлый период значение индекса Kcl составило 5.8 и 6.3 в регионах Кайбарьен и Батабано соответственно. Индексы Kcl и BRI были выше для самцов лобстера. Это может быть связано с процессом размножения. Однако на это могут влиять внутренние морфометрические различия между самцами и самками. Значения морфометрических показателей были выше для современного периода. Пространственные изменения морфометрических показателей статистически значимо различались для прошлого периода, что было связано с разными природными условиями в каждом регионе. Индекс BRI был выше в регионе Батабано, что, вероятно, связано с лучшим состоянием донных сообществ и лучшим качеством воды. Полученные результаты способствуют пониманию условий питания лобстера в естественной среде обитания, главным образом, в регионе Кайбарьен, где на сегодняшний день проведено мало исследований.

Ключевые слова: десятиногие ракообразные, лангуст, морфофизиологические индексы, экофизиология, энергозапасы ракообразных

MANATEE WATCHING IS WIDESPREAD AND SEASONALLY AFFECTED IN NORTHEAST BRAZIL: A CASE OF THE ENDANGERED *TRICHECHUS MANATUS MANATUS* (SIRENIA: TRICHECHIDAE)

Paula D. F. Coutinho^{ID}, Ana L. L. Matte^{ID}, Bruna Bezerra^{ID}

Universidade Federal de Pernambuco, Brazil

e-mail: paula.djanira@ufpe.br, analuiza.matte@ufpe.br, bruna.bezerra@ufpe.br

Received: 04.06.2023. Revised: 20.09.2023. Accepted: 08.10.2023.

Marine mammal watching is a non-consumptive wildlife-oriented tourism practice. *Trichechus manatus manatus* (hereinafter – Antillean manatee) belongs to the charismatic marine megafauna and is subject to this practice at many places. Here we investigated the Antillean manatee watching in Brazil, focusing on mapping this activity across the country, identifying hotspot areas, analysing the potential seasonality of this practice, and assessing the interactions between people and Antillean manatees. We used a social network as data source since this species often appears on social media. The species is charismatic and have characteristics, which attract public affection such as large body size, gentle behaviour, and distinct physical appearance. We detected Antillean manatee watching in 91 localities distributed across 19 municipalities and nine states in northern and north-eastern Brazil. We considered six localities as Antillean manatee watching hotspots because of their high number of associated images. Five of the hotspots were located within three Protected Areas for sustainable use. We found up to 23 people depicted in a single manatee-related picture posted on social network, but up to five people appeared in most posts (photos and videos). Furthermore, images were significantly posted mostly during the summer months, indicating seasonality in Antillean manatee watching. We classified the manatee-watching interactions collected as either prohibited or permitted by the Brazilian law. Permitted interactions were significantly more frequent, but the occurrence of prohibited interactions reveals the current lack of compliance with Brazilian regulations. We suggest that tourism management strategies prioritise Antillean manatee watching hotspot areas, focusing on reinforcing compliance with local regulations and preferably involving local residents to ensure the sustainability of this practice in Brazil.

Key words: ecotourism, human-wildlife interaction, sirenians, tourism sustainability, travel behaviour, wildlife

Introduction

Non-consumptive wildlife-oriented recreation is defined as a human recreational activity focusing on interacting with nature and wildlife, wherein the focal organisms are not purposefully removed or have their well-being affected by the engagement (Duffus & Dearden, 1990; Bejder et al., 2022). If conducted properly and in a sustainable non-invasive manner, such tourism practices can provide economic benefits to local communities (O'Connor et al., 2009; Hunt et al., 2015; Zimmerhackel et al., 2019; Dembovska & Zvaigzne, 2021), promote habitat conservation (Thurstan et al., 2012; Hunt et al., 2015; Stronza et al., 2019), and wildlife protection (Tisdell & Wilson, 2005; Ballantyne et al., 2011; Lin & Kuo, 2016; Fumagalli et al., 2021).

Wildlife watching is nowadays intrinsically linked to taking photographs and/or videos with the option of posting them on social media. Photographs and videos that have been posted on social media platforms have been widely explored to trace practices and interactions related to various species. The combination of smartphone availability, built in

Global Positioning Systems (GPS), high-resolution cameras, and internet connectivity, with social media usage, has introduced a new range of data to be explored, spontaneously generated by social media (Hamme et al., 2021; Kroetz et al., 2021). Social media have also created an opportunity to collect data on human-nature interactions on both spatial and temporal scales (Dickison et al., 2012; Toivonen et al., 2019; Papafitsoros et al., 2021; Cheung et al., 2022), allowing the collection of large volumes of location-based ecological data (Dickison et al., 2012). For example, social media data, such as data extracted from Instagram, have answered questions regarding wildlife trade (Di Minin et al., 2019; Wyatt et al., 2022), wildlife distribution, monitoring of rare and data deficient populations (Jeawak et al., 2018; Sullivan et al., 2019; Cranswick et al., 2022), visitation patterns in conservation areas (Tenkanen et al., 2017), tourist preferences (Hausmann et al., 2018; Kroetz et al., 2021), and tourist sentiments and perceptions of the environment (Becken et al., 2017; Kroetz et al., 2021; Palazzo et al., 2021; Šmelhausová et al., 2022), in addition to visitor pressure on wildlife

welfare (Sullivan et al., 2019; Papafitsoros et al., 2021, 2023; Hamme et al., 2021).

The rapid uncoordinated growth of tourist practices involving marine mammals can cause short-term or immediate effects (Cecchetti et al., 2018; Machernis et al., 2018). For instance, animals may demonstrate behavioural changes in response to approaching boats, such as changing orientation, depth and fluking behaviour (Rycyk et al., 2018), increasing swimming speed (Nowacek et al., 2004), performing fewer surface, social, resting and forage-feeding behaviours (Marega-Imamura et al., 2018), and changing respiration rates (Christiansen et al., 2014; Fiori et al., 2019). Short-term behavioural responses can lead to long-term biological consequences for individuals and populations, such as habitat abandonment, reduced reproductive success, a decrease in growth rate, and, consequently, population decline (Bejder et al., 2006; Lusseau & Bejder, 2007; Higham et al., 2008; Mortensen et al., 2021).

In Brazil, *Trichechus manatus manatus* Linnaeus, 1758 (hereinafter – Antillean manatee; Fig. 1) is targeted by animal-watching tourism practices (Izidoro & Shiavetti, 2022). Such practices are often related to community-based tourism (Braga & Selva, 2016; Lepre, 2018). The Brazilian federal government regulates Antillean manatee watching through Conservation Action Plans and local legislation (ICMBio, 2013, 2018a,b, 2021; Luna et al., 2022). Such regulations focus on determining the organisations that can practice Antillean manatee watching, the type of vessels allowed, the carrying capacity of the vessels, the minimum distance from the animals, and the duration of the observation time. But there is limited information about where this practice occurs and the pressure it may put on the animals. The Antillean manatee has a disjointed distribution throughout northern and north-eastern Brazil, extending from Amapá to Alagoas states (Luna et al., 2008; Lima et al., 2011; Alves et al., 2016; Favero et al., 2020), where warm waters and rich biodiversity often attract tourists from around the world. *Trichechus manatus* Linnaeus, 1758 is globally classified as Vulnerable by the IUCN (Deutsch et al., 2008). Its subspecies, *Trichechus manatus manatus*, is classified as Endangered on the Brazilian list of threatened species and on the IUCN Red List (Self-Sullivan & Mignucci-Giannoni, 2008; MMA, 2022). Thus, any practice related to this subspecies should be well-tracked and regulated to guarantee its long-term survival in the wild.

Fig. 1. Male Antillean manatee (*Trichechus manatus manatus*) at a soft-release (acclimatisation) facility situated in the mangrove area of the River Tatuamunha in the Costa dos Corais Protected Area, Porto de Pedras municipality, Alagoas state, Brazil (Author: Paula D. F. Coutinho).

In the present study, we aimed to assess Antillean manatee watching in Brazil, focusing on: 1) mapping the areas where it occurs in Brazil; 2) comparing the incidence of Antillean manatee watching per municipality and state; 3) identifying potential hotspot areas; 4) investigating the temporal and seasonal patterns of this activity; and 5) investigating manatee-watching interactions to assess how Antillean manatee watching may impact Antillean manatee behaviour. We used a social media platform to obtain such information. We expected to find Antillean manatee watching hotspots (estimated by a high number of Instagram posts) in Alagoas and Paraíba states, where Antillean manatee watching and the presence of native and reintroduced Antillean manatees have been previously reported in Brazil (e.g. Luna et al., 2008; Lima et al., 2011; Alves et al., 2016; Favero et al., 2020; Izidoro & Shiavetti, 2022; Santos et al., 2022). We also expected Antillean manatee watch-

ing to be more frequent during the summer, when the temperature is higher, and the water turbidity is lower in north-eastern Brazil (Garcia, 2017; Favero et al., 2020), thereby attracting more tourists. Furthermore, considering that Antillean manatees are relatively calm and curious animals (Gomes et al., 2008; Charles et al., 2022; Ponnampalam et al., 2022), we expected a wide range of spontaneous close contact manatee-watching interactions to be depicted on the Instagram social media platform, as previously observed for other marine megafauna, such as seals (Sullivan et al., 2019) or sea turtles (Leitão et al., 2022).

Material and Methods

Ethical note

No specific licence is required for the data mining of publicly available social media data. We gathered data by inspecting publicly available images (photos and videos) on the Instagram platform. We followed the terms and conditions of the platform to protect their users' identity. We concealed the identity of the users that posted the inspected images in our study and only considered the relevant information to avoid image duplication during data compilation.

Data collection

We obtained data from publicly available photos and videos posted on the Instagram platform (Meta, California, USA) from October 2010 to August 2022. We chose the platform because of its growing use for obtaining wildlife data for several purposes (e.g. Sullivan et al., 2019; Hamme et al., 2021; Papafitsoros et al., 2021; Barros et al., 2022; Leitão et al., 2022). We used the hashtag search tool, where a word or phrase is preceded by the hash sign (#) to identify specific topics. We used the hashtag tool combined with the Geotag tool to facilitate data mining, which has previously allowed scientists to search and filter for posts specific to a species or region (e.g. Sullivan et al., 2019; Papafitsoros et al., 2021, 2023; Palazzo et al., 2021; Leitão et al., 2022). We then used the website <https://snapinsta.app/pt> to download the available images depicting Antillean manatees and Antillean manatee watching to create our image bank for the detailed analysis and extraction of our data.

Data processing

From each image (photos and videos), we compiled information on the Instagram user pro-

file, image inspection date, the original date of the post, locality, municipality, state (the latter three were obtained from geotags and post caption information), Antillean manatee presence and absence, number of Antillean manatees and number of people. We also compiled data on Antillean manatee behaviour and the interactions between humans and Antillean manatees. We followed the data mining methodology of Leitão et al. (2022), adapted to our target species (Fig. 2).

We classified manatee-watching interactions as «Prohibited» and «Permitted» according to the current Brazilian legislation. Prohibited interactions included when a person was in the water with a Antillean manatee but not fully submerged, swam underwater with an Antillean manatee (when the person's body was fully submerged), collected underwater footage and/or underwater photos, touched an Antillean manatee, chased an Antillean manatee, tried to attract an Antillean manatee, posed for a photo with an Antillean manatee, kissed an Antillean manatee, or provided water and/or food to an Antillean manatee (for complete regulation, see Federal Law №9.605/1988 and Decree №6.514/2008, article 30; https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/ato2007-2010/2008/decreto/d6514.htm). Permitted interactions included behaviours such as when a person approached and retreated from the Antillean manatee without direct physical contact and when the person passively observed an Antillean manatee from land or boat. Such interactions are not prohibited by the Brazilian law.

Mapping the distribution of Antillean manatee watching

To construct the map of Antillean manatee watching locations in Brazil, we used ArcGIS 10.4 (ESRI, Redlands, USA). We plotted the municipalities and specific localities whenever available (i.e. the name of the beach where an Antillean manatee was observed) that were geotagged or specified in the captions of the Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatees. To obtain the municipalities' central locations (geographic co-ordinates), we considered the IBGE 2021 municipality data (IBGE, 2021). To obtain specific localities (e.g. beaches, river mouths), we used Google Earth to extract the geographic co-ordinates of the location. Finally, we assigned the number of posts depicting Antillean manatees and Antillean manatee watching for each location.

Fig. 2. Data mining method used to obtain data on the distribution of Antillean manatee (*Trichechus manatus manatus*) watching and the manatee-watching interactions from October 2010 to August 2022.

Behavioural data collection

We obtained human and Antillean manatee behavioural data from the video posts on Instagram. We considered the all-occurrence method (Altmann, 1974) when extracting behavioural data from the videos. We scored the behaviours in these videos using Datavyu 1.5.3 software (Datavyu Team, 2014). Furthermore, we considered additional data from photo posts to complement information from the list of manatee-watching interactions and to compare the incidence of prohibited and permitted interactions.

Data analysis

Considering that the number of posts reflects the popularity of places on Instagram (e.g. Shuqair & Cragg, 2017; Kroetz et al., 2021; Asdecker, 2022), we used the number of Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatees in the area to determine Antillean manatee watching hotspots. Areas with over

25 posts were considered hotspots. We used a Chi-Square test to investigate whether the incidence of Antillean manatee watching (estimated from the frequency of Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatees) was evenly distributed across the municipalities and states where this practice occurs in Brazil, accessing the significance of differences among independent categories. We conducted the Kruskal-Wallis test to compare the incidence of Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatee watching between years since this test is indicated to test for differences among three or more independent samples. We excluded the years 2010, 2011, 2012 and 2022 from the comparison between years because there were no complete data for the years 2010 and 2022 (since the Instagram platform was launched in October 2010, and we concluded our data mining in August 2022), and there were no **Antillean manatee watching-related** images for the years 2011 and 2012 (see result

section). We kept the COVID-19 lockdown period because we expected a variation due to the pandemic restrictions (Vărzaru et al., 2021) and wanted to confirm this variation through the Instagram platform. We conducted the Mann-Whitney U-test, comparing two independent groups, to verify whether Antillean manatee watching was more frequent in the summer months compared to other months to investigate whether this practice was seasonally oriented or not. We considered December, January, February and March as the summer months in the north-eastern and northern coastal areas of Brazil (CPTEC/INPE, 2022), where Antillean manatees are known to occur. We conducted the Chi-square test to identify whether the number of people depicted in Antillean manatee-related Instagram posts varied per post, i.e. to test if the categories of number of people varied per post. We used the Chi-square test with Yates correction due to the small degree of freedom, to test whether the number of posts depicting prohibited interactions and permitted interactions was evenly distributed in these two categories of manatee-watching interactions. The Kruskal-Wallis and Mann-Whitney U test were performed using GraphPad Prism 9 software (<https://www.graphpad.com/company>). The Chi-Square test was conducted using Microsoft Excel 365 software. Significance was attained at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Antillean manatee watching hotspots in Brazil

We obtained 1819 images using 21 hashtags (1374 photos and 445 videos). From these images, Antillean manatee watching was registered on 91 locali-

ties (including indigenous villages, islands, beaches, mangroves, and river mouths), distributed across 19 municipalities (Fig. 3) and nine states in northern and north-eastern Brazil (Electronic Supplement 1, Electronic Supplement 2). Six of the 91 localities presented more than 25 Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatees. Therefore, we considered these areas as Antillean manatee watching hotspots. Five of the hotspots are included in three Protected Areas, namely Costas dos Corais Environmental Protected Area, Alagoas State (N = 2), Barra de Mamanguape Environmental Protected Area, Paraíba State (N = 2), and Delta do Parnaíba Environmental Protected Area, Piauí State (N = 1). These Protected Areas permit the sustainable use of resources. The number of Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatees was not evenly distributed across the different Brazilian States ($\chi^2 = 658.8$, $df = 8$, $p < 0.001$) and municipalities ($\chi^2 = 83$, $df = 18$, $p < 0.001$).

Temporal evaluation of Antillean manatee watching

We only found Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatee watching from April 2013 to August 2022 (the month we ended data collection). There were no such Instagram posts in 2010, 2011, and 2012. Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatee watching varied between years (Kruskal Wallis, $H(8): 66.56$, $p < 0.001$), increasing from 2013 to 2021 (Fig. 4, Fig. 5). There was a slight decrease in Instagram posts in 2020, i.e. at the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic in Brazil. Furthermore, since our analysis only included data up to August 2022, the number of posts for this year was slightly lower than for the previous five years (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Municipalities (on the left) and specific localities (i.e. beaches, mangroves, rivers, and estuaries) (on the right), where Antillean manatee (*Trichechus manatus manatus*) watching was detected in social network posts from October 2010 to August 2022.

Most Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatees were detected in January (234), March (233), and November (200). We found a significant difference in the incidence of Antillean manatee watching when comparing the average number of Instagram posts between the summer months (December, January, February and March) and the other months of the year (Mann Whitney U test, $N_1 = 4$, $N_2 = 8$, $U = 2$ $p = 0.017$) (Fig. 5).

Manatee-watching interactions

From the 1819 images collected, Antillean manatees were present in 1222 and absent in 597 ones. People were present in 1791 images and absent in 28. Of the 1791 images with people, 1353 were photos and 438 were videos. In 606 photos, we could not assess the number of people because they were outside the photo's frame. However, in the remaining photos, the number of people ranged from one to twenty-three per photo. In 259 videos, we could not assess the number of people because they were outside the video frame. In the remaining videos, the total number of people per video ranged from one to twenty. However, there were only up to five people (total number) in most of the images (photos and videos) ($\chi^2 = 420.7$, $df = 2$, $p < 0.001$; Fig. 6).

We found 1206 images featuring people and Antillean manatees simultaneously including 399 videos and 807 photos. From these images, it was possible to detect 29 types of Antillean manatee-watching interactions. People initiated 16 types of interactions, which we classified into three categories (Table 1). Antillean manatees initiated 13 types of interactions, which we also classified into three categories (Table 2).

From the inspection of 399 videos (people and Antillean manatees present at the same time), we observed a higher number of permitted ($N = 268$) than prohibited interactions ($N = 178$) ($\chi^2 = 9.1$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.01$). When inspecting all 807 photos (people and Antillean manatees present at the same time), we observed the same pattern, where most of the images depicted permitted interactions ($N = 602$) compared to prohibited interactions ($N = 298$), $\chi^2 = 51.3$, $df = 1$, $p < 0.001$).

Antillean manatee behaviours when not depicted in direct contact with people

When there was no direct contact with people (i.e. no physical interaction between Antillean manatees and people or their objects), it was possible to detect 16 behaviour types performed by the Antillean manatees (Table 3).

Fig. 4. Average number of social network posts (bars indicate the standard errors) related to Antillean manatee (*Trichechus manatus manatus*) watching per year in Brazil from 2010 to 2022.

Fig. 5. Distribution of social network posts related to Antillean manatee (*Trichechus manatus manatus*) watching in Brazil between 2013 and 2022 during summer months (i.e. December, January, February, and March) and non-summer months (i.e. April to November) in northern and north-eastern Brazil (mean and standard error).

Fig. 6. Social network posts and the number of people depicted in the images from April 2013 to August 2022. Designations: A – the number of social network photos depicting Antillean manatee-watching interactions; B – the number of social network videos depicting Antillean manatee-watching interactions.

Discussion

The images obtained through Instagram posts evidenced Antillean manatee watching practices in the north-eastern region of Brazil, in the states of Alagoas, Paraíba, Pernambuco, Piauí, and Sergipe. The municipalities and localities obtained from Instagram posts matched previously recorded Antillean manatee distributions (Luna et al., 2008; Lima et al., 2011; Alves et al., 2016; Favero et al., 2020). An aerial survey of Antillean manatees from Piauí to Alagoas states revealed that the state of Piauí supported

the highest Antillean manatee population density (Alves et al., 2016). This survey also revealed a discontinuity in Antillean manatee sightings in the states of Pernambuco, Rio Grande do Norte, and Ceará. Land-based and boat surveys in Piauí state revealed that Antillean manatee distribution is intrinsically related to the availability of natural resources, e.g. fresh water and food (Favero et al., 2020). Santos et al. (2022) monitored the home ranges of Antillean manatees, which

were reintroduced in the states of Alagoas and Paraíba, and found that Astro, an Antillean manatee released in Alagoas state, was the only individual, which used the areas of the states of Sergipe and Bahia. Astro’s home range comprised the River Vaza Barris and the estuarine complex of the Piauí/Fundo/Real Rivers. This could explain the Instagram posts depicting Antillean manatees in Sergipe and Bahia states, despite the lack of known native individuals.

Table 1. Categorisation and description of Antillean manatee-watching interactions initiated by people, collected from social network posts from April 2013 to August 2022

Behavioural category	Prohibited?	Behaviour (n)	Description
Passive observation	No	Observe from land (video = 41, photo = 50)	The person passively observes the Antillean manatee from the land
	No	Observe from the motorboat (video = 32, photo = 37)	The person passively observes the Antillean manatee from a small motorboat
	No	Observe from a non-motorised boat (video = 184, photo = 165)	The person passively observes the Antillean manatee from a raft, a kayak or a stand-up board
	No	Approach (video = 4, photo = 0)	The person moves towards the Antillean manatee
	No	Retreat (video = 1, photo = 0)	The person moves in the opposite direction of the Antillean manatee
Active interaction with manatee	Yes	In the water with manatee (video = 54, photo = 128)	The person approaches the Antillean manatee and gets into the water with the animal but does not dive
	Yes	Swim with manatee (video = 22, photo = 36)	The person swims with the Antillean manatee, i.e. their entire body is in the water with the animal
	Yes	Underwater footage (video = 5, photo = 0)	The person puts the camera into the water or is diving with an Antillean manatee and records underwater footage
	Yes	Underwater photo (video = 0, photo = 9)	The person puts the camera into the water or is diving with an Antillean manatee and takes underwater photos
	Yes	Touch the manatee (video = 73, photo = 87)	The person touches and rubs the Antillean manatee gently
	Yes	Chase (video = 6, photo = 0)	The person actively swims or moves towards the Antillean manatee that is swimming away
	Yes	Try to attract the manatee (video = 5, photo = 0)	The person puts their hand or an object into the water and splashes the water, trying to attract the Antillean manatee
	Yes	Posing (video = 2, photo = 18)	The person positions themselves so that the manatee is visible in the image background. The person does not touch the Antillean manatee
Nutrition	Yes	Kiss (video = 1, photo = 1)	The person stays in the water with the manatee and kisses the Antillean manatee
	Yes	Feed (video = 3, photo = 2)	The person actively attempts to/or feeds the Antillean manatee
	Yes	Provide water (video = 5, photo = 8)	The person actively attempts to/or provides water to the Antillean manatee

Table 2. Categorisation and description of the Antillean manatee-watching interactions initiated by the Antillean manatees, collected from social network posts from April 2013 to August 2022

Behavioural category	Behaviour (n)	Description
Boat interaction	Approach boat (video = 69, photo = 0)	The animal swims towards boat
	Retreat from boat (video = 2, photo = 0)	The animal swims in the opposite direction of the boat
	Circle the boat (video = 6, photo = 0)	The animal swims around the boat
	Flipper (forelimb) on the boat (video = 8, photo = 0)	The animal uses its flipper (forelimb) to touch the boat
	Snout on the boat (video = 20, photo = 14)	The animal uses its snout to touch the boat
	Hug the boat (video = 84, photo = 86)	The animal uses both flippers (forelimbs) to hold the boat
	Exposure of the penis on the boat (video = 1, photo = 0)	The animal exposes its penis and makes copulatory movements on the boat
	Swim under the boat (video = 1, photo = 0)	The animal swims under the boat
	Chase the boat (video = 4, photo = 0)	The animal actively swims after the boat
Observer interaction	Approach observer (video = 9, photo = 0)	The animal swims towards the person
	Observer contact (video = 46, photo = 110)	The animal is in direct physical contact with the observer
	Retreat observer (video = 1, photo = 0)	The animal swims in the opposite direction to the person
Object interaction	Interaction with an underwater camera (video = 2, photo = 11)	The animal approaches and touches the person’s underwater camera

Table 3. Antillean manatee behaviours in the absence of direct physical interaction with people collected from social network posts from April 2013 to August 2022

Behaviour (n)	Description
Surface swim (video = 78, photo = 40)	The animal swims slowly at the surface
Water column swim (video = 38, photo = 0)	The animal swims slowly in the water column
Shallow swim (video = 20, photo = 15)	The animal swims slowly in shallow water
Spinning swim (video = 2, photo = 0)	The animal pivots in the water by using its flippers
Inverted swim (video = 2, photo = 1)	The animal turns upside down and swims
Surface rest (video = 10, photo = 3)	The animal remains with its eyes closed, positioned at the surface of the water, performing breathing movements
Inverted rest (video = 0, photo = 9)	The animal stays with its ventral region facing upwards, keeping its body positioned on the surface of the water or the substrate, with its eyes closed, performing breathing movements
Shallow rest (video = 5, photo = 11)	The animal is in shallow waters and maintains its eyes closed, positioned at the surface of the water, performing breathing movements
Walk to the bottom (video = 8, photo = 0)	The animal uses both flippers to pull itself through the substrate as if walking using its upper limbs
Float (video = 1, photo = 0)	The animal maintains its eyes closed, positioned in the water column, performing only unconscious breathing movements
Dive (video = 2, photo = 0)	The animal swims in deeper waters
Surface feed (video = 30, photo = 1)	The animal eats at the surface, including foraging (searching for food) and grazing (consumption) behaviours
Touch another Antillean manatee (video = 8, photo = 2)	The animal uses its snout to have direct physical contact with another Antillean manatee
Embrace another Antillean manatee (video = 0, photo = 3)	The animal uses both flippers (forelimbs) to embrace another Antillean manatee
Embrace semi-captive (video = 3, photo = 1)	The animal uses both flippers (forelimbs) to embrace the semi-captive Antillean manatee reintroduction structure
Copulation attempt (video = 4, photo = 1)	The animal tries to attach its body to another individual, but there is no penetration

Of the 91 localities mapped in our study, six could be considered potential Antillean manatee watching hotspots, based on the high number of Instagram posts. The incidence of social media posts in a region can often indicate its touristic popularity (Orsi & Geneletti, 2013; Hausmann et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2021). For instance, areas used for recreational bluefish angling have been identified from videos posted on the YouTube platform (Eryaşar & Saygu, 2022). Such hotspot areas may be important for local economies. Antillean manatees are charismatic animals, and its native and reintroduced individuals seem to attract visitors to natural areas and, thus, may contribute to the development of local community economies, if tourism is performed responsibly and sustainably (Stronza & Pêgas, 2008; Lebrão et al., 2021; Ventura et al., 2022). This pattern of animal-watching associated with the development of local community economies has been observed for other species, such as primates at the Mamirauá Sustainable Development Reserve in Brazilian Amazon (Lebrão et al., 2021), reintroduced *Castor fiber* Linnaeus, 1758 in the River Otter (Denver, England) (Auster et al., 2020), and sea turtles in the fishing village of Praia do Forte, Bahia state, Brazil (Pegas et al., 2013). Considering that five of the six hotspots for Antillean manatee watching were within Protected Areas of sustainable use, governments could formally consider Antillean man-

atee watching as one of the official non-consumptive wildlife-oriented recreations of the regions to attract tourists. Nevertheless, the practice should be supervised to guarantee its sustainability.

The hotspot municipalities and localities have varied tourism capacities, access difficulties and economic-related metrics (Electronic Supplement 3). For instance, Patacho Beach was indicated as a hotspot for Antillean manatee watching tourism in Alagoas state being located in Porto de Pedras municipality within the Costas dos Corais Environmental Protected Area. The estuary of the River Tatuamunha in Porto de Pedras municipality seems to be the only place in Alagoas state, where Antillean manatee watching is allowed, and it is considered community-based tourism (Lepre, 2018; Izidoro & Schiavetti, 2022). Locals take visitors to see Antillean manatees in rehabilitation enclosures using a raft steered by rowers (Braga & Selva, 2016). For the state of Pernambuco, Olinda municipality was considered a hotspot. This is a very surprising result since Olinda is a large city (population size: 393 734; Human Development Indices (2010): 0.735; population density (inhabitant/km²) (2010): 9063.58; IBGE, 2021) and the beaches are not a main tourist attraction since they are highly polluted. Thus, we suspected that interactions with Antillean manatees were most likely performed by residents. In the Paraíba state, the indigenous villages of Camurupim and Barra de

Mamanguape are hotspots in the Mamanguape municipality within the Barra de Mamanguape Environmental Protected Area, where visitors need to use a dirt road to access these areas (Silvestre et al., 2011). Tourism in the area has increased in recent years, with local communities constructing accommodation and developing ecotourism, like Antillean manatee watching (Barbosa & Crispim, 2015; Temoteo et al., 2018). In Cajueiro da Praia municipality, which falls within the Delta do Parnaíba Environmental Protected Area (in Piauí state), the presence of the Projeto Peixe-Boi Marinho, under the responsibility of the Aquatic Mammals Centre and ICMBio, allowed for the development of Antillean manatee watching in this area. Fishermen perform this activity during boat trips (Perinotto et al., 2008; Carvalho, 2010).

From a temporal perspective, we observed an increase in posts depicting Antillean manatees and Antillean manatee watching over the years. This finding matches the increase of Instagram users each year (Statista, 2022), the growing popularity of Antillean manatee watching (Normande et al., 2015; Braga & Selva, 2016), increasing access to mobile phones, and the development of new mobile phone camera and internet coverage technologies (Blahnik & Schindelbeck, 2021; Techterms, 2021). Thus, it is unlikely that the increase in posts depicting Antillean manatees reflects an increase in Antillean manatee population size. As expected, we observed a higher average number of manatee-related Instagram posts during the summer months compared to the other months of the year, suggesting seasonality in Antillean manatee watching in Brazil. Climate is among the factors that strongly motivate and determine tourist flow and trends (Scott & Lemieux, 2010). Thus, it is worth pointing out the potential effects of climate change on Antillean manatee watching. Climate changes may result in extreme climate events, changes in rainfall patterns, biodiversity loss, sea-level rise, beach erosion, vector-borne diseases, and insect or water-borne pests (UNWTO, 2016). Consequently, these changes may cause shifts in tourism flow in north-eastern Brazil since this area may be prone to some of these events. The seasonality of Antillean manatee watching may also be affected by the Antillean manatee reproductive season in north-eastern Brazil. This season (mating and birth season) starts in October and finishes in March in north-eastern Brazil (O’Shea et al., 2022). During this period, the Antillean manatees search for places with calm water, such as channels, lakes and rivers, to reproduce and give birth to their young ones (Hartman, 1979; O’Shea et al., 2022). During the

reproduction season, more attention must be given to possible encounters with females and their newborn calves. Although Antillean manatee strandings have been recorded during all months of the year, the highest frequency has been recorded during the summer (Balensiefer et al., 2017), matching the Antillean manatee reproductive season (O’Shea et al., 2022) and our findings of the highest frequencies of Antillean manatee watching-related Instagram posts.

Overcrowding is a consequence of tourism seasonality and can affect the target animals of this study. In most of the Instagram photo and video posts, we observed a small number of people per photo and video (i.e. 1–5 individuals). Nonetheless, these data can be underestimated as it is possible that there were more people out of the photo and video frames. The number of tourists strongly influences visitors’ satisfaction, with regards to tourism practices, where tourists are less likely to return to a destination that experiences excessive levels of use (Avila-Foucat et al., 2013; Fernandes & Rossi-Santos, 2018; Dogru-Dastan, 2022; Nie et al., 2022). The number of tourists also influences marine mammal welfare and behaviour. For instance, *Trichechus manatus* ssp. *latirostris* (Harlan, 1824) spent less time nursing and bottom-resting and more time milling when the number of swimmers and boats increased (King & Heinen, 2004). Furthermore, *T. m.* ssp. *latirostris* use protected (no-entry) sanctuaries more often when the number of swimmers and boats increases (King & Heinen, 2004). Therefore, a higher number of tourists can lead to habitat abandonment (Christiansen et al., 2014; Fiori et al., 2019). Thus, understanding how the number of people impacts Antillean manatee behaviour, and determine the maximum number of people that could cause less effects on Antillean manatee behaviour for a specific time period, may help to establish guidelines for the sustainability of this practice in Brazil and could, therefore, be the subject of future studies.

We observed several interactions between Antillean manatees and people in Brazil. At least 11 interaction types could be classified as prohibited by the Brazilian law. Even though permitted interactions were more frequent, the fact that prohibited interactions were recorded in a considerable number of photos and videos is very alarming. We observed interactions where people were in the water with the animal and even kissed and provided food and water to the Antillean manatees. This proximity is known to be dangerous as it can be the source of several diseases (Orams, 2002; Borges et al., 2009; Glasser et al., 2021; Hamme et al., 2021; Melo et al., 2022),

changes in vocal and postural behaviours (Nowacek et al., 2004; Borges et al., 2007; Rucyk et al., 2018; Brady et al., 2020; Toro et al., 2021; Umeed et al., 2018, 2022) and unwanted habituation to humans (Bach & Burton, 2017; Hutschenreiter et al., 2022; Simmonds & Nunny, 2022). As such, we believe that social media data are a key to obtain information on spontaneous interactions between people and Antillean manatees, as previously observed for other marine mammals. For instance, Sullivan et al. (2019) found a significant discrepancy when comparing the level of human-seal major disturbances between social media data and traditional datasets, where disturbance was detected 20 times more frequently in Instagram posts. Thus, we also recommend the use of the Instagram platform as a source of data on spontaneous human-manatee interactions.

We registered behaviours that can be considered as habituation, such as approaching the boat, embracing the boat and putting a flipper (forelimb) on the boat (Sorice et al., 2003; Simmonds & Nunny, 2022). Such behaviours could also be a consequence of the role of tactile signals in Antillean manatees. Antillean manatee's tactile behaviours play an important role in environmental exploration, mother-calf cohesion, and self-maintenance (Lucchini et al., 2021, 2023). Understanding the effects of viewing pressure on individual animals within a population can help manage tourist practices and ensure that target individuals or groups are protected. Papafitsoros et al. (2021) used social media data to quantify whether tourism pressure varied in *Caretta caretta* (Linnaeus, 1758) population in Laganas Bay (Greece), a loggerhead sea turtle breeding area and a popular summer tourism destination. They found that even during the breeding season, resident turtles represented most of the social media entries, indicating that operators are targeting a specific area of the bay where these individuals are more likely to be found, representing a higher risk of trauma or mortality to these animals, as the authors observed through photo-identification of carapace damage.

Conclusions

Our study detected the occurrence of Antillean manatee watching in Brazil in 91 locations, six of which could be considered hotspots for this economically positive activity for local communities. We also detected several prohibited interactions between humans and Antillean manatees at these localities, revealing a lack of compliance with existing Brazilian regulations. The mapped locations, especially the hotspot areas, should be the target of environmental education campaigns and good-conduct

recycling courses for local guides to assure the long-term sustainability of Antillean manatee watching. We recommend that good-conduct recycling courses focus on human-animal proximity and the behaviour of tour guide operators. We suggest periodical data mining from the Instagram platform to evaluate public attitudes towards threatened species, such as Antillean manatees, to guide management strategies, such as expand protection and inspection actions in the most affected areas. Areas with high incidence of prohibited behaviour should be targeted by government inspections and environmental education actions. This may allow for the monitoring of Antillean manatee watching tourism in near real-time, providing updated information for decision-makers.

Acknowledgements

We thank all Instagram users whose posts have made this study possible. We thank the professors João Feitosa, José Botelho, and Vanice Selva (all – Federal University of Pernambuco, Brazil) for their comments on an early draft of this paper. Paula D.F. Coutinho was funded by a scholarship from FACEPE (IBPG-0883-2.05/19) and CAPES (Financial Code 001). Ana L.L. Matte was funded by CNPq (SET 1-F) and a CAPES scholarship (Financial Code 001). Bruna Bezerra and the entire study were supported by FACEPE (BFT-01602.04/17; BFT-0014-2.05/20; APQ-1230-2.05/22; BCT-0667-2.04/22) and CNPq productive grant (309256/2019-4).

Supporting Information

Municipalities (Electronic Supplement 1. Municipalities reported in social network posts depicting Antillean manatees and manatee-watching in northern and north-eastern Brazil from April 2013 to August 2022) and specific localities (Electronic Supplement 2. Specific localities reported in social network posts depicting Antillean manatees and manatee-watching in northern and north-eastern Brazil from April 2013 to August 2022) reported in social network posts depicting *Trichechus manatus manatus* in northern and north-eastern Brazil, together with characteristics of the manatee-watching hotspots municipalities (Electronic Supplement 3. Characteristics of the manatee-watching hotspots municipalities) may be found in the [Supporting Information](#).

References

- Altmann J. 1974. Observational Study of Behavior: Sampling Methods. *Behaviour* 49(3/4): 227–266. DOI: 10.1163/156853974x00534
- Alves M.D.O., Kinas P.G., Marmontel M., Borges J.C.G., Costa A.F., Schiel N., Araújo M.E. 2016. First abundance estimate of the Antillean manatee (*Trichechus mana-*

- tus manatus*) in Brazil by aerial survey. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 96(4): 955–966. DOI: 10.1017/S0025315415000855
- Asdecker B. 2022. Travel-related influencer content on Instagram: How social media fuels wanderlust and how to mitigate the effect. *Sustainability* 14(2): 885. DOI: 10.3390/su14020855
- Auster R.E., Barr S.W., Brazier R.E. 2020. Wildlife tourism in reintroduction projects: Exploring social and economic benefits of beaver in local settings. *Journal for Nature Conservation* 58: 125920. DOI: 10.1016/j.jnc.2020.125920
- Avila-Foucat V.S., Sánchez Vargas A., Frisch-Jordán A., Ramírez Flores O.M. 2013. The impact of vessel crowding on the probability of tourists returning to whale watching in Banderas Bay, Mexico. *Ocean and Coastal Management* 78: 12–17. DOI: 10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2013.03.002
- Bach L., Burton M. 2017. Proximity and animal welfare in the context of tourist interactions with habituated dolphins. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 25(2): 181–197. DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2016.1195835
- Balensiefer D.C., Attademo F.L.N., Souza G.P., Freire A.C.B., da Cunha F.A.G.C., Alencar A.E.B., Silva F.J.L., Luna F.O. 2017. Three decades of Antillean Manatee (*Trichechus manatus manatus*) stranding along the Brazilian coast. *Tropical Conservation Science* 10(1): 1–9. DOI: 10.1177/1940082917728375
- Ballantyne R., Packer J., Sutherland L.A. 2011. Visitors' memories of wildlife tourism: Implications for the design of powerful interpretive experiences. *Tourism Management* 32(4): 770–779. DOI: 10.1016/j.tourman.2010.06.012
- Barbosa I.K.P., Crispim M.C. 2015. Potencialidades para o ecoturismo e etnoturismo na aldeia potiguara de Tramataia, APA da Barra do Rio Mamanguape (PB). *Revista Brasileira de Ecoturismo* 8(1): 176–192. DOI: 10.34024/rbecotur.2015.v8.6333
- Barros C., Gutiérrez J., García-Palomares J. 2022. Geotagged data from social media in visitor monitoring of protected areas; a scoping review. *Current Issues in Tourism* 25(9): 1399–1415. DOI: 10.1080/13683500.2021.1931053
- Becken S., Stantic B., Chen J., Alaei A.R., Connolly R.M. 2017. Monitoring the environment and human sentiment on the Great Barrier Reef: Assessing the potential of collective sensing. *Journal of Environmental Management* 203(1): 87–97. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2017.07.007
- Bejder L., Samuels A., Whitehead H., Gales N., Mann J., Connor R., Heithaus M., Watson-Capps J., Flaherty C., Krützen M. 2006. Decline in relative abundance of bottlenose dolphins exposed to long-term disturbance. *Conservation Biology* 20(6): 1791–1798. DOI: 10.1111/j.1523-1739.2006.00540.x
- Bejder L., Higham J.E.S., Lusseau D. 2022. Tourism and research impacts on marine mammals: a bold future informed by research and technology. In: G.N. di Sciara, B. Wursig (Eds.): *Marine Mammals: the Evolving Human Factor*. Switzerland: Springer Nature. P. 255–275. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-98100-6_8
- Blahnik V., Schindelbeck O. 2021. Smartphone imaging technology and its applications. *Advanced Optical Technologies* 10(3): 145–232. DOI: 10.1515/aot-2021-0023
- Borges J.C.G., Vergara-Parente J.E., Alvite C.M.C., Marcondes M.C.C., Lima R.P. 2007. Embarcações motorizadas: uma ameaça aos peixes-boi marinhos (*Trichechus manatus*) no Brasil. *Biota Neotropica* 7(3): 199–204. DOI: 10.1590/S1676-06032007000300021
- Borges J.C.G., Alves L.C., Vergara-Parente J.E., Faustino M.A.G., Machado E.C.L. 2009. Ocorrência de infecção *Cryptosporidium* spp. em peixe-boi marinho (*Trichechus manatus*). *Revista Brasileira de Parasitologia Veterinária* 18(1): 60–61. DOI: 10.4322/rbpv.01801011
- Brady B., Hedwig D., Trygonis V., Gerstein E. 2020. Classification of Florida manatee (*Trichechus manatus latirostris*) vocalizations. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America* 147(3): 1597–1606. DOI: 10.1121/10.0000849
- Braga M.B., Selva V.S.F. 2016. O Turismo de base comunitária pode ser um caminho para o desenvolvimento Local?. *Rede – Revista Eletrônica do PRODEMA* 10(1): 38–53.
- Carvalho S.M.S. 2010. A Percepção do turismo por parte da comunidade local e dos turistas no município de Cajueiro da Praia – PI. *Turismo em Análise* 21(3): 470–493. DOI: 10.11606/issn.1984-4867.v21i3p470-493
- Cecchetti A., Stockin K.A., Gordon J., Azevedo J.M.N. 2018. Short-term effects of tourism on the behaviour of common dolphins (*Delphinus delphis*) in the Azores. *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 98(5): 1187–1196. DOI: 10.1017/S0025315417000674
- Charles A., Henaut Y., Jalme M.S., Mulot B., Lecu A., Delfour F. 2022. Studying Antillean manatees' (*Trichechus manatus manatus*) temperament in zoological parks: exploration of boldness, sociality and reactivity to humans. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science* 246: 105512. DOI: 10.1016/j.applanim.2021.105512
- Cheung S.Y., Leung Y.F., Larson L.R. 2022. Citizen science as a tool for enhancing recreation research in protected areas: Applications and opportunities. *Journal of Environmental Management* 305: 114353. DOI: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2021.114353
- Christiansen F., Rasmussen M.H., Leusseau D. 2014. Inferring energy expenditure from respiration rates in minke whales to measure the effects of whale watching boat interactions. *Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology* 459: 96–104. DOI: 10.1016/j.jembe.2014.05.014
- CPTEC/INPE. 2022. *Centro de Previsão de Tempo e Estudos Climáticos*. Available from <https://clima1.cptec.inpe.br/estacoes>
- Cranswick A.S., Constantine R., Hendriks H., Carroll E.L. 2022. Social media and citizen science records are important for the management of rarely sighted whales. *Ocean and Coastal Management* 226: 106271. DOI: 10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2022.106271
- Datavyu Team. 2014. *Datavyu: A Video Coding Tool. Data-rary Project*. New York: New York University. Available from <http://datavyu.org>
- Dembovska I.Z.A., Zvaigzne A. 2021. Sustainability and its challenges in destinations that highly depend on tourism: a thematic literature review. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes* 13(6): 697–708. DOI: 10.1108/WHATT-07-2021-0098

- Deutsch C.J., Self-Sullivan C., Mignucci-Giannoni A. 2008. *Trichechus manatus*. In: *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2008: e.T22103A9356917*. Available from <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2008.RLTS.T22103A9356917.en>
- Di Minin E., Fink C., Hiippala T., Tenkanen H. 2019. A framework for investigating illegal wildlife trade on social media with machine learning. *Conservation Biology* 33(1): 210–213. DOI: 10.1111/cobi.13104
- Dickison J.L., Shirk J., Bonter D., Bonney R., Crain R.L., Martin J., Phillips T., Purcell K. 2012. The current state of citizen science as a tool for ecological research and public engagement. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 10(6): 291–297. DOI: 10.1890/110236
- Dogru-Dastan H. 2022. A chronological review on perceptions of crowding in tourism and recreation. *Tourism Recreation Research* 47(2): 190–210. DOI: 10.1080/02508281.2020.1841373
- Duffus D.A., Dearden P. 1990. Non-consumptive wildlife-oriented recreation: A Conceptual Framework. *Biological Conservation* 53(3): 213–231. DOI: 10.1016/0006-3207(90)90087-6
- Eryaşar A.R., Saygu İ. 2022. Using social media to identify recreational bluefish angling in the Mediterranean and Black Sea. *Marine Policy* 135: 104834. DOI: 10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104834
- Favero I.T., Favero G.E., Choi-Lima K.F., Santos H.F., Souza-Alves J.P., Silva J.S., Feitosa J.L.L. 2020. Effects of freshwater limitation on distribution patterns and habitat use of the West Indian manatee, *Trichechus manatus*, in the northern Brazilian coast. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 30(8): 1665–1673. DOI: 10.1002/aqc.3363
- Fernandes L., Rossi-Santos M.R. 2018. An integrated framework to assess the carrying capacity of Humpback whale-watching tourism in Praia do Forte, Northeastern Brazil. In: M. Rossi-Santos, C. Finkl (Eds.): *Advances in Marine Vertebrate Research in Latin America*. Vol. 22. Cham: Springer. P. 41–73. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-319-56985-7_3
- Fiori L., Martinez E., Orams M.B., Bollard B. 2019. Effects of whale-based tourism in Vava'u, Kingdom of Tonga: Behavioural responses of humpback whales to vessel and swimming tourism activities. *PLoS ONE* 14(7): e0219364. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0219364
- Fumagalli M., Guerra M., Brough T., Carome W., Constantine R., Higham J., Rayment W., Slooten E., Stockin K., Dawson S. 2021. Looking back to move forward: Lessons From three decades of research and management of Cetacean tourism in New Zealand. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8: 624448. DOI: 10.3389/fmars.2021.624448
- Garcia C. 2017. *O que é o nordeste brasileiro (first ed.)*. Brasília: Editora Brasiliense. 65 p.
- Glasser D.B., Goldberg T.L., Guma N., Balyesiima G.B., Agaba H., Gessa S.J., Rothman J.M. 2021. Opportunities for respiratory disease transmission from people to chimpanzees at an East African tourism site. *American Journal of Primatology* 83(2): e23228. DOI: 10.1002/ajp.23228
- Gomes F.F.A., Vergara-Parente J.E., Ferrari S.F. 2008. Behaviour patterns in captive manatees (*Trichechus manatus*) at Itamaracá Island, Brazil. *Aquatic Mammals* 34(3): 269–276. DOI: 10.1578/AM.34.3.2008.269
- Hamme G.V., Svensson M.S., Morcatty T.Q., Nekaris K.A. 2021. Keep your distance: Using Instagram posts to evaluate the risk of anthroponotic disease transmission in gorilla ecotourism. *People and Nature* 3(2): 325–334. DOI: 10.1002/pan3.10187
- Hartman D.S. 1979. *Ecology and behavior of the manatee (Trichechus manatus) in Florida*. American Society of Mammalogists, Special Publication 5. New York: Cornell University. 153 p.
- Hausmann A., Toivonen T., Slotow R., Tenkanen H., Moilanen A., Heikinheimo V., Di Minin E. 2018. Social media data can be used to understand tourists' preferences for nature-based experiences in Protected Areas. *Conservation Letters* 11(1): e12343. DOI: 10.1111/conl.12343
- Higham J.E.S., Bejder L., Lusseau D. 2008. An integrated and adaptive management model to address the long-term sustainability of tourist interactions with cetaceans. *Environmental Conservation* 35(4): 294–302. DOI: 10.1017/S0376892908005249
- Hunt C.A., Durham W.H., Driscoll L., Honey M. 2015. Can ecotourism deliver real economic, social, and environmental benefits? A study of the Osa Peninsula, Costa Rica. *Journal of Sustainable Tourism* 23(3): 339–357. DOI: 10.1080/09669582.2014.965176
- Hutschenreiter A., Kalan A.K., Moheno M.B., Mávil J.E.M., Mandujano S., Jaramillo M.B., Spann D., Aureli F. 2022. Spider Monkeys (*Ateles geoffroyi*) Habituate to anthropogenic pressure in a low-impact tourism area: Insights from a multi-method approach. *International Journal of Primatology* 43(5): 946–964. DOI: 10.1007/s10764-022-00310-1
- IBGE. 2021. *Instituto Brasileiro de Geografia e Estatística. Malha Municipal Digital*. Rio de Janeiro: IBGE. Available from <https://www.ibge.gov.br/geociencias/organizacao-do-territorio/malhas-territoriais/15774-malhas.html>
- ICMBio. 2013. *Instituto Chico Mendes de Conservação da Biodiversidade. Portaria №144, de 04 de Fevereiro de 2013. Plano de Manejo da Área de Proteção Ambiental da Costa dos Corais*. Available from https://www.icmbio.gov.br/cepsul/images/stories/legislacao/Portaria/2013/p_icmbio_144_2013_planodemanejo_apacostadoscorais_pe_al.pdf
- ICMBio. 2018a. *Instituto Chico Mendes de Conservação da Biodiversidade. Turismo de base comunitária em unidades de conservação federais: princípios e diretrizes*. Available from https://ava.icmbio.gov.br/pluginfile.php/4592/mod_data/content/19095/turismo_de_base_comunitaria_em_uc_2017.pdf
- ICMBio. 2018b. *Instituto Chico Mendes de Conservação da Biodiversidade. Portaria №249, de 4 de abril de 2018. Plano Nacional para conservação do peixe-boi marinho*. Available from <https://www.gov.br/icmbio/pt-br/assuntos/biodiversidade/pan/pan-peixe-boi-marinho/1-ciclo/pan-peixe-boi-marinho-portaria-aprovacao.pdf>
- ICMBio. 2021. *Instituto Chico Mendes de Conservação da Biodiversidade. Portaria №308, de 21 de julho de 2021. Plano de Manejo da Área de Proteção Ambiental da Costa*

- dos Corais. Available from https://www.icmbio.gov.br/aparostadoscorais/images/stories/PM_APACC_2021.pdf
- Izidoro F.B., Shiavetti A. 2022. Associated benefits of manatee watching in the Costa dos Corais Environmental Protection Area. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 9: 1002855. DOI: 10.3389/fmars.2022.1002855
- Jeawak S.S., Jones C.B., Schockaert S. 2018. Mapping wildlife species distribution with social media: Augmenting text classification with species names. In: *International Conference of Geographic Information Science*. Vol. 45. P. 34:1–34:6. DOI: 10.4230/LIPics.GISCIENCE.2018.34
- Kim G.S., Chun J., Kim Y., Kim C.K. 2021. Coastal tourism spatial planning at the regional unit: Identifying coastal tourism hotspots based on social media data. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* 10(3): 167. DOI: 10.3390/ijgi10030167
- King J.M., Heinen J.T. 2004. An assessment of the behaviors of overwintering manatees as influenced by interactions with tourists at two sites in central Florida. *Biological Conservation* 117(3): 227–234. DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2003.07.001
- Kroetz A.M., Brame A.B., Bernanke M., McDavitt M.T., Wiley T.R. 2021. Tracking public interest and perceptions about smalltooth sawfish conservation in the USA using Instagram. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Freshwater Ecosystems* 31(10): 2901–2909. DOI: 10.1002/aqc.3680
- Lebrão C., Rosa L.M.V., Paim F.P., Nassar P.M., El Bizri H.R., Silva F.E. 2021. Community-based ecotourism and primate watching as a conservation toll in the Amazon Rainforests. *International Journal of Primatology* 42: 523–527. DOI: 10.1007/s10764-021-00226-2
- Leitão A.T.T.S., Alves M.D.O., Santos J.C.P., Bezerra B. 2022. Instagram as a data source for sea turtle surveys in shipwrecks in Brazil. *Animal Conservation* 25(6): 736–747. DOI: 10.1111/acv.12802
- Lepre P.R. 2018. Service design for community based tourism – The Brazilian case study. In: *Linköping Electronic Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 150. Milan: Linköping University Electronic Press. P. 940–953.
- Lima R.P., Paludo D., Soavinski R.J., da Silva K.G., Oliveira E.M.A. 2011. Levantamento da distribuição, ocorrência e status de conservação do peixe-boi marinho (*Trichechus manatus*, Linnaeus, 1758) no litoral nordeste do Brasil. *Natural Resources* 1(2): 41–57. DOI: 10.6008/ESS2237-9290.2011.002.0006
- Lin C., Kuo B.Z. 2016. The Behavioral Consequences of Tourist Experience. *Tourism Management Perspectives* 18: 84–91. DOI: 10.1016/j.tmp.2015.12.017
- Lucchini K., Umeed R., Guimarães L., Santos P., Sommer I., Bezerra B. 2021. The role of touch in captive and semi-captive Antillean manatees (*Trichechus manatus manatus*). *Behaviour* 158(3/4): 291–313. DOI: 10.1163/1568539X-bja10069
- Lucchini K., Umeed R., Santos P.J.P., Attademo F.L.N., Luna F.O., Bezerra B. 2023. Tactile responses to environmental enrichment in captive Antillean manatees (*Trichechus manatus manatus*). *Applied Animal Behaviour Science* 261: 105879. DOI: 10.1016/j.applanim.2023.105879
- Luna F.O., Lima R.P., Araújo J.P., Passavante J.Z.O. 2008. Status de conservação do peixe-boi marinho (*Trichechus manatus manatus* Linnaeus, 1758) no Brasil. *Revista Brasileira de Zootecias* 10(2): 145–153.
- Luna F.O., Attademo F.L.N., Soares M.L., Paiva Jr.L.H., Zanoni S.A., Cunha F.A.G. 2022. *Manual de boas práticas de interação com Sirênios no Brasil*. Brasília: ICMBio. 27 p.
- Lusseau D., Bejder L. 2007. The Long-term Consequences of Short-term Responses to Disturbance Experiences from Whalewatching Impact Assessment. *International Journal of Comparative Psychology* 20(2): 228–236. DOI: 10.46867/ijcp.2007.20.02.04
- Machernis A.F., Powell J.R., Engleby L.K., Spradlin T.R. 2018. *An updated literature review examining the impacts of tourism on marine mammals over the last fifteen years (2000–2015) to inform research and management programs*. NOAA Technical Memorandum NMFS-SER-7. USA: National Marine Fish Service, U.S. Department of Commerce. 66 p. DOI: 10.7289/V5/TM-NMFS-SER-7
- Marega-Imamura M., Carvalho G.H., Le Pendu Y., da Silva P.S., Schiavetti A. 2018. Behavioral responses of *Sotalia guianensis* (Cetartiodactyla, Delphinidae) to boat approaches in northeast Brazil. *Latin American Journal of Aquatic Research* 46(2): 268–279. DOI: 10.3856/vol46-issue2-fulltext-3
- Melo F.L., Bezerra B., Luna F.O., Barragan N.A.N., Arcoverde R.M.L., Umeed R., Lucchini K., Attademo F.L.N. 2022. Coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) in Antillean manatees (*Trichechus manatus manatus*). In: *Research Square*. Available from <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-1065379/v1>
- MMA. 2022. *Portaria MMA Nº148, de 07 de Junho de 2022*. Available from <https://in.gov.br/en/web/dou/-/portaria-mma-n-148-de-7-de-junho-de-2022-406272733>
- Mortensen L.O., Chudzinska M.E., Slabbekoorn H., Thomsen F. 2021. Agent-based models to investigate sound impact on marine animals: bridging the gap between effects on individual behaviour and population level consequences. *Oikos* 130(7): 1074–1086. DOI: 10.1111/oik.08078
- Nie Z., Xu L., Zhang H., Cao Y., Zhang C., Pan J., Zhang J. 2022. Crowding and vaccination: Tourist's two-sided perception on crowding and the moderating effect of vaccination status during COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Destination Marketing and Management* 24: 100705. DOI: 10.1016/j.jdmm.2022.100705
- Normande I.C., Luna F.O., Malhado A.C.M., Borges J.C.G., Viana Junior P.C., Attademo F.L.N., Ladle R.J. 2015. Eighteen years of Antillean manatee *Trichechus manatus manatus* releases in Brazil: lessons learnt. *Oryx* 49(2): 338–344. DOI: 10.1017/S0030605313000896
- Nowacek S.M., Wells R.S., Owen E.C.G., Speakman T.R., Flamm R.O., Nowacek D.P. 2004. Florida manatees, *Trichechus manatus latirostris*, respond to approaching vessels. *Biological Conservation* 119(4): 517–523. DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2003.11.020
- O'Connor S., Campbell R., Knowles T., Cortez H., Grey F., Hoyt E., Iñiguez M. 2009. *Whale watching worldwide. Tourism numbers, expenditures and expanding economic benefits. A special report*. Yarmouth MA, USA: International Fund for Animal Welfare. 295 p.

- O'Shea T.J., Beck C.A., Hodgson A.J., Keith-Diagne L., Marmontel M. 2022. Social and reproductive behaviors. In: H. Masch (Ed.): *Ethology and Behavioral Ecology of Sirenia*. Cham: Springer. P. 101–154. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-90742-6_4
- Orams M.B. 2002. Feeding wildlife as a tourism attraction: a review of issues and impacts. *Tourism Management* 23(3): 281–293. DOI: 10.1016/S0261-5177(01)00080-2
- Orsi F., Geneletti D. 2013. Using geotagged photographs and GIS analysis to estimate visitor flows in natural areas. *Journal for Nature Conservation* 21(5): 359–368. DOI: 10.1016/j.jnc.2013.03.001
- Palazzo M., Vollero A., Vitale P., Siano A. 2021. Urban and rural destinations on Instagram: Exploring the influencers' role in #sustainabletourism. *Land Use Policy* 100: 104915. DOI: 10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104915
- Papafitsoros K., Panagopoulou A., Schofield G. 2021. Social media reveals consistently disproportionate tourism pressure on a threatened marine vertebrate. *Animal Conservation* 24(4): 568–579. DOI: 10.1111/acv.12656
- Papafitsoros K., Adam L., Schofield G. 2023. A social media-based framework for quantifying temporal changes to wildlife viewing intensity. *Ecological Modelling* 476: 110223. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2022.110223
- Pegas F.V., Coghlan A., Stronza A., Rocha V. 2013. For love or for money? Investigating the impact of an ecotourism programme on local residents' assigned values towards sea turtles. *Journal of Ecotourism* 12(2): 90–106. DOI: 10.1080/14724049.2013.831099
- Perinotto A.R.C., Santos B.R., Santos M.S. 2008. Comunicação turística no município de Cajueiro da Praia-Piauí/Brasil. *Educação, Cultura e Comunicação* 8(16): 23–41.
- Ponnampalam L.S., Keith-Diagne L., Marmontel M., Marshall C.D., Reep R.L., Powell J., Marsh H. 2022. Historical and current interactions with humans. In: H. Masch (Ed.): *Ethology and Behavioral Ecology of Sirenia*. Cham: Springer. P. 299–349. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-90742-6_7
- Rycyk A.M., Deutsch C.J., Barlas M.E., Hardy S.K., Frisch K., Leone E.H., Nowacek D.P. 2018. Manatee behavioral response to boats. *Marine Mammal Science* 34(4): 924–962. DOI: 10.1111/mms.12491
- Santos S.S., Medeiros I.S., Rebelo V.A., Carvalho B., Dubut J.P., Mantovani J.E., Círiaco R.D., dos Santos R.E.G., Marmontel M., Normande I.C., Veloso T.M.G., Borges J.C.G. 2022. Home ranges of released West Indian manatees *Trichechus manatus* in Brazil. *Oryx* 56(6): 939–946. DOI: 10.1017/S003060532100079X
- Scott D., Lemieux C. 2010. Weather and Climate Information for Tourism. *Procedia Environmental Sciences* 1: 146–183. DOI: 10.1016/j.proenv.2010.09.011
- Self-Sullivan C., Mignucci-Giannoni A. 2008. *Trichechus manatus* ssp. *manatus*. In: *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2008: e.T22105A9359161*. Available from <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2008.RLTS.T22105A9359161.en>
- Shuqair S., Cragg P. 2017. The immediate impact of Instagram posts on changing the viewers' perceptions towards travel destinations. *Asia Pacific Journal of Advanced Business and Social Studies* 3(2). DOI: 10.25275/apjabssv3i2bus1
- Silvestre L.C., Farias D.L.S., Lourenço S.J.D., Barros S.C.A., Braga N.M.P. 2011. Diagnóstico dos impactos ambientais advindo de atividades antrópicas na APA da Barra do Rio Mamanguape. *Enciclopédia Bioesfera, Centro Científico Conhecer* 7(12): 1–11.
- Simmonds M.P., Nunny L. 2022. Marine mammals seeking human company. In: G. Notarbartolo di Sciarra, B. Würsig (Eds.): *Marine Mammals: the Evolving Human Factor*. Cham: Springer. P. 307–335. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-030-98100-6_10
- Šmelhausová J., Riepe C., Jarić I., Essl F. 2022. How Instagram users influence nature conservation: A case study on protected areas in Central Europe. *Biological Conservation* 276: 109787. DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2022.109787
- Sorice M., Shafer C.S., Scott D. 2003. Managing endangered species within the use/preservation paradox: Understanding and defining harassment of the West Indian Manatee (*Trichechus manatus*). *Coastal Management* 31(4): 319–338. DOI: 10.1080/08920750390232983
- Statista. 2022. *Number of monthly active Instagram users from January 2013 to December 2021*. Available from <https://www.statista.com/statistics/253577/number-of-monthly-active-instagram-users/>
- Stronza A., Pêgas F. 2008. Ecotourism and conservation: Two Cases from Brazil and Peru. *Human Dimensions of Wildlife* 13(4): 263–279. DOI: 10.1080/10871200802187097
- Stronza A.L., Hunt C.A., Fitzgerald L.A. 2019. Ecotourism for Conservation?. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* 44: 229–253. DOI: 10.1146/annurev-environ-101718-033046
- Sullivan M., Robinson S., Littnan C. 2019. Social media as a data resource for #monkseal conservation. *PLoS ONE* 14(10): e0222627. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0222627
- Techterms. 2021. *Smartphones vs cameras: Closing the gap on image quality*. Available from <https://www.dxomark.com/smartphones-vs-cameras-closing-the-gap-on-image-quality/>
- Temoteo J.A.G., Brandão J.M.F., Crispim M.C. 2018. Turismo e Sustentabilidade em Unidades de Conservação: Um Estudo sobre as Alternativas de Emprego e Renda na Área de Proteção Ambiental da Barra do Rio Mamanguape-PB. *Revista de Gestão Ambiental e Sustentabilidade* 7(1): 43–61. DOI: 10.5585/geas.v7i1.552
- Tenkanen H., Di Minin E., Heikinheimo V., Hausmann A., Herbst M., Kajala L., Toivonen T. 2017. Instagram, flickr, or twitter: assessing the usability of social media data for visitor monitoring in protected areas. *Scientific Reports* 7(1): 17615. DOI: 10.1038/s41598-017-18007-4
- Thurstan R.H., Hawkins J.P., Neves L., Roberts C.M. 2012. Are marine reserves and non-consumptive activities compatible? A global analysis of marine reserve regulations. *Marine Policy* 36(5): 1096–1104. DOI: 10.1016/j.marpol.2012.03.006
- Tisdell C., Wilson C. 2005. Perceive impacts of ecotourism on environmental learning and Conservation: Turtle watching as a case of study. *Environment, Development and Sustainability* 7(3): 291–302. DOI: 10.1007/s10668-004-7619-6
- Toivonen T., Heikinheimo V., Fink C., Hausmann A., Hiipala T., Järv O., Tenkanen H., Di Minin E. 2019. Social media data for conservation science: A methodological

- overview. *Biological Conservation* 233: 298–315. DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2019.01.023
- Toro F., Alarcón J., Toro-Barros B., Mallea G., Capella J., Umaran-Young C., Abarca P., Lakestani N., Peña C., Alavarado-Rybak M., Cruz F., Vilina Y., Gibbons J. 2021. Spatial and temporal effects of whale watching on a tourism-naïve resident population of bottlenose dolphins (*Tursiops truncatus*) in the Humboldt Penguin National Reserve, Chile. *Frontiers in Marine Science* 8: 624974. DOI: 10.3389/fmars.2021.624974
- Umeed R., Attademo F.L.N., Bezerra B. 2018. The influence of age and sex on the vocal repertoire of the Antillean manatee (*Trichechus manatus manatus*) and their responses to call playback. *Marine Mammal Science* 34(3): 577–594. DOI: 10.1111/mms.12467
- Umeed R., Lucchini K., Santos P.J.P., Attademo F., Luna F., Normande I., Bezerra B. 2022. Vocal complexity in Antillean manatees (*Trichechus manatus manatus*). *Behaviour* 160(3/4): 217–256. DOI: 10.1163/1568539X-bja1019
- UNWTO. 2016. *Tourism Highlights, 2016 Edition*. Madrid: UNWTO. Available from www.e-unwto.org/doi/pdf/10.18111/9789284418145
- Vărzaru A.A., Bocean C.G., Cazacu M. 2021. Rethinking tourism industry in pandemic COVID-19 Period. *Sustainability* 13(12): 6956. DOI: 10.3390/su13126956
- Ventura M., Costa A.C., Botelho A.Z. 2022. Community engagement with tourism management in small Atlantic islands. In: S.L. Slocum, P. Wiltshier, J.B. Read IV (Eds.): *Tourism Transformations in Protected Area Gateway Communities*. UK: CABI. P. 85–194. DOI: 10.1079/9781789249033.0007
- Wyatt T., Miralles O., Massé F., Lima R., Costa T.V., Giovanini D. 2022. Wildlife trafficking via social media in Brazil. *Biological Conservation* 265: 109420. DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2021.109420
- Zimmerhackel J.S., Kragt M.E., Rogers A.A., Ali K., Meekan M.G. 2019. Evidence of increased economic benefits from shark-diving tourism in the Maldives. *Marine Policy* 100: 21–26. DOI: 10.1016/j.marpol.2018.11.004

НАБЛЮДЕНИЯ ЗА ЛАМАНТИНАМИ ШИРОКО РАСПРОСТРАНЕНЫ И ПОДВЕРЖЕНЫ СЕЗОННЫМ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯМ НА СЕВЕРО-ВОСТОКЕ БРАЗИЛИИ НА ПРИМЕРЕ ИСЧЕЗАЮЩЕГО (EN) *TRICHECHUS MANATUS MANATUS* (SIRENIA: TRICHECHIDAE)

П. Д. Ф. Котинью

Федеральный университет Пернамбуку, Бразилия
e-mail: paula.djanira@ufpe.br, analuiza.matte@ufpe.br, bruna.bezerra@ufpe.br

Наблюдение за морскими млекопитающими является рациональным туристическим подходом, ориентированным на дикую природу. *Trichechus manatus manatus* (далее – ламантин) являются примером харизматических видов морской мегафауны, являясь объектом наблюдений во многих пунктах, где вид встречается. В данной работе были изучены наблюдения за ламантинами в Бразилии, сосредоточив внимание на картографировании наблюдений в стране, выявлении горячих точек, анализе потенциальной сезонности этой практики и оценке взаимодействия между людьми и ламантинами. В качестве источника данных мы использовали одну из широко используемых социальных сетей, поскольку этот вид часто появляется в ее постах. Ламантин харизматичен и обладает характеристиками, которые привлекают публичное внимание, такими как большой размер тела, нежное поведение и привлекательный внешний вид. Наблюдения за ламантинами были отмечены в 91 локалитете, расположенном в 19 муниципалитетах и девяти штатах севера и северо-востока Бразилии. Шесть локалитетов были приняты за горячие точки наблюдений за ламантинами из-за большого количества связанных с ними изображений. Пять горячих точек были расположены на трех особо охраняемых природных территориях для устойчивого использования. Было отмечено до 23 человек на одной фотографии, связанной с ламантином, размещенной в социальной сети; но в большинстве постов (фото и видео) фигурировало до пяти человек. Кроме того, изображения значимо чаще публиковались в летние месяцы, что указывает на сезонность наблюдений за ламантинами. Собранные наблюдения за ламантинами были классифицированы как запрещенные или разрешенные законодательством Бразилии. Разрешенные взаимодействия происходили значимо чаще, но возникновение запрещенных взаимодействий свидетельствует о текущем несоблюдении природоохраняемых законов Бразилии. Мы предлагаем, чтобы в стратегиях управления туризмом приоритет отдавался наблюдению за ламантинами в горячих точках, уделяя особое внимание усилению соблюдения местного законодательства и предпочтительному привлечению местных жителей для обеспечения устойчивости этой практики в Бразилии.

Ключевые слова: взаимодействие человека и дикой природы, дикая природа, поведение в путешествии, сирены, устойчивое развитие туризма, экотуризм

ВОЗРАСТНАЯ СТРУКТУРА И РОСТ *BUFO VERRUCOSISSIMUS* (AMPHIBIA, ANURA, BUFONIDAE) В КAVKAZСКОМ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОМ ПРИРОДНОМ БИОСФЕРНОМ ЗАПОВЕДНИКЕ (РОССИЯ) В КОНЦЕ XX ВЕКА

А. А. Кидов^{1,*} ,
К. А. Магушкина¹

¹Российский государственный аграрный университет – МСХА имени К.А. Тимирязева, Россия
*e-mail: kidov@rgau-msha.ru

²Сочинский национальный парк, Россия

Поступила: 26.06.2023. Исправлена: 03.10.2023. Принята к опубликованию: 05.10.2023.

В Российской Федерации *Bufo verrucosissimus* является видом, находящимся под угрозой исчезновения. Одной из крупнейших особо охраняемых природных территорий, на которой обитает *B. verrucosissimus*, является Кавказский государственный природный биосферный заповедник. В работе представлены данные о возрастной структуре и росте особей этого вида, собранных в Кавказском государственном природном биосферном заповеднике в 1987–1990 гг. и хранящихся в коллекции Сочинского национального парка. Возраст 16 самок и 51 самца определяли при помощи метода скелетохронологии. Возраст взрослых самок составил 6–10 лет (в среднем 7.9 лет), а самцов 2–9 лет (в среднем 5.8 лет). По среднему возрасту самки статистически значимо превосходили самцов. По длине тела достоверные различия между самцами и самками были отмечены в группах семилетних и девятилетних животных. Длина тела изученных животных (60.8–116.4 мм для самок и 61.2–86.3 мм для самцов) соответствует размерам взрослых особей *B. verrucosissimus* из других локалитетов на Северном Кавказе. Самки равномерно растут в течение всей жизни, тогда как рост самцов существенно замедляется после достижения половой зрелости. Самцы оказались способны достигать предельной длины тела быстрее, чем самки (коэффициент роста составил 0.722 для самцов и 0.163 для самок). Согласно уравнению фон Бергаланфи, максимально возможная длина тела составила 130.9 мм для самок и 74.6 мм для самцов.

Ключевые слова: бесхвостые земноводные, демография, коэффициент роста, продолжительность жизни, Северный Кавказ, скелетохронология

Введение

Исследование возрастной структуры популяций животных является важнейшим этапом для разработки мероприятий по их охране и управлению (Legendre, 2004). Наиболее широко распространенным методом определения возраста амфибий на протяжении более чем полувека остается скелетохронология (Клейненберг, Смирина, 1969). К настоящему времени были изучены возрастная структура и особенности роста у десятков видов, однако в большинстве своем скелетохронологическими исследованиями были охвачены наиболее многочисленные из них (Smirina, 1994; Sinsch, 2015; Клевезаль, Смирина, 2016). При этом метод позволяет определять возраст у животных из музейных коллекций, собранных в природе десятилетия и даже столетия назад, выявлять влияние различных факторов за эти периоды на динамику демографических показателей (Ehret, 2007).

Bufo verrucosissimus (Pallas, 1914) последние 30–40 лет принадлежит к числу интенсивно изучаемых амфибий Палеарктики. В прошлом

этот таксон считался кавказским подвигом широко распространенного в лесном поясе Северной Евразии вида *Bufo bufo* Linnaeus, 1758 (Терентьев, Чернов, 1949; Банников и др., 1977). Но к концу XX в. сформировалось представление о *B. verrucosissimus*, как о самостоятельном виде, эндемике лесов колхидского типа и их дериватов на Западном Кавказе (Боркин, 1987; Орлова, Туниев, 1989). Относившихся ранее к этому таксону особей из Гирканики (прикаспийские склоны Талыша и Эльбурса, Ленкоранская и Южно-Каспийская низменности) в последующем описали как самостоятельный вид *Bufo eichwaldi* Litvinchuk, Rosanov, Borkin & Skorinov, 2008 (Litvinchuk et al., 2008), валидность которой признается большинством авторов (Recuero et al., 2012; Kidov et al., 2020). Проведение специальных молекулярно-генетических исследований позволило предполагать конспецифичность серых жаб Колхиды и Леванта (северо-запад Сирии, Ливан, юго-восток Турции) (Jablonski & Sadek, 2019), а также обнаружить зоны интеграции между *B. verrucosissimus* и *B. bufo* как на северо-востоке,

так и на юго-востоке Анатолии (Özdemir et al., 2020; Dursun et al., 2023).

Несмотря на относительно широкое распространение, *Bufo verrucosissimus* является одним из наиболее быстро исчезающих видов амфибий на Кавказе (Красная книга Российской Федерации, 2021). Массовая гибель на дорогах, разрушение местообитаний и исчезновение мест размножения уже длительное время способствуют сокращению популяций этого вида на всем протяжении ареала (Кузьмин, 2012). Однако в современности главным лимитирующим фактором для *B. verrucosissimus* стал инвазионный хищник-батрахофаг *Procyon lotor* Linnaeus, 1758 (Туниев, Туниев, 2006, 2013). Завезенный на Кавказ в середине XX в. (Верещагин, 1959), *P. lotor* быстро распространился. Уже к началу 2000-х гг. он почти полностью уничтожил многие популяции амфибий на Черноморское побережье (Туниев, Туниев, 2006) и продолжил распространение в горы на северном макросклоне. К 2020 г. массово выедал большую часть взрослых особей *B. verrucosissimus* на нерестилищах в ущельях от Малой Лабы до верховий Кубани (данные авторов). При этом *P. lotor* присутствует уже почти на всех российских особо охраняемых природных территориях, где обитает *B. verrucosissimus*. В связи с вышесказанным, в федеральной Красной книге статус вида был повышен с категории 2 (сокращающийся в численности узкоареальный вид, эндемик лесов Западного Кавказа и Юго-Восточного Закавказья) (Красная книга Российской Федерации, 2001) до категории 1 (находящийся под угрозой исчезновения вид) (Красная книга Российской Федерации, 2021).

Повсеместное исчезновение и высокий охранный статус *Bufo verrucosissimus* в России не позволяет проводить исследования, связанные с изъятием животных из естественной среды обитания. Однако в фондах ряда музеев хранятся крупные выборки этого вида, добытые в конце XX в., то есть, когда вид был еще многочисленным и не был внесен в списки охраняемых животных. Одна из наиболее представительных коллекций *B. verrucosissimus* с большей части видового ареала хранится в Сочинском национальном парке (г. Сочи, Краснодарский край, Россия). Особую ценность представляют экземпляры, собранные на особо охраняемых природных территориях в тот период, когда на популяционную структуру *B. verrucosissimus* еще не повлиял *P. lotor*.

Целью настоящей работы являлась оценка возрастной структуры и роста *B. verrucosissimus* на территории одного из крупнейших резерватов для этого вида в России, Кавказского заповедника, до 1990 г. включительно по результатам изучения экземпляров из музейной коллекции.

Материал и методы

Материалом для исследований послужили взрослые особи кавказской жабы, собранные в период размножения (март – апрель) в 1987–1990 гг. на территории Кавказского государственного природного биосферного заповедника (Северо-Западный Кавказ, Россия) и в его охранный зоне (рис. 1) и хранящиеся в фондовой коллекции Сочинского национального парка. Все выборки были сделаны в локалитетах, расположенных на северном макросклоне Кавказа, не изолированы друг от друга географически, и относятся к одной популяции. У экземпляров, зафиксированных в 70% этаноле, электронным штангенциркулем с погрешностью 0.1 мм измеряли длину тела (SVL) и отсекали третью фалангу четвертого пальца задней правой конечности.

Скелетохронологическое исследование осуществляли по стандартной методике (Смирин, 1989; Смирин, Макаров, 1987). Каждую фалангу пальцев очищали от окружающих мягких тканей и затем декальцинировали в 6%-ном растворе HNO_3 в течение 0.2–0.3 ч. Поперечные срезы фаланги толщиной 15–20 мкм изготавливали с использованием замораживающего микротомы, а затем окрашивали гематоксилином Эрлиха. Индивидуальный возраст определяли путем подсчета тонких темных линий остановленного роста, которые образуются в надкостнице во время периода зимней спячки (рис. 2).

Используя методы нелинейной регрессии, модель асимптотического роста фон Бергаланфи (Bertalanffy, 1938) была адаптирована к нашим данным по длине тела в разном возрасте для каждого пола:

$$SVL_t = SVL_{\max} - (SVL_{\max} - SVL_0) \times e^{-k \times (t - t_0)},$$

где SVL_t – средняя длина тела в определенном возрасте, SVL_{\max} – предельная длина тела (может отличаться от максимальной зарегистрированной длины тела), SVL_0 – средняя длина тела вышедших на метаморфоз молодых жаб, k – коэффициент роста, t – количество пережитых зимовок, t_0 – возраст в начале исследуемого интервала роста.

Рис. 1. Находки *Bufo verrucosissimus* на Северо-Западном Кавказе (Кузьмин, 2012; Африн, 2023). Точки сбора животных, задействованных в исследовании: 1 – Черноречье; 2 – Третья Рота; 3 – Карапырь; 4 – Загедан.

Fig. 1. Records of *Bufo verrucosissimus* in the North-Western Caucasus (Kuzmin, 2012; Afrin, 2023). Collection points of animals used in the study: 1 – Chernorechye; 2 – Tretya Rota; 3 – Karapyr; 4 – Zagedan.

Рис. 2. Окрашенные гематоксилином поперечные срезы фаланг пальцев *Bufo verrucosissimus*. Обозначения: а – двухлетний самец (SVL = 68.8 мм; Карапырь); б – восьмилетний самец (SVL = 74.0 мм; Третья Рота); в – десятилетняя самка (SVL = 104.9 мм; Загедан); стрелки указывают на линии останков роста.

Fig. 2. Hematoxylin-stained cross-sections of *Bufo verrucosissimus* finger phalanges. Designations: а – 2-year old male (SVL = 68.8 mm; Karapyr); б – 8-year old male (SVL = 74.0 mm; Tretya Rota); в – 10-year old female (SVL = 104.9 mm; Zagedan); arrows indicate the lines of arrested growth.

U-критерий Манна-Уитни ($U_{эмп}$) использовался для сравнения средних значений измеренной длины тела между полами (в пределах каждого возраста). Для статистических анализов использовался пакет программ Statistica 8.0 (Dell, USA).

Результаты

В общей сложности были изучены препараты от 16 самок и 51 самца. На всех срезах были хорошо заметны линии остановленного роста, соответствующие зимовкам. Дополнительных линий между ними отмечено не было, что свидетельствует об отсутствии летней спячки.

Возрастная структура *Bufo verrucosissimus* во всех изученных локалитетах была схожей, что особенно наглядно при анализе среднего возраста (табл. 1; Приложение). В целом, в Кавказском заповеднике и его охранной зоне средний возраст самок составил 7.9 ± 1.4 лет при диапазоне 6–10 лет, а самцов – 5.8 ± 1.6 лет и 2–9 лет, соответственно. Самки статистически значимо ($U_{эмп} = 129$; $p < 0.01$) превосходили по этому показателю самцов.

Статистически значимые различия по длине тела между самцами и самками были отмечены в группах семилетних ($U_{эмп} = 4$; $p < 0.05$) и девятилетних ($U_{эмп} = 0$; $p < 0.05$) животных.

Учитывая размеры тела молоди, только что прошедшей метаморфоз (10.9–13.3 мм, в среднем 12.4 ± 0.6), можно считать, что самки к возрасту шести лет прирастают в длину на 392.2–680.4%, к семи годам – на 507.1–747.5%, к восьми годам – на 690.9–722.5%, к девяти годам – на 622.1–842.3%, к десяти годам – на 749.2–788.0%. Самцы от метаморфоза к двум годам вырастают на 454.8%, к трем годам – на 401.6–407.3%, к четырем годам – на 405.6–520.2%, к пяти годам – на 393.5–503.2%, к шести годам – на 403.2–555.6%, к семи годам – на 579.8–508.1%, к восьми годам – на 471.0–557.3%, к девяти годам – на 596.0–566.1%.

Самки относительно равномерно растут в течение всей жизни, тогда как рост самцов существенно замедляется после достижения половой зрелости (рис. 3). Согласно уравнению фон Бергаланфи, максимально возможная длина тела, которую особи из изученной популяции способны достичь в течение жизни,

была определена как 130.9 ± 31.2 мм для самок и 74.6 ± 1.3 мм для самцов. Самцы оказались способны достигать предельной длины тела быстрее, чем самки (к составил 0.722 ± 0.112 для самцов и 0.163 ± 0.085 для самок).

Обсуждение

Длина тела изученных особей с территории Кавказского государственного природного биосферного заповедника (60.8–116.4 мм для самок и 61.2–86.3 мм для самцов) соответствует размерам взрослых особей *Bufo verrucosissimus* из других локалитетов на Северном Кавказе (78.6–119.4 мм для самок и 61.1–88.7 мм для самцов) (Кидов и др., 2015; Африн, 2023). В целом по ареалу для этого вида другими исследователями была указана максимальная длина самок в 154 мм (Кузьмин, 2012) и 170 мм (Ананьева и др., 1998), а для самцов – 96 мм (Кузьмин, 2012) и 120 мм (Ананьева и др., 1998).

Таблица 1. Возрастная структура и длина тела особей *Bufo verrucosissimus* на территории Кавказского государственного природного биосферного заповедника (Россия) и в его охранной зоне

Table 1. Age structure and body length of *Bufo verrucosissimus* individuals in the Caucasian State Natural Biosphere Reserve (Russia) and its buffer zone

Локалитет и период сбора	M ± SD (min–max)					
	самки			самцы		
	n	возраст, лет	длина тела, мм	n	возраст, лет	длина тела, мм
Кордон Черноречье, Мостовский район, Краснодарский край, 825 м н.у.м., 1988 г.	–	–	–	30	5.9 ± 1.6 (3–9)	71.6 ± 6.18 (61.2–86.3)
Кордон Третья Рота, Мостовский район, Краснодарский край, 910 м н.у.м., 1987 г.	3	7.3 ± 1.5 (6–9)	89.9 ± 12.9 (75.0–98.2)	1	8.0	81.5
Кордон Карапырь, Урупский район, Карачаево-Черкесская Республика, 1170 м н.у.м., 1990 г.	8	8.3 ± 1.2 (7–10)	102.6 ± 8.9 (89.2–116.4)	17	5.5 ± 1.8 (2–9)	72.6 ± 5.36 (62.9–82.6)
Поселок Загедан, Урупский район, Карачаево-Черкесская Республика, 1330 м н.у.м., 1990 г.	5	7.8 ± 1.8 (6–10)	88.2 ± 16.91 (60.8–104.9)	3	5.3 ± 1.2 (4–6)	74.1 ± 6.96 (67.4–81.3)

Рис. 3. Траектории роста у самок (а) и самцов (б) *Bufo verrucosissimus* в соответствии с измеренной длиной тела (SVL) в каждой возрастной группе.

Fig. 3. Growth trajectories in females (a) and males (b) of *Bufo verrucosissimus* according to the measured body length (SVL) for each age group.

До настоящего времени возраст и рост *Bufo verrucosissimus* при помощи скелетохронологии исследовали только в Боржомском ущелье (край Самцхе-Джавахети, Грузия) (Gokhelaşvili & Tarkhishvili, 1994), на горе Стрижамент (Ставропольский край, Россия) (Африн и др., 2022), в окрестностях озер Узунгель (ил (край) Трабзон, Турция) (Kalayci et al., 2019) и Карагель (ил (край) Артвин, Турция) (Dursun & Özdemir, 2022). В Боржоме в высотном градиенте 900–1200 м н.у.м. взрослые самки (n = 56) имели возраст от трех до десяти лет, а самцы (n = 49) – от двух до девяти лет. При этом большинство самок (68%) были 5–7-летними, а самцов (78%) – 3–5-летними (Gokhelaşvili & Tarkhishvili, 1994). Возраст изученных взрослых самок (n = 7) со Стрижамента (680–700 м н.у.м.) составил 5–12 лет (7-летние особи – 57.1%), а самцов (n = 12) – 3–7 лет (4–5-летние особи – 75%) (Африн и др., 2022). На оз. Узунгель (1090 м н.у.м.) возраст самок (n = 5) составил 2–7 лет (по одной особи (по 20%) в возрасте двух, трех и шести лет и две особи (40%) в возрасте семи лет), а самцов (n = 19) – 3–6 лет (4–5-летние особи – 73.7%). Самки (n = 14) с оз. Карагель (1450–1480 м н.у.м.) имели возраст 5–8 лет (6–7-летние особи – 85.7%), а самцы (n = 15) – 2–7 лет (4–6-летние особи – 80%) (Dursun & Özdemir, 2022).

Для большинства изученных амфибий (Боркин, Тихенко, 1979; Sinsch, 2015; Кидов и др., 2022), включая представителей семейства Bufonidae (Матушкина и др., 2015; Lyarkov et al., 2020, 2021; Kidov et al., 2023), характерна почти полная остановка роста после достижения половой зрелости. Отмечено это явление и для *Bufo verrucosissimus* из других локалитетов (Gokhelaşvili & Tarkhishvili, 1994; Kalayci et al., 2019; Dursun & Özdemir, 2022; Африн и др., 2022). Рост особей *Bufo verrucosissimus* в Кавказском государственном природном биосферном заповеднике замедляется с наступлением половой зрелости (что особенно заметно для самцов), но не останавливается. При этом самки *B. verrucosissimus* в Кавказском государственном природном биосферном заповеднике относительно равномерно растут и после созревания, что отличает их от самок из других изученных популяций.

В целом, сравнивая известные к настоящему времени данные о возрастной структуре и росте *B. verrucosissimus* с другими представителями рода, можно отметить их высокую схожесть. Так, все они поздно достигают половой зрелости (с 2–6 лет, самцы – на 1–2 года раньше самок) и имеют высокий предельный возраст (до 6–15 лет) (Nemelaar,

1988; Schabetsberger et al., 2000; Mi, 2015; Sun et al., 2016; Эпова, Куранова, 2019). Лишь представители некоторых видов, обитающие в южной части ареала рода *Bufo*, могут созревать раньше (уже после первой зимовки), но эти случаи единичны (Kusano et al., 2010; Матушкина и др., 2015).

Заключение

Таким образом, *Bufo verrucosissimus* на всем протяжении ареала при близких размерных показателях демонстрирует схожую возрастную структуру. Первые самцы созревают с возраста двух лет, а большинство – с четырех лет, самки – с трех лет, а в массе – с 5–6 лет. Во всех изученных локалитетах особи характеризуются высокой максимальной продолжительностью жизни: самки до 6–12 лет, а самцы до 7–9 лет. Интересно, что, в отличие от всех остальных изученных популяций, самки *B. verrucosissimus* в Кавказском государственном природном биосферном заповеднике растут поступательно и после достижения половой зрелости, а самые старые особи зачастую оказываются и самыми крупными.

Благодарности

Работа выполнена за счет средств Программы развития РГАУ – МСХА имени К.А. Тимирязева в рамках Программы стратегического академического лидерства «Приоритет-2030».

Литература

- Ананьева Н.Б., Боркин Л.Я., Даревский И.С., Орлов Н.Л. 1998. Земноводные и пресмыкающиеся. Энциклопедия природы России. М.: АБФ. 576 с.
- Африн К.А. 2023. Распространение, изменчивость, экология и охрана кавказской жабы (*Bufo verrucosissimus*) в Российской Федерации. Дис. ... канд. биол. наук. Москва. 188 с.
- Африн К.А., Степанкова И.В., Кидов А.А. 2022. Возрастная структура кавказской жабы (*Bufo verrucosissimus*) на Ставропольской возвышенности (по результатам изучения погибших на дорогах особей) // Естественные и технические науки. №1(164). С. 89–92. DOI: 10.25633/ETN.2022.01.07
- Банников А.Г., Даревский И.С., Ищенко В.Г., Рустамов А.К., Щербак Н.Н. 1977. Определитель земноводных и пресмыкающихся фауны СССР. М.: Просвещение. 414 с.
- Боркин Л.Я. 1986. О систематике и зоогеографии амфибий Кавказа // Труды Зоологического института АН СССР. Т. 158. С. 47–58.
- Боркин Л.Я., Тихенко Н.Д. 1979. Некоторые аспекты морфологической изменчивости, полиморфизма окраски, роста, структуры популяции и суточной активности *Rana lessonae* на северной границе ареала // Труды Зоологического института АН СССР. Т. 89. С. 18–54.

- Верещагин Н.К. 1959. Млекопитающие Кавказа (история формирования фауны). М.; Л.: Издательство АН СССР. 703 с.
- Кидов А.А., Матушкина К.А., Африн К.А., Блинова С.А. 2015. Стандартные методы морфометрии в прижизненном изучении изменчивости кавказской жабы, *Bufo verrucosissimus* (Pallas, 1814) на Северо-Западном Кавказе // Вестник Московского государственного областного университета. Серия: Естественные науки. №1. С. 22–28.
- Кидов А.А., Иволга Р.А., Кондратова Т.Э., Иванов А.А. 2022. Возраст, рост и плодовитость у лягушки Терентьева (*Pelophylax terentievi*, Amphibia, Ranidae) // Зоологический журнал. Т. 101(12). С. 1384–1393. DOI: 10.31857/S004451342211006X
- Клевезаль Г.А., Смирин Э.М. 2016. Регистрирующие структуры наземных позвоночных. Краткая история и современное состояние исследований // Зоологический журнал. Т. 95(8). С. 872–896. DOI: 10.7868/S0044513416080079
- Клейнбергер С.Е., Смирин Э.М. 1969. К методике определения возраста амфибий // Зоологический журнал. Т. 48(7). С. 1090–1094.
- Красная книга Российской Федерации. Животные. М.: АСТ Астрель, 2001. 864 с.
- Красная книга Российской Федерации. Животные. 2-е изд. М.: ВНИИ Экология, 2021. 1128 с.
- Кузьмин С.Л. 2012. Земноводные бывшего СССР. Москва: Товарищество научных изданий КМК. 370 с.
- Матушкина К.А., Янчуревич О.В., Кидов А.А. 2015. Возраст и рост тальшской жабы (*Bufo eichwaldi* Litvinchuk, Borkin, Skorinov et Rosanov, 2008) в Ленкоранской низменности (Юго-Восточный Азербайджан) // Современная герпетология. Т. 15(3–4). С. 114–119.
- Орлова В.Ф., Туниев Б.С. 1989. К систематике кавказских серых жаб группы *Bufo bufo verrucosissimus* (Pallas) (Amphibia, Anura, Bufonidae) // Бюллетень МОИП. Т. 94(3). С. 13–24.
- Смирин Э.М. 1989. Методика определения возраста амфибий и рептилий по слоям в кости // Руководство по изучению земноводных и пресмыкающихся. Киев. С. 144–153.
- Смирин Э.М., Макаров А.Н. 1987. Об установлении соответствия числа слоев в трубчатых костях у амфибий возрасту особей // Зоологический журнал. Т. 66(4). С. 599–604.
- Терентьев П.В., Чернов С.А. 1949. Определитель пресмыкающихся и земноводных. Третье дополненное издание. М.: Советская Наука. 340 с.
- Туниев Б.С., Туниев С.Б. 2006. Редкие виды земноводных и пресмыкающихся Сочинского национального парка // Инвентаризация основных таксономических групп и сообществ, зоологические исследования Сочинского национального парка – первые итоги первого в России национального парка. М.: Престиж. С. 205–225.
- Туниев Б.С., Туниев С.Б. 2013. Последствия инвазии ента-полоскуна (*Procyon lotor* L., 1758) в Краснодарском крае // Сборник научных трудов Сочинского научно-исследовательского центра РАН. Сочи: РИО СНИЦ РАН. С. 180–186.
- Эпова Л.А., Куранова В.Н. 2019. Некоторые аспекты демографической структуры популяций обыкновенной жабы, *Bufo bufo* (Anura, Amphibia) Кузнецкого Алатау в градиенте высотной зональности // Известия высших учебных заведений. Поволжский регион. Естественные науки. №1(25). С. 181–197. DOI: 10.21685/2307-9150-2019-1-18
- Bertalanffy L. 1938. A quantitative theory of organic growth (Inquiries on growth laws. II) // Human Biology. Vol. 10(2). P. 181–213.
- Dursun C., Özdemir N. 2022. Morphological variability and age structure in a population of *Bufo verrucosissimus* (Anura: Bufonidae) from Artvin, Turkey // Phyllomedusa. Vol. 21(1). P. 31–49. DOI: 10.11606/issn.2316-9079.v21i1p31-49
- Dursun C., Özdemir N., Gül S. 2023. Easternmost distribution of *Bufo bufo* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Türkiye: implications for the putative contact zone between *B. bufo* and *B. verrucosissimus* // Genetica. Vol. 151(1). P. 11–27. DOI: 10.1007/s10709-022-00175-5
- Ehret D.J. 2007. Skeletochronology: a method for determining the individual age and growth of modern and fossil tortoises (Reptilia: Testudines) // Bulletin of the Florida Museum of Natural History. Vol. 47(2). P. 49–72.
- Gokheshvili R.K., Tarkhishvili D.N. 1994. Age structure of six Georgian anuran populations and its dynamics during two consecutive years // Herpetozoa. Vol. 7(1/2). P. 11–18.
- Hemelaar A. 1988. Age, growth and other population characteristics of *Bufo bufo* from different latitudes and altitudes // Journal of Herpetology. Vol. 22(4). P. 369–388. DOI: 10.2307/1564332
- Jablonski D., Sadek R.A. 2019. The Caucasian toad, *Bufo verrucosissimus* (Pallas, 1814) in the Levant: evidence from mitochondrial DNA // Herpetozoa. Vol. 32. P. 255–258. DOI: 10.3897/herpetozoa.32.e37560
- Kalayci T.E., Gül S., Dursun C., Karaoğlu H., Özdemir N. 2019. Age structure and body size variation in common toad (*Bufo bufo*, Linnaeus 1758) from three different altitudes in Turkey // Russian Journal of Ecology. Vol. 50(4). P. 397–403. DOI: 10.1134/S106741361904009X
- Kidov A.A., Matushkina K.A., Litvinchuk S.N. 2020. Distribution and conservation status of the Eichwald's toad, *Bufo eichwaldi* in Azerbaijan // Russian Journal of Herpetology. Vol. 27(1). P. 11–18. DOI: 10.30906/1026-2296-2020-27-1-11-18
- Kidov A.A., Lyapkov S.M., Stepankova I.V., Afrin K.A., Kidova E.A., Kondratova T.E., Litvinchuk S.N. 2023. Age structure and growth rate of the triploid Batura toad, *Bufo fotes baturae* (Anura: Bufonidae), inhabitant of a high altitude hot spring in the Eastern Pamirs (Tajikistan) // Russian Journal of Herpetology. Vol. 30(2). P. 79–87. DOI: 10.30906/1026-2296-2023-30-2-79-87
- Kusano T., Maruyama K., Kaneko S. 2010. Body size and age structure of a breeding population of the Japanese common toad, *Bufo japonicus formosus* (Amphibia: Bufonidae) // Current Herpetology. Vol. 29(1). P. 23–31. DOI: 10.3105/018.029.0103

- Legendre S. 2004. Age structure, mating system, and population viability // Evolutionary Conservation Biology / R. Ferrière, U. Dieckmann, D. Couvet (Eds.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. P. 41–58.
- Litvinchuk S.N., Borkin L.J., Skorinov D.V., Rosanov J.M. 2008. A new species of common toads from the Talysh mountains, south-eastern Caucasus: genome size, allozyme, and morphological evidences // Russian Journal of Herpetology. Vol. 15(1). P. 19–43.
- Lyapkov S.M., Kidov A.A., Stepankova I.V., Afrin K.A., Litvinchuk S.N. 2020. Age Structure and Growth in the Lataste's Toad, *Bufoles latastii* (Anura: Bufonidae) // Russian Journal of Herpetology. Vol. 27(3). P. 165–171. DOI: 10.30906/1026-2296-2020-27-3-165-17
- Lyapkov S.M., Kidov A.A., Stepankova I.V., Afrin K.A., Litvinchuk S.N. 2021. Age structure and growth in the Zamda toad, *Bufoles zamdaensis* (Anura, Bufonidae) // Russian Journal of Herpetology. Vol. 28(3). P. 138–144. DOI: 10.30906/1026-2296-2021-28-3-138-144
- Mi Z.P. 2015. Age structure and body size in a breeding population of Asiatic toad (*Bufo gargarizans*) in southwestern China // North-Western Journal of Zoology. Vol. 11(1). P. 178–182.
- Özdemir N., Dursun C., Üzüm N., Kutrup B., Gül S. 2020. Taxonomic assessment and distribution of common toads (*Bufo bufo* and *B. verrucosissimus*) in Turkey based on morphological and molecular data // Amphibia-Reptilia. Vol. 41(3). P. 399–411. DOI: 10.1163/15685381-bja10009
- Recuero E., Canestrelli D., Vörös J., Szabó K., Poyarkov N.A., Arntzen J.W., Crnobrnja-Isailovic J., Kidov A.A., Cogălniceanu D., Caputo F.P., Nascetti G., Martínez-Solano I. 2012. Multilocus species tree analyses resolve the radiation of the widespread *Bufo bufo* species group (Anura, Bufonidae) // Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution. Vol. 62(1). P. 71–86. DOI: 10.1016/j.ympev.2011.09.008
- Schabetsberger R., Langer H., Jersabek C.D., Goldschmid A. 2000. On age structure and longevity in two populations of *Bufo bufo* (Linnaeus, 1758), at high altitude breeding sites in Austria // Herpetozoa. Vol. 13(3/4). P. 187–191.
- Sinsch U. 2015. Review: skeletochronological assessment of demographic life-history traits in amphibians // Herpetological Journal. Vol. 25(1). P. 5–13.
- Smirina E.M. 1994. Age determination and longevity in Amphibians // Gerontology. Vol. 40(2–4). P. 133–146. DOI: 10.1159/000213583
- Sun Y., Xiong J., Lv Y., Zhang Y. 2016. Age, body size, and growth in a population of the Asiatic toad *Bufo gargarizans* from Central China // Russian Journal of Herpetology. Vol. 23(1). P. 35–40.
- Stavropol upland (based on study of road killed specimens). *Natural and Technical Sciences* 1(164): 89–92. DOI: 10.25633/ETN.2022.01.07 [In Russian]
- Ananjeva N.B., Borkin L.J., Darevsky I.S., Orlov N.L. 1998. *Amphibians and reptiles. Encyclopedia of Russian Nature*. Moscow: ABF. 576 p. [In Russian]
- Bannikov A.G., Darevsky I.S., Ishchenko V.G., Rustamov A.K., Shcherbak N.N. 1977. *A Determinant Key of Amphibians and Reptiles of Fauna of the USSR*. Moscow: Prosveshchenie. 414 p. [In Russian]
- Bertalanffy L. 1938. A quantitative theory of organic growth (Inquires on growth laws. II). *Human Biology* 10(2): 181–213.
- Borkin L.J. 1986. On the systematics and zoogeography of amphibians of the Caucasus. *Proceedings of the Zoological Institute AS USSR* 158: 47–58. [In Russian]
- Borkin L.J., Tikhenko N.D. 1979. Some aspects of morphological variation, color polymorphisms, growth, population structure, and daily activity in *Rana lessonae* in the northern range limit. *Proceedings of the Zoological Institute AS USSR* 89: 18–54. [In Russian]
- Dursun C., Özdemir N. 2022. Morphological variability and age structure in a population of *Bufo verrucosissimus* (Anura: Bufonidae) from Artvin, Turkey. *Phyllomedusa* 21(1): 31–49. DOI: 10.11606/issn.2316-9079.v21i1p31-49
- Dursun C., Özdemir N., Gül S. 2023. Easternmost distribution of *Bufo bufo* (Linnaeus, 1758) in Türkiye: implications for the putative contact zone between *B. bufo* and *B. verrucosissimus*. *Genetica* 151(1): 11–27. DOI: 10.1007/s10709-022-00175-5
- Ehret D.J. 2007. Skeletochronology: a method for determining the individual age and growth of modern and fossil tortoises (Reptilia: Testudines). *Bulletin of the Florida Museum of Natural History* 47(2): 49–72.
- Epova L.A., Kuranova V.N. 2019. Some aspects of demographic structure of the Common toad populations, *Bufo bufo* (Anura, Amphibia), of the Kuznetsk Alatau mountains (Russia) in an altitude gradient. *University Proceedings. Volga Region. Natural Sciences* 1(25): 181–197. DOI: 10.21685/2307-9150-2019-1-18 [In Russian]
- Gokhelasvili R.K., Tarkhishvili D.N. 1994. Age structure of six Georgian anuran populations and its dynamics during two consecutive years. *Herpetozoa* 7(1/2): 11–18.
- Hemelaar A. 1988. Age, growth and other population characteristics of *Bufo bufo* from different latitudes and altitudes. *Journal of Herpetology* 22(4): 369–388. DOI: 10.2307/1564332
- Jablonski D., Sadek R.A. 2019. The Caucasian toad, *Bufo verrucosissimus* (Pallas, 1814) in the Levant: evidence from mitochondrial DNA. *Herpetozoa* 32: 255–258. DOI: 10.3897/herpetozoa.32.e37560
- Kalayci T.E., Gül S., Dursun C., Karaoğlu H., Özdemir N. 2019. Age structure and body size variation in common toad (*Bufo bufo*, Linnaeus 1758) from three different altitudes in Turkey. *Russian Journal of Ecology* 50(4): 397–403. DOI: 10.1134/S106741361904009X
- Kidov A.A., Ivolga R.A., Kondratova T.E., Ivanov A.A. 2022. Age, growth and fertility in Terentiev's frog (*Pelophylax terentievi*, Amphibia, Ranidae). *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal* 101(12): 1384–1393. DOI: 10.31857/S004451342211006X [In Russian]

References

- Afrin K.A. 2023. *Distribution, variability, ecology and conservation of the Caucasian toad (Bufo verrucosissimus) in the Russian Federation*. PhD Thesis. Moscow. 188 p. [In Russian]
- Afrin K.A., Stepankova I.V., Kidov A.A. 2022. Age structure of the Caucasian toad (*Bufo verrucosissimus*) on the

- Kidov A.A., Matushkina K.A., Litvinchuk S.N. 2020. Distribution and conservation status of the Eichwald's Toad, *Bufo eichwaldi* in Azerbaijan. *Russian Journal of Herpetology* 27(1): 11–18. DOI: 10.30906/1026-2296-2020-27-1-11-18
- Kidov A.A., Lyapkov S.M., Stepankova I.V., Afrin K.A., Kidova E.A., Kondratova T.E., Litvinchuk S.N. 2023. Age structure and growth rate of the triploid Batura toad, *Bufo baturae* (Anura: Bufonidae), inhabitant of a high altitude hot spring in the Eastern Pamirs (Tajikistan). *Russian Journal of Herpetology* 30(2): 79–87. DOI: 10.30906/1026-2296-2023-30-2-79-87
- Kidov A.A., Matushkina K.A., Afrin K.A., Blinova S.A. 2015. Standard methods of morphometry in lifetime studies of variability of Caucasian toad *Bufo verrucosissimus* (Pallas, 1814) in the Northwestern Caucasus. *Bulletin of the Moscow Region State University. Series: Natural Sciences* 1: 22–28. [In Russian]
- Kleinenberg S.E., Smirina E.M. 1969. A contribution to the method of age determination in amphibians. *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal* 48(7): 1090–1094. [In Russian]
- Klevezal G.A., Smirina E.M. 2016. Recording structures of terrestrial vertebrates. A sketch of history and the current state of investigations. *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal* 95(8): 872–896. DOI: 10.7868/S0044513416080079 [In Russian]
- Kusano T., Maruyama K., Kaneko S. 2010. Body size and age structure of a breeding population of the Japanese common toad, *Bufo japonicus formosus* (Amphibia: Bufonidae). *Current Herpetology* 29(1): 23–31. DOI: 10.3105/018.029.0103
- Kuzmin S.L. 2012. *Amphibians of the Former Soviet Union*. Moscow: Moscow: KMK Scientific Press Ltd. 370 p. [In Russian]
- Legendre S. 2004. Age Structure, Mating System, and Population Viability. In: R. Ferrière, U. Dieckmann, D. Couvet (Eds.): *Evolutionary Conservation Biology*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. P. 41–58.
- Litvinchuk S.N., Borkin L.J., Skorinov D.V., Rosanov J.M. 2008. A new species of common toads from the Talysh mountains, south-eastern Caucasus: genome size, allozyme, and morphological evidences. *Russian Journal of Herpetology* 15(1): 19–43.
- Lyapkov S.M., Kidov A.A., Stepankova I.V., Afrin K.A., Litvinchuk S.N. 2020. Age Structure and Growth in the Lataste's Toad, *Bufo latastii* (Anura: Bufonidae). *Russian Journal of Herpetology* 27(3): 165–171. DOI: 10.30906/1026-2296-2020-27-3-165-17
- Lyapkov S.M., Kidov A.A., Stepankova I.V., Afrin K.A., Litvinchuk S.N. 2021. Age structure and growth in the Zamda toad, *Bufo zamdaensis* (Anura, Bufonidae). *Russian Journal of Herpetology* 28(3): 138–144. DOI: 10.30906/1026-2296-2021-28-3-138-144
- Matushkina K.A., Yanchurevich O.V., Kidov A.A. 2015. Age and growth of the Eichwald's toad (*Bufo eichwaldi* Litvinchuk, Borkin, Skorinov et Rosanov, 2008) in the Lenkoran Lowland (Southeastern Azerbaijan). *Current Studies in Herpetology* 15(3–4): 114–119. [In Russian]
- Mi Z.P. 2015. Age structure and body size in a breeding population of Asiatic toad (*Bufo gargarizans*) in southwestern China. *North-Western Journal of Zoology* 11(1): 178–182.
- Orlova V.F., Tuniyev B.S. 1989. On the taxonomy of the Caucasian common toads belonging to the group *Bufo bufo verrucosissimus* (Pallas) (Amphibia, Anura, Bufonidae). *Bulletin of Moscow Society of Naturalists* 94(3): 13–24. [In Russian]
- Özdemir N., Dursun C., Üzümlü N., Kutrup B., Gül S. 2020. Taxonomic assessment and distribution of common toads (*Bufo bufo* and *B. verrucosissimus*) in Turkey based on morphological and molecular data. *Amphibia-Reptilia* 41(3): 399–411. DOI: 10.1163/15685381-bja10009
- Recuero E., Canestrelli D., Vörös J., Szabó K., Poyarkov N.A., Arntzen J.W., Crnobrnja-Isailovic J., Kidov A.A., Cogălniceanu D., Caputo F.P., Nascetti G., Martínez-Solano I. 2012. Multilocus species tree analyses resolve the radiation of the widespread *Bufo bufo* species group (Anura, Bufonidae). *Molecular Phylogenetics and Evolution* 62(1): 71–86. DOI: 10.1016/j.ympev.2011.09.008
- Red Data Book of the Russian Federation. Animals. Moscow: Astrel, 2001. 862 p. [In Russian]
- Red Data Book of the Russian Federation. Animals. Moscow: VNIIEcologiya, 2021. 1128 p. [In Russian]
- Schabetsberger R., Langer H., Jersabek C.D., Goldschmid A. 2000. On age structure and longevity in two populations of *Bufo bufo* (Linnaeus, 1758), at high altitude breeding sites in Austria. *Herpetozoa* 13(3/4): 187–191.
- Sinsch U. 2015. Review: skeletochronological assessment of demographic life-history traits in amphibians. *Herpetological Journal* 25(1): 5–13.
- Smirina E.M. 1989. A technique for determining the age of amphibians and reptiles by layers in bones. In: *A Guide to the Study of Amphibians and Reptiles*. Kiev. P. 144–153. [In Russian]
- Smirina E.M. 1994. Age determination and longevity in Amphibians. *Gerontology* 40(2–4): 133–146. DOI: 10.1159/000213583
- Smirina E.M., Makarov A.N. 1987. On ascertainment of accordance between the number of layers in tubular bones of amphibians and the age of individuals. *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal* 66(4): 599–604. [In Russian]
- Sun Y., Xiong J., Lv Y., Zhang Y. 2016. Age, body size, and growth in a population of the Asiatic toad *Bufo gargarizans* from Central China. *Russian Journal of Herpetology* 23(1): 35–40.
- Terentyev P.B., Chernov A.S. 1949. *Key for Determination of Reptiles and Amphibians*. 3rd supplemented edition. Moscow: Sovetskaya Nauka. 340 p. [In Russian]
- Tuniyev B.S., Tuniyev S.B. 2006. Rare species of amphibians and reptiles of the Sochi National Park. In: *Inventory of the main taxonomic groups and communities, zoological studies of the Sochi National Park – the first outcomes of the first Russian national park*. Moscow: Prestizh. P. 205–225. [In Russian]
- Tuniyev B.S., Tuniyev S.B. 2013. Consequences of raccoon (*Procyon lotor* L., 1758) invasion in the Krasnodarsky Krai. In: *Proceedings of the Sochi Scientific Centre of the RAS*. Sochi: Sochi Scientific Centre of the RAS. P. 180–186. [In Russian]
- Vereshchagin N.K. 1959. *Mammals of the Caucasus (a history of the fauna evolution)*. Moscow; Leningrad: AS USSR. 703 p. [In Russian]

Приложение. Длина тела взрослых особей *Bufo verrucosissimus* в различных возрастных группах на территории Кавказского государственного природного биосферного заповедника (Россия).

Supplement. Body length of adult *Bufo verrucosissimus* individuals of various age groups in the Caucasian State Natural Biosphere Reserve, Russia.

Возраст, лет	Длина тела (SVL), мм					
	самки			самцы		
	n	M ± SD	min–max	n	M ± SD	min–max
Черноречье						
3	–	–	–	1	62.2	–
4	–	–	–	6	69.8 ± 6.13	62.7–76.8
5	–	–	–	6	69.2 ± 5.15	61.2–74.8
6	–	–	–	6	69.0 ± 3.68	62.4–73.1
7	–	–	–	7	76.3 ± 5.23	69.8–84.3
8	–	–	–	2	73.0 ± 1.48	71.9–74.0
9	–	–	–	2	79.1 ± 10.25	71.8–86.3
Третья Рота						
6	1	96.4	–	–	–	–
7	1	75	–	–	–	–
8	–	–	–	1	81.5	–
9	1	98.2	–	–	–	–
Карапырь						
2	–	–	–	1	68.8	–
3	–	–	–	1	62.9	–
4	–	–	–	3	71.7 ± 7.05	63.7–76.9
5	–	–	–	2	69.7 ± 0.85	69.1–70.3
6	–	–	–	7	75.4 ± 2.77	71.3–79.1
7	3	99.8 ± 7.45	91.2–104.7	1	67.3	–
8	1	101.6	–	1	70.8	–
9	3	103.3 ± 13.62	89.2–116.4	1	82.6	–
10	1	109.7	–	–	–	–
Загедан						
4	–	–	–	1	67.4	–
6	2	73.1 ± 17.32	60.8–85.3	2	77.5 ± 5.37	73.7–81.3
8	1	97.7	–	–	–	–
9	1	92.1	–	–	–	–
10	1	104.9	–	–	–	–

AGE STRUCTURE AND GROWTH OF *BUFO VERRUCOSISSIMUS* (AMPHIBIA, ANURA, BUFONIDAE) IN THE CAUCASIAN STATE NATURE BIOSPHERE RESERVE (RUSSIA) AT THE END OF THE XX CENTURY

Artem A. Kidov^{1,*} ,
Kseniya A. Matushkina¹

¹Russian State Agrarian University – K.A. Timiryazev Moscow Agricultural Academy, Russia

*e-mail: kidov@rgau-msha.ru

²Sochi National Park, Russia

Bufo verrucosissimus is an endangered species in the Russian Federation. One of the largest protected areas where *B. verrucosissimus* is preserved is the Caucasian State Nature Biosphere Reserve. The paper presents data on age structure and growth of *B. verrucosissimus* collected in the Caucasian State Nature Biosphere Reserve in 1987–1990 and stored in the collection of Sochi National Park. The age of 16 females and 51 males was determined using the method of skeletochronology. The age of adult females was 6–10 years (on average 7.9 years), and males 2–9 years (on average 5.8 years). Females were statistically significantly superior to males in average age. In terms of body length, significant differences between males and females were noted in groups of seven- and ten-year-old animals. The body length of studied animals (60.8–116.4 mm for females and 61.2–86.3 mm for males) corresponds to the size of adult toads from other localities in the North Caucasus. Females grow evenly throughout their lives, while the growth of males slows down significantly after reaching puberty. Males were able to reach the maximum body length faster than females (the growth coefficient was 0.722 for males and 0.163 for females). According to the von Bertalanffy equation, the maximum possible body length was 130.9 mm for females and 74.6 mm for males.

Key words: demography, growth rate, life longevity, North Caucasus, skeletochronology, tailless amphibians

WITHIN-GROUP SPATIAL POSITION IN *SAIGA TATARICA* (BOVIDAE) IN THE STEPNOI STATE NATURE SANCTUARY, ASTRAKHAN REGION, RUSSIA

Karina A. Karenina^{ID}, Ekaterina A. Berezina^{ID}, Andrey N. Giljov^{*ID}

Saint Petersburg State University, Russia

*e-mail: a.gilev@spbu.ru, zoology.gilev@gmail.com

Received: 07.07.2023. Revised: 27.09.2023. Accepted: 07.10.2023.

In group-living animals, the social structure and organisation play a significant role in survival and reproduction. Understanding the social aspects of animal lives in the wild may be crucially important for effective conservation of threatened species. The fitness costs and benefits of living in a group are related to particular spatial positions individuals take within their groups. Age and sex of the individual is a major factor determining intra-group spatial position. In the present study, we investigated the within-group spatial positioning of individuals in the Critically Endangered *Saiga tatarica* (hereinafter – saiga). In saigas living under natural predation pressure in the Stepnoi State Nature Sanctuary (Astrakhan Region, Russia), we investigated the sex-age category of the first individual in the group, the inter-individual distance in the front individuals and the individuals following them, and the distribution of individuals of each sex-age category between various parts of the group. Three (summer) or four (autumn) sex-age categories of the individuals in the moving groups were recognised by direct observations in the field. In summer, adult females, accompanied by their calves, were the very first individuals in most saiga groups observed. This result agrees with the previous notion that experienced females often lead the saiga groups. However, further investigation is needed to confirm whether adult females do indeed take the role of a leader during long-distance group movements. In line with the results on other mammals, the majority of adult females moved in the central third of the group. Spatial preferences of adult females seem to be based on the risk minimisation as the central positions are likely the safest in the group. In autumn, juvenile males were moving first in the majority of the investigated groups probably because they were the most active and fast-moving sex-age category during this season. In addition, juvenile males and females were significantly more often observed in the first third of the group than in the central and the rear thirds. We suggest that despite the fact that the front edge of the group could be the most dangerous spatial position, foraging benefits may outweigh the increased risk for juvenile saigas. In contrast to some other mammals, adult males did not tend to move at the front edge and were equally often observed in the front, central and rear parts of saiga groups. Finally, our results showed that saigas closer to the front edge of the group maintained shorter inter-individual distances than the individuals positioned behind them. The tighter spacing could be used by front individuals to compensate for the increased risks associated with their within-group spatial position.

Key words: antelope, Artiodactyla, group behaviour, group structure, inter-individual distance, intra-group position, northwest pre-Caspian, spatial relations

Introduction

Saiga tatarica, Linnaeus, 1766 (hereinafter – saiga) is a migratory ungulate of the steppes and deserts of Central Asia and the pre-Caspian (Bekenov et al., 1998). Once an abundant species, the saiga faced a drastic decline in the global population which has led to a Critically Endangered listing on the Global IUCN Red List (Milner-Gulland et al., 2003). In the northwestern pre-Caspian region of Russia, a striking poaching pressure on the saiga population of the nominate subspecies (*S. t. tatarica*) in the 1990s caused a most sudden decline of the species abundance (Kühl et al., 2009; Karimova & Lushchekina, 2018). During the last decade, the local population is slowly recovering within Protected Areas, but it still remains the most threatened saiga population in the world (Karimova et al., 2021).

In group-living animals, the social structure can play a pivotal role in survival and reproduction. In case of threatened species, understanding the social

aspects of animals in the wild may be critically important for effective conservation practice (Caro, 1999). Almost all our knowledge of saiga's sociality is based on the studies conducted decades ago (Zhirmov, 1977; Sokolov & Zhirmov, 1998), when the species was much more abundant and its habitat and migratory routes were considerably less disturbed by anthropogenic activities. The knowledge of saiga's social behaviour under the current conditions of very low population size and restricted migration remains very limited. In the northwestern pre-Caspian region, small (21–200 individuals) and very small (1–20 individuals) saiga groups constitute 80–90% of the population (Karimova & Lushchekina, 2018). However, little is known about the structural characteristics of these groups.

It is widely recognised that the fitness costs and benefits of living in a group differ between group members, and within-group spatial position is one of the key factors underlying this difference (Krause,

1994; Krause & Ruxton, 2002). The growing evidence indicates that variation in individual risks is related to particular spatial, which are taken by individuals within their groups. The current theoretical framework and empirical evidence indicate that individuals in front positions of their groups may be exposed to a higher general risk as they are the first ones to explore new areas and face the threats. Front individuals have considerably higher predator encounter rates than individuals in more rear positions (Balmford & Turyaho, 1992; Bumann et al., 1997; Lingle, 2001). To reduce an individual's predation risk, individuals in front positions often demonstrate increased vigilance (Di Blanco & Hirsch, 2006) and maintain smaller inter-individual distances (Hamilton, 1971; Bumann et al., 1997) than individuals elsewhere in the group. At the same time, individuals on the front are more likely to access food patches before others, i.e. they have higher foraging success than the rest of the group because of food depletion from the front to the back (Janson, 1990a; Krause et al., 1992; Rowcliffe et al., 2004). Thus, a trade-off exists for the individuals moving in a group, in which a strategy minimising predation risk by moving not in the front of the group may lower foraging success, whereas a strategy maximising food acquisition may negatively impact individual safety (Beecham & Farnsworth, 1999; Carbone et al., 2003; Teichroeb et al., 2015).

Age and sex influence both predation risk and intra-group spatial position (reviewed in Schmitt & Di Fiore, 2015; Teichroeb et al., 2015). The relative positioning of individuals of various sex and age in mixed groups can vary considerably between the species. However, in many primate species adult males tend to be at the front of moving groups, while females and juveniles typically stay closer to the group's centre (Teichroeb et al., 2015). The males' tendency to maintain front positions in the groups could be especially pronounced in sexually dimorphic primate species because larger males may be less vulnerable to predators and more actively participate in antipredator defence (Schmitt & Di Fiore, 2015). In primates, juveniles usually stay more central because they face the greatest risk of predation and have to rely on adults for vigilance (Teichroeb et al., 2015). However, in some other mammals such as *Nasua nasua* (Linnaeus, 1766), juveniles appear to choose spatial locations based on feeding success and not predation avoidance and therefore prefer the positions at the front of the group (Hirsch, 2011).

In this study, we aimed to explore the spatial position of individuals of various sex and age in saiga groups in the wild. Sexual dimorphism and

synchronous calving in saigas allow clear recognition of main sex and age classes and makes this species a convenient model for this study. In saigas living under natural predation pressure, we assessed the sex-age category of the first individual in the group, the inter-individual distance for the front individuals and the individuals following them, and the distribution of individuals of each sex-age category between various parts of the group. Based on the previous reports on other mammal species, we hypothesised that the relatively more risky front positions in the groups will be predominantly occupied by adult males. With larger body size and horns as a defence, adult saiga males may be less vulnerable to predation and, therefore, benefit more from primary access to food patches associated with the front position. In females and juveniles, which may face a greater risk of predation, the costs of being in front of the group may outweigh the benefits, and therefore, they may gravitate to central positions. Alternatively, juveniles and young individuals may base their spatial choices more on feeding success than predation risk, and prefer the front positions. We hypothesised that if front positions are perceived by saigas as the riskiest ones, the individuals at the front edge will maintain shorter inter-individual distances than the individuals positioned behind them.

Material and Methods

Study subjects and site

Saiga is a harem-breeding ungulate, with an adult male typically defending a group of females during the rut in December (Bekenov et al., 1998; Sokolov & Zhirnov, 1998). Once the rut is over, group size and composition beyond the rut period are highly variable and may depend on the weather conditions, food availability, migratory activity, population size and other factors (Sokolov & Zhirnov, 1998; Karimova et al., 2020). Saigas occasionally occur in large aggregations of several thousand of individuals but the typical group size is referred to as approximately 30 individuals on average (Bekenov et al., 1998). Mixed-sex groups are common throughout the year, while male- or female-only groups and large aggregations occur seasonally (Bekenov et al., 1998). Unfortunately, to date, we have very limited knowledge of saiga social structure and organisation.

The individuals observed in the present study belong to the northwest pre-Caspian population of saigas. In the mid-XX century, the population of the saiga in this region reached over 800 000 individuals. At the early XXI century, the population dropped to about 8000–9000 individuals in re-

sponse to a combination of multiple negative factors (Neronov et al., 2012), with the most considerable effect of poaching (Kühl et al., 2009; Karimova & Lushchekina, 2018). Nowadays, the remaining population of the saiga inhabit an area of about 2000–3000 km², with the core habitat lying within the two contiguous Protected Areas within the northwestern pre-Caspian region of Russia, Stepnoi State Nature Sanctuary (Astrakhan Region) and Chernye Zemli State Nature Biosphere Reserve (Republic of Kalmykia) (Karimova & Lushchekina, 2018).

The present study was conducted at Stepnoi Nature Sanctuary which includes well-preserved native steppe pastures and several major watering places attracting saigas throughout the year. The sanctuary belongs to the northern subzone of the desert zone characterised by a dry continental climate and even a landscape with low vegetation. In this area, saigas exist under natural predation pressure, with *Canis lupus* Linnaeus, 1758 assumed to be a major predator (Karimova & Lushchekina, 2018). Human disturbance within the sanctuary has been kept to a minimum for the last decade. Poaching, unauthorised vehicle traffic and cattle grazing have been eliminated.

Data collection and analysis

The data for this study were collected in two various periods of the year when the majority of the groups are mixed-sex and mixed-age (single-sex/age groups were excluded) and sex-age classes can reliably be determined in the field. At late May – early June (further referred to as «summer»; Fig.

1A), mixed-sex saiga groups with recently born calves were observed and three categories of individuals were distinguished, namely adult males (more than two years old), one-year-old young males and adult females with calves. The recognition of male age categories was based on the size of the horns. Since early September, the sex of the saigas, which were born this year, can be easily distinguished from a distance. Juvenile males have short black horns, while the body size of juvenile females is noticeably smaller than that of adult females. In September (further referred to as «autumn»; Fig. 1B), four sex-age categories were recognised in saiga groups, namely adult males, adult females, juvenile males and juvenile females. The data collection was conducted during a total of 85 days in 2020, 2022, and 2023, and included observations with binoculars from a watching tower, landscape elevations and stationary hides as described elsewhere (Gilev & Karenina, 2015; Giljov et al., 2019; Fourie et al., 2021).

In mixed-sex and mixed-age groups, we recorded i) the sex-age category of the first individual at the front edge of the group, ii) the inter-individual distance in the first and second ten individuals in the group, and iii) the distribution of individuals of each category between the front, central and rear thirds of the group. Only slowly moving groups of minimally 30 and maximally 60 individuals were included in all analyses to minimise the effect of significant variations in group size and activity on the investigated parameters.

Fig. 1. Saiga (*Saiga tatarica*) groups in summer (A) and autumn (B) in the Stepnoi State Nature Sanctuary, Astrakhan Region, Russia.

Three (summer) or four (autumn) sex-age categories of the first individuals in the groups were recognised by direct observations in the field. Whether individuals of a particular sex-age category predominantly took the first front position was tested using a Chi-square test.

To assess the inter-individual spacing in front individuals and individuals moving behind them, we recorded distances between the first ten individuals and the second ten individuals in the groups. For the first ten individuals, nine distances were recorded (e.g. between the individuals one and two, two and three, three and four). Similarly, nine distances were recorded for the second ten individuals (e.g. between individuals 11 and 12, 12 and 13). The distance was scored in adult male body lengths (approximately 1 m; see Sokolov & Zhirnov, 1998) and was estimated using a marine binocular with built-in reticle scales. For this analysis, only the groups moving along the visible saiga trails in the steppe were investigated. Such long-lasting trails are common in many parts of the the Stepnoi State Nature Sanctuary regularly visited by saigas. When using a trail, saigas moved one after another in a line that helped reliable estimation of inter-individual distance. Based on the approach suggested by McDonald (2014), mean distances between the first ten individuals and the second ten individuals were compared using the Mann-Whitney U-test.

To assess the distribution of individuals of various sex and age between various parts of the group, the total number of individuals was divided into three thirds (front, central and rear). This analysis was carried out only for the data collected in autumn. For each sex-age category, the distribution of individuals between the thirds was estimated using the Kruskal-Wallis test (with a DSCF post-test). The statistical analysis was performed with Jamovi v. 2.3.18 software (Jamovi project, 2022). All statistical tests were two-tailed, and the level of p-value was less than 0.05.

Ethical statement

The study has been conducted with the approval of the Stepnoi State Nature Sanctuary authorities. The ethical permission for the study was obtained from the St. Petersburg State University (Russia) ethical committee (permit №131-03-3). The study was purely observational. A considerable effort was made to minimise the disturbance of the animals.

Results

A total of 173 groups were observed, including 93 ones in summer, and 80 in autumn. The analysis of the sex-age category of the first individual at

the front edge of the group showed that in summer adult females were moving first in the majority of the groups (54 groups; $\chi^2(2) = 26$, $p < 0.001$; Fig. 1A). One-year-old young males were the first individuals in 22 groups, and adult males in 17 groups. In autumn, the first individual in most groups was a juvenile male (40 groups; $\chi^2(3) = 28.3$, $p < 0.001$; Fig. 1B). Adult females took the first front position in 18 groups, adult males in 11 groups, and juvenile females in 11 groups.

The estimation of the inter-individual spacing in front individuals and individuals moving behind them revealed that the distances between the first ten individuals were shorter than the distances between the second ten individuals both in autumn (Mann-Whitney $U = 630$, $p = 0.005$; median = 1.25 for the first ten saigas and 1.60 for the second ten ones) and in summer (Mann-Whitney $U = 1308$, $p = 0.005$; median = 1.90 for the first ten saigas and 2.20 for the second ten ones).

The distribution of individuals of various sex and age between the front, central and rear thirds of the groups showed that adult females predominantly (53.2%) moved in the central third (Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2 = 36.3$, $p < 0.001$; DSCF post-test: $p < 0.001$ for front vs. central and central vs. rear thirds; $p = 0.120$ for front vs. rear thirds; Fig. 2). In contrast, adult males were distributed equally across various parts of the groups (Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2 = 2.19$, $p = 0.334$; DSCF post-test: $p > 0.05$; Fig. 2). The majority of juvenile males (60.3%) were observed in the front third of their groups (Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2 = 37.2$, $p < 0.001$; DSCF post-test: $p < 0.001$ for front vs. central and front vs. rear thirds; $p = 0.993$ for central vs. rear thirds). Similarly, juvenile females predominantly (50.6%) moved in the front third of the groups (Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2 = 38.8$, $p < 0.001$; DSCF post-test: $p < 0.001$ for front vs. central and front vs. rear thirds; $p = 0.082$ for central vs. rear thirds; Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Percentage distribution of individuals of each sex-age category between the front, central and rear thirds of the studied groups of saiga (*Saiga tatarica*) in the Stepnoi State Nature Sanctuary, Astrakhan Region, Russia. Bars represent standard deviation (SD).

Discussion

The present study showed some patterns of within-group spatial positioning of individuals in saigas. The analysis of the sex-age category of individuals maintaining the very first front position in moving groups showed seasonal variation in this parameter. In summer, adult females accompanied by their calves were the first individuals in the considerable majority of saiga groups observed, while in autumn juvenile males were moving first in most cases. Contrary to our prediction and the results of the previous studies on other mammals such as primates (e.g. Schmitt & Di Fiore, 2015; Teichroeb et al., 2015), adult males did not tend to be the first individuals in their groups. In addition, the analysis of the distribution of adult males within the mixed groups showed that they did not prefer to be in the first third of the group and were roughly equally distributed between the front, central and rear parts. At the front edge of the group, individuals are supposed to face a greater risk of predation and other threats. They are the first ones to explore new areas and may thereby be exposed to higher general risk. At the same time, front individuals have a higher foraging success accessing food patches before others (Balmford & Turyaho, 1992; Krause et al., 1992; Bumann et al., 1997; Lingle, 2001; Rowcliffe et al., 2004). Larger body size and horns could make adult saiga males less vulnerable to predation. Therefore, the front position is potentially less costly for them. Nevertheless, adult males did not tend to take front positions and this could be associated with their functional role within a group. Adult males often display so-called herding behaviour aimed to maintain the integrity of the group and avoid spatial separation of females and calves moving too slowly or away from the others (Sokolov & Zhirnov, 1998; Giljov et al., 2019). In this regard, it could be beneficial for adult males to move between various parts of the group and monitor other individuals. This, in turn, may result in the absence of any preference to stay in a particular part of the group in adult males.

Our results showing that adult females tend to be the first individuals in summer groups agree with the previous notions that experienced females often maintain the front position and take the role of leaders during group movements (Zhirnov, 1977; Sokolov & Zhirnov, 1998). Similarly, an adult (or old) female may take the role of a leader in the groups of feral horses (*Equus ferus* ssp. *przewalskii* Poliakov, 1881) (Bourjade et al., 2015). According to the current knowledge, the first individual in a group probably, but not necessarily, is actually a group leader (Boinski & Garber, 2000). A number of studies

showed that group leaders are typically located at the front of the group. At the same time, in some species, the leader determines the direction of travelling from a central spatial position (Boinski & Garber, 2000; Couzin et al., 2005). However, it is questionable, whether the mechanisms of central leadership could efficiently be used in relatively large groups, in which visual contact between all group members is hardly possible (Hirsch, 2007). Thus, it is plausible that adult females do indeed lead the saiga groups in summer. A more focused future study may confirm this using various signs of the leadership. For example, one of the proposed ways of identifying leaders in groups of herbivores is to identify the individual that is consistently the one, which initiates long-distance spontaneous group movements toward a new feeding site (Dumont et al., 2005).

The tendency of juvenile males to be the first individuals in their groups in autumn matches the distribution of this sex-age category between various parts of the group. Juvenile males were considerably more often observed in the first third of the group than in the central and the rear thirds. The same preference was found in juvenile females. These results correspond with the previous results on juvenile *Nasua nasua*, which preferentially maintain the positions at the front of the group (Hirsch, 2011). It has been suggested that despite the front edge could be the most dangerous spatial position, foraging benefits may outweigh the increased risk of predation for juvenile *N. nasua*. The same may be true for saigas. In autumn, when nutrient-rich food becomes scarce, the possibility to reach untouched grass patches before the others may considerably increase food acquisition in juveniles. It is difficult to explain why juvenile males are typically the first individuals in the moving groups, while both male and female juveniles tend to occupy the front third of the group. It has been suggested that in some cases, the most actively moving individuals become the leaders in saiga groups (Sokolov & Zhirnov, 1998). Probably, juvenile males are the most active and fast-moving sex-age category in autumn and, as a result, they often become the very first individuals in a group.

Adult females were observed in the centre more often than at the front or rear thirds of the group. This result agrees with the general tendency of females to stay closer to the group's centre found in other mammals (Janson, 1990b; Ron et al., 1996; Hirsch, 2011; Teichroeb et al., 2015). In some species, adult dominant females aggressively defend central positions and actively exclude subordinates from the centre of the group (Hirsch, 2011; Teichroeb et al.,

2015). The cumulative evidence indicates that central spatial positions are likely the safest within a group. Central individuals typically spend less time being vigilant (Burger & Gochfeld, 1994; Di Blanco & Hirsch, 2006; Blanchard et al., 2008) and face a lower risk of predation (Balmford & Turyaho, 1992; Bumann et al., 1997; Lingle, 2001) than the individuals at the edges of the group. The preference for the central position in a group suggests that in adult female saigas, the choice of spatial positions is based on risk minimisation.

Our results showed that the distances between the first ten individuals were shorter than the distances between the second ten individuals. These differences were significant both in summer and in autumn. That is, irrespective of the groups' sex-age composition and category of individuals moving first, saigas closer to the front edge of the group maintained shorter inter-individual distances than the individuals positioned behind them. Tighter spacing between individuals is typical for animal groups facing an increased threat (Bumann et al., 1997). Staying closer to their neighbours, animals may decrease their individual predation risk by reducing their domain of danger (Hamilton, 1971; De Vos & O'Riain, 2010). Saigas moving close to the front edge may maintain shorter inter-individual distances to compensate for the increased risks associated with their spatial position. Tighter spacing in front of individuals implies that saigas likely perceive the front positions as more dangerous than the more rear ones. The comparison of the levels of vigilance between individuals in various parts of saiga groups may be a promising direction for future study.

Conclusions

The present study adds to the scarce knowledge of within-group spatial interactions of mammals in the wild. Investigation of the positioning of individuals in saigas showed that age and sex of the individual is a major factor determining intra-group spatial position. In summer, adult females were the first individuals in the majority of groups, while in autumn juvenile males maintained the very first front position in most cases. The distribution of individuals of each sex-age category between various parts of the group had the following pattern. Juvenile males and females were more often observed in the first third of the group than in the central and the rear thirds, while the majority of adult females moved in the central third of the group. Adult males were observed equally often in the front, central and rear parts of saiga groups. Some of our results followed

the patterns found previously in other mammal species, while some did not. Our study emphasises the specific characteristics of spatial interactions within saiga groups. This knowledge can be used to improve our very limited understanding of saiga's sociality. Currently, when the saiga population size is critically low, such understanding may have practical implications for species conservation.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Anna Lushchekina (A.N. Severtsov Institute of Ecology and Evolution of the RAS, Russia) and the staff of the Stepnoi State Nature Sanctuary (Astrakhan Region, Russia), with special thanks to Vladimir Kalmykov and Galina Kalmykova, for their valuable assistance during data collection. This study was supported by RSF grant №22-24-00403.

References

- Balmford A., Turyaho M. 1992. Predation risk and lek-breeding in Uganda kob. *Animal Behaviour* 44(1): 117–127. DOI: 10.1016/S0003-3472(05)80761-4
- Beecham J.A., Farnsworth K.D. 1999. Animal group forces resulting from predator avoidance and competition minimization. *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 198(4): 533–548. DOI: 10.1006/jtbi.1999.0930
- Bekenov A.B., Grachev I.A., Milner-Gulland E.J. 1998. The ecology and management of the Saiga antelope in Kazakhstan. *Mammal Review* 28(1): 1–52. DOI: 10.1046/j.1365-2907.1998.281024.x
- Blanchard P., Sabatier R., Fritz H. 2008. Within-group spatial position and vigilance: a role also for competition? The case of impalas (*Aepyceros melampus*) with a controlled food supply. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology* 62(12): 1863–1868. DOI: 10.1007/s00265-008-0615-3
- Boinski S., Garber P.A. 2000. *On the Move: How and Why Animals Travel in Groups*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press. 811 p.
- Bourjade M., Thierry B., Hausberger M., Petit O. 2015. Is leadership a reliable concept in animals? An empirical study in the horse. *PLoS ONE* 10(5): e0126344. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0126344
- Bumann D., Krause J., Rubenstein D. 1997. Mortality risk of spatial positions in animal groups: the danger of being in the front. *Behaviour* 134(13/14): 1063–1076. DOI: 10.1163/156853997X00403
- Burger J., Gochfeld M. 1994. Vigilance in African mammals: differences among mothers, other females, and males. *Behaviour* 131(3/4): 153–169. DOI: 10.1163/156853994X00415
- Carbone C., Thompson W.A., Zadorina L., Rowcliffe J.M. 2003. Competition, predation risk and patterns of flock expansion in barnacle geese (*Branta leucopsis*). *Journal of Zoology* 259(3): 301–308. DOI: 10.1017/S0952836902003278
- Caro T. 1999. The behaviour–conservation interface. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution* 14(9): 366–369. DOI: 10.1016/S0169-5347(99)01663-8
- Couzin I.D., Krause J., Franks N.R., Levin S.A. 2005. Effective leadership and decision-making in animal

- groups on the move. *Nature* 433(7025): 513–516. DOI: 10.1038/nature03236
- De Vos A., O’Riain M.J. 2010. Sharks shape the geometry of a selfish seal herd: experimental evidence from seal decoys. *Biology Letters* 6(1): 48–50. DOI: 10.1098/rsbl.2009.0628
- Di Blanco Y., Hirsch B.T. 2006. Determinants of vigilance behavior in the ring-tailed coati (*Nasua nasua*): the importance of within-group spatial position. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology* 61(2): 173–182. DOI: 10.1007/s00265-006-0248-3
- Dumont B., Boissy A., Achard C., Sibbald A.M., Erhard H.W. 2005. Consistency of animal order in spontaneous group movements allows the measurement of leadership in a group of grazing heifers. *Applied Animal Behaviour Science* 95(1–2): 55–66. DOI: 10.1016/j.applanim.2005.04.005
- Fourie B., Berezina E., Giljov A., Karenina K. 2021. Visual lateralization in artiodactyls: A brief summary of research and new evidence on saiga antelope. *Laterality* 26(1–2): 106–129. DOI: 10.1080/1357650X.2020.1852245
- Gilev A., Karenina K. 2015. The significance of artesian wells for saigas within the Stepnoi Sanctuary, Astrakhan region. *Saiga News* 20: 15–17.
- Giljov A., Malashichev Y., Karenina K. 2019. What do wild saiga antelopes tell us about the relative roles of the two brain hemispheres in social interactions?. *Animal Cognition* 22(5): 635–643. DOI: 10.1007/s10071-019-01259-0
- Hamilton W.D. 1971. Geometry for the selfish herd. *Journal of Theoretical Biology* 31(2): 295–311. DOI: 10.1016/0022-5193(71)90189-5
- Hirsch B.T. 2007. Costs and benefits of within-group spatial position: a feeding competition model. *Quarterly Review of Biology* 82(1): 9–27. DOI: 10.1086/511657
- Hirsch B.T. 2011. Within-group spatial position in ring-tailed coatis: balancing predation, feeding competition, and social competition. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology* 65(2): 391–399. DOI: 10.1007/s00265-010-1056-3
- Jamovi project. 2022. *jamovi (version 2.3)*. Computer Software. Available from <https://www.jamovi.org>
- Janson C.H. 1990a. Ecological consequences of individual spatial choice in foraging groups of brown capuchin monkeys, *Cebus apella*. *Animal Behaviour* 40(5): 922–934. DOI: 10.1016/S0003-3472(05)80994-7
- Janson C.H. 1990b. Social correlates of individual spatial choice in foraging groups of brown capuchin monkeys, *Cebus apella*. *Animal Behaviour* 40(5): 910–921. DOI: 10.1016/S0003-3472(05)80993-5
- Karimova T.Yu., Lushchekina A.A. 2018. Features of the spatial distribution and ethological structure of saiga population within the “Stepnoy” sanctuary (Astrakhan oblast). *Ecosystems: Ecology and Dynamics* 2(1): 73–91. DOI: 10.24411/2542-2006-2017-10004 [In Russian]
- Karimova T.Y., Lushchekina A.A., Neronov V.M., Pyurvenova N.Y., Arylov Y.N. 2020. Biological Features of the Northwest Pre-Caspian Saiga Population at Different Sizes. *Arid Ecosystems* 10(4): 298–304. DOI: 10.1134/S2079096120040113
- Karimova T.Y., Lushchekina A.A., Neronov V.M. 2021. Saiga populations of Russia and Kazakhstan: current status and retrospective analysis of some biological parameters. *Arid Ecosystems* 11(2): 164–172. DOI: 10.1134/S2079096121020074
- Krause J. 1994. Differential fitness returns in relation to spatial position in groups. *Biological Reviews of the Cambridge Philosophical Society* 69(2): 187–206. DOI: 10.1111/j.1469-185x.1994.tb01505.x
- Krause J., Ruxton G.D. 2002. *Living in Groups*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 211 p.
- Krause J., Bumann D., Todt D. 1992. Relationship between the position preference and nutritional state of individuals in schools of juvenile roach (*Rutilus rutilus*). *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology* 30(3–4): 177–180. DOI: 10.1007/BF00166700
- Kühl A., Balinova N., Bykova E., Arylov Yu.N., Esipov A., Lushchekina A.A., Milner-Gulland E.J. 2009. The role of saiga poaching in rural communities: Linkages between attitudes, socio-economic circumstances and behaviour. *Biological Conservation* 142(7): 1442–1449. DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2009.02.009
- Lingle S. 2001. Anti-predator strategies and grouping patterns in white-tailed deer and mule deer. *Ethology* 107(4): 295–314. DOI: 10.1046/j.1439-0310.2001.00664.x
- McDonald J.H. 2014. Nested ANOVA. In: *Handbook of Biological Statistics* (3rd ed.). Baltimore, Maryland: Sparky House Publishing. P. 165–172.
- Milner-Gulland E.J., Bukreeva O.M., Coulson T., Lushchekina A.A., Kholodova M.V., Bekenov A.B., Grachev I.A. 2003. Reproductive collapse in saiga antelope harems. *Nature* 422(6928): 135. DOI: 10.1038/422135a
- Neronov V.M., Lushchekina A.A., Karimova T.Y., Arylova N.Y. 2012. Population dynamics of a key steppe species in a changing world: the critically endangered saiga antelope. In: *Eurasian steppes. Ecological problems and livelihoods in a changing world*. Dordrecht: Springer. P. 335–356. DOI: 10.1007/978-94-007-3886-7_12
- Ron T., Henzi S.P., Motro U. 1996. Do female chacma baboons compete for a safe spatial position in a southern woodland habitat?. *Behaviour* 133(5/6): 475–490. DOI: 10.1163/156853996X00549
- Rowcliffe J.M., Pettifor R.A., Carbone C. 2004. Foraging inequalities in large groups: quantifying depletion experienced by individuals in goose flocks. *Journal of Animal Ecology* 73(1): 97–108. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2656.2004.00783.x
- Schmitt C.A., Di Fiore A. 2015. Predation risk sensitivity and the spatial organization of primate groups: A case study using GIS in lowland Woolly Monkeys (*Lagothrix lagotricha poeppigii*). *American Journal of Physical Anthropology* 156(1): 158–165. DOI: 10.1002/ajpa.22612
- Sokolov V.E., Zhirnov L.V. (Eds.). 1998. *The Saiga: phylogeny, systematics, ecology, conservation and use*. Moscow: Russian Academy of Sciences. 356 p. [In Russian]
- Teichroeb J.A., White M.M.J., Chapman C.A. 2015. Vervet (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*) intragroup spatial positioning: dominants trade-off predation risk for increased food acquisition. *International Journal of Primatology* 36(1): 154–176. DOI: 10.1007/s10764-015-9818-4
- Zhirnov L.V. 1977. *The Saiga. Ungulates*. Moscow: Lesnaya Promyshlennost. P. 79–118. [In Russian]

ПРОСТРАНСТВЕННОЕ РАСПОЛОЖЕНИЕ ОСОБЕЙ ВНУТРИ ГРУППЫ У *SAIGA TATARICA* (BOVIDAE) В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОМ ПРИРОДНОМ ЗАКАЗНИКЕ «СТЕПНОЙ», АСТРАХАНСКАЯ ОБЛАСТЬ, РОССИЯ

К. А. Каренина

Санкт-Петербургский государственный университет, Россия

*e-mail: a.gilev@spbu.ru, zoology.gilev@gmail.com

У животных, ведущих групповой образ жизни, структура и организация сообществ играют важную роль в выживании и размножении. Знания об особенностях социального поведения животных в природе могут иметь большое значение для принятия эффективных мер по сохранению редких видов. Преимущества и недостатки жизни в группе для отдельных особей взаимосвязаны с тем, какое пространственное положение они занимают относительно других особей. Возраст и пол являются важными факторами, определяющими пространственное взаиморасположение членов группы. В этой работе мы исследовали пространственное расположение особей друг относительно друга в группах *Saiga tatarica* (далее – сайгак), вида, находящегося на грани вымирания. У сайгаков, живущих в условиях естественного пресса хищничества в государственном природном заказнике «Степной» (Астраханская область, Россия), была исследована половозрастная категория первых особей в группе, дистанция между особями в передней и последующей за ней частях группы и распределение особей разного пола и возраста между разными частями группы. В ходе наблюдений в природе мы выделяли три (летом) или четыре (осенью) половозрастные категории в перемещающихся группах сайгаков. Летом взрослые самки с детенышами двигались первыми в большинстве исследованных групп. Этот результат согласуется с более ранними исследованиями, предполагавшими, что группу сайгаков обычно ведет опытная самка. Для того чтобы подтвердить лидирующую роль взрослых самок необходимы дальнейшие исследования. Как и у других видов млекопитающих, исследованных ранее, большинство самок сайгака двигались в центральной части группы. Пространственные предпочтения взрослых самок, видимо, основаны на минимизации рисков, так как расположение в центре группы, скорее всего, обеспечивает наибольшую безопасность. Осенью первыми в группах чаще всего шли самцы-сеголетки, что, вероятно, связано с тем, что они были наиболее активной и быстро перемещающейся категорией особей в это время года. Сеголеток обоих полов значительно чаще наблюдали перемещающимися в первой трети группы, чем в центральной и задней. Несмотря на то, что расположение в передней части группы, вероятно, наиболее опасно, в случае с сеголетками, преимущества, связанные с приоритетным доступом к пище могут перевешивать повышенные риски. В отличие от некоторых других млекопитающих, взрослые самцы сайгака не были склонны располагаться на переднем крае группы, и их с одинаковой частотой наблюдали в передней, центральной и задней частях групп. Мы также обнаружили, что особи, перемещавшиеся у переднего края группы, располагались ближе друг к другу, чем особи позади них. Более тесное расположение передних животных может быть направлено на компенсацию повышенных рисков, связанных с их пространственным расположением внутри группы.

Ключевые слова: Artiodactyla, антилопа, групповое поведение, дистанция между особями, положение внутри группы, пространственные отношения, Северо-Западный Прикаспий, структура группы

ЭКОЛОГО-ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПАРАМЕТРЫ *MYOTIS DASYCNEME* (MAMMALIA CHIROPTERA: VESPERTILIONIDAE) ФАУНЫ УРАЛА

Л. А. Ковальчук^{1,*}

¹Институт экологии растений и животных УрО РАН, Россия

*e-mail: kovalchuk@ipae.uran.ru

²Федеральный научно-исследовательский институт вирусных инфекций «Виром» Роспотребнадзора, Россия

³Уральский государственный педагогический университет, Россия

Поступила: 27.04.2023. Исправлена: 17.10.2023. Принята к опубликованию: 20.10.2023.

Понимание эволюции гомеостаза летучих мышей и формирования адаптивной стратегии животных к климатическим флуктуациям и патогенам среды обитания определяют необходимость в дальнейших лабораторных и модельных исследованиях по экологии и физиологии рукокрылых. Целью исследования была оценка гематологических и биохимических параметров гомеостаза охраняемого вида рукокрылых эндемиков фауны Урала *Myotis dasycneme*. Животные (n = 65) были отловлены в зоне массового обитания летучих мышей на Южном (Челябинская область) и Среднем Урале (Свердловская область). Были использованы выборки из популяций летучих мышей, обитающих в Ильменском государственном заповеднике. Многомерный непараметрический дисперсионный анализ показал отсутствие у летучих мышей значимых половых различий по параметрам красной крови (p > 0.05). Кровь рукокрылых характеризуется высоким уровнем содержания гемоглобина (167.9–187.2 г/л), гематокрита (47.2–51.5%), эритроцитов ($9.6–11.5 \times 10^{12}/л$), тромбоцитов ($136.8–271.3 \times 10^9/л$). В осенне-зимний период гибернации при гипоксической нагрузке на организм и длительного воздействия низких положительных и околонулевых температур отмечается в крови самок и самцов повышенное содержание агранулоцитов (50.6–53.6%), обеспечивающих иммунный «надзор» и специфическую реактивность организма (адаптивный иммунитет) в этот период. Весенний процесс пробуждения и выхода из глубокой гипотермии сопровождается значимой реактивностью системы врожденного иммунитета у самцов и самок (гранулоциты: 53.2–54.2%), обеспечивающей неспецифическую срочную защиту организма, в том числе для предотвращения вирусной инвазии до выработки специфической защиты адаптивной иммунной системой. В наиболее критичный в жизни зимний период гипобиоза у летучих мышей возрастание основного обмена сопровождается повышенной концентрацией глюкозы в крови до 4.7 ± 0.5 ммоль/л в сравнении с летним периодом (p < 0.05). Отмечено отсутствие статистически значимых половых различий по содержанию глюкозы и триглицеридов (p > 0.05) в плазме крови животных. Вероятно, это связано с одинаковым субстратным обеспечением метаболических процессов (углеводный и липидный обмен) во все сезонные периоды их годового жизненного цикла. Аминокислотный фонд плазмы крови летучих мышей представлен 22 аминокислотами (АК). В плазме крови самцов и самок фонд свободных АК снижается в течение года: лето \geq осень \geq зима > весна (p < 0.05). Не выявлено половых различий в содержании метаболических групп АК (глюкогенных, заменимых, с разветвленной углеродной цепью) (p > 0.05). Значительная аккумуляция метаболически активного глюкостероидного аланина в крови самок в осенний (в 3.1 раза) и зимний (в 2.3 раза), а у самцов в осенний и зимний (в 2.0 и 1.9 раза, соответственно) сезоны года свидетельствует о его роли в качестве низкотемпературного адаптогена. В условиях низких положительных температур в плазме крови *M. dasycneme* наблюдали исчезновение незаменимой АК триптофана (p < 0.05). Это позволяет сделать предположение о его высокой востребованности в синтезе серотонина, как одного из триггеров, активно участвующего в поддержании гипотермии и гипометаболизма рукокрылых. Таким образом, биохимические и иммуногематологические параметры, полученные в ходе проведенных исследований, позволяют расширить и систематизировать имеющиеся сведения о механизмах участия системы крови в регуляторных процессах летучих мышей. Они могут быть использованы для осуществления долговременного мониторинга при решении задач сохранения и численности здоровых популяций рукокрылых, адаптирующихся как к сезонным модуляциям и биотическим факторам, так и к стрессорам зоонозного значения.

Ключевые слова: летучие мыши, основной обмен, охраняемый вид, параметры периферической крови, свободные аминокислоты, сезонная изменчивость

Введение

Исследования по сохранению биологического разнообразия и обеспечению гомеостаза экосистем в современных условиях приобретают все большую значимость. Летучие мыши, на долю которых приходится пятая часть биоразнообразия млекопитающих (Burgin et al., 2018; Simmons & Ciranello, 2021), представлена более чем

1400 видами, обладающими эволюционно высокой стратегией выживания в экосистемах целых континентов (Fenton & Simmons, 2015; Voigt & Kingston, 2016; Wilkinson & Adams, 2019). Исследователями они рассматриваются в качестве приоритетных объектов природоохранной деятельности, как индикаторы жизнеспособности и высокого гомеостаза наземных и водных биоце-

нозов (Park, 2015; Zukal et al., 2015; López-Baucells et al., 2017; Russo et al., 2021).

Большое количество видов рукокрылых находится под угрозой локального исчезновения и глобального вымирания как по причине утраты и деградации естественных мест обитания и усиливающимся антропогенным и техногенным воздействиям (Zukal et al., 2015; Flache et al., 2016; Frick et al., 2017, 2020; Heiker et al., 2018; Ruiz et al., 2019), так и в результате климатических флуктуаций (Sherwin et al., 2013; Amorim et al., 2015; Tilman et al., 2017). Ряд экологических факторов (чрезвычайная продолжительность жизни, симпатрия, высокая численность и плотность выводковых колоний особей различных видов летучих мышей, совместное использование с грызунами их зимних убежищ, широкий температурный диапазон обитания и способность к длительной гibernации, синантропность, длительные сезонные миграции) способствует, в свою очередь, передаче вирусов, эктопаразитов и грибковых инфекций между отдельными особями и популяциями рукокрылых, что приводит к постоянному воздействию патогенов (Breed et al., 2010; Luis et al., 2013; O'Shea et al., 2014; Schountz, 2014). Также летучие мыши восприимчивы к сезонным зоонозным инфекциям, вызванным как кровососущими членистоногими, так и патогенными вирусами, воздействием бактерий, простейших, нематод и трематод (Ляпунов, Панюкова, 2010; George et al., 2011; Moore et al., 2013; Schountz, 2014; Wray et al., 2018). Учитывая растущую общественную настороженность по отношению к летучим мышам и их вирусам, следует активизировать просветительскую деятельность в сфере биологии этих животных, способствующую снижению угроз, как для населения, так и для самих рукокрылых (Kohl & Kurth, 2014).

По оценке Международного союза охраны природы и природных ресурсов (МСОП) в настоящее время около 20% видов летучих мышей находятся под угрозой исчезновения, а более половины видов имеют неизвестные или сокращающиеся популяционные тенденции (IUCN, 2022). Вид рукокрылых *Myotis dasycneme* Boie, 1825 (Mammalia Chiroptera: Vespertilionidae) занесен в международный Красный список МСОП, как вид, находящийся в состоянии, близком к угрожаемому (Near Threatened, NT), имеющий невысокую, в последнее время стремительно сокращающуюся, численность, и находящийся под угрозой сокращения и исчезновения (Piraccini, 2016). Учитывая быстрый рост глобальной урбанизации,

необходимость принятия мер как по сохранению среды обитания, так и поддержания численности жизнеспособных и устойчивых популяций рукокрылых становится очевидной. В Красную книгу Среднего Урала (1996) *M. dasycneme* включен как «уязвимый» вид (категория 3). В последние десятилетия рукокрылым фауны Урала уделяется повышенное внимание в аспекте фаунистических и экологических исследований и разработке эффективной программы сохранения их разнообразия (Снитько, 2000; Большаков и др., 2005). Разработка принципов минимизации рисков для сохранения редких и находящихся под угрозой исчезновения природных популяций летучих мышей фауны Урала требует надежных технологий диагностики и дальнейших экспериментальных исследований. К ним можно отнести функциональные возможности интегрирующей роли системы крови и изучение иммунологической компетентности этих животных (Kovalchuk et al., 2017; 2018a,b; 2021; 2022; Mishchenko et al., 2018; Ковальчук и др., 2023). При большом фактическом материале по биологии и экологии уральских рукокрылых (Снитько, 2001; Ильин и др., 2002; Большаков и др., 2005; Первушина и др., 2011; Orlova et al., 2012) основная информация о генетически детерминированных эколого-физиологических механизмах поддержания гомеостаза при адаптации к биотическим и абиотическим факторам среды явно ограничена. Целью данного исследования была оценка гематологических и биохимических параметров гомеостаза *Myotis dasycneme*, охраняемого вида рукокрылых фауны Урала.

Материал и методы

Эволюционно обладающие высокой экологической пластичностью особи *M. dasycneme* формируют крупные выводковые колонии на Среднем и Южном Урале (Кузякин, 1950; Снитько, 2001; Большаков и др., 2005). Взрослые особи *M. dasycneme* были отловлены в зоне массового обитания летучих мышей на Южном (Челябинская область; 55.16678° N, 60.35022° E) и Среднем Урале (Свердловская область; 56.42889° N, 61.61222° E) в 2013–2015 гг. Климат района исследования умеренно-континентальный с продолжительной холодной зимой и сравнительно теплым коротким летом. В качестве объектов исследования использованы выборки из популяций летучих мышей, обитающих на особо охраняемой природной территории «Ильменский государственный заповедник». Район исследования расположен вблизи населенного пункта Миассово (Челябин-

ской область) на берегу оз. Малое Миассово в дер. Уразбаево на опушке березового леса и оз. Большой Кисегач, которые являются главными кормовыми участками *M. dasycneme* (Снитыко, 2001). На территории Ильменского заповедника в 2003 г. отмечалась численность этих животных около 1500 особей (Большаков и др., 2005). Питаются летучие мыши преимущественно комарами-звонцами (Chironomidae) (Кузякин, 1950; Ляпунов, Панюкова, 2010). На Среднем Урале на территории Каменского района (Свердловская область) в Смолинской карстовой пещере *M. dasycneme* формирует крупные выводковые колонии до 1000 и более особей (Bolshakov & Orlov, 2002). Животные были сняты вручную со стен зимних убежищ в Смолинской пещере или отловлены паутиными сетями в ее окрестностях. Отловы проводили с наступлением сумерек и заканчивали перед рассветом. Исследования летучих мышей без признаков заболеваний из природных популяций были проведены в сезонные периоды жизненных циклов: летом (вторая декада июля, как период воспроизводства популяции), осенью (третья декада сентября, как период массовых миграций к местам зимовки и завершающей стадии подготовки к зимнему сезону), зимой (третья декада февраля, как период продолжительного гипобиоза) и весной (первая декада апреля, как завершающий период гипотермии и оцепенения). По данным Большакова и др. (2005), в спячку животные впадают в последней декаде сентября – начале октября, и первые пробуждения отмечены в третьей декаде апреля. В период отлова среднесуточная температура воздуха на местности была в апреле от +3°C до +8°C, в июле – от +21°C до +23°C, и в сентябре от +5°C до +7°C. В феврале среднесуточная температура воздуха была от -16°C до -20°C. Зимуют рукокрылые в глубине пещеры при температуре от 0°C до +2°C в условиях чрезвычайно высокой (90–100%) влажности (Большаков и др., 2005).

Отлов и содержание животных ($n = 65$), доставленных в лабораторию, осуществляли с соблюдением международных принципов Хельсинской декларации (Yaggi, 2005). Взрослых животных отличали от сеголеток визуально по степени окостенения эпифизов костей крыла – метакарпалий и фаланг (Стрелков, 1999). Для стандартизации условий все животные в течение суток находились в контейнере, где каждая особь выбирала определенное место и в дальнейшем их двигательная активность не наблюдалась. Животные находились в состоянии покоя, минимизируя потери массы тела, связанные со стрессом. Следует отметить, что пи-

тающиеся насекомыми рукокрылые поглощают большие объемы пищи относительно собственного веса (Кузякин, 1950). Чтобы свести к минимуму ошибку массы тела за счет содержимого пищеварительного тракта, взвешивание животных проводили не менее чем через 12 ч. после отлова. Массу тела исследуемых животных определяли взвешиванием на электронных весах «Acculab PP-200dl1» (Germany) с точностью ± 0.1 г.

Физиологическое состояние животных оценивали по температуре тела (измеряли ректально датчиком электротермометра «ТПЭМ-1») и по параметрам основного обмена (регистрировали по потреблению кислорода (мл/г \times час) с помощью газоанализатора «МН-5130» (Россия)). Забор крови проводили после декапитации животных в охлажденные стерильные вакутайнеры «Bekton Dickinson ВР», обработанные антикоагулянтом К3-EDTA 15% (Великобритания). В периферической крови (400–800 μ л) экспериментальных животных с помощью гематологического анализатора «BC-5800» (Mindray, China) определяли 11 показателей. К ним относятся общее количество лейкоцитов (WBC), лимфоциты (LYM), общее количество эритроцитов (RBC), содержание гемоглобина (HGB), гематокритный показатель (HCT), средний объем эритроцита (MCV), среднее содержание гемоглобина в эритроците (MCH), среднюю концентрацию гемоглобина в эритроците (MCHC), количество тромбоцитов (PLT), средний объем тромбоцитов (MPV), тромбокрит (PCT). Лейкоцитарную формулу подсчитывали в мазках крови, окрашенных по Романовскому-Гимзе (на 100 лейкоцитов). Абсолютное соотношение лейкоцитов (10^9 клеток/л) получали путем перевода процентного содержания на общее количество лейкоцитов (Камышников, 2004). Плазму получали центрифугированием крови в рефрижераторной ультрацентрифуге «K-23D» (Germany) в течение 15 мин при 3000 оборотов/мин. Глюкозу и триглицериды определяли в плазме крови энзиматическим колориметрическим методом с использованием наборов фирмы «BioSystems» (Spain). Оптическую плотность стандартной пробы и образцов измеряли на спектрофотометре «СФ-50 Ломо Спектр» (Россия) при длине волны 500 нм.

Свободные аминокислоты (АК) и концентрацию мочевины в плазме крови летучих мышей определяли методом ионообменной жидкостной хроматографии на автоматическом анализаторе «AAA-339M» (Microtechna, Чехия) при температуре 38°C, 57°C и 64°C в системе, состоящей из пятиступенчатого градиента литий-цитрат-

ного буфера (№1 – 0.18 n, pH = 2.90, №2 – 0.20 n, pH = 3.1, №3 – 0.35 n, pH = 3.35, №4 – 0.33 n, pH = 4.05, №5 – 1.2 n, pH = 4.9). Использовали колонку 0.47 × 24.0 см; неподвижная фаза – катионообменная смола Ostion LG FA. Подготовку образцов к исследованию содержания свободных АК и мочевины в плазме крови животных проводили по стандартной методике (James, 1997). Кровь центрифугировали при 8000 оборотов/мин × 15 мин., 0°C в рефрижераторной ультрацентрифуге «К-23D». После окончания центрифугирования плазма аспирировалась в полиэтиленовую пробирку, где проводили ее депротеинизацию, т.е. к 0.5 мл супернатанта (плазмы) добавляли 0.1 мл 30% сульфосалициловой кислоты (ССК). Добавляли 0.2 мл 7% гидроксида лития (LiOH) для нейтрализации кислой реакции раствора и 0.1 мл норлейцина (C₆H₁₃NO₂ – 2.5 μмоль/л) (LaChema, Чехия) в качестве внутреннего стандарта. Вторично центрифугировали содержимое пробирки при 10 000 оборотов/мин. × 30 минут, 0°C. Супернатант (400 μл), подготовленный для проведения анализа, наносили на колонку аминокислотного анализатора. Послеколоночная модификация аминокислот проводилась с нингидрином. Интенсивность его окрашивания измеряли при 525 нм. Для каждой серии опытов прописывали хроматограмму стандартной смеси АК из 36 компонентов (0.1 μмоль/л), к которым относились цистеиновая кислота, таурин, фосфоэтанолламин, мочевины (10 ×), аспарагиновая кислота, гидроксипролин, треонин, серин, аспарагин, глутаминовая кислота, глутамин, α-аминоадипиновая кислота, пролин, глицин, аланин, цитруллин, α-аминомасляная кислота, валин, ½ цистин, метионин, цистатионин, изолейцин, лейцин, тирозин, фенилаланин, β-аланин, β-аминоизомасляная кислота, γ-аминомасляная кислота, этаноламин, аммиак, орнитин, лизин, гистидин, 1-метилгистидин, 3-метилгистидин, аргинин (LaChema, Чехия). Для количественной оценки рассчитывали коэффициент цветности АК (отношение площади пика отдельной аминокислоты к площади пика норлейцина). Концентрацию аминокислот в плазме крови (μмоль/л) определяли соотношением полученных коэффициентов цветности в пробе и в стандартной смеси. Для каждого исследуемого образца на хроматограмме прописывали весь спектр свободных АК и определяли концентрацию каждой из них в μмоль/л и в процентном отношении от суммарного содержания. Рассчитывали суммарные концентрации заменимых АК (ЗАК), незаменимых АК (НАК), глюкогенных АК (ГАК) и серосодер-

жащих АК (ССАК: цистеин, метионин, таурин), АК с разветвленной углеродной цепью (АКРУЦ: валин, лейцин, изолейцин), ароматических АК (АРАК: фенилаланин, тирозин). Выполнен анализ 946 аминокислотных проб. Результаты обработаны с использованием пакета лицензионных прикладных программ Statistica v. 10.0 (StatSoft Inc., USA). Независимые группы сравнивались с помощью дисперсионного анализа с перестановочным тестом (Permutation ANOVA; $p = \Pr(F_{\text{ran}} \geq F_{\text{obs}})$), последующие (post-hoc) межгрупповые сравнения проведены с помощью критерия Тьюки (Шитиков, Розенберг, 2014). Метод главных компонент (PCA) реализован посредством статистической среды R v. 3.1.2 (R Core Team, 2020) с использованием пакетов vegan (Oksanen et al., 2020) и ade4 (Chessel et al., 2004; Dray et al., 2022).

Результаты

Сравнительный анализ колебаний массы тела у летучих мышей, независимо от их половой принадлежности ($p > 0.05$), показал статистически значимые различия между сезонными периодами их годового цикла: лето-осень-зима-весна ($p < 0.05$) (табл. 1). В осенний период подготовки к длительной гибернации животные затрачивают больше энергии для поддержания жизненно важных функций. В свою очередь, это ведет к возрастанию интенсивности метаболических процессов (5.6 ± 0.4 мл/г × ч., $p < 0.05$). Кроме того, если осенью наблюдали увеличение массы тела *M. dasycneme* в среднем на 14% относительно летних особей, то в третьей декаде февраля в период длительного гипобиоза у животных отмечено снижение массы тела на 21%, а у весенних особей – на 33%, достигая минимальных значений к моменту пробуждения ($p < 0.05$). Ректальная температура самцов осенью увеличена на 20% по сравнению с летним периодом, тогда как у самок она остается стабильной. Поддержание температурного гомеостаза животных в зимний период сопровождается возрастанием основного обмена в 1.6 раза по сравнению с летним периодом, т.е. с 3.9 ± 0.41 мл/г × ч. до 6.4 ± 0.5 мл/г × ч. ($p < 0.05$). В первой декаде апреля при завершающем этапе зимней гибернации у самцов ректальная температура снижается до $15.5 \pm 0.8^\circ\text{C}$ ($p < 0.05$). У самок температура тела отмечается на уровне показателей зимних животных, $26.5 \pm 2.8^\circ\text{C}$ ($p > 0.05$). В наиболее критичный в жизни зимний период гипобиоза у летучих мышей возрастание основного обмена сопровождается повышенной концентрацией глюкозы в крови до 4.7 ± 0.5 ммоль/л ($p < 0.05$) (табл. 1).

Таблица 1. Морфофизиологические и биохимические показатели плазмы крови *Myotis dasycneme* (самцы + самки) из уральских природных популяций в период годового жизненного цикла**Table 1.** Morphophysiological and biochemical parameters in the blood plasma of *Myotis dasycneme* (males + females) from the Urals populations during the annual life cycle

I. Лето (n = 24) ♂ (n = 13), ♀ (n = 11)	II. Осень (n = 12) ♂ (n = 6), ♀ (n = 6)	III. Зима (n = 19) ♂ (n = 9), ♀ (n = 10)	IV. Весна (n = 10) ♂ (n = 5), ♀ (n = 5)
Масса тела, г			
♂ + ♀ 14.7 ± 0.2 (14.3–15.1)	♂ + ♀ 16.8 ± 0.6* (15.5–18.0)	♂ + ♀ 13.4 ± 0.4* [▲] (12.7–14.1)	♂ + ♀ 11.3 ± 0.3* [▲] (10.8–12.0)
Потребление O ₂ (pO ₂), мл/г × час			
♂ + ♀ 3.9 ± 0.4 (3.1–4.7)	♂ + ♀ 5.6 ± 0.4* (4.8–6.4)	♂ + ♀ 6.4 ± 0.5* (5.5–7.3)	♂ + ♀ 6.1 ± 0.6* (4.9–7.3)
Ректальная температура, t, °C			
♂ 28.8 ± 1.7 (25.3–32.1) ♀ 32.2 ± 0.3 (31.7–33.0)	♂ 35.2 ± 0.3* (34.6–35.7) ♀ 33.1 ± 1.4 (30.1–35.1)	♂ 32.5 ± 0.4 [▲] (31.7–33.3) ♀ 26.0 ± 1.7* ^{▲@} (22.8–29.4)	♂ 15.5 ± 0.8* [▲] (13.9–17.1) ♀ 26.5 ± 2.8* [@] (21.2–31.5)
Глюкоза, ммоль/л			
♂ + ♀ 3.0 ± 0.3 (2.4–3.6)	♂ + ♀ 4.1 ± 0.4* (3.4–4.9)	♂ + ♀ 4.7 ± 0.5* (3.8–5.7)	♂ + ♀ 3.1 ± 0.6 (2.1–4.4)
Триглицериды, ммоль/л			
♂ + ♀ 0.5 ± 0.1 (0.4–0.7)	♂ + ♀ 0.3 ± 0.0* (0.2–0.4)	♂ 0.7 ± 0.1 (0.3–0.7) ♀ 0.9 ± 0.2 [▲] (0.6–1.2)	–
Мочевина, мкмоль/л			
♂ + ♀ 731.2 ± 119.5 (500.5–969.8)	♂ + ♀ 672.9 ± 159.4 (411.3–1021.1)	♂ + ♀ 640.5 ± 145.5 (389.8–956.4)	♂ + ♀ 772.2 ± 174.7 (473.5–1159.8)

Примечание: Обозначения статистически значимых различий между группами: * – I и II, I и III, I и IV (p < 0.05); [▲] – II и III, II и IV (p < 0.05); [†] – III и IV (p < 0.05); [@] – половые различия (p < 0.05); M_{boot} ± SE_{boot} – среднее арифметическое и ошибка среднего бутстреп-распределения; (95% CI_{boot}) – доверительный интервал бутстреп-распределения.

Повышение уровня метаболизма (p < 0.05) в февральский период торпора при действии околонулевых температур в сравнении с осенним периодом подготовки к гипобиозу сопровождается увеличением содержания в крови триглицеридов (ответственных за липидный обмен) в три раза у самок (0.9 ± 0.2 ммоль/л) и в 2.3 раза у самцов (0.7 ± 0.1 ммоль/л) (p < 0.05). В летний и осенний периоды в плазме крови животных не выявлено статистически значимых половых различий по содержанию глюкозы и триглицеридов (p > 0.05). Триглицериды в зимний период поддерживают в пределах физиологического жизнеобеспечения температуру тела самок 26.0 ± 0.7°C (p < 0.05) и самцов 32.5 ± 0.4°C (p < 0.05). У исследуемых животных концентрация мочевины оставалась постоянной в течение года и не зависит от половой принадлежности (p > 0.05); также отсутствуют колебания в сезонные периоды (p > 0.05) (табл. 1). Кровь рукокрылых при отсутствии значимых половых различий (p > 0.05) характеризуется высоким уровнем содержания гемоглобина, гематокрита и эритроцитов, что согласуется с результатами исследований Vandouchova et al. (2020) (табл. 2).

Во все сезоны годового жизненного цикла у летучих мышей отмечено отсутствие статистически значимых различий по концентрации гемоглобина (HGB: 167.9–187.2 г/л, p > 0.05), гематокрита (HCT: 47.2–51.5%, p > 0.05), среднего содержания гемоглобина в эритроците (MCH: 15.9–17.6 пг, p > 0.05), средней концентрации гемоглобина в эритроците (MCHC: 343.8–380.3 г/л, p > 0.05). Наблюдаемое снижение среднего объема эритроцита (MCV) осенью на 5% и зимой на 9%, в сравнении с летним периодом (p < 0.05) способствует возрастанию скорости поглощения кислорода гемоглобином в кровеносном русле, повышая качество газообмена (табл. 2). В осенне-зимний период и весной у *M. dasycneme* отмечено повышение циркулирующих в крови тромбоцитов (PLT = 256.2–271.3 г/л, p < 0.05) и тромбокриты (PCT = 0.16–0.17%, p < 0.05). Нами показано, что абсолютное содержание лимфоцитов в крови самок во все сезоны значимо выше, чем у самцов летом в 2.0 раза, осенью в 2.3 раза, зимой в 1.7 раза, весной в 1.8 раза (p < 0.05) (табл. 3). Количественное содержание моноцитов, продуцирующих провоспалительные цитокины, у

самок значительно выше, чем у самцов в летний период (в 4.3 раза) и в 2.5 раза в период глубокой зимней спячки ($p < 0.05$). У зимующих самцов и самок летучих мышей, находящихся в состоянии гибернации, количество моноцитов значительно возрастает в сравнении с летним сезоном ($p < 0.05$). Анализ показал отсутствие в крови животных индикаторов клеточных воспалительных и аллергических реакций замедленного типа (базофильных гранулоцитов) (табл. 3). Динамика процентного содержания лимфоцитов, обеспечивающих значительную эффективность клеточного иммунитета, показана как у самцов (37.8–46.6%), так и у самок (37.8–51.7%) в течение всего года (табл. 3). В лимфоцитарно-гранулоцитарном составе крови летом у самок преобладают агранулоциты (54.1%), а у самцов гранулоциты (53.6%) ($p < 0.05$). В осенне-зимний период гибернации отмечается в крови самок и самцов повышенное содержание агранулоцитов (50.6–53.6%). При этом у животных отмечено отсутствие половых различий и по процентному содержанию гранулоцитов в периферической крови (47.1–49.4%, $p > 0.05$) (табл. 3).

Качественный состав аминокислотного спектра плазмы крови исследованных особей *Myotis dasycneme* представлен 22 АК. Отмечен полный спектр функционально значимых незаменимых АК (треонин, валин, лизин, лейцин, изолейцин, метионин, фе-

нилаланин, аргинин, гистидин, триптофан). Многомерный непараметрический анализ показал отсутствие половых различий у рукокрылых по концентрации 14 свободных АК в сезонные периоды их годового жизненного цикла, включая таурин, аспарат, треонин, серин, глутамин, аланин, валин, изолейцин, лейцин, тирозин, триптофан, лизин, гистидин, аргинин ($p > 0.05$). Исследование сезонных особенностей аминокислотного обмена *M. dasycneme* показало, что фонд свободных АК в плазме крови самцов и самок снижается по сезонам: лето \geq осень \geq зима $>$ весна ($p < 0.05$). Максимальные концентрации свободных АК в плазме крови (у самцов – 1500.6 ± 269.4 мкмоль/л и у самок – 1355.1 ± 130.4 мкмоль/л) наблюдали летом в период активного размножения и набора массы тела (14.7 ± 0.2 г) рукокрылых. В заключительный период гибернации (первая декада апреля) в крови весенних особей *M. dasycneme* наблюдаемая гипоаминоацидемия проявляется в падении общего фонда свободных АК в 2.3 раза (664.6 ± 75.2 мкмоль/л, $p < 0.05$) у самцов и в 1.9 раза (698.9 ± 51.9 мкмоль/л, $p < 0.05$) у самок. Значительная аккумуляция метаболически активной группы глюкогенных аминокислот, имеющих ролевое значение в межклеточном обмене (аланин, глутамин, глицин, глутамат), выявлена в крови рукокрылых в летний (66%) и осенний (75%) периоды (рис. 1).

Таблица 2. Сезонная динамика показателей периферической крови *Myotis dasycneme* (самцы + самки) из уральских природных популяций

Table 2. Seasonal dynamics of peripheral blood indicators of *Myotis dasycneme* (males + females) from the Urals populations

Показатели	I. Лето (n = 10)	II. Осень (n = 15)	III. Зима (n = 16)	IV. Весна (n = 10)
Эритроциты (RBC), $10^{12}/л$	9.6 ± 0.3 (9.0–10.2)	$10.8 \pm 0.3^*$ (10.2–11.4)	$11.5 \pm 0.4^*$ (10.9–12.2)	10.6 ± 0.5 (9.6–11.6)
Гемоглобин (HGB), г/л	167.9 ± 6.3 (155.5–180.3)	173.0 ± 5.1 (161.7–180.6)	187.2 ± 4.9 (177.9–197.0)	180.1 ± 4.8 (170.4–189.2)
Гематокритный показатель (HCT), %	47.2 ± 1.5 (44.3–50.2)	50.1 ± 1.1 (47.8–52.2)	51.5 ± 1.3 (49.1–54.1)	47.5 ± 1.5 (44.6–50.3)
Средний объем эритроцита (MCV), фл	49.1 ± 0.4 (48.3–49.9)	$46.7 \pm 0.5^*$ (45.7–47.5)	$45.3 \pm 0.7^*$ (43.9–46.8)	$45.2 \pm 1.3^*$ (42.8–47.8)
Среднее содержание HGB в эритроците (MCH), пг	17.6 ± 0.6 (16.2–18.6)	15.9 ± 0.6 (14.7–17.0)	16.5 ± 0.5 (15.5–17.5)	17.3 ± 1.0 (15.7–19.4)
Средняя концентрация HGB в эритроците (MCHC), г/л	365.8 ± 6.3 (354.9–379.4)	343.8 ± 11.3 (318.9–363.9)	364.1 ± 6.3 (352.6–377.0)	380.3 ± 11.8 (360.1–405.6)
Тромбоциты (PLT), $10^9/л$	136.8 ± 14.3 (109.2–165.2)	$267.3 \pm 18.7^*$ (230.0–303.0)	$256.2 \pm 19.7^*$ (217.7–295.2)	$271.3 \pm 24.4^*$ (227.3–321.9)
Средний объем тромбоцитов (MPV), фл	5.8 ± 0.2 (5.5–6.1)	$6.4 \pm 0.1^*$ (6.2–6.6)	$6.3 \pm 0.1^*$ (6.1–6.6)	$6.3 \pm 0.1^*$ (6.1–6.5)
Тромбокрит (PCT), %	0.08 ± 0.01 (0.06–0.09)	$0.16 \pm 0.01^*$ (0.13–0.18)	$0.16 \pm 0.01^*$ (0.14–0.19)	$0.17 \pm 0.02^*$ (0.14–0.21)

Примечание: * – обозначения статистически значимых различий: I и II, I и III, I и IV ($p < 0.05$); $M_{boot} \pm SE_{boot}$ – среднее арифметическое и ошибка среднего бутстреп-распределения; (95% CI_{boot}) – доверительный интервал бутстреп-распределения.

Таблица 3. Лейкоцитарный состав периферической крови *Myotis dasycneme* из уральских природных популяций
Table 3. Leukocyte composition of peripheral blood of *Myotis dasycneme* from the Urals populations

Показатели	Пол	I. Лето n: ♂(5)/♀(5)	II. Осень n: ♂(7)/♀(8)	III. Зима n: ♂(9)/♀(7)	IV. Весна n: ♂(5)/♀(5)
Лейкоциты, 10 ⁹ /л	♂	1.6 ± 0.1 (1.5–1.8)	2.3 ± 0.3 (1.9–2.9)	1.2 ± 0.2 [▲] (0.9–1.5)	2.0 ± 0.3 [†] (1.71–2.65)
	♀	2.8 ± 0.1 [@] (2.7–3.0)	4.7 ± 0.2 ^{*@} (4.3–5.1)	2.2 ± 0.1 ^{*▲@} (1.9–2.5)	3.7 ± 0.3 ^{*▲@} (3.1–4.3)
Лимфоциты, 10 ⁹ /л	♂	0.7 ± 0.1 (0.6–0.9)	1.1 ± 0.1 (0.9–1.3)	0.6 ± 0.1 [▲] (0.4–0.7)	0.8 ± 0.1 (0.6–1.1)
	♀	1.4 ± 0.1 [@] (1.3–1.5)	2.4 ± 0.1 ^{*@} (2.2–2.7)	1.0 ± 0.1 ^{*▲@} (0.8–1.1)	1.4 ± 0.1 ^{▲@} (1.2–1.6)
Моноциты, 10 ⁹ /л	♂	0.03 ± 0.01 (0.002–0.06)	0.11 ± 0.03 (0.05–0.17)	0.08 ± 0.02 (0.05–0.11)	0.18 ± 0.04 ^{*†} (0.12–0.26)
	♀	0.13 ± 0.02 [@] (0.08–0.17)	0.09 ± 0.02 (0.06–0.12)	0.20 ± 0.03 ^{▲@} (0.16–0.26)	0.29 ± 0.04 ^{*▲} (0.22–0.37)
Нейтрофилы, %	♂	52.8 ± 1.6 (49.8–55.8)	48.3 ± 1.7 (44.9–51.4)	45.6 ± 1.3 (43.0–48.0)	52.6 ± 1.5 (49.4–55.4)
	♀	47.0 ± 3.0 (41.2–53.2)	47.4 ± 1.0 (45.5–49.5)	45.4 ± 1.6 (42.1–48.3)	52.4 ± 0.9 (49.6–54.0)
юные, %	♂	8.4 ± 2.8 (3.2–14.2)	2.4 ± 0.4 [*] (1.7–3.1)	1.8 ± 0.4 [*] (1.1–2.6)	5.6 ± 0.4 ^{*†} (5.0–6.4)
	♀	2.6 ± 0.6 [@] (1.6–3.8)	1.8 ± 0.2 (1.5–2.2)	3.6 ± 0.6 (2.4–4.6)	3.8 ± 0.5 [▲] (2.8–4.8)
палочкоядерные, %	♂	24.4 ± 2.5 (20.6–29.8)	19.3 ± 2.1 (15.4–23.6)	14.1 ± 1.1 [*] (12.0–16.3)	21.0 ± 0.8 [†] (19.2–22.4)
	♀	32.6 ± 2.3 (28.4–37.6)	19.6 ± 1.3 [*] (17.4–22.3)	14.6 ± 0.7 [*] (13.1–16.0)	22.8 ± 1.3 ^{*†} (20.4–25.2)
сегментоядерные, %	♂	20.0 ± 3.9 (11.6–26.2)	26.6 ± 2.8 (20.9–31.7)	29.7 ± 1.3 (27.2–32.0)	26.0 ± 1.1 (24.0–28.0)
	♀	11.8 ± 4.1 (4.2–20.0)	26.0 ± 0.7 [*] (24.5–27.3)	27.3 ± 1.3 [*] (24.6–29.6)	25.8 ± 0.7 [*] (24.6–27.2)
Лимфоциты, %	♂	44.6 ± 1.5 (42.2–47.8)	46.2 ± 1.0 (44.1–48.0)	46.6 ± 1.1 (44.3–48.8)	37.8 ± 1.7 ^{*†} (34.6–41.2)
	♀	49.5 ± 2.1 (45.0–53.0)	51.7 ± 0.9 [@] (50.1–53.5)	43.6 ± 1.6 [▲] (40.4–46.9)	37.8 ± 0.5 ^{*†} (36.8–38.8)
Моноциты, %	♂	1.8 ± 0.9 (0.2–3.6)	4.4 ± 1.0 (2.6–6.4)	6.1 ± 0.8 [*] (4.6–7.6)	9.0 ± 1.2 ^{*▲} (6.6–11.2)
	♀	4.6 ± 0.8 (3.0–6.2)	1.9 ± 0.3 (1.3–2.6)	9.3 ± 1.0 ^{*@} (7.7–11.4)	8.0 ± 1.0 [▲] (6.0–10.0)
Эозинофилы, %	♂	0.8 ± 0.3 (0.2–1.4)	1.1 ± 0.4 (0.4–1.9)	1.8 ± 0.4 (0.9–2.6)	0.6 ± 0.4 (0.0–1.4)
	♀	1.2 ± 0.3 (0.6–1.8)	0.8 ± 0.2 (0.4–1.0)	1.7 ± 0.4 (1.0–2.4)	1.8 ± 0.3 (1.2–2.4)

Примечание: * – статистически значимые различия: I и II, I и III, I и IV (p < 0.05); ▲ – статистически значимые различия: II и III, II и IV (p < 0.05); † – статистически значимые различия: III и IV (p < 0.05); @ – половые различия (p < 0.05); M_{boot} ± SE_{boot} – среднее арифметическое и ошибка среднего бутстреп-распределения; (95% CI_{boot}) – доверительный интервал бутстреп-распределения.

Рис. 1. Сезонная динамика метаболических групп свободных аминокислот (% от общего пула) в плазме крови *Myotis dasycneme* из уральских природных популяций. Обозначения: ГТАК – глюкогенные аминокислоты (АК), ЗАК – заменимые АК, НАК – незаменимые АК, ССАК – серосодержащие АК, АКРУЦ – АК с разветвленной углеродной цепью, АРАК – ароматические АК; p – уровень значимости двухфакторного дисперсионного анализа с перестановочным тестом (рандомизация).
Fig. 1. Seasonal dynamics of metabolic groups of free amino acids (% of the total pool) in the blood plasma in *Myotis dasycneme* populations from the Urals. Designations: ГТАК – glucocogenic amino acids (AA), ЗАК – nonessential AA, НАК – essential AA, ССАК – sulfur containing AA, АКРУЦ – AA with branched carbon chains, АРАК – aromatic AA; p – the significance level of a two-factor analysis of variance with a permutation test (randomisation).

По содержанию метаболических групп АК (ГТАК – глюкогенных, ЗАК – заменимых, АКРУЦ – с разветвленной углеродной цепью) не выявлено половых различий ($p > 0.05$) (рис. 1). Это, несомненно, указывает на единство обменных процессов, направленных на поддержание гомеостаза, обеспечивающего возможность выживания животных во время длительного 5–7-месячного периода гибернации как у самцов, так и у самок. У животных после длительного пребывания в состоянии гипобиоза содержание серосодержащих АК (ССАК: цистеин, таурин, метионин) весной возрастает в 2.3 раза у самцов и в 2.2 раза у самок. Это, несомненно, связано с участием данных АК в синтезе нуклеиновых кислот, коллагена и других белков в предстоящий период активного летнего роста и развития (рис. 1). В плазме крови показана специфичность метаболизма аминокислот с разветвленной углеродной цепью (АКРУЦ), участвующих в качестве регуляторов и стимуляторов физиологических функций исследованных летучих мышей. Максимальные суммарные концентрации АКРУЦ (валин, изолейцин, лейцин), являющихся дополнительным источником энергии и обладающих иммуномодулирующими свойствами, характерны для плазмы крови летних особей рукокрылых, а минимальные – для весенних особей. При этом осенью и зимой наблюдается их пониженный уровень ($p < 0.05$). По процентному содержанию пула АКРУЦ, защищающих мышечные волокна от окисления и деструкции, половых и сезонных значимых различий не выявлено, что, несомненно, важно в условиях интенсивных нагрузок и стресса летучих мышей в течение всего периода наблюдений (осень–зима–весна) ($p > 0.05$) (рис. 1). При изучении половых особенностей рукокрылых по уровню содержания основных метаболических групп АК в плазме крови летних особей обнаружено, что самки отличаются от самцов более высоким пулом серосодержащих АК (181.3 мкмоль/л, при $p < 0.05$) при понижении пула ароматических АК (АРАК: фенилаланин, тирозин) на 60% ($p < 0.05$). Необходимо отметить, что для плазмы крови летних самцов в сравнении с самками характерно высокое содержание не только АРАК, но и пула незаменимых АК. В остальные сезоны года значимых различий по процентному содержанию этой группы АК в плазме крови не выявлено, что можно объяснить однонаправленностью физиологических функций, связанных с поддержанием гомеостаза в условиях длительного воздействия низких положительных температур (рис. 1).

В осенний и зимний периоды в условиях низких положительных температур в плазме крови *Myotis dasycneme* наблюдается эффект исчезновения незаменимой АК триптофана ($p < 0.05$). В период пробуждения животных от спячки в первой декаде апреля и летом в период воспроизводства популяции и активации синтеза альбуминов и глобулинов отмечается присутствие триптофана в плазме крови. К третьей декаде февраля в период продолжительного гипобиоза, длящегося более полугодом, в крови отмечено значительное ($p < 0.05$) снижение общего фонда АК (у самцов на 42% и у самок на 29%). Однако на фоне снижения общего фонда свободных АК в плазме крови *M. dasycneme* вклад таурина в завершающий весенний период выхода из гипобиоза возрастает в 3.3 раза у самок и в 6.5 раза у самцов ($p < 0.05$), что также отмечено в немногочисленных исследованиях других видов животных (Karapova, 2009a,b, 2011). Достаточно интенсивная аккумуляция серосодержащей сульфаминокислоты таурина весной существенно компенсирует снижение пулов таких АК, как аланин в 1.9 раза, валин в 2.3 раза, аспарат в 4.0 раза, треонин в 3.3 раза, глутамин в 2.2 раза, глицин в 4.9 раза ($p < 0.05$). Специфика низкотемпературной адаптации рукокрылых проявляется в падении до следовых количеств концентраций заменимых АК аспарагина, цистеина и незаменимых АК аргинина и триптофана у самцов и самок *M. dasycneme* в сезонные периоды их годового жизненного цикла (рис. 1).

Методом главных компонент визуализирована половая и сезонная специфика спектра 22 АК в плазме крови самцов и самок *Myotis dasycneme* в различные периоды их годового жизненного цикла. Это подтверждает результаты представленно-го выше статистического анализа (рис. 2).

Анализ сезонной динамики свободных АК в плазме крови *Myotis dasycneme* показал, что 20.98% общей дисперсии приходится на первую главную компоненту PC1, 19.30% – на вторую PC2 и 14.38% – на третью PC3. Показано, что PC1 дифференцировала животных по изучаемым параметрам (процентное содержание аминокислот) на две сезонные группы: весенние и летние + осенние + зимние. Из рис. 2 видна четкая пространственная обособленность самцов и самок весенней группы. Самый высокий вклад в PC1 вносят таурин, треонин, цистеиновая кислота и серин (48.72%). Для данных аминокислот отмечены высокие значимые коэффициенты корреляции с PC1: -0.86 (таурин), 0.80 (треонин), -0.71 (цистеиновая кислота), 0.67 (серин) ($p < 0.05$) (рис. 2).

Рис. 2. Свободные аминокислоты плазмы крови *Myotis dasycneme* (% от общего фонда) из уральских природных популяций в период годового жизненного цикла в пространстве первых трех главных компонент. Обозначения: PC1, PC2 – оси главных компонент, % – процент дисперсии данных, объясненных главной компонентой. Стрелки отражают корреляцию главных компонент с исходными показателями (аминокислоты). Эллипсы представляют собой 95% доверительные области; А – биplot PC1 и PC2, В – биplot PC1 и PC3; Cya – цистеиновая кислота, Tau – таурин, Asp – аспарагиновая кислота, Thr – треонин, Ser – серин, Asn – аспарагин, Glu – глутаминовая кислота, Gln – глутамин, Gly – глицин, Ala – аланин, Val – валин, Cys – цистеин, Met – метионин, Ile – изолейцин, Leu – лейцин, Tyr – тирозин, Phe – фенилаланин, Trp – триптофан, Orn – орнитин, Lys – лизин, His – гистидин, Arg – аргинин.

Fig. 2. Free amino acids in *Myotis dasycneme* blood plasma (% of the total pool) in the Urals populations during the annual life cycle in the environment of the first three main components. Designations: PC1, PC2 – are the principal component axes, % is the percentage of data variance explained by the principal components; arrows reflect the correlation of the main components with the initial indicators (amino acids); ellipses represent 95% confidence areas; A – biplot PC1 and PC2, B – biplot PC1 and PC3; Cya – cysteic acid, Tau – taurine, Asp – aspartic acid, Thr – threonine, Ser – serine, Asn – asparagine, Glu – glutamic acid, Gln – glutamine, Gly – glycine, Ala – alanine, Val – valine, Cys – cysteine, Met – methionine, Ile – isoleucine, Leu – leucine, Tyr – tyrosine, Phe – phenylalanine, Trp – tryptophan, Orn – ornithine, Lys – lysine, His – histidine, Arg – arginine.

Вторая главная компонента, как и первая, отражает сезонные различия аминокислотного состава плазмы крови *Myotis dasycneme*, но уже по другим аминокислотам, процентное содержание большинства из которых максимально летом. Показана корреляционная связь следующих АК с PC2: цистеина (-0.77), аспарагина (-0.73) изолейцина (-0.67), аспарагиновой кислоты (-0.66), триптофана (-0.65), глицина (-0.57) и аланина (0.47) ($p < 0.05$). Вклад цистеина, аспарагина, изолейцина, аспарагиновой кислоты, триптофана во вторую компоненту составляет 54.75%. По этим переменным PC2 отделяет летних самцов и самок *M. dasycneme* от особей остальных сезонных групп (рис. 2). Все вышеперечисленные АК, за исключением аланина, преобладают в процентном содержании от общего фонда у самцов и самок в летний период. Максимальное процентное содержание аланина в плазме крови рукокрылых отмечено в осенне-зимний период. PC3 определяет половые различия *M. dasycneme* в сезонной динамике аминокислот. Третья

главная компонента отделяет летних самцов от осенних, зимних и весенних особей. Аминокислотный спектр плазмы крови у самок в зимний и весенний периоды отличается по PC3 от летних и осенних особей (рис. 2). Выявленная половая дифференциация аминокислотного спектра плазмы крови *M. dasycneme*, несомненно, связана с физиологическими особенностями самцов и самок в период размножения, роста и развития.

Обсуждение

Впервые представлен сравнительный анализ эколого-физиологических параметров гомеостаза охраняемого вида фауны Урала *Myotis dasycneme* в сезонные периоды годового жизненного цикла. При статистически значимых различиях по массе тела и основного обмена у исследованных животных, независимо от их половой принадлежности, зарегистрированы активация основного обмена, стабильный уровень содержания глюкозы в крови в осенний и зимний периоды. Заслуживает внимания роль углеводов как легкодоступного энергетиче-

ческого материала, покрывающего основные физиологические потребности организма быстрее, чем жиры и белки (Meng et al., 2016). Отмечается термозащитная роль триглицеридов в плазме крови летучих мышей. Значение триглицеридов для нормального функционирования организма в условиях низких температур показано и другими исследователями (Wang et al., 1997; Storey, 2012).

Учитывая, что устойчивая адаптация обеспечивается оптимально отрегулированными физиологическими процессами, особое значение приобретает исследование крови как функциональной системы *Myotis dasycneme* в условиях, связанных с их сезонным жизненным циклом (Bandouchova et al., 2020). Многомерный непараметрический дисперсионный анализ показал отсутствие значимых половых различий у летучих мышей по исследованным параметрам красной крови ($p > 0.05$). Это, несомненно, отражает универсальность адаптивной реакции самцов и самок на поддержание их гомеостаза. Параметры периферической крови особей *M. dasycneme* (HGB, HCT, MCH, MCHC) характеризуются невысокой вариабельностью в период подготовки к зимней спячке и во время гибернации (осень, зима, весна) в сравнении с летними животными ($p > 0.05$). Выявлены существенные изменения в функциональной активности системы крови (RBC, MCV, PLT, MPV, PCT) у самцов и самок *M. dasycneme* в условиях, связанных с их сезонным жизненным циклом ($p < 0.05$). Двукратное повышение циркулирующих в крови *M. dasycneme* тромбоцитов и тромбокрита ($p < 0.05$) в осенне-зимний и весенний периоды по сравнению с активными летними животными указывает на возросшую долю объема цельной крови, занимаемой тромбоцитами, участвующими в качестве эффекторов иммунной системы (Хаитов, 2013; Шахматов и др., 2014). Гипотермическое воздействие (осень-зима-весна) способствует возникновению состояния тромботической активности: возрастает количество тромбоцитов и их агрегационная способность, угнетается фибринолитическая активность плазмы крови животных (Шахматов и др., 2014). Следует отметить и отсутствие в крови рукокрылых базофильных гранулоцитов, являющихся основными депо гистамина, гепарина и серотонина (Черешнев и др., 2007; Хаитов, 2013).

Лейкоцитарный состав крови рукокрылых, как и у всех позвоночных, представлен двумя группами клеток: гранулоциты (гетерофилы, эозинофилы), ответственные за проявление реакции врожденного иммунитета и агранулоциты

(моноциты, лимфоциты), ответственные за проявление реакции адаптивного иммунного ответа (Davis et al., 2008). Механизмы врожденного иммунитета обеспечивают как первоначальную защиту, так и стимулируют иммунные реакции в организме рукокрылых. Лимфоциты, как основа гуморального иммунитета, ограничивают распространение инфекций, выполняя функцию иммунного надзора в организме, и отвечают за формирование общего и специфического иммунитета (Baker et al., 2013; Schountz, 2014). Лейкоцитарные клетки периферической крови *Myotis dasycneme* подвержены определенным колебаниям в различные сезонные периоды года. В крови самцов и самок *M. dasycneme* не отмечено сезонных значимых изменений в процентном соотношении группы гранулоцитарных лейкоцитов (палочкоядерные, сегментоядерные, эозинофилы), что, по всей вероятности, обусловлено идентичностью механизмов их врожденного (естественного) иммунитета. Следует отметить значимую роль нейтрофилов в обеспечении неспецифической формы лейкоцитарной защиты системы крови на широкий спектр патогенов среды обитания *M. dasycneme*. Показаны значимые половые и сезонные изменения в крови *M. dasycneme* по содержанию гранулоцитарных лейкоцитов (палочкоядерные, сегментоядерные нейтрофилы) в осенний период подготовки животных к гипобиозу, в состоянии торпора зимой и при весеннем пробуждении ($p < 0.05$). При сопоставлении сезонной динамики гематологических параметров животных прослеживаются и единые закономерности в активации иммунных процессов. Так, репрезентативным показателем усиления пресса сезонной (осень и зима) холодовой и гипоксической нагрузки на организм является повышенный уровень агранулоцитов в крови самцов и самок (50.6–53.5%), обеспечивающих иммунный «надзор» и специфическую реактивность организма *M. dasycneme* (адаптивный иммунитет). Возросшее содержание моноцитов, продуцирующих провоспалительные цитокины, в осенне-зимний период иллюстрирует модуляцию иммунной системы на поддержание адаптивного потенциала животных к патогенному спектру антигенов низкотемпературной среды их обитания (Coico et al., 2003; Zimmerman et al., 2014). Установлено, что лейкоцитарный состав крови исследованных летучих мышей поддерживается на базовом уровне за счет перестройки соотношения клеток гранулоцитарного и агранулоцитарного рядов. У самцов и самок весенний процесс пробуждения и

выход из глубокой гипотермии сопровождаются значимой реактивностью системы врожденного иммунитета (гранулоциты: 53.2–54.2%, $p > 0.05$), обеспечивающей неспецифическую срочную защиту организма, в том числе и для предотвращения вирусной инвазии до выработки специфической защиты адаптивной иммунной системой (Koyama et al., 2008).

Известно, что в формировании адаптивных изменений в метаболических и молекулярных механизмах поддержания гомеостаза в организме значимая роль принадлежит полифункциональным свободным аминокислотам (Bruhat et al., 2009; Wu, 2009; Гараева и др., 2009). Проведенные исследования подтверждают связующую роль полифункциональных аминокислот в интеграции основных метаболических процессов. Это связано не только с энергетическим обменом, но и с обеспечением клеточного и гуморального иммунитета при формировании адаптивной стратегии, обеспечивающей устойчивость популяционного гомеостаза *Myotis dasycneme* в экстремальных условиях среды, протяженных во времени. У летучих мышей, находящихся в состоянии гибернации практически отсутствуют половые различия по количественной структуре аминокислотного спектра, что, несомненно, указывает на единство обменных процессов самцов и самок, направленных на поддержание гомеостаза в условиях длительного воздействия низких положительных и околонулевых температур.

Известно, что аланин-глюкозный цикл непосредственно связан с межклеточным обменом белков, жиров и углеводов. Наблюдается значительная аккумуляция метаболически активного глюкостатического аланина в крови *M. dasycneme* в осенний и зимний периоды. По данным исследований Озернюк (2003), Kaganova (2011), экстрагируемый из кровотока печенью аланин не только сам включается в этап образования углеводов, но и активизирует скорость синтеза гликогена и глюкозы, что предполагает криопротекторную роль аминокислоты в условиях низкоположительных и околонулевых температур среды обитания. Весной при выходе животных из гипобриоза в плазме крови отмечали снижение в общем фонде свободных АК пула глюкостатических АК до 46.4%. Однако на фоне снижения общего фонда свободных АК в плазме крови *M. dasycneme* в завершающий весенний период гибернации обращает на себя внимание достоверное четырехкратное возрастание содержания таурина, обладающего антиоксидантными и мембраностабилизирующими

свойствами. Таурин, как сульфаминокислота с иммуностимулирующими свойствами участвует и в активации лимфоцитов и, обладая выраженным антиоксидантным действием, подавляет агрегационную способность тромбоцитов (Engel et al., 2006). Серосодержащим АК (ССАК) принадлежит связующая роль в интеграции основных метаболических процессов, поскольку уровень свободных аминокислот и их производных является регулирующим фактором многих узловых звеньев метаболизма (Северин, 2004). У осенних особей летучих мышей необходимо отметить существенный расход тирозина и фенилаланина, как предшественников катехоламинов (адреналина и норадреналина), играющих важную роль в функционировании механизмов зимней спячки гетеротермных (Rasmussen et al., 1983; Северин, 2004; Kobayashi, 2010). В условиях низких положительных температур в плазме крови самцов и самок *M. dasycneme* наблюдали исчезновение незаменимой АК триптофана. Гипотермический эффект биогенного амина серотонина отмечали исследователи у представителей рода *Spermophilus* (Якименко, Попова, 1976), зимующих *Mesocricetus auratus* (Waterhouse, 1839) (Jansky et al., 1973). Вероятно, отсутствие триптофана является проявлением одного из механизмов низкотемпературной адаптации в результате его полного расходования на синтез серотонина, как одного из триггеров, активно участвующего в поддержании гипотермии и гипометаболизма животных в осенний период подготовки к зимней спячке (Слоним, 1979).

Заключение

Впервые дана эколого-физиологическая оценка гомеостаза охраняемого вида *Myotis dasycneme* хироцерофауны Урала. Результаты исследований позволяют определить связующую роль системы крови и свободных аминокислот в интеграции метаболических процессов, сформировавшихся в ходе эволюции рукокрылых и способствующих их высокой резистентности к ряду экологических факторов: широкому температурному диапазону среды обитания, длительной гибернации, высокой численности выводковых колоний и синантропности. Наряду с выявленными единичными закономерностями поддержания гомеостаза, показана и определена разнонаправленность в мобилизации механизмов аварийного регулирования лимфоидной системы крови самцов и самок *M. dasycneme* в сезонные периоды их годового жизненного цикла.

Таким образом, биохимические и иммуногематологические параметры, определенные в ходе выполненных исследований, позволяют расширить и систематизировать сведения о механизмах участия системы крови в регуляторных процессах организма летучих мышей. Они могут служить основой для осуществления долговременного мониторинга при решении задач сохранения численности здоровых популяций рукокрылых, адаптирующихся как к сезонным модуляциям и биотическим факторам, так и к стрессорам зоонозного значения.

Благодарности

Работа выполнена при поддержке Министерства образования и науки РФ в рамках государственного задания Института экологии растений и животных УрО РАН (№122021000091-2). Авторы выражают признательность В.П. Снитько (Южно-Уральский федеральный научный центр минералогии и геоэкологии УрО РАН, Россия) за существенную помощь во время проведения полевых исследований и М.В. Чибиряку (Институт экологии растений и животных УрО РАН, Россия) за участие в работе по определению параметров основного обмена летучих мышей.

Дополнительная информация

Фотографии объекта исследования и его местообитаний на территории исследований, а также некоторые физиологические показатели (Электронное приложение. Фотографии *Myotis dasycneme*, места обитания, показатели крови на Урале) могут быть найдены в [Электронном приложении](#).

Литература

- Большаков В.Н., Орлов О.Л., Снитько В.П. 2005. Летучие мыши Урала. Екатеринбург: Академкнига. 176 с.
- Гараева С.Н., Редкозубова Г.В., Постолати Г.В. 2009. Аминокислоты в живом организме. Кишнев: Типография Академии Наук Молдовы. 552 с.
- Ильин В.Ю., Смирнов Д.Г., Яняева Н.М. 2002. К фауне, распространению и ландшафтной приуроченности рукокрылых (Chiroptera: Vespertilionidae) Южного Урала и прилегающих территорий // *Plecotus et al.* №5. С. 63–80.
- Камышников В.С. 2004. Справочник по клинико-биохимическим исследованиям и лабораторной диагностике. М.: МЕДПресс-информ. 920 с.
- Ковальчук Л.А., Черная Л.В., Мищенко В.А., Берзин Д.Л., Микшевич Н.В. 2023. Оценка гематологических и биохимических параметров представителя амфибионтов фауны Урала *Salamandrella keyserlingii* (Caudata, Amphibia) // *Nature Conservation Research. Заповедная наука*. Т. 8(1). С. 34–48. DOI: 10.24189/ncr.2023.002
- Красная книга Среднего Урала (Свердловская и Пермская области): Редкие и находящиеся под угрозой исчезновения виды животных и растений. Екатеринбург: Изд-во Уральского университета, 1996. 279 с.
- Кузякин А.П. 1950. Летучие мыши. М.: Советская наука. 444 с.
- Ляпунов А.Н., Панюкова Е.В. 2010. О роли имаго кровососущих комаров (Diptera, Culicidae) в питании рукокрылых (Chiroptera Vespertilionidae) Кировской области // *Теоретическая и прикладная экология*. №4. С. 87–93.
- Озернюк Н.Д. 2003. Феноменология и механизмы адаптационных процессов. М.: МГУ. 215 с.
- Первушина Е.М., Замшина Г.А., Николаева Н.В., Федякина М.А. 2011. Трофические связи насекомоядных рукокрылых на юге Среднего Урала // *Вестник Удмуртского университета. Серия биология. Науки о земле*. №3. С. 65–73.
- Северин Е.С. (ред.). 2004. Биохимия. М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа. 784 с.
- Слоним А.Д. (ред.). 1979. Экологическая физиология животных. Часть. 1. Общая экологическая физиология и физиология адаптаций. Л.: Наука. 440 с.
- Снитько В.П. 2000. Предлагаемые мероприятия по мониторингу рукокрылых в ООПТ Урала // *Координация экомониторинга в ООПТ Урала*. Екатеринбург. С. 239.
- Снитько В.П. 2001. Рукокрылые (Chiroptera) Ильменского заповедника // *Plecotus et al.* №4. С. 69–74.
- Стрелков П.П. 1999. Соотношение полов в сезон вывода потомства у взрослых особей перелетных видов летучих мышей (Chiroptera, Vespertilionidae) Восточной Европы и смежных территорий // *Зоологический журнал*. Т. 78(12). С. 1441–1454.
- Хаитов Р.М. 2013. Иммунология: структура и функции иммунной системы. М.: ГЭОТАР-Медиа. 280 с.
- Черешнев В.А., Ющков Б.Г., Климин В.Г., Буторина Е.В. 2007. Тромбоцитопоз. М.: «Медицина». 270 с.
- Шахматов И.И., Лычева Н.А., Киселев В.И., Вдовин В.М. 2014. Вклад стрессоров различной природы в формировании ответной гемостатической реакции организма при действии общей гипотермии // *Фундаментальные исследования*. №7(1). С. 106–110.
- Шитиков В.К., Розенберг Г.С. 2014. Рандомизация и бутстреп: статистический анализ в биологии и экологии с использованием R. Тольятти: Кассандра. 314 с.
- Якименко М.А., Попова Н.К. 1976. Влияние 5-окситриптофана на сократительный термогенез // *Бюллетень экспериментальной биологии и медицины*. Т. 81(2). С. 230–231.
- Amorim F., Mata V.A., Beja P., Rebelo H. 2015. Effects of a drought episode on the reproductive success of European free-tailed bats (*Tadarida teniotis*) // *Mammalian Biology*. Vol. 80(3). P. 228–236. DOI: 10.1016/j.mambio.2015.01.005
- Baker M.L., Schountz T., Wang L.F. 2013. Antiviral Immune Responses of Bats: A Review // *Zoonoses and Public Health*. Vol. 60(1). P. 104–116. DOI: 10.1111/j.1863-2378.2012.01528.x
- Bandouchova H., Zukal J., Linhart P., Berkova H., Brichta J., Kovacova V., Kubickova A., Abdelsalam E.E.E., Bartonička T., Zajíčková R., Pikula J. 2020. Low sea-

- sonal variation in greater mouse-eared bat (*Myotis myotis*) blood parameters // PLoS ONE. Vol. 15(7). Article: e0234784. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0234784
- Bolshakov V.N., Orlov O.L. 2002. Results of long-term study of bats in Smolinskaja cave Middle Urals // 9th European Bat Research Symposium. Le Havre: University of Le Havre. P. 47.
- Breed A.C., Field H.E., Smith C.S., Edmonston J., Meers J. 2010. Bats without borders: long-distance movements and implications for disease risk management // EcoHealth. Vol. 7(2). P. 204–212. DOI: 10.1007/s10393-010-0332-z
- Bruhat A., Chérasse Y., Chaveroux C., Maurin A.C., Jousse C., Fafournoux P. 2009. Amino acids as regulators of gene expression in mammals: molecular mechanisms // Biofactors. Vol. 35(3). P. 249–257. DOI: 10.1002/biof.40
- Burgin C.J., Colella J.P., Kahn P.L., Upham N.S. 2018. How many species of mammals are there? // Journal of Mammalogy. Vol. 99(1). P. 1–14. DOI: 10.1093/jmammal/gyx147
- Chessel D., Dufour A.B., Thioulouse J. 2004. The ade4 package-I: One-table methods // R News. Vol. 4. P. 5–10.
- Coico R., Sunshine G., Benjamini E. 2003. Immunology. A Short Course. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons Inc. 361 p.
- Davis A.K., Maney D.L., Maerz J.C. 2008. The use of leukocyte profiles to measure stress in vertebrates: a review for ecologists // Functional Ecology. Vol. 22(5). P. 760–772. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2435.2008.01467.x
- Dray S., Dufour A., Thioulouse J. 2022. ade4: Analysis of Ecological Data: Exploratory and Euclidean Methods in Environmental Sciences. R package version 1.7-19. Available from <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ade4>
- Engel J.M., Mühlhling J., Weiss S., Kärcher B., Löhr T., Menges T., Little S., Hempelmann G. 2006. Relationship of taurine and other amino acids in plasma and in neutrophils of septic trauma patients // Amino Acids. Vol. 30(1). P. 87–94. DOI: 10.1007/s00726-005-0238-1
- Fenton M.B., Simmons N.B. 2015. Bats: A world of science and mystery. Oxford: University of Chicago Press. 240 p.
- Flache L., Ekschmitt K., Kierdorf U., Czarnecki S., Düring R.A., Encarnação J.A. 2016. Reduction of metal exposure of Daubenton's bats (*Myotis daubentonii*) following remediation of pond sediment as evidenced by metal concentrations in hair // Science of the Total Environment. Vol. 547. P. 182–189. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.12.131
- Frick W.F., Baerwald E.F., Pollock J.F., Barclay R.M.R., Szymanski J.A., Weller T.J., Russell A.L., Loeb S.C., Medellin R.A., McGuire L.P. 2017. Fatalities at wind turbines may threaten population viability of a migratory bat // Biological Conservation. Vol. 209. P. 172–177. DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2017.02.023
- Frick W.F., Kingston T., Flanders J. 2020. A review of the major threats and challenges to global bat conservation // Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences. Vol. 1469(1). P. 5–25. DOI: 10.1111/nyas.14045
- George D.B., Webb C.T., Farnsworth M.L., O'Shea T.J., Bowen R.A., Smith D.L., Stanley T.R., Ellison L.E., Rupprecht C.E. 2011. Host and viral ecology determine bat rabies seasonality and maintenance // Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America. Vol. 108(25). P. 10208–10213. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1010875108
- Heiker L.M., Adams R.A., Ramos C.V. 2018. Mercury bioaccumulation in two species of insectivorous bats from urban China: influence of species, age, and land use type // Archives of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology. Vol. 75(4). P. 585–593. DOI: 10.1007/s00244-018-0547-5
- IUCN. 2022. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2022-2. Available from <https://www.iucnredlist.org>
- James L.B. 1997. Amino acid analysis: a fall-off in performance // Journal of Chromatography A. Vol. 408. P. 291–295. DOI: 10.1016/s0021-9673(01)81812-4
- Jansky L., Lehouckova M., Vybiral S., Bartunkova R., Stefl B. 1973. Effect of serotonin on thermoregulation of a hibernator (*Mesocricetus auratus*) // Physiologia Bohemoslovaca. Vol. 22(2). P. 115–124.
- Karanova M.V. 2009a. Free amino acid composition in blood and muscle of the gobi *Percottus glehni* at the period of preparation and completion of hibernation // Journal of Evolutionary Biochemistry and Physiology. Vol. 45(1). P. 67–77. DOI: 10.1134/S0022093009010062
- Karanova M.V. 2009b. Glycemia and free sugar levels of the gobi *Percottus glehni* depending on period before the beginning and after the end of hibernation // Journal of Evolutionary Biochemistry and Physiology. Vol. 45(3). P. 382–388. DOI: 10.1134/S0022093009030077
- Karanova M.V. 2011. The effect of cold shock on the free amino acid pool of rotan pondfish *Percottus glehni* (Eleotridae, Perciformes) // Biology Bulletin. Vol. 38(2). P. 116–124. DOI: 10.1134/S106235901102004X
- Kobayashi Y. 2010. The regulatory role of nitric oxide in proinflammatory cytokine expression during the induction and resolution of inflammation // Journal of Leukocyte Biology. Vol. 88(6). P. 1157–1162. DOI: 10.1189/jlb.0310149
- Kohl C., Kurth A. 2014. European bats as carriers of viruses with zoonotic potential // Viruses. Vol. 6(8). P. 3110–3128. DOI: 3390/v6083110
- Kovalchuk L., Mishchenko V., Chernaya L., Snitko V., Mikshevich N. 2017. Haematological parameters of pond bats (*Myotis dasycneme* Boie, 1825 Chiroptera: Vespertilionidae) in the Ural Mountains // Zoology and Ecology. Vol. 27(2). P. 168–175. DOI: 10.1080/21658005.2017.1305153
- Kovalchuk L.A., Mishchenko V.A., Mikshevich N.V., Chernaya L.V., Chibiriyak M.V., Yastrebov A.P. 2018a. Free Amino Acid Profile in Blood Plasma of Bats (*Myotis dasycneme* Boie, 1825) Exposed to Low Positive and Near-Zero Temperatures // Journal of Evolutionary Biochemistry and Physiology. Vol. 54(4). P. 281–291. DOI: 10.1134/S002209301804004
- Kovalchuk L.A., Mishchenko V.A., Chernaya L.V., Snitko V.P. 2018b. Species-specific features of blood plasma amino acid spectrum of bats (Mammalia: Chiroptera) in the Urals // Russian Journal of Ecology. Vol. 49(4). P. 325–331. DOI: 10.1134/S1067413618040082
- Kovalchuk L.A., Mishchenko V.A., Chernaya L.V., Bolshakov V.N. 2021. Characteristic immunohematological parameters of migratory (*Vespertilio murinus* Linnaeus, 1758)

- and resident (*Myotis dasycneme* Boie, 1825) bat species of the ural fauna // Doklady Biological Sciences. Vol. 501(1). P. 210–213. DOI: 10.1134/S001249662106003X
- Kovalchuk L.A., Mishchenko V.A., Chernaya L.V., Snitko V.P., Bolshakov V.N. 2022. Assessment of seasonal variability of the spectrum of free amino acids in the blood plasma of the boreal bat species (*Myotis dasycneme* Boie, 1825) of the Ural fauna // Doklady Biochemistry and Biophysics. Vol. 507(1). P. 268–272. DOI: 10.1134/S1607672922060060
- Koyama S., Ishii K.J., Coban C., Akira S. 2008. Innate immune response to viral infection // Cytokine. Vol. 43(3). P. 336–341. DOI: 10.1016/j.cyto.2008.07.009
- López-Baucells A., Casanova L., Puig-Montserrat X., Espinal A., Páramo F., Flaquer C. 2017. Evaluating the use of *Myotis daubentonii* as an ecological indicator in Mediterranean riparian habitats // Ecological Indicators. Vol. 74. P. 19–27. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.11.012
- Luis A.D., Hayman D.T.S., O’Shea T.J., Cryan P.M., Gilbert A.T., Pulliam J.R.C., Mills J.N., Timonin M.E., Willis C.K.R., Cunningham A.A., Fooks A.R., Rupprecht C.E., Wood J.L.N., Webb C.T. 2013. A comparison of bats and rodents as reservoirs of zoonotic viruses: Are bats special? // Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences. Vol. 280(1756). Article: 20122753. DOI: 10.1098/rspb.2012.2753
- Meng F., Zhu L., Huang W., Irwin D.M., Zhang S. 2016. Bats: Body mass index, forearm mass index, blood glucose levels and SLC2A2 genes for diabetes // Scientific Reports. Vol. 6. Article: 29960. DOI: 10.1038/srep29960
- Mishchenko V.A., Kovalchuk L.A., Bolshakov V.N., Chernaya L.V. 2018. **Comparative Analysis of the Amino Acid Spectrum of Blood Plasma in Chiroptera (*Vespertilio murinus* L., 1758 and *Myotis dasycneme* B., 1825) in the Fauna of the Ural Mountains** // Doklady Biological Sciences. Vol. 481(1). P. 157–159. DOI: 10.1134/S0012496618040105
- Moore M.S., Reichard J.D., Murtha T.D., Nabhan M.L., Pian R.E., Ferreira J.S., Kunz T.H. 2013. Hibernating little brown myotis (*Myotis lucifugus*) show variable immunological responses to white-nose syndrome // PLoS ONE. Vol. 8(3): e58976. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0058976
- O’Shea T.J., Cryan P.M., Cunningham A.A., Fooks A.R., Hayman D.T.S., Luis A.D., Peel A.J., Plowright R.K., Wood J.L.N. 2014. Bat flight and zoonotic viruses // Emerging Infectious Diseases. Vol. 20(5). P. 741–745. DOI: 10.3201/eid2005.130539
- Oksanen J., Simpson G.L., Blanchet F.G., Kindt R., Legendre P., Minchin P.R., O’Hara R.B., Solymos P., Stevens M.H.H., Szoecs E., Wagner H., Barbour M., Bedward M., Bolker B., Borcard D., Carvalho G., Chirico M., Caceres M., Durand S., Evangelista H.B.A., FitzJohn R., Friendly M., Furneaux B., Hannigan G., Hill M.O., Lahti L., McGlenn D., Ouellette M.H., Cunha E.R., Smith T., et al. 2020. vegan: Community Ecology Package. R package. version 2.6-4. Available from <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan>
- Orlova M.V., Orlov O.L., Kshnyasev I.A. 2012. Changes in the abundance of parasitic gamasid mite *Macronyssus corethroproctus* (Oudemans, 1902) during the overwintering period of its host, the pond bat *Myotis dasycneme* (Boie, 1825) // Russian Journal of Ecology. Vol. 43(4). P. 328–332. DOI: 10.1134/S1067413612040108
- Park K.J. 2015. Mitigating the impacts of agriculture on biodiversity: bats and their potential role as bioindicators // Mammalian Biology. Vol. 80(3). P. 191–204. DOI: 10.1016/j.mambio.2014.10.004
- Piraccini R. 2016. *Myotis dasycneme* // The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2016: e.T14127A22055164. Available from <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2016-2.RLTS.T14127A22055164.en>
- R Core Team. 2020. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing. Available from <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Rasmussen D.D., Ishizuka B., Quigley M.E., Yen S.S.C. 1983. Effects of Tyrosine and Tryptophan Ingestion on Plasma Catecholamine and 3,4-Dihydroxyphenylacetic Acid Concentrations // Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism. Vol. 57(4). P. 760–763. DOI: 10.1210/jcem-57-4-760
- Ruiz S.R., Eeva T., Kanerva M., Blomberg A., Lilley T.M. 2019. Metal and metalloid exposure and oxidative status in free-living individuals of *Myotis daubentonii* // Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety. Vol. 169. P. 93–102. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecoenv.2018.10.083
- Russo D., Salinas-Ramos V.B., Cistrone L., Smeraldo S., Bosso L., Ancillotto L. 2021. Do We Need to Use Bats as Bioindicators? // Biology. Vol. 10(8). Article: 693. DOI: 10.3390/biology10080693
- Schountz T. 2014. Immunology of bats and their viruses: challenges and opportunities // Viruses. Vol. 6(12). P. 4880–4901. DOI: 10.3390/v6124880
- Sherwin H.A., Montgomery I., Lundy M.G. 2013. The impact and implications of climate change for bats // Mammal Review. Vol. 43(3). P. 171–182. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2907.2012.00214.x
- Simmons N.B., Cirranello A.L. 2021. Bat Species of the World: A Taxonomic and Geographic Database. Available from <https://batnames.org>
- Storey K.B. 2012. Biochemical regulation of carbohydrate metabolism in hibernating bats // Living in a Seasonal World: Thermoregulatory and Metabolic Adaptations / T. Ruf, C. Bieber, W. Arnold, E. Millesi (Eds.). Chapter 36. Berlin: Springer. P. 411–421. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-28678-0_36
- Tilman D., Clark M., Williams D.R., Kimmel K., Polasky S., Packer C. 2017. Future threats to biodiversity and pathways to their prevention // Nature. Vol. 546(7656). P. 73–81. DOI: 10.1038/nature22900
- Voigt C.C., Kingston T. 2016. Bats in the Anthropocene: Conservation of bats in a Changing World. Cham: Springer. 606 p.
- Wang P., Walter R.D., Bhat B.G., Florant G.L., Coleman R.A. 1997. Seasonal changes in enzymes of lipogenesis and triacylglycerol synthesis in the golden-mantled ground squirrel (*Spermophilus lateralis*) // Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part B: Biochemistry and Molecular Biology. Vol. 118(2). P. 261–267. DOI: 10.1016/s0305-0491(97)00102-8

- Wilkinson G.S., Adams D.M. 2019. Recurrent evolution of extreme longevity in bats // *Biology Letters*. Vol. 15(4). Article: 20180860. DOI: 10.1098/rsbl.2018.0860
- Wray A.K., Jusino M.A., Banik M.T., Palmer J.M., Kaarakka H., White J.P., Lindner D.L., Gratton C., Peery M.Z. 2018. Incidence and taxonomic richness of mosquitoes in the diets of little brown and big brown bats // *Journal of Mammalogy*. Vol. 99(3). P. 668–674. DOI: 10.1093/jmammal/gyy044
- Wu G. 2009. Amino acids: metabolism, functions, and nutrition // *Amino Acids*. Vol. 37(1). P. 1–17. DOI: 10.1007/s00726-009-0269-0
- Yarri D. 2005. *The Ethics of animal experimentation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 240 p.
- Zimmerman L.M., Bowden R.M., Vogel L.A. 2014. A vertebrate cytokine primer for eco-immunologists // *Functional Ecology*. Vol. 28(5). P. 1061–1073. DOI: 10.1111/1365-2435.12273
- Zukal J., Pikula J., Bandouchova H. 2015. Bats as bioindicators of heavy metal pollution: history and prospect // *Mammalian Biology*. Vol. 80(3). P. 220–227. DOI: 10.1016/j.mambio.2015.01.001
- Amorim F., Mata V.A., Beja P., Rebelo H. 2015. Effects of a drought episode on the reproductive success of European free-tailed bats (*Tadarida teniotis*). *Mammalian Biology* 80(3): 228–236. DOI: 10.1016/j.mambio.2015.01.005
- Baker M.L., Schountz T., Wang L.F. 2013. Antiviral Immune Responses of Bats: A Review. *Zoonoses and Public Health* 60(1): 104–116. DOI: 10.1111/j.1863-2378.2012.01528.x
- Bandouchova H., Zukal J., Linhart P., Berkova H., Brichta J., Kovacova V., Kubickova A., Abdelsalam E.E.E., Bartonička T., Zajíčková R., Pikula J. 2020. Low seasonal variation in greater mouse-eared bat (*Myotis myotis*) blood parameters. *PLoS ONE* 15(7): e0234784. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0234784
- Bolshakov V.N., Orlov O.L. 2002. Results of long-term study of bats in Smolinskaja cave Middle Urals. In: *9th European Bat Research Symposium*. Le Havre: University of Le Havre. P. 47.
- Bolshakov V.N., Orlov O.L., Snitko V.P. 2005. *Bats of the Urals*. Yekaterinburg: Akademkniga. 176 p. [In Russian]
- Breed A.C., Field H.E., Smith C.S., Edmonston J., Meers J. 2010. Bats without borders: long-distance movements and implications for disease risk management. *EcoHealth* 7(2): 204–212. DOI: 10.1007/s10393-010-0332-z
- Bruhat A., Chérasse Y., Chaveroux C., Maurin A.C., Jousse C., Fournoux P. 2009. Amino acids as regulators of gene expression in mammals: molecular mechanisms. *Biofactors* 35(3): 249–257. DOI: 10.1002/biof.40
- Burgin C.J., Colella J.P., Kahn P.L., Upham N.S. 2018. How many species of mammals are there?. *Journal of Mammalogy* 99(1): 1–14. DOI: 10.1093/jmammal/gyx147
- Chereshnev V.A., Yushchikov B.G., Klimin V.G., Butorina E.V. 2007. *Thrombocytopoiesis*. Moscow: Medicine. 270 p. [In Russian]
- Chessell D., Dufour A.B., Thioulouse J. 2004. The ade4 package-I: One-table methods. *R News* 4: 5–10.
- Coico R., Sunshine G., Benjamini E. 2003. *Immunology. A Short Course*. Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons Inc. 361 p.
- Davis A.K., Maney D.L., Maerz J.C. 2008. The use of leukocyte profiles to measure stress in vertebrates: a review for ecologists. *Functional Ecology* 22(5): 760–772. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2435.2008.01467.x
- Dray S., Dufour A., Thioulouse J. 2022. *ade4: Analysis of Ecological Data: Exploratory and Euclidean Methods in Environmental Sciences. R package version 1.7-19*. Available from <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ade4>
- Engel J.M., Mühlhling J., Weiss S., Kärcher B., Löhr T., Menges T., Little S., Hempelmann G. 2006. Relationship of taurine and other amino acids in plasma and in neutrophils of septic trauma patients. *Amino Acids* 30(1): 87–94. DOI: 10.1007/s00726-005-0238-1
- Fenton M.B., Simmons N.B. 2015. *Bats: A world of science and mystery*. Oxford: University of Chicago Press. 240 p.
- Flache L., Ekschmitt K., Kierdorf U., Czarnecki S., Düring R.A., Encarnação J.A. 2016. Reduction of metal exposure of Daubenton's bats (*Myotis daubentonii*) following remediation of pond sediment as evidenced by metal concentrations in hair. *Science of the Total Environment* 547: 182–189. DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.12.131
- Frick W.F., Baerwald E.F., Pollock J.F., Barclay R.M.R., Szymanski J.A., Weller T.J., Russell A.L., Loeb S.C., Medellin R.A., McGuire L.P. 2017. Fatalities at wind turbines may threaten population viability of a migratory bat. *Biological Conservation* 209: 172–177. DOI: 10.1016/j.biocon.2017.02.023
- Frick W.F., Kingston T., Flanders J. 2020. A review of the major threats and challenges to global bat conservation. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences* 1469(1): 5–25. DOI: 10.1111/nyas.14045
- Garaeva S.N., Redkozubova G.V., Postolati G.V. 2009. *Amino acids in a living organism*. Kishinev: Printing House of the Academy of Sciences of Moldova. 552 p. [In Russian]
- George D.B., Webb C.T., Farnsworth M.L., O'Shea T.J., Bowen R.A., Smith D.L., Stanley T.R., Ellison L.E., Rupprecht C.E. 2011. Host and viral ecology determine bat rabies seasonality and maintenance. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America* 108(25): 10208–10213. DOI: 10.1073/pnas.1010875108
- Heiker L. M., Adams R. A., Ramos C.V. 2018. Mercury bioaccumulation in two species of insectivorous bats from urban China: influence of species, age, and land use type. *Archives of Environmental Contamination and Toxicology* 75(4): 585–593. DOI: 10.1007/s00244-018-0547-5
- Ilyin V.Yu., Smirnov D.G., Yanyaeva N.M. 2002. On the fauna, distribution and landscape confinement of bats (Chiroptera: Vespertilionidae) of the Southern Urals and adjacent territories. *Plecotus et al.* 5: 63–80. [In Russian]
- IUCN. 2022. *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2022-2*. Available from <https://www.iucnredlist.org>
- James L.B. 1997. Amino acid analysis: a fall-off in performance. *Journal of Chromatography A* 408: 291–295. DOI: 10.1016/s0021-9673(01)81812-4

- Jansky L., Lehouckova M., Vybiral S., Bartunkova R., Steff B. 1973. Effect of serotonin on thermoregulation of a hibernator (*Mesocricetus auratus*). *Physiologia Bohemoslovaca* 22(2): 115–124.
- Kamyshnikov V.S. 2004. *Handbook of clinical and biochemical studies and laboratory diagnostics*. Moscow: MEDPress-inform. 920 p. [In Russian]
- Karanova M.V. 2009a. Free amino acid composition in blood and muscle of the gobi *Percottus glehni* at the period of preparation and completion of hibernation. *Journal of Evolutionary Biochemistry and Physiology* 45(1): 67–77. DOI: 10.1134/S0022093009010062
- Karanova M.V. 2009b. Glycemia and free sugar levels of the gobi *Percottus glehni* depending on period before the beginning and after the end of hibernation. *Journal of Evolutionary Biochemistry and Physiology* 45(3): 382–388. DOI: 10.1134/S0022093009030077
- Karanova M.V. 2011. The effect of cold shock on the free amino acid pool of rotan pondfish *Percottus glehni* (Eleotridae, Perciformes). *Biology Bulletin* 38(2): 116–124. DOI: 10.1134/S106235901102004X
- Khaitov R.M. 2013. *Immunology: structure and function of the immune system*. Moscow: GEOTAR-Media 280 p. [In Russian]
- Kobayashi Y. 2010. The regulatory role of nitric oxide in pro-inflammatory cytokine expression during the induction and resolution of inflammation. *Journal of Leukocyte Biology* 88(6): 1157–1162. DOI: 10.1189/jlb.0310149
- Kohl C., Kurth A. 2014. European bats as carriers of viruses with zoonotic potential. *Viruses* 6(8): 3110–3128. DOI: 3390/v6083110
- Kovalchuk L., Mishchenko V., Chernaya L., Snitko V., Mikshevich N. 2017. Haematological parameters of pond bats (*Myotis dasycneme* Boie, 1825 Chiroptera: Vespertilionidae) in the Ural Mountains. *Zoology and Ecology* 27(2): 168–175. DOI: 10.1080/21658005.2017.1305153
- Kovalchuk L.A., Mishchenko V.A., Mikshevich N.V., Chernaya L.V., Chibiryak M.V., Yastrebov A.P. 2018a. Free Amino Acid Profile in Blood Plasma of Bats (*Myotis dasycneme* Boie, 1825) Exposed to Low Positive and Near-Zero Temperatures. *Journal of Evolutionary Biochemistry and Physiology* 54(4): 281–291. DOI: 10.1134/S002209301804004X
- Kovalchuk L.A., Mishchenko V.A., Chernaya L.V., Snitko V.P. 2018b. Species-specific features of blood plasma amino acid spectrum of bats (Mammalia: Chiroptera) in the Urals. *Russian Journal of Ecology* 49(4): 325–331. DOI: 10.1134/S1067413618040082
- Kovalchuk L.A., Mishchenko V.A., Chernaya L.V., Bolshakov V.N. 2021. Characteristic immunohematological parameters of migratory (*Vespertilio murinus* Linnaeus, 1758) and resident (*Myotis dasycneme* Boie, 1825) bat species of the ural fauna. *Doklady Biological Sciences* 501(1): 210–213. DOI: 10.1134/S001249662106003X
- Kovalchuk L.A., Mishchenko V.A., Chernaya L.V., Snitko V.P., Bolshakov V.N. 2022. Assessment of seasonal variability of the spectrum of free amino acids in the blood plasma of the boreal bat species (*Myotis dasycneme* Boie, 1825) of the Ural fauna. *Doklady Biochemistry and Biophysics* 507(1): 268–272. DOI: 10.1134/S1607672922060060
- Kovalchuk L.A., Chernaya L.V., Mishchenko V.A., Berzin D.L., Mikshevich N.V. 2023. Estimation of hematological and biochemical parameters of a representative of the amphibious fauna of the Urals: *Salamandrella keyserlingii* (Caudata, Amphibia). *Nature Conservation Research* 8(1): 34–48. DOI: 10.24189/ncr.2023.002 [In Russian]
- Koyama S., Ishii K.J., Coban C., Akira S. 2008. Innate immune response to viral infection. *Cytokine* 43(3): 336–341. DOI: 10.1016/j.cyto.2008.07.009
- Kuzyakin A.P. 1950. *Bats*. Moscow: Sovetskaya Nauka. 444 p. [In Russian]
- López-Baucells A., Casanova L., Puig-Montserrat X., Espinal A., Páramo F., Flaquer C. 2017. Evaluating the use of *Myotis daubentonii* as an ecological indicator in Mediterranean riparian habitats. *Ecological Indicators* 74: 19–27. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.11.012
- Luis A.D., Hayman D.T.S., O’Shea T.J., Cryan P.M., Gilbert A.T., Pulliam J.R.C., Mills J.N., Timonin M.E., Willis C.K.R., Cunningham A.A., Fooks A.R., Rupprecht C.E., Wood J.L.N., Webb C.T. 2013. A comparison of bats and rodents as reservoirs of zoonotic viruses: Are bats special?. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 280(1756): 20122753. DOI: 10.1098/rspb.2012.2753
- Lyapunov A.N., Panyukova E.V. 2010. On the role of adults of mosquitoes (Diptera, Culicidae) in the diet of bats (Chiroptera Vespertilionidae) of the Kirov Region. *Theoretical and Applied Ecology* 4: 87–93. [In Russian]
- Meng F., Zhu L., Huang W., Irwin D.M., Zhang S. 2016. Bats: Body mass index, forearm mass index, blood glucose levels and SLC2A2 genes for diabetes. *Scientific Reports* 6: 29960. DOI: 10.1038/srep29960
- Mishchenko V.A., Kovalchuk L.A., Bolshakov V.N., Chernaya L.V. 2018. Comparative Analysis of the Amino Acid Spectrum of Blood Plasma in Chiroptera (*Vespertilio murinus* L., 1758 and *Myotis dasycneme* B., 1825) in the Fauna of the Ural Mountains. *Doklady Biological Sciences* 481(1): 157–159. DOI: 10.1134/S0012496618040105
- Moore M.S., Reichard J.D., Murtha T.D., Nabhan M.L., Pian R.E., Ferreira J.S., Kunz T.H. 2013. Hibernating little brown myotis (*Myotis lucifugus*) show variable immunological responses to white-nose syndrome. *PloS One* 8(3): e58976. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0058976
- O’Shea T.J., Cryan P.M., Cunningham A.A., Fooks A.R., Hayman D.T.S., Luis A.D., Peel A.J., Plowright R.K., Wood J.L.N. 2014. Bat flight and zoonotic viruses. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 20(5): 741–745. DOI: 10.3201/eid2005.130539
- Oksanen J., Simpson G.L., Blanchet F.G., Kindt R., Legendre P., Minchin P.R., O’Hara R.B., Solymos P., Stevens M.H.H., Szoecs E., Wagner H., Barbour M., Bedward M., Bolker B., Borcard D., Carvalho G., Chirico M., Caceres M., Durand S., Evangelista H.B.A., FitzJohn R., Friendly M., Furneaux B., Hannigan G., Hill M.O., Lahti L., McGlenn D., Ouellette M.H., Cunha E.R., Smith T., et al. 2020. *vegan: Community Ecology Package. R package. version 2.6-4*. Available from <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan>

- Orlova M.V., Orlov O.L., Kshnyasev I.A. 2012. Changes in the abundance of parasitic gamasid mite *Macronyssus corethroproctus* (Oudemans, 1902) during the overwintering period of its host, the pond bat *Myotis dasycneme* (Boie, 1825) // Russian Journal of Ecology. Vol. 43(4). P. 328–332. DOI: 10.1134/S1067413612040108
- Ozernyuk N.D. 2003. *Phenomenology and mechanisms of adaptation processes*. Moscow: Moscow State University. 215 p. [In Russian]
- Park K.J. 2015. Mitigating the impacts of agriculture on biodiversity: bats and their potential role as bioindicators. *Mammalian Biology* 80(3): 191–204. DOI: 10.1016/j.mambio.2014.10.004
- Pervushina E.M., Zamshina G.A., Nikolaeva N.V., Fedyakina M.A. 2011. Trophic relations of insectivorous bats in the south of the Middle Urals. *Bulletin of Udmurt University. Series Biology. Earth Sciences* 3: 65–73. [In Russian]
- Piraccini R. 2016. *Myotis dasycneme*. In: *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2016: e.T14127A22055164*. Available from <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2016-2.RLTS.T14127A22055164.en>
- R Core Team. 2020. *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing. Available from <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Rasmussen D.D., Ishizuka B., Quigley M.E., Yen S.S. 1983. Effects of Tyrosine and Tryptophan Ingestion on Plasma Catecholamine and 3,4-Dihydroxyphenylacetic Acid Concentrations. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology and Metabolism* 57(4): 760–763. DOI: 10.1210/jcem-57-4-760
- Red Data Book of the Middle Urals (Sverdlovsk and Perm Regions): Rare and endangered species of animals and plants. Yekaterinburg: Publishing House of the Ural University, 1996. 279 p. [In Russian]
- Ruiz S.R., Eeva T., Kanerva M., Blomberg A., Lilley T.M. 2019. Metal and metalloid exposure and oxidative status in free-living individuals of *Myotis daubentonii*. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 169: 93–102. DOI: 10.1016/j.ecoenv.2018.10.083
- Russo D., Salinas-Ramos V.B., Cistrone L., Smeraldo S., Bosso L., Ancillotto L. 2021. Do We Need to Use Bats as Bioindicators?. *Biology* 10(8): 693. DOI: 10.3390/biology10080693
- Schountz T. 2014. Immunology of bats and their viruses: challenges and opportunities. *Viruses* 6(12): 4880–4901. DOI: 10.3390/v6124880
- Severin E.S. (Ed.). 2004. *Biochemistry*. Moscow: GEOTAR-Media. 784 p. [In Russian]
- Shakhmatov I.I., Lycheva N.A., Kiselev V.I., Vdovin V.M. 2014. Contribution stressors of different nature in the formation of a hemostatic response reaction of the organism under the influence of general hypothermia. *Fundamental Research* 7(1): 106–110. [In Russian]
- Sherwin H.A., Montgomery I., Lundy M.G. 2013. The impact and implications of climate change for bats. *Mammal Review* 43(3): 171–182. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2907.2012.00214.x
- Shitikov V.K., Rosenberg G.S. 2014. *Randomization and bootstrap: statistical analysis in biology and ecology using R*. Tolyatti: Cassandra. 314 p. [In Russian]
- Simmons N.B., Cirranello A.L. 2021. *Bat Species of the World: A Taxonomic and Geographic Database*. Available from <https://batnames.org>
- Slonim A.D. (Ed.). 1979. *Ecological Animal Physiology. Part. 1. General ecological physiology and physiology of adaptations*. Leningrad: Nauka. 440 p. [In Russian]
- Snitko V.P. 2000. Proposed measures for monitoring bats in the Urals Protected Areas. In: *Coordination of ecomonitoring in the Urals Protected Areas*. Yekaterinburg. P. 239. [In Russian]
- Snitko V.P. 2001. Bats (Chiroptera) of the Ilmensky State Nature Reserve. *Plecotus et al.* 4: 69–74. [In Russian]
- Storey K.B. 2012. *Biochemical regulation of carbohydrate metabolism in hibernating bats*. In: T. Ruf, C. Bieber, W. Arnold, E. Millei (Eds.): *Living in a Seasonal World: Thermoregulatory and Metabolic Adaptations*. Chapter 36. Berlin: Springer. P. 411–421. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-642-28678-0_36
- Strelkov P.P. 1999. Sex ratio in the breeding season in adults of migratory bat species (Chiroptera, Vespertilionidae) of Eastern Europe and adjacent territories. *Zoologicheskii Zhurnal* 78(12): 1441–1454. [In Russian]
- Tilman D., Clark M., Williams D.R., Kimmel K., Polasky S., Packer C. 2017. Future threats to biodiversity and pathways to their prevention. *Nature* 546(7656): 73–81. DOI: 10.1038/nature22900
- Voigt C.C., Kingston T. 2016. *Bats in the Anthropocene: Conservation of bats in a Changing World*. Cham: Springer. 606 p.
- Wang P., Walter R.D., Bhat B.G., Florant G.L., Coleman R.A. 1997. Seasonal changes in enzymes of lipogenesis and triacylglycerol synthesis in the golden-mantled ground squirrel (*Spermophilus lateralis*). *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology B: Biochemistry and Molecular Biology* 118(2): 261–267. DOI: 10.1016/s0305-0491(97)00102-8
- Wilkinson G.S., Adams D.M. 2019. Recurrent evolution of extreme longevity in bats. *Biology Letters* 15(4): 20180860. DOI: 10.1098/rsbl.2018.0860
- Wray A.K., Jusino M.A., Banik M.T., Palmer J.M., Kaarakka H., White J.P., Lindner D.L., Gratton C., Peery M.Z. 2018. Incidence and taxonomic richness of mosquitoes in the diets of little brown and big brown bats. *Journal of Mammalogy* 99(3): 668–674. DOI: 10.1093/jmammal/gyy044
- Wu G. 2009. Amino acids: metabolism, functions, and nutrition. *Amino Acids* 37(1): 1–17. DOI: 10.1007/s00726-009-0269-0
- Yakimenko M.A., Popova N.K. 1976. Influence of 5-hydroxytryptophan on contractile thermogenesis. *Bulletin of Experimental Biology and Medicine* 81(2): 230–231.
- Yarri D. 2005. *The Ethics of animal experimentation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 240 p.
- Zimmerman L.M., Bowden R.M., Vogel L.A. 2014. A vertebrate cytokine primer for eco-immunologists. *Functional Ecology* 28(5): 1061–1073. DOI: 10.1111/1365-2435.12273
- Zukal J., Pikula J., Bandouchova H. 2015. Bats as bioindicators of heavy metal pollution: history and prospect. *Mammalian Biology* 80(3): 220–227. DOI: 10.1016/j.mambio.2015.01.001

ECOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF *MYOTIS DASYCNEME* (MAMMALIA: CHIROPTERA: VESPERTILIONIDAE) IN THE URALS

Liudmila A. Kovalchuk^{1,*} ,
Liudmila V. Chernaya¹

¹*Institute of Plant and Animal Ecology, Ural Branch of RAS, Russia*

**e-mail: kovalchuk@ipae.uran.ru*

²*Federal Research Institute of Viral Infections «Virom» of the Russian Consumer Protection Agency, Russia*

³*Ural State Pedagogical University, Russia*

Understanding the evolution of bat homeostasis and the formation of an adaptive strategy of animals to climatic fluctuations and pathogens determine the need for further laboratory and modelling studies devoted to the ecology and physiology of bats. This study was aimed to assess the hematological and biochemical parameters of homeostasis of *Myotis dasycneme*, a protected endemic bat species of the Urals. Animals ($n = 65$) were caught in the zone of mass habitation of bats in the Southern Urals (Chelyabinsk Region) and the Middle Urals (Sverdlovsk Region). We used samples from *M. dasycneme* populations in the Ilmensky State Nature Reserve (Russia). Multivariate non-parametric analysis of variance has shown no significant sex differences in red blood parameters in bats ($p > 0.05$). The blood of bats was characterised by high levels of hemoglobin (167.9–187.2 g/L), hematocrit (47.2–51.5%), erythrocytes ($9.6\text{--}11.5 \times 10^{12}/\text{L}$), platelets ($136.8\text{--}271.3 \times 10^9/\text{L}$). In the autumn-winter period of hibernation, under hypoxic load on the body and prolonged exposure to low positive and near-zero temperatures, an increased content of agranulocytes (50.6–53.6%) was noted in the blood of females and males. The spring process of awakening and exit from deep hypothermia is accompanied by the reactivity of the innate immune system in males and females (granulocytes: 53.2–54.2%). During the winter period of hypobiosis in bats, the basal metabolism increases and the concentration of glucose in the blood increases to 4.7 ± 0.5 mmol/L ($p < 0.05$). The absence of statistically significant sex differences in the content of glucose and triglycerides ($p > 0.05$) in the blood plasma of animals has been noted. This ensures metabolic processes (carbohydrate and lipid metabolism) in all seasonal periods of their annual life cycle. The amino acid fund of blood plasma of bats is represented by 22 amino acids. In the blood plasma of males and females, the fund of free amino acids decreases during the year in the following direction: summer \geq autumn \geq winter $>$ spring ($p < 0.05$). There were no sex differences ($p > 0.05$) in the content of amino acid metabolic groups, namely glycogenic (GGAA), non-essential (NEAA), branched carbon chain (BCCA). A significant accumulation of metabolically active glucoplasmic alanine in autumn (3.1 times) and winter (2.3 times) in the blood of females, and in autumn and winter (2.0 and 1.9 times) in males indicates its role as a low-temperature adaptogen. Under conditions of low positive temperatures, in the blood plasma of *M. dasycneme*, the disappearance of the essential amino acid tryptophan was observed ($p < 0.05$). This suggests a high demand for serotonin synthesis as one of triggers actively involved in maintaining hypothermia and hypometabolism in bats. Thus, the biochemical and immunohematological parameters, obtained in the course of the study, make it possible to expand and systematise the available information on the mechanisms of participation of the blood system in the regulatory processes in bats. They can be used for long-term monitoring in solving problems of conservation and abundance of healthy populations of bats that adapt both to seasonal modulations and biotic factors, and to stressors of zoonotic significance.

Key words: bats, basal metabolism, free amino acids, peripheral blood parameters, protected species, seasonal variability

RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN THE SEASONAL DYNAMICS OF SOIL FUNGI BIOMASS AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS IN PREDOMINATING FOREST TYPES IN THE BRYANSK WOODLANDS (EUROPEAN RUSSIA)

Anton D. Kataev^{1,*},
Daria N. Tebenkova¹

¹Centre for Forest Ecology and Productivity of the RAS, Russia

*e-mail: talion08@bk.ru

²Lomonosov Moscow State University, Russia

³Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve, Russia

Received: 25.05.2023. Revised: 05.10.2023. Accepted: 10.10.2023.

Being the crucial part of the forest soil's microbial pool, soil fungi in general and mycorrhizal fungi in particular are an important study object when it comes to forest ecosystems sustainability and preservation. Thus, the study of ectomycorrhizal fungi has been carried out in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve, located in the south-eastern part of the Bryansk woodlands (European Russia). Forest types featured in the study are the local predominating types, namely green-moss-fructicolose pine forests and polydominant deciduous broadleaved nemoral-herbaceous forests with spruce. This study was aimed to assess seasonal dynamics of soil fungi' biomass overall and ectomycorrhizal fungi in particular over the course of the 2017 vegetation period (May – November) and its dependence on biotic and abiotic environmental factors, such as soil water content, temperature and vegetation. The vegetation period was divided into three periods of observation, namely an early (May – July), middle (July – September) and late (September – November) one. The method used to assess the fungal biomass was direct microscopic observation using the fluorescein diacetate staining. In order to estimate the ectomycorrhizal fungi biomass separately, trenching and in-growth mesh bags were employed. The obtained results suggest that the soil fungi biomass steadily increases over the vegetation period in both studied forest types. This is mostly affected by the forest type, available water amount and seasonal changes, while the temperature's impact is less pronounced. On average, the soil fungi biomass was higher in broadleaved forests than in pine forests (2.288 mg C × g⁻¹ soil vs. 1.672 mg C × g⁻¹ soil, respectively), with non-ectomycorrhizal component having comparable biomass. The dynamics of biomass differed in the two forest types. However, noticeable differences ($p < 0.1$) between the two forest types have only been recorded during the July – September period. The biomass of ectomycorrhizal fungi is smaller than the biomass of non-mycorrhizal fungi, but at the same time it is less affected by changes in moisture. Besides that, the study has shown that the forest litter characteristics can greatly affect the dynamics of the fungal biomass.

Key words: Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve, deciduous-coniferous forests, ectomycorrhizal fungi, soil water, temperature, vegetation

Introduction

Forest ecosystems have a complex, multicomponent structure, one of the fundamental elements of which are soil fungi. They are the most important component of the forest soils microbial pools, constituting 60–80% of the forest soils' active biomass (Anderson & Domsch, 1975). Soil fungi, and especially mycorrhizal fungi, play a crucial role in the restoration and self-organisation of forest ecosystems (Futai et al., 2008). Inoculation with mycorrhizal fungi also improves plants vitality (Valdés et al., 2019) and may play a role in protecting them from diseases (Gonthier et al., 2019). The preservation of mycorrhizal fungal communities highly contributes to the stabilisation of forests and soils under negative impacts (Kropp & Langlois, 1990; Pagano, 2014).

The soil fungi are actively involved in the nutrient cycles, and mycorrhizal fungi are an integral part of the higher plant life, supplying the nutrients (Cairney, 2012; Bahr et al., 2013; Hendricks et al., 2016), and, according to some data, water as well (Allen, 2007) to plant symbionts. Mycorrhiza is the most important of the symbiosis involving plants and soil fungi. It is universal for most of the terrestrial ecosystems, since while non-mycorrhizal plants do exist, the non-mycorrhizal plant communities are virtually unheard of. The majority of plants form some type of the mycorrhiza (Brundrett, 2002). In the boreal zone, the main role belongs to ectomycorrhiza, associated with the woody plants dominating there. Mycorrhiza has a considerable impact on an ecosystem. Soil fungi are able to maintain communication between plants that belong

not only to various species, but also to various tiers, uniting them into a single system with a common circulation of biogenic elements (Read & Perez-Moreno, 2003; Booth, 2004). In addition, 50–70% of soil humus carbon enters from roots and fungi associated with them (Clemmensen et al., 2013), which makes mycorrhizal fungi one of the main sources of the stable soil carbon. The arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi contribute to the pool of stable soil organic matter by increasing the amount of mineral-associated organic matter in the lower soil horizons (Craig et al., 2018; Keller et al., 2021), while the ectomycorrhizal fungi produce more recalcitrant organic matter in the upper horizons that takes longer to decompose (Cornelissen et al., 2001; Clemmensen et al., 2013; Craig et al., 2018). This makes mycorrhizal fungi overall a very important factor of climate regulation.

Many studies show that the biomass and composition of soil fungi communities in forests can depend on external factors such as temperature, humidity, soil type, nutrient content and vegetation composition and structure (Wallander et al., 2001; Pietikäinen et al., 2005; Kaisermann et al., 2015; Štursová et al., 2020; Karliński, 2021). However, the nature of this dependence and quantitative indicators vary highly in various studies, with authors coming to opposite conclusions about just how the soil fungi are affected by seasonal changes in environment (Okada et al., 2011; Štursová et al., 2020). Moreover, it was shown that certain factors, while not necessarily affecting the biomass of fungi, can cause shifts in the fungal communities' composition (Kaisermann et al., 2015). Finally, such studies are still fairly few and far between in Russia. Most of them have been conducted on abandoned arable lands (Susyan et al., 2011; Nikitin et al., 2019) or in different climate zones (Korneykova et al., 2023).

Meanwhile, with the climate is changing, the understanding of the processes occurring in forest soils under the influence of these conditions can be crucial in conservation efforts and sustainable management of the forest ecosystems. Forest conservation and degradation mitigation, as well as sustainable forest management are important strategies for maintaining ecosystem resilience. All of them may highly benefit from studying the conditions, under which soil fungi function in forest ecosystems (Simard & Austin, 2010).

In this regard, the aim of this study was to assess the impact of biotic (forest type) and abiotic (temperature and moisture conditions) environmental factors on the soil fungi biomass seasonal dynamics

in the dominant types of coniferous-deciduous forests in Eastern Europe, in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Reserve, European Russia. The main scientific question answered by this article is what factors can explain the seasonal dynamics of soil fungi biomass?

Material and Methods

Study area

The study plots were set up in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve (European Russia), within the coniferous-deciduous mixed forests zone (Fig. 1). The local climate is temperate continental. The average temperature is -7°C to -9°C in January, and 18 – 19°C in July. The average annual precipitation in the study area (Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve) is 560–600 mm (Kuznetsova et al., 2019).

In order to assess the seasonal dynamics of the soil fungi and the environmental factors affecting them, four study plots were established in two forest types, two in each, namely green-moss-fructicolose pine forests (hereinafter – pine forests) and polydominant deciduous broadleaved nemoral-herbaceous forests with spruce, *Picea abies* (L.) H.Karst. (hereinafter – broadleaved forests) (Fig. 2). Broadleaved forests are considered secondary forests in the study area, situating on the previously disturbed areas, being recognised as the most common forest type there. Their cover percentage is 70–90%. Broadleaved forests represent an advanced stage in the vegetation formation in absence of any major anthropogenic impacts for a long time (e.g. more than 120 years) (Gornov et al., 2018). The factors considered in this study were vegetation (including litter quality), soil temperature and gravitational water amount.

Soil characteristics

The on-site studies have been carried out in 2016–2017. They showed that the soil cover is dominated by Albic Umbric Podzol (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015) on fluvio-glacial sediments. The soil has a light texture, with 1.2–1.3% of a heavy (< 0.002 mm) fraction. In pine forests, the upper, destructive layer of the forest litter (L horizon) consists of the past and current year litter (*Pinus sylvestris* L. needles, leaves of *Quercus robur* L., bark, pine cones, and small twigs) and dead moss with the predominance of *Pleurozium schreberi* (Willd. ex Brid.) Mitt. and *Dicranum polysetum* Sw. The thickness of pine forest's litter is 3–7 cm. In broadleaved forests, horizon L is characterised by an abundance of leafy litter consisting of *Acer*

platanoides L., *Ulmus glabra* Huds., *Tilia cordata* Mill., *Betula pubescens* Ehrh., and *Q. robur*. Numerous acorns, tree bark and twigs can also be found in the litter. The lower, fermentative-humified, layer of the forest litter (FH horizon) mostly contains decaying litter and wood residues. It is permeated with numerous plant roots and mycelium. The litter in broadleaved forests differs from the one in pine forests by being thinner (2–4 cm) and having a higher fragmentation rate of the enzymatic horizon. It happens due to the rapid mineralisation of leafy litter and its integration in an active biological cycle (Kazakova et al., 2018). The details on soil features can be found in Table 1.

Vegetation characteristics

In the geobotanical studies, 20 × 20-m plots were laid out in 2017. In total, 11 descriptions

were made in pine forests and 13 in broadleaved forests, due to its more complex structure. The complete floristic list has been compiled for all sites, taking into account the layered structure of the forest. In each stage, the projective coverage of plant species was assessed according to Braun-Blanquet (1964). Scientific names of vascular plants are given according to the Plants of the World Online database (<https://powo.science.kew.org/>). To assess seasonal changes in vegetation cover, data from the permanent phenological route of the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve were used. Observations began from the time of stable transition of the maximum air temperatures through the zero mark. The monitoring frequency of the plant development was once every five days, and the woody plants' stages of development were taken into account.

Fig. 1. The location of the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve (a, b) and the study plots (c; d1 – pine forests; d2 – broadleaved forests).

Fig. 2. The pine forest (A) and broadleaved forest (B) presented on the study plots in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve, Russia.

Table 1. Studied forest types’ soil and vegetation characteristics on both study plots in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve in 2016–2017

Forest type	Pine forests	Broadleaved forests
Soil characteristics		
Litter store, kg × m ²	2.5 ± 0.2	1.3 ± 0.1
Litter pH	4.7 ± 0.4	6.1 ± 0.3
Litter C/N ratio	34 ± 7	21 ± 4
Litter N, %	1.4 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.2
Horizon AY C/N	18 ± 2	11 ± 1
Horizon AY N, %	0.08 ± 0.01	0.23 ± 0.03
Vegetation characteristics		
Forest stand’s composition	90% <i>Pinus sylvestris</i> , 10% <i>Betula pubescens</i> + solitary <i>Quercus robur</i>	30% <i>Quercus robur</i> , 30% <i>Acer platanoides</i> , 30% <i>Tilia cordata</i> , 10% <i>Picea abies</i> + solitary <i>Ulmus glabra</i> , <i>Populus tremula</i> , and <i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>
Forest stand’s age, years	40–60	> 120
Number of studied plots	11	13
Storey A, %	58.64 ± 1.66	72.08 ± 5.79
Storey B, %	22.45 ± 5.57	35.83 ± 3.53
Storey C, %	46.82 ± 3.77	68.33 ± 2.61
Mean number of species:	14	34
Storey A	1.64 ± 0.15	5.33 ± 0.26
Storey B	3.91 ± 0.21	5.33 ± 0.36
Storey C	12.45 ± 0.78	32.25 ± 0.27

Pine forests are formed by the predominant *Pinus sylvestris*, sometimes with participation of *Betula pubescens*, and solitary *Quercus robur*. The undergrowth layer consists of *B. pubescens*, *Q. robur*, and *Picea abies*. Among shrubs, *Frangula alnus* Mill. and *Chamaecytisus ruthenicus* (Fisch. ex Woł.) Klásk. have been recorded. The herb cover was dominated by boreal species, namely *Vaccinium vitis-idaea* L., *V. myrtillus* L., *Calluna vulgaris* (L.) Hull. The green-moss coverage was high, reaching 90%.

In broadleaved forests, the tree layer is dominated by *Quercus robur*, *Picea abies*, *Acer platanoides*, *Tilia cordata*, *Ulmus glabra*, and *Fraxinus excelsior* L. The undergrowth layer was dominated by *U. glabra*, *A. platanoides*, *T. cordata*, while such species as *P. abies* and *F. excelsior* were less common. Shrubs were mostly represented by *Corylus avellana* L. and *Prunus padus* L. The herb cover was dominated

by nemoral plants, namely *Rabelera holostea* (L.) M.T.Sharples & E.A.Tripp., *Carex pilosa* Scop., *Mercurialis perennis* L., and *Aegopodium podagraria* L. Ground bryophytes did not seem to grow in these forests due to the scarcity of light resource. Further details on forest layers can be found in Table 1.

Soil fungi study

When assessing the soil fungi biomass dynamics in both forest types, four 1 × 2-m study plots were established in 2016. Two plots were selected as «natural» without any special treatments. The other two plots (isolated control) were entrenched and isolated from the surrounding soil by sheets of 2 mm thick foamed polyvinyl chloride (PVC) plastic up to 1 m in depth. This was done to isolate the study area from the root systems of trees, and thus, to exclude the ectomycorrhizal fungi (Fisher & Gosz,

1986). The sheet joints at the corners of the plots were additionally reinforced using polyethylene film. After laying down the isolation and burying it from the outside, the plots were left for a year for incubation, which resulted in the chopped tree roots dying out and the cessation of mycorrhizal relations on the isolated plots. In pine forests, all shrubs were also removed from the experimental plots.

On the «natural» plots, the mycelium biomass assessment for all the functional groups of soil fungi was carried out in samples taken from the top 10-cm soil layer. The exact method was as follows: five smaller samples were collected in the corners and the centre of a square plot of 1 m² and then combined into one mixed sample.

To assess specifically the biomass of mycorrhizal mycelium, batches of mesh bags were prepared: 24 rectangular bags of polyamide mesh fabric (5 × 10 × 2 cm; 56-µm mesh diameter). The bags were filled with washed quartz sand (grain diameter: 0.5–1.0 mm) and then sealed. Afterwards, three bags were placed on all sites. The placement was vertical, covering the depth of 0–10 cm under the litter (i.e. the most root-inhabited soil layer). The bags were exposed for two months, starting from May, after which the bags were removed, and the next batch was laid in their place. In total, three batches of 24 bags were laid by this way, making up three periods of exposure, namely May – July, July – September, and September – November 2017. Thus, they cover the vegetation season in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve. The design was chosen based on the studies showed that the vast majority of fungal mycelium biomass growing into sacs is ectomycorrhizal (Wallander et al., 2001). However, the method requires a control batch as well in order to take into account a possible error, since Boddy (1993) shows the ability of rhizomorphic fungi to grow in areas with extremely low nutrient concentrations. Nilsson et al. (2005) mentioned arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi mycelium growing into the bags under certain circumstances, while Carteron et al. (2021) confirmed that the mycelium of the saprotrophic fungi can still be found there, despite the absolute predominance of mycorrhizal fungi in low-nutrient mineral soil horizons. Thus, the bags were placed on the isolated sites as a control, showing the possible error of the method.

The biomass of mycorrhizal mycelium was determined by the difference between the average biomass of the mycelium in the mesh bags on the «natural» and isolated plots. The biomass of non-mycorrhizal mycelium was determined by the

difference between the biomass of mycelium in soil samples taken from the «natural» plots and the biomass of mycelium from the mesh bags from the «natural» plots.

The exact method was as follows: an aqueous suspension of sand from the mesh bags/soil samples (sand samples: 10 ml of distilled water, 2.5 g of sand; soil samples: 100 ml of distilled water, 1 g of soil) was stirred on a vortex (Biosan V1 plus) for 1 min., after which 5 ml of the supernatant was filtered through a Whatman polycarbonate membrane (hole diameter: 0.4 µm). For determining the fungi biomass, the luminescent staining method was chosen as an often employed, reliable and easily accessible method (Korneykova et al., 2022; Nikitin et al., 2023). The membranes were then stained with fluorescein diacetate (Söderström, 1977). Then, the membranes were examined under a fluorescent microscope at × 40 magnification with 30 fields of view per sample. The stained hyphae of fungi were measured using an eyepiece with a ruler. Then, the length of the hyphae was re-calculated into their mass using the formula proposed by Zvyagintsev (1991). The data obtained were used to calculate the dynamics of the biomass of soil fungi during the growing season.

Soil water and temperature

An assessment of the abiotic factors was conducted as a part of complex biogeocenotic studies in the study area, employing rain catchers, lysimeters, and Thermochron iButton temperature loggers. In order to characterise the temperature regime of the studied periods (vegetation period of 2017), three loggers have been placed in both forest type, right underneath the LFH horizons (5 cm). For each period, the mean temperature and the sum of active temperatures (exceeding 10°C) have been calculated. As for the assessment of the water supply for the studied periods, ten rain catchers and six soil lysimeters (as designed by Derome & Nieminen (1998) placed underneath the LFH horizons at 5-cm deep) have been placed in the under-crown areas in both forest types, six rain catchers and three lysimeters in each. Accounting for the volume of throughfall (i.e. precipitation coming through the forest canopy to the ground) and soil water volumes assessment was carried out monthly.

Statistical analysis

Statistical processing of the results was carried out in the STATISTICA 12.0 (StatSoft, Germany; <https://www.statsoft.de/en/home/>)

package ($\alpha = 0.05$). The significance of differences was assessed using the Mann-Whitney U-test. To assess the dependence between the biomass of various groups of soil fungi and environmental conditions, a selection of essential features was compiled based on the study of correlations between the abiotic (temperature, precipitation and gravitational soil water content) environmental factors and the biomass of soil fungi. In order to assess the degree of influence of environmental conditions on the state of various groups of soil fungi, the Spearman correlation coefficients were calculated for the biomass value and the values of other studied factors.

Results

Seasonal dynamics of the soil fungi

The soil fungi biomass has been found steadily increasing throughout the vegetation period from 1.127 mg C \times g⁻¹ soil in May – July to 2.587 mg C \times g⁻¹ soil in September – November in pine forests ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2). In broadleaved forests, the results were less obvious ($p < 0.1$). In their case, the absolute minimum occurred during the May – July period as well (1.040 mg C \times g⁻¹ soil). However, the maximum was registered during the July – September period (3.600 mg C \times g⁻¹ soil).

The biomass of non-ectomycorrhizal fungi throughout the growing season in pine forests varied from 0.771 mg C \times g⁻¹ to 2.120 mg C \times g⁻¹ (Table

2). The biomass of ectomycorrhizal mycelium (EM) in soils ranged from 0.233 mg C \times g⁻¹ to 0.467 mg C \times g⁻¹. During the autumn (September – November) period, the biomass of both EM and non-ectomycorrhizal mycelium (non-EM) was on average higher than in the summer (May – September) period, but the distinction was non-significant ($p < 0.1$). In pine forests, the ratio of EM to non-EM significantly ($p < 0.05$) shifted towards the non-EM (up to 1:5), reaching a maximum in the autumn period.

In broadleaved forests, the biomass of non-EM was in the range of 0.639–2.691 mg C \times g⁻¹ (Table 2). The lowest biomass was recorded in the period from May to June, while the highest one in the period from July to September ($p < 0.1$). The biomass of EM in soils was relatively constant and ranged from 0.400 mg C \times g⁻¹ to 0.909 mg C \times g⁻¹. In broadleaved forests, the ratio of EM to non-EM was less skewed towards the non-EM fungi, reaching 1:3 in the July – September period.

On average, the soil fungi biomass was higher in broadleaved forests at 2.288 mg C \times g⁻¹ soil, compared to pine forests (1.672 mg C \times g⁻¹ soil). It is worth mentioning though, that over the course of the vegetation period the fungal biomass was comparable in both forest types most of the time. However, the July – September period demonstrated a dramatic increase the biomass of soil fungi in broadleaved forests.

Table 2. Seasonal dynamics of the soil fungi biomass and the abiotic environmental factors measured in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve during the vegetation period in 2017

Indicators	Time period					
	01.05 – 01.07		01.07 – 01.09		01.09 – 01.11	
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
Pine forests						
Fungal biomass, mg C \times g ⁻¹ soil comprising:	1.127	0.199	1.301	0.417	2.587	0.755
EM	0.356	0.065	0.233	0.105	0.467	0.079
Non-EM	0.771	0.264	1.068	0.312	2.120	0.675
Precipitation amount, mm	54.787	15.371	143.810	4.222	71.656	0.704
Lysimetric water amount, mm	6.513	1.567	16.799	0.338	27.070	22.519
Temperature, °C	11.7	2.1	16.1	1.4	11.4	2.8
Sum of active temperatures (> 10°C)	526.2	–	998.5	–	535.4	–
Broadleaved forests						
Fungal biomass, mg C \times g ⁻¹ soil comprising:	1.040	0.034	3.600	0.120	2.224	0.683
EM	0.400	0.056	0.909	0.606	0.777	0.146
Non-EM	0.639	0.023	2.691	0.726	1.447	0.214
Precipitation amount, mm	50.590	7.506	150.527	5.278	70.910	13.723
Lysimetric water amount, mm	0.0	–	11.2	11.3	4.5	0.1
Temperature, °C	12.4	2.6	16.6	2.1	10.4	3.5
Sum of active temperatures (> 10°C)	553.8	–	1030.0	–	381.1	–

Note: M – mean value, SD – standard deviation, EM – ectomycorrhizal mycelium, Non-EM – non-ectomycorrhizal mycelium.

The non-EM biomass was generally comparable in both pine and broadleaved forests and amounted on average to 1.320 mg C × g⁻¹ and 1.592 mg C × g⁻¹, respectively. However, when comparing seasonal dynamics, some differences can still be observed. In the periods of May – July and September – November, the biomass of non-EM was higher in pine forests (on average 0.771 mg C × g⁻¹ and 2.120 mg C × g⁻¹, respectively) than in broadleaved forests (0.639 mg C × g⁻¹ and 1.447 mg C × g⁻¹, respectively). On the contrary, in the period of July – September, the biomass of non-EM was higher in broadleaved forests (on average 2.691 mg C × g⁻¹) compared to pine forests (1.068 mg C × g⁻¹).

The biomass of EM on average was higher in broadleaved forests than in pine forests and amounted to 0.695 mg C × g⁻¹ and 0.352 mg C × g⁻¹, respectively. In the period of May – September, the biomass of EM tended to be higher (p < 0.1) in broadleaved forests. The biomass of non-EM fungi in both forest types was generally higher than the biomass of EM fungi. The growth dynamics of non-EM fungi turned out to be different in pine forests and broadleaved forests. In pine forests, its maximum occurs in November, while in broadleaved forests in September.

Seasonal dynamics explains 52% of the EM biomass dispersion (p < 0.1) and 73% of the non-EM biomass (p < 0.05). The periods with different moisture levels explain 66% of fungal biomass

(p < 0.05), mostly due to the contribution of the non-EM fungi (Table 3).

Temperature

In pine forests (Table 2), the sum of active temperatures (exceeding 10°C) was 2060°C for the observation period, which is comparable to broadleaved forests, where the sum of active temperatures was 1965°C. The average temperature of the organogenic soil horizons in both forest types was 13.1°C, with both forests having the coldest period in September–November (11.4°C and 10.4°C respectively) and the warmest in July – September (16.1°C and 16.6°C). Among the three studied periods, the one in autumn (September – November) had the highest difference in temperatures between the two forest types. Being the coldest period, this difference bore extra significance for the plants and soil organisms alike. The autumn period was solely the reason the total sum of active temperatures turned out to be higher in pine forests.

The amplitude of soil temperature changes at various times of the day (daily dynamics) was smaller in pine forests compared to broadleaved forests (Fig. 3). Thus, it can be stated that the temperature fluctuations were milder in soils in pine forests than in soils in broadleaved forests. These differences can be explained by differences in the tree layer composition, which leads to differences in the litter thickness in the studied areas (2–4 cm in broadleaved forests vs. 3–7 cm in pine forests).

Table 3. One-way ANOVA of various factors, affecting temperature, throughfall, soil lysimetric water volumes and soil fungi in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve (Russia) during the vegetation period of 2017

Variables	Factor										
	Forest type		Seasonal dynamics (summer – autumn periods)				Moisture-driven dynamics (dry – moist periods)				n
			Pine forests		Broadleaved forests		Pine forests		Broadleaved forests		
	R ²	p	R ²	p	R ²	p	R ²	p	R ²	p	
Temperature											
Temperature, °C	0.01	0.951	0.31	0.255	0.56	0.086	0.20	0.375	0.04	0.707	6
Sum of active temperatures (> 10 °C)	0.01	0.844	0.24	0.329	0.49	0.117	0.26	0.296	0.07	0.618	6
Throughfall and soil lysimetric water volumes											
Throughfall, mm	0.01	0.982	0.11	0.518	0.10	0.536	0.41	0.173	0.42	0.162	20
Lysimetric water amount, mm	0.09	0.253	0.34	0.224	0.01	0.887	0.34	0.224	0.32	0.237	10
Soil fungi											
Fungal biomass, mg C × g ⁻¹ soil	0.09	0.319	0.76	0.025	0.01	0.937	0.27	0.293	0.66	0.048	12
EM	0.19	0.159	0.52	0.106	0.01	0.825	0.01	0.962	0.18	0.402	12
Non-EM	0.02	0.596	0.73	0.030	0.01	0.829	0.34	0.222	0.56	0.086	12

Note: R² – coefficient of determination, p – p-value, EM – ectomycorrhizal mycelium, Non-EM – non-ectomycorrhizal mycelium.

Fig. 3. Daily amplitude of the temperature of the organogenic horizons in pine forests (1), and broadleaved forests (2) in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve, Russia.

During the first two studied periods (May – July and July – September), the average temperatures and the sum of active temperatures were rising steadily, followed by a sharp decline at the end of the second period or beginning of the third period (September – November). These dynamics were observed in both forest types. Seasonal dynamics explain 43% of the average temperature dispersion ($p < 0.05$) and 36% of the active temperature sum dispersion (Table 3).

Water regime

In general, the vegetative season started with a period of draught, with the largest amount of precipitation coming between July and September. This period is also distinguished by the highest average temperature. Comparing the beginning of the summer period (May – June; hereinafter – dry period) with the later, moister summer and autumn transitional period (July – October; hereinafter – moist period), a significant ($p < 0.01$) increase in the amount of precipitation coming under the forest canopy was revealed and, accordingly, the increased volume of lysimetric waters ($p < 0.1$). Periods with different moisture levels explain 41% of the throughfall dispersion ($p < 0.05$) and 23% of the lysimetric waters volumes ($p < 0.1$) (Table 3).

In pine forests, the throughfall amount was 270 mm for the observation period. The amount of free soil water in lysimeters was 51 mm. The wettest period lasted from July to September. The highest amount of soil water was recorded in the autumn period (September – November) (Table 2).

In broadleaved forests, the throughfall amount was 272 mm. The amount of free soil water in lysimeters was 16 mm. The wettest period lasted from July to August. The highest

amount of soil water was recorded from July to September. From May to July, no soil water runoff was recorded, which indicates extremely dry conditions during this period.

After assessing the moisture conditions in both forest types, the amount of lysimetric waters in broadleaved forests was found to be significantly ($p < 0.05$) lower, compared to pine forests. Thus, the water availability can be considered the main limiting factor in broadleaved forests. In pine forests, it is also crucial to take into account the soils' temperature regime, as they may affect the ectomycorrhizal fungi biomass and the group composition of soil fungi overall.

Despite the close proximity of the studied sites, the environmental conditions in their soils had noticeable differences. A thicker litter in pine forests (Table 1) retained moisture better than the litter in broadleaved forests. An accumulation of moisture was observed in pine forests towards the end of the growing season. Unlike pine forests, broadleaved forests went through the periods with zero lysimetric water volume, and the volume of gravitational water directly correlated with the amount of precipitation during the corresponding period. To sum up, both the temperature and moisture conditions in pine forests' soils were more stable throughout both a day and a year, forming a milder climatic regime than the one in soils in broadleaved forests.

Vegetation

Noticeable differences were found between pine and broadleaved forests in terms of floristic composition, stem wood stock, projective cover of forest layers, and species richness. The highest species richness was recorded in broadleaved-spruce forests (34 species), while in pine forests it was noticeably lower (14 species).

The one-way ANOVA test shows the lack of the «forest type» factor's contribution to the considered indicators' variation (Table 3). However, the vegetation itself was shown to have an indirect effect, taking into account the seasonality of samples. The «seasonal dynamics» factor had noticeable value for most of the indicators, both within each forest type and when comparing them to each other (Table 3). Clear seasonal dynamics were observed based on the phenological observations of woody plants carried out in 2017 (Table 4).

Table 4. Projective plant cover and phenological observations of woody plants in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve (Russia) in 2017

Species (n)	Projective plant cover, %		Leaves sprouting, beginning	Full leaves sprouting	Mass ripening/falling of fruits	Autumn colouration, beginning	Mass autumn colouration	Leaves fall, beginning	Mass leaves fall	Leaves fall, end
	Pine forests	Broadleaved forests								
<i>Betula pubescens</i> Ehrh.	10	10	27.04	13.05	–	15.09	10.10	21.09	13.10	21.10
<i>Quercus robur</i> L.	5	35	03.05	05.06	–	16.09	09.10	24.09	16.10	23.10
<i>Acer platanoides</i> L.	1	25	–	14.05	–	18.09	24.09	22.09	07.10	11.10
<i>Tilia cordata</i> Mill.	–	20	–	–	–	14.08	27.09	–	06.10	14.10
<i>Prunus padus</i> L.	–	5	–	10.05	–	–	–	28.08	10.09	10.10
<i>Frangula alnus</i> Mill.	20	5	–	–	05.08	08.08	–	09.09	25.09	20.10
<i>Corylus avellana</i> L.	–	5	–	–	–	25.09	10.10	05.10	13.10	20.10

The active leaf fall period starts in September and lasts till late October. This coincides with the last, autumn, period. In pine forests, the projective plant cover is noticeably smaller than in broadleaved forests (Table 1). Therefore, the litter amount in pine forests is also comparatively lower, which can be considered an additional limiting factor for the soil fungi in pine forests' soils.

Assessing the environmental condition effects on soil fungi

The obtained data allow us to trace certain relationships between the biomass of various soil fungi groups and environmental conditions. It has been established that the biomass of ectomycorrhizal mycelium in pine forests is more affected by the temperature regime. It is characterised by a highest correlation index (Table

5). At the same time, the ratio of EM to non-EM in pine forests was influenced by the amount of precipitation and soil water, as well as the sum of active temperatures over 10°C. In broadleaved forests, no linear relationships with abiotic factors were found for the EM fungi.

Thus, it can be stated that the EM fungi biomass is affected by the temperature regime, which manifested itself in pine forests with more moisture. At the same time, in relatively dry broadleaved forests, this pattern did not show itself so evidently, and changes in the EM fungi biomass were generally multidirectional.

Considering the non-EM biomass in broadleaved forests, the relationships can be most clearly traced with the amount of lysimetric water and the amount of atmospheric precipitation. In pine forests, no linear relationships with abiotic factors were found for the non-EM.

Table 5. Spearman correlation (R_s) of soil fungi biomass with various environmental conditions on study sites in the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve (Russia) in 2017

Parameters	Temperature, °C	Sum of active temperatures (> 10°C)	Throughfall, mm	Lysimetric water amount, mm
Pine forests				
EM fungal biomass	-0.96***	-0.48	-0.48	0.14
Non-EM fungal biomass	-0.60	0.24	0.31	0.60
Proportion of the EM fungi from total biomass	-0.24	-0.84**	-0.71*	-0.77*
Broadleaved forests				
EM fungal biomass	0.24	0.24	0.31	0.12
Non-EM fungal biomass	0.48	0.48	0.94***	0.81**
Share of the EM fungi from total biomass	-0.12	-0.12	-0.37	-0.49

Note: EM – ectomycorrhizal mycelium, Non-EM – non-ectomycorrhizal mycelium, R_s – Spearman's rank correlation coefficient; asterisks (*) indicate the correlations' significance: * – $p \leq 0.1$, ** – $p \leq 0.05$, *** – $p \leq 0.01$.

Thus, the direct influence of the forest (formation of various symbiotic relationships between various species of dominant woody plants with local soil fungi), and the indirect influence (changes in local conditions of the soil fungi functioning, such as the temperature regime of soils, soil moisture and water supply) lead to changes in the biomass and group composition of soil fungi. Each forest type brings forth a corresponding set of abiotic factors affecting the soil and soil fungi.

Discussion

Effect of the temperature on the soil fungi biomass

The temperature regime is widely considered one of the leading factors that can affect the biomass production and the activity of soil fungi (Compant et al., 2010; Okada et al., 2011; Osono et al., 2011). Osono et al. (2011) showed that the rate of growth and decomposition of the substrate by fungi directly depend on temperature, with a clearly pronounced maximum when thermal optimums are reached and a decrease in activity when moving away from them. Pietikäinen et al. (2005) show that soil respiration increases with temperature, reaching a peak when a certain limit is reached. Compant et al. (2010) stated the decrease in the EM fungi' biological activity as one of the consequences of an increase in temperature. For pine forests, there was recorded an inverse relationship between the dynamics of fungal biomass and temperature (Okada et al., 2011). This is also confirmed by our data, since the absence of a significant increase in the production of fungal mycelium was recorded in the warmest period (Table 2). However, Okada et al. (2011) also noted the variability of such trends in various years, so there may be more factors affecting the outcome.

In contrast to pine forests, in broadleaved forests a decrease in the biomass of soil fungi can be found in the period from September to November, where the average temperature decreases, and the highest amplitude of daily temperatures was observed (Fig. 4). In natural forest ecosystems, differences in vegetation and litter can explain the difference in daily temperature dynamics. The litter thickness is higher in pine forests, which provides the underlying soil with better insulation. This leads to a smaller amplitude of daily changes in soil temperature and higher soil temperatures in the colder autumn period, compared to broadleaved forests with thinner and relatively less developed litter layer (Table 1). Temperature fluctuations were mentioned as one of the factors with an adverse impact on biological processes (Xu, 1996).

Influence of the throughfall and lysimetric water volumes on the soil fungi biomass

According to Heinemeyer et al. (2007), Allison & Treseder (2008), Compant et al. (2010), and Hawkes et al. (2011), low soil moisture can be a limiting factor for the soil fungi's vital activity. Since the amount of soil water in pine forests, even in the driest part of the growing season, was 1.5–2.0 times higher than in the wettest season in broadleaved forests, where the biomass of soil fungi was comparable to that in pine forests, it can be assumed that the humidity was not the limiting factor for at least the pine forests' soil fungi.

The growth dynamics of the non-EM fungi was found to be closely related to the soil moisture, since in pine forests the peak of non-EM fungi biomass occurs in September – November, and in July – September in broadleaved forests. It coincides with the humidity peak, i.e. the highest amount of soil water in both forest types. In both forest types, the minimum biomass was recorded in the period from May to July, which coincides with the driest conditions in soils during the vegetation season.

During periods of lower rainfall (May – July and September – November), the biomass of non-EM fungi was higher in pine forests compared to broadleaved forests. Such a difference can be explained by the higher moisture content of pine forest soils, where a higher amount of soil water was recorded during these periods in comparison with broadleaved forests, by creating more comfortable conditions for a longer time for saprotroph organisms, which are unable to directly receive the required water from plant symbionts.

In predominantly oak forests of the temperate zone, the pre-existing data on the biomass dynamics of EM fungi also indicated an increase in the EM fungi biomass at late summer and its subsequent decrease by late autumn (Voříšková et al., 2014). In general, in broadleaved forests, the soil fungi's biomass dynamics curve has a very typical shape, with a maximum at late summer, and a minimum at early summer, which corresponds to the literature (Wallander et al., 2001; Allen & Kitajima, 2014; Voříšková et al., 2014; Štursová et al., 2020).

Influence of vegetation on the soil fungi biomass

Vegetation indirectly affects the production of fungal biomass, for instance, by changing the temperature and water regime (Laganière et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2019). The litter thickness and quality seem to have a major impact on the upper organogenic soil horizons' temperature regime. According to our data, the litter thickness and its stock determine the fluctuation amplitude for the temperature regime of

the organogenic horizon. The water regime of the upper organogenic soil horizons depends on both the throughfall amount, regulated mainly by the forest canopy, and the litter properties. With almost the same amount of precipitation, the amount of free soil water in both forest types differed significantly (Table 2), which is associated with different activity of water absorption by vegetation (Lukina, 2018) and different water interception and absorption capacity in the litter of pine and broadleaved forests (Sato et al., 2004). Moreover, by the virtue of being a supplier of organic material, vegetation also affects the production of fungal biomass directly through the quantity and quality of litter on the one hand, and through the ability to form symbiotic bonds on the other hand (Kernaghan, 2005).

The growth dynamics of non-mycorrhizal fungi turned out to be different in pine and broadleaved forests. In case of pine forests, the maximum occurs in the period of September – November, while in broadleaved forests, it occurs in the period of July – September. In pine forests, due to the insignificant amount of easily decomposable litter, fungal communities may demonstrate a more pronounced reaction to its input. The peak of the non-EM fungi biomass coincides with the humidity peak, as well as with the influx of the main proportion of *Betula pubescens* litter. Autumn litter seems to be the most intensively concentrated influx of relatively easily decomposable material in local pine forests, which contributed to an increase in the biomass of saprotroph organisms under conditions of sufficient moisture. In general, the relationship between the vegetative activity of plants and the dynamics of fungal biomass can also be affected by the EM fungi symbiosis in soils (Smith & Read, 2008).

In broadleaved forests, there is a sufficient amount of nutrient substrate for the saprotrophic fungi, since the litter of deciduous trees and herbs is rich in easily decomposable compounds. Therefore, when water regime conditions become optimal, a high production of non-EM fungi could be observed there. It should also be noted, that from September to November, when the litter amount was much higher, the biomass of non-EM fungi decreased significantly (almost two-times decrease), which coincides with an almost two-fold decrease in the soil water volume. In this case, humidity seems to be a more significantly limiting factor.

In both forest types, the biomass of EM fungi in the period from May to July, characterised by a low amount of precipitation and soil water, was almost the same. Perhaps this is caused by the fact that

this was the least favourable period for the biomass production due to the lack of water and a low amount of incoming forest litter during the period. Because EM fungi can obtain water from the plant, they may not depend much on the upper soil layer's moisture by surviving this period in a relatively stable state (Smith & Read, 2008).

Smith & Read (2008) also mentioned that a higher plant species richness leads to a higher diversity and biomass of mycorrhizal symbionts, which occurred in our study during the periods of July – September and September – November. During these periods, the EM fungi biomass was significantly higher in broadleaved forests. This is related to data on the species number, i.e. an average of 36 species in broadleaved forests vs. 12 species in pine forests (Table 1). Since the arbuscular mycorrhiza has not been accounted in our study, it is uncertain how much do the associated tree species, appearing in broadleaved forests (*Acer platanoides*, *Fraxinus excelsior*), affect the biomass of EM and non-EM fungi.

Conclusions

During the growing season, the soil fungi biomass in the two studied forest types changed significantly, along with fluctuating environmental factors such as temperature and soil gravitational water content. In pine forests, the amplitude of changes of the soil fungi's total biomass was lower than in broadleaved forests. The total biomass did not have significant differences in the early and late growing season (i.e. in the periods from May to July and from September to November). However, in the period from July to September, the biomass of soil fungi in broadleaved forests was noticeably higher, which completely coincides with the period of the highest soil humidity there.

In both forest types, the non-EM fungi biomass dynamics was closely correlated to the gravitational soil water content, being higher during periods with a higher humidity. In pine forests, the non-EM fungi biomass was higher than in broadleaved forests during periods with the total less throughfall due to the better moisture retention capabilities of the litter. During the periods with the highest precipitation, the non-EM fungi biomass in broadleaved forests exceeded values of this parameter in pine forests by 2.5 times. During the growing season, no clear effect of the average temperature on the non-EM fungi biomass was found. In broadleaved forests, a significant decrease in their biomass was noted from September to November, where the average temperature decreased. However, it was also the period, when the highest amplitude of daily temperatures was observed, which could

also play its role in the found changes. The EM fungi biomass dynamics did not correlate directly with humidity or temperature fluctuations, having a different nature in the studied forest types and presumably depending mainly on nutrient inputs and vegetative activity of plants.

Acknowledgements

The study was conducted within the framework of the youth laboratory of the Centre for Forest Ecology and Productivity of the RAS «Climate-regulating functions and forest biodiversity» (№122111500023-6). The study carried out by A.V. Gornov and M.V. Gornova has been performed within the framework of the State contract with the Centre for Forest Ecology and Productivity of the RAS «Methodical approaches to assessing structural organisation and functioning of forest ecosystems» (№121121600118-8). Phenological observations were carried out within the framework of the State Contract with the Bryanskiy Les State Nature Biosphere Reserve (№1022090100010-8-1.6.20).

References

- Allen M.F. 2007. Mycorrhizal fungi: highways for water and nutrients in arid soils. *Vadose Zone Journal* 6(2): 291–297. DOI: 10.2136/vzj2006.0068
- Allen M.F., Kitajima K. 2014. Net primary production of ectomycorrhizas in a California forest. *Fungal Ecology* 10: 81–90. DOI: 10.1016/j.funeco.2014.01.007
- Allison S.D., Treseder K.K. 2008. Warming and drying suppress microbial activity and carbon cycling in boreal forest soils. *Global Change Biology* 14(12): 2898–2909. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2486.2008.01716.x
- Anderson J.P.E., Domsch K.H. 1975. Measurement of bacterial and fungal contributions to respiration of selected agricultural and forest soils. *Canadian Journal of Microbiology* 21(3): 314–322. DOI: 10.1139/m75-045
- Bahr A., Ellström M., Akselsson C., Ekblad A., Mikusinska A., Wallander H. 2013. Growth of ectomycorrhizal fungal mycelium along a Norway spruce forest nitrogen deposition gradient and its effect on nitrogen leakage. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 59: 38–48. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilbio.2013.01.004
- Boddy L. 1993. Saprotrophic cord-forming fungi: warfare strategies and other ecological aspects. *Mycological Research* 97(6): 641–655. DOI: 10.1016/S0953-7562(09)80141-X
- Booth M.G. 2004. Mycorrhizal networks mediate overstorey-understorey competition in a temperate forest. *Ecology Letters* 7(7): 538–546. DOI: 10.1111/j.1461-0248.2004.00605.x
- Braun-Blanquet J. 1964. *Pflanzensociologie*. Vienna: Springer Vienna. 865 p.
- Brundrett M.C. 2002. Coevolution of roots and mycorrhizas of land plants. *New Phytologist* 154(2): 275–304. DOI: 10.1046/j.1469-8137.2002.00397.x
- Cairney J.W. 2012. Extramatrical mycelia of ectomycorrhizal fungi as moderators of carbon dynamics in forest soil. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 47: 198–208. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilbio.2011.12.029
- Carteron A., Beigas M., Joly S., Turner B.L., Laliberté E. 2021. Temperate forests dominated by arbuscular or ectomycorrhizal fungi are characterized by strong shifts from saprotrophic to mycorrhizal fungi with increasing soil depth. *Microbial Ecology* 82(2): 377–390. DOI: 10.1007/s00248-020-01540-7
- Clemmensen K.E., Bahr A., Ovaskainen O., Dahlberg A., Ekblad A., Wallander H., Stenlid J., Finlay R.D., Wardle D.A., Lindahl B. 2013. Roots and associated fungi drive long-term carbon sequestration in boreal forest. *Science* 339(6127): 1615–1618. DOI: 10.1126/science.1231923
- Compant S., van der Heijden M.G.A., Sessitsch A. 2010. Climate change effects on beneficial plant–microorganism interactions. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology* 73(2): 197–214. DOI: 10.1111/j.1574-6941.2010.00900.x
- Cornelissen J., Aerts R., Cerabolini B., Werger M., van der Heijden M. 2001. Carbon cycling traits of plant species are linked with mycorrhizal strategy. *Oecologia* 129(4): 611–619. DOI: 10.1007/s004420100752
- Craig M.E., Turner B.L., Liang C., Clay K., Johnson D.J., Phillips R.P. 2018. Tree mycorrhizal type predicts within-site variability in the storage and distribution of soil organic matter. *Global Change Biology* 24(8): 3317–3330. DOI: 10.1111/gcb.14132
- Derome J., Nieminen T. 1998. Metal and macronutrient fluxes in heavy-metal polluted Scots pine ecosystems in SW Finland. *Environmental Pollution* 103(2–3): 219–228. DOI: 10.1016/S0269-7491(98)00118-3
- Fisher F.M., Gosz J.R. 1986. Effects of trenching on soil processes and properties in a New Mexico mixed-conifer forest. *Biology and Fertility of Soils* 2(1): 35–42. DOI: 10.1007/BF00638959
- Futai K., Taniguchi T., Kataoka R. 2008. Ectomycorrhizae and Their Importance in Forest Ecosystems. In: Z.A. Siddiqui, M.S. Akhtar, K. Futai (Eds.): *Mycorrhizae: sustainable agriculture and forestry*. Dordrecht: Springer. P. 241–285. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4020-8770-7_11
- Gonthier P., Giordano L., Zampieri E., Lione G., Vizzini A., Colpaert J.V., Balestrini R. 2019. An ectomycorrhizal symbiosis differently affects host susceptibility to two congeneric fungal pathogens. *Fungal Ecology* 39: 250–256. DOI: 10.1016/j.funeco.2018.12.008
- Gornov A.V., Gornova M.V., Tikhonova E.V., Shevchenko N.E., Kuznetsova A.I., Ruchinskaya E.V., Tebenkova D.N. 2018. Population-based assessment of succession stage of mixed forests in european part of Russia. *Russian Journal of Forest Science* 4: 243–257. DOI: 10.1134/S0024114818040083 [In Russian]
- Hawkes C.V., Kivlin S.N., Rocca J.D., Huguet V., Thomsen M.A., Suttle K.B. 2011. Fungal community responses to precipitation. *Global Change Biology* 17(4): 1637–1645. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2486.2010.02327.x
- Heinemeyer A., Hartley I.P., Evans S.P., Carreira de La Fuente J.A., Ineson P. 2007. Forest soil CO₂ flux: uncovering the contribution and environmental responses of ectomycorrhizas. *Global Change Biology* 13(8): 1786–1797. DOI: 10.1111/j.1365-2486.2007.01383.x

- Hendricks J.J., Mitchell R.J., Kuehn K.A., Pecot S.D. 2016. Ectomycorrhizal fungal mycelia turnover in a longleaf pine forest. *New Phytologist* 209(4): 1693–1704. DOI: 10.1111/nph.13729
- IUSS Working Group WRB. 2015. *International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps*. World Soil Resources Reports №106. Rome: FAO. 216 p.
- Kaisermann A., Maron P.A., Beaumelle L., Lata J.C. 2015. Fungal communities are more sensitive indicators to non-extreme soil moisture variations than bacterial communities. *Applied Soil Ecology* 86: 158–164. DOI: 10.1016/j.apsoil.2014.10.009
- Karliński L. 2021. Biomass of external mycelium of ectomycorrhizal fungi associated with poplars – The impact of tree genotype, tree age and soil environment. *Applied Soil Ecology* 160: 103847. DOI: 10.1016/j.apsoil.2020.103847
- Kazakova A.I., Semikolennykh A.A., Gornov A.V., Gornova M.V., Lukina N.V. 2018. Influence of vegetation on the lability characteristics of sandur areas of the Bryansky Les Nature Reserve. *Moscow University Soil Science Bulletin* 73(3): 100–106. DOI: 10.3103/S0147687418030055
- Keller A.B., Brzostek E.R., Craig M.E., Fisher J.B., Phillips R.P. 2021. Root-derived inputs are major contributors to soil carbon in temperate forests, but vary by mycorrhizal type. *Ecology Letters* 24(4): 626–635. DOI: 10.1111/ele.13651
- Kernaghan G. 2005. Mycorrhizal diversity: cause and effect?. *Pedobiologia* 49(6): 511–520. DOI: 10.1016/j.pedobi.2005.05.007
- Korneykova M.V., Vasenev V.I., Nikitin D.A., Dolgikh A.V., Soshina A.S., Myazin V.A., Nakhaev M.R. 2022. Soil microbial community of urban green infrastructures in a polar city. *Urban Ecosystems* 25(5): 1399–1415. DOI: 10.1007/s11252-022-01233-8
- Korneykova M.V., Myazin V.A., Fokina N.V., Chaporgina A.A., Nikitin D.A., Dolgikh A.V. 2023. Structure of Microbial Communities and Biological Activity in Tundra Soils of the Euro-Arctic Region (Rybachy Peninsula, Russia). *Microorganisms* 11(5): 1352. DOI: 10.3390/microorganisms11051352
- Kropp B.R., Langlois C.G. 1990. Ectomycorrhizae in reforestation. *Canadian Journal of Forest Research* 20(4): 438–451. DOI: 10.1139/x90-061
- Kuznetsova A.I., Lukina N.V., Tikhonova E.V., Gornov A.V., Gornova M.V., Smirnov V.E., Geraskina A.P., Shevchenko N.E., Tebenkova D.N., Chumachenko S.I. 2019. Carbon stock in sandy and loamy soils of coniferous–broadleaved forests at different succession stages. *Eurasian Soil Science* 52(7): 756–768. DOI: 10.1134/S1064229319070081
- Laganière J., Paré D., Bergeron Y., Chen H.Y.H. 2012. The effect of boreal forest composition on soil respiration is mediated through variations in soil temperature and C quality. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 53: 18–27. DOI: 10.1016/j.soilbio.2012.04.024
- Lukina N.V. 2018. *Carbon accumulation and the succession status of forests*. Moscow: KMK Scientific Press Ltd. 232 p. [In Russian]
- Nikitin D.A., Chernov T.V., Zhelezova A.D., Tkhakakhova A.K., Nikitina S.A., Semenov M.V., Xenofontova N.A., Kutovaya O.V. 2019. Seasonal dynamics of microbial biomass in soddy-podzolic soil. *Eurasian Soil Science* 52(11): 1414–1421. DOI: 10.1134/S1064229319110073
- Nikitin D.A., Semenov M.V., Ksenofontova N.A., Tkhakakhova A.K., Rusakova I.V., Lukin S.M. 2023. Effect of Fresh Organic Matter of Straw on Microbiological Parameters of Soddy-Podzolic Soil. *Eurasian Soil Science* 56(5): 651–662. DOI: 10.1134/s1064229322601950
- Nilsson L.O., Giesler R., Bååth E., Wallander H. 2005. Growth and biomass of mycorrhizal mycelia in coniferous forests along short natural nutrient gradients. *New Phytologist* 165(2): 613–622. DOI: 10.1111/j.1469-8137.2004.01223.x
- Okada K., Okada S., Yasue K., Fukuda M., Yamada A. 2011. Six-year monitoring of pine ectomycorrhizal biomass under a temperate monsoon climate indicates significant annual fluctuations in relation to climatic factors. *Ecological Research* 26(2): 411–419. DOI: 10.1007/s11284-011-0800-0
- Osono T., Hagiwara Y., Masuya H. 2011. Effects of temperature and litter type on fungal growth and decomposition of leaf litter. *Mycoscience* 52(5): 327–332. DOI: 10.1007/S10267-011-0112-9
- Pagano M.C. 2014. Drought stress and mycorrhizal plant. In: M. Miransari (Eds.): *Use of Microbes for the Alleviation of Soil Stresses*. Vol. 1. New York: Springer. P. 97–110. DOI: 10.1007/978-1-4614-9466-9_5
- Pietikäinen J., Pettersson M., Bååth E. 2005. Comparison of temperature effects on soil respiration and bacterial and fungal growth rates. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology* 52(1): 49–58. DOI: 10.1016/j.femsec.2004.10.002
- Read D.J., Perez-Moreno J. 2003. Mycorrhizas and nutrient cycling in ecosystems – a journey towards relevance?. *New Phytologist* 157(3): 475–492. DOI: 10.1046/j.1469-8137.2003.00704.x
- Sato Y., Kumagai T., Kume A., Otsuki K., Ogawa S. 2004. Experimental analysis of moisture dynamics of litter layers – the effects of rainfall conditions and leaf shapes. *Hydrological Processes* 18(16): 3007–3018. DOI: 10.1002/hyp.5746
- Simard S., Austin M. 2010. The role of mycorrhizas in forest soil stability with climate change. In: S. Simard (Ed.): *Climate change and variability*. InTech (On-line). P. 275–302. DOI: 10.5772/9813
- Smith S.E., Read D.J. 2008. *Mycorrhizal Symbiosis*. London: Academic Press. 800 p.
- Söderström B.E. 1977. Vital staining of fungi in pure cultures and in soil with fluorescein diacetate. *Soil Biology and Biochemistry* 9(1): 59–63. DOI: 10.1016/0038-0717(77)90061-X
- Susyan E.A., Wirth S., Ananyeva N.D., Stolnikova E.V. 2011. Forest succession on abandoned arable soils in European Russia – Impacts on microbial biomass, fungal-bacterial ratio, and basal CO₂ respiration activity. *European Journal of Soil Biology* 47(3): 169–174. DOI: 10.1016/j.ejsobi.2011.04.002
- Štursová M., Kohout P., Human Z.R., Baldrian P. 2020. Production of fungal mycelia in a temperate coniferous forest shows distinct seasonal patterns. *Journal of Fungi* 6(4): 190. DOI: 10.3390/jof6040190
- Valdés R.C., Mendoza-Villarreal R., García F.G., González-Morales S., Sánchez-Peña S. 2019. Improved paramete-

- ters of *Pinus greggii* seedling growth and health after inoculation with ectomycorrhizal fungi. *Southern Forests* 81(1): 23–30. DOI: 10.2989/20702620.2018.1474415
- Voříšková J., Brabcová V., Cajthaml T., Baldrian P. 2014. Seasonal dynamics of fungal communities in a temperate oak forest soil. *New Phytologist* 201(1): 269–278. DOI: 10.1111/nph.12481
- Wallander H., Nilsson L.O., Hagerberg D., Bååth E. 2001. Estimation of the biomass and seasonal growth of external mycelium of ectomycorrhizal fungi in the field. *New Phytologist* 151(3): 753–760. DOI: 10.1046/j.0028-646x.2001.00199.x
- Wang C., Fu B., Zhang L., Xu Z. 2019. Soil moisture–plant interactions: an ecohydrological review. *Journal of Soils and Sediments* 19(1): 1–9. DOI: 10.1007/s11368-018-2167-0
- Xu X.M. 1996. On estimating non-linear response of fungal development under fluctuating temperatures. *Plant Pathology* 45(2): 163–171. DOI: 10.1046/j.1365-3059.1996.d01-134.x
- Zvyagintsev D.G. 1991. *Methods of the soil microbiology and biochemistry*. Moscow: Moscow State University. 304 p. [In Russian]

СВЯЗЬ МЕЖДУ СЕЗОННОЙ ДИНАМИКОЙ ПОЧВЕННЫХ ГРИБОВ И ФАКТОРАМИ СРЕДЫ В ПРЕОБЛАДАЮЩИХ ТИПАХ ЛЕСА БРЯНСКОГО ПОЛЕСЬЯ (ЕВРОПЕЙСКАЯ РОССИЯ)

А. Д. Катаев^{1,*} ,
Д. Н. Тебенькова¹

¹Центр по проблемам экологии и продуктивности лесов РАН, Россия

*e-mail: talion08@bk.ru

²Московский государственный университет имени М.В. Ломоносова, Россия

³Государственный природный биосферный заповедник «Брянский Лес», Россия

Являясь важнейшей частью микробного пула лесной почвы, почвенные грибы в целом и микоризные грибы в частности являются важным объектом изучения, когда речь идет об устойчивости и сохранении лесных экосистем. С целью оценки сезонной динамики биомассы почвенных грибов в целом и эктомикоризных грибов в частности в течение вегетационного периода (май – ноябрь) и ее зависимости от биотических и абиотических факторов среды, таких как влажность почвы, температура и растительность, было проведено исследование в Государственном природном биосферном заповеднике «Брянский лес», расположенном в юго-восточной части Брянского полесья (Европейская Россия). Исследование проводилось в двух типах лесов: сосняках зеленомошно-кустарниковых и полидоминантных лиственно-широколиственных неморально-травных лесах с елью. Вегетационный период был разделен на три периода наблюдения: ранний (май – июль), средний (июль – сентябрь) и поздний (сентябрь – ноябрь). Метод, использованный для оценки биомассы грибов, представлял собой прямое микроскопическое наблюдение с окрашиванием образцов флуоресцеина диацетатом; для оценки биомассы эктомикоризных грибов отдельно использовали методы окапывания и сетчатых мешков. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о том, что биомасса почвенных грибов увеличивается в обоих типах леса в течение вегетационного периода, в большей степени зависит от типа леса, количества доступной воды и сезонных изменений, в то время как влияние температуры менее выражено. В среднем биомасса почвенных грибов была выше в широколиственных лесах, при этом неэктомикоризный компонент имел сопоставимую биомассу в обоих типах. Динамика биомассы различалась в разных типах леса, однако заметные различия между ними были отмечены только в июле – сентябре. Биомасса эктомикоризных грибов была меньше, чем биомасса немикоризных грибов, но в то же время менее подвержена влиянию изменений влажности. Кроме того, исследования показали, что характеристики лесной подстилки могут существенно влиять на динамику биомассы грибов. Полученные данные могут быть полезны в дальнейших исследованиях микоризных грибов в условиях меняющегося климата.

Ключевые слова: государственный природный биосферный заповедник «Брянский лес», почвенная вода, температура, растительность, хвойно-широколиственные леса, эктомикоризные грибы

Contents

RESEARCH ARTICLES

- GENETIC STRUCTURE OF *SOLIDAGO* × *NIEDEREDERI* (ASTERACEAE) POPULATION IN THE «ALEKSIN BOR» NATURAL MONUMENT (EUROPEAN RUSSIA) 1
S.N. Lysenkov, M.A. Galkina
- AVIFAUNA DIVERSITY ASSESSMENT IN THE COMMUNAL NATURAL PROTECTED AREA EL GAVILÁN, CENTRAL COAST OF OAXACA, MEXICO 9
J. García-Grajales, C.D. Juárez-Santiago, A. Buenrostro-Silva
- GENERAL PATTERNS OF MACROZOOBENTHOS DISTRIBUTION IN TWO RIVERS BASINS OF THE KHABAROVSKY KRAI (FAR EAST OF RUSSIA) 21
L.V. Vorobjeva, E.S. Chertoprud
- THE BIVALVES (MOLLUSCA) FROM PRIORITY MARINE REGIONS IN THE CENTRE-SOUTH OF THE MEXICAN TRANSITIONAL PACIFIC, ASSOCIATED WITH THE ROCKY INTERTIDAL ZONE 36
V.I. López-Rojas, C. Torreblanca-Ramírez, J.G. Padilla-Serrato, P. Flores-Rodríguez, R. Flores-Garza
- LONG-TERM VARIATIONS IN NUTRITIONAL CONDITION OF *PANULIRUS ARGUS* (DECAPODA: PALINURIDAE) IN CUBA: ANALYTICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL APPROACHES 48
A. Lopeztegui-Castillo
- MANATEE WATCHING IS WIDESPREAD AND SEASONALLY AFFECTED IN NORTHEAST BRAZIL: A CASE OF THE ENDANGERED *TRICHECHUS MANATUS MANATUS* (SIRENIA: TRICHECHIDAE) 61
P.D.F. Coutinho, A.L.L. Matte, B. Bezerra
- AGE STRUCTURE AND GROWTH OF *BUFO VERRUCOSISSIMUS* (AMPHIBIA, ANURA, BUFONIDAE) IN THE CAUCASIAN STATE NATURE BIOSPHERE RESERVE (RUSSIA) AT THE END OF THE XX CENTURY 76
A.A. Kidov, K.A. Afrin, I.V. Stepankova, K.A. Matushkina, B.S. Tuniyev
- WITHIN-GROUP SPATIAL POSITION IN *SAIGA TATARICA* (BOVIDAE) IN THE STEPNOI STATE NATURE SANCTUARY, ASTRAKHAN REGION, RUSSIA 86
K.A. Karenina, E.A. Berezina, A.N. Giljov
- ECOLOGICAL AND PHYSIOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF *MYOTIS DASYCNEME* (MAMMALIA: CHIROPTERA: VESPERTILIONIDAE) IN THE URALS 94
L.A. Kovalchuk, V.A. Mishchenko, L.V. Chernaya, N.V. Mikshevich
- RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN THE SEASONAL DYNAMICS OF SOIL FUNGI BIOMASS AND ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS IN PREDOMINATING FOREST TYPES IN THE BRYANSK WOODLANDS (EUROPEAN RUSSIA) 112
A.D. Kataev, A.I. Kuznetsova, V.A. Kuznetsov, A.V. Gornov, D.N. Tebenkova, M.V. Gornova, E.Yu. Kaygordova, A.D. Nikitina

Содержание

ОРИГИНАЛЬНЫЕ СТАТЬИ

- ГЕНЕТИЧЕСКАЯ СТРУКТУРА ПОПУЛЯЦИИ *SOLIDAGO* × *NIEDEREDERI* (ASTERACEAE) В ПАМЯТНИКЕ ПРИРОДЫ «АЛЕКСИН БОР» (ЕВРОПЕЙСКАЯ РОССИЯ) 1
С.Н. Лысенков, М.А. Галкина
- ОЦЕНКА РАЗНООБРАЗИЯ ОРНИТОФАУНЫ НА ОБЩЕСТВЕННОЙ ОСОБО ОХРАНЯЕМОЙ ПРИРОДНОЙ ТЕРРИТОРИИ ЭЛЬ ГАВИЛАН, ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЕ ПОБЕРЕЖЬЕ ШТАТА ОАХАКА, МЕКСИКА 9
Х. Гарсиа-Грахалес, К.Д. Хуарес-Сантьяго, А. Буэнростро-Сильва
- ОБЩИЕ ЗАКОНОМЕРНОСТИ РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ МАКРОЗООБЕНТОСА В БАССЕЙНАХ ДВУХ РЕК ХАБАРОВСКОГО КРАЯ (ДАЛЬНИЙ ВОСТОК РОССИИ) 21
Л.В. Воробьева, Е.С. Чертопруд
- ДВУСТВОРЧАТЫЕ МОЛЛЮСКИ (MOLLUSCA) КАМЕНИСТОЙ ПРИЛИВНОЙ ЗОНЫ В ПРИОРИТЕТНЫХ МОРСКИХ РЕГИОНАХ ЦЕНТРАЛЬНОЙ ЧАСТИ ЮГА МЕКСИКАНСКОГО ПЕРЕХОДНОГО ТИХООКЕАНСКОГО РЕГИОНА 36
В.И. Лопес-Роха, К. Торребланка-Рамирес, Х.Г. Падилья-Серрато, П. Флорес-Родригес, Р. Флорес-Гарса
- ДОЛГОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ УСЛОВИЙ ПИТАНИЯ *PANULIRUS ARGUS* (DECAPODA: PALINURIDAE) НА КУБЕ: АНАЛИТИЧЕСКИЕ И МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПОДХОДЫ 48
А. Лопестегьи-Кастильо
- НАБЛЮДЕНИЯ ЗА ЛАМАНТИНАМИ ШИРОКО РАСПРОСТРАНЕНЫ И ПОДВЕРЖЕНЫ СЕЗОННЫМ ИЗМЕНЕНИЯМ НА СЕВЕРО-ВОСТОКЕ БРАЗИЛИИ НА ПРИМЕРЕ ИСЧЕЗАЮЩЕГО (EN) *TRICHECHUS MANATUS MANATUS* (SIRENIA: TRICHECHIDAE) 61
П.Д.Ф. Котинью, А.Л.Л. Матте, Б. Безерра
- ВОЗРАСТНАЯ СТРУКТУРА И РОСТ *BUFO VERRUCOSISSIMUS* (AMPHIBIA, ANURA, BUFONIDAE) В КАВКАЗСКОМ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОМ ПРИРОДНОМ БИОСФЕРНОМ ЗАПОВЕДНИКЕ (РОССИЯ) В КОНЦЕ XX ВЕКА 76
А.А. Кидов, К.А. Африн, И.В. Степанкова, К.А. Матушкина, Б.С. Туниев
- ПРОСТРАНСТВЕННОЕ РАСПОЛОЖЕНИЕ ОСОБЕЙ ВНУТРИ ГРУППЫ У *SAIGA TATARICA* (BOVIDAE) В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОМ ПРИРОДНОМ ЗАКАЗНИКЕ «СТЕПНОЙ», АСТРАХАНСКАЯ ОБЛАСТЬ, РОССИЯ 86
К.А. Каренина, Е.А. Березина, А.Н. Гилёв
- ЭКОЛОГО-ФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ПАРАМЕТРЫ *MYOTIS DASYSNEME* (MAMMALIA CHIROPTERA: VESPERTILIONIDAE) ФАУНЫ УРАЛА 94
Л.А. Ковальчук, В.А. Мищенко, Л.В. Черная, Н.В. Микшевич
- СВЯЗЬ МЕЖДУ СЕЗОННОЙ ДИНАМИКОЙ ПОЧВЕННЫХ ГРИБОВ И ФАКТОРАМИ СРЕДЫ В ПРЕОБЛАДАЮЩИХ ТИПАХ ЛЕСА БРЯНСКОГО ПОЛЕСЬЯ (ЕВРОПЕЙСКАЯ РОССИЯ) 112
А.Д. Катаев, А.И. Кузнецова, В.А. Кузнецов, А.В. Горнов, Д.Н. Тебенькова, М.В. Горнова, Е.Ю. Кайгородова, А.Д. Никитина

The journal «Nature Conservation Research» was founded in 2016. It is aimed to show the quality and level of scientific investigations carried out in Protected Areas, studies of biological diversity and also of biology and ecology of threatened species.

Publisher: Fund for Support and Development of Protected Areas «Bear Land» with the support of Joint Directorate of the Mordovia State Nature Reserve and National Park «Smolny».

The main requirements for submitting manuscripts: they must be based on studies conducted (completely or predominantly) within (a) Protected Area(s) or devoted (completely or predominantly) to threatened species; a manuscript must be of interest to an international readership, even if its immediate scope is local

The journal «Nature Conservation Research» publishes research articles, review articles, short communications, research notes, discussions, as well as chronicles, and book reviews.

The publication frequency: four issues a year. Additionally, up to two special issues can be published.

A digital version is available on our web-site: <http://ncr-journal.bear-land.org/>

Indexation: Among others Web of Science Core Collection (ESCI), SCOPUS, Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), CrossRef, Russian Science Citation Index, CAB Abstracts; included in the List of peer-reviewed scientific editions, where should be published main scientific results of dissertations for Candidate of Sciences (PhD) degree, dissertations for Doctor of Sciences (Dr. Sc.) degree.

Managing Editor: Anatoliy A. Khapugin.

E-mail: ncr.journal@yandex.ru or hapugin88@yandex.ru.

Журнал «Nature Conservation Research. Заповедная наука» был учрежден в 2016 г. Его целью является освещение качества и уровня научных исследований, проводимых на территории заповедников и национальных парков всего мира, изучение их биологического разнообразия, а также биологии и экологии редких видов.

Издатель: Фонд поддержки и развития заповедных территорий «Медвежья Земля» при поддержке ФГБУ «Заповедная Мордовия».

Основные требования к рукописям: они должны основываться на исследованиях, проведенных (полностью или преимущественно) на ООПТ или быть посвященными (полностью или преимущественно) охраняемым или угрожаемым видам; рукопись должна представлять интерес для международной аудитории, даже если она выполнена на местном (региональном) уровне.

Журнал «Nature Conservation Research. Заповедная наука» публикует обзоры, оригинальные статьи, краткие сообщения, научные заметки, дискуссии, а также материалы в рубрики хроники и рецензии.

Периодичность: 4 выпуска в год. Дополнительно публикуется до двух специальных выпусков в год.

Электронная версия журнала доступна на нашем веб-сайте: <http://ncr-journal.bear-land.org/>

Индексация: Web of Science Core Collection (ESCI), SCOPUS, Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ), CrossRef, Российский Индекс Научного Цитирования (РИНЦ), CAB Abstracts и др.; включен в Перечень рецензируемых научных изданий Высшей аттестационной комиссии (ВАК).

Исполнительный редактор: Анатолий Александрович Хапугин.

E-mail: ncr.journal@yandex.ru, дополнительный: hapugin88@yandex.ru.

Cover photo: *Momotus mexicanus* Swainson, 1827 (Aves: Coraciiformes: Momotidae) in the Communal Natural Protected Area El Gavilán, Oaxaca state, Mexico (Author: PhD Jesús García-Grajales)

Фото на обложке: *Momotus mexicanus* Swainson, 1827 (Aves: Coraciiformes: Momotidae) на общественной особо охраняемой природной территории Эль Гавилан (штат Оахака, Мексика) (Автор: PhD Х. Гарсиа-Гражалес)

Адрес редакции: 430005, Россия, Республика Мордовия, город Саранск, ул. Красная, д. 30,
e-mail: ncr.journal@yandex.ru, hapugin88@yandex.ru

Editorial office: 430005, Russia, Republic of Mordovia, Saransk, Krasnaya Street, 30.
e-mail: ncr.journal@yandex.ru, hapugin88@yandex.ru

Подписано в печать 30.11.2023. Формат 60×84 1/8. Тираж 300.

Печать офсетная. Бумага офсетная.

Отпечатано в типографии ООО «Аверс» г. Брянск